

**HYDROGEOMORPHIC ANALYSIS
OF
TITTUR DRAINAGE BASIN**

**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO
NORTH MAHARASHTRA UNIVERSITY, JALGAON**

**FOR THE AWARD OF DEGREE OF
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN GEOGRAPHY
(FACULTY OF SCIENCE)**

**BY
AGONE VIKRAM MADHUKAR**

JANUARY 2013

CERTIFICATE

(Form – A)

Certified that the work incorporate in the thesis entitled
“Hydrogeomorphic Analysis of Tittur Drainage Basin”
submitted by ***Agone Vikram Madhukar*** was carried out by the
candidate under my supervision. Such material as has been
obtained from other sources has been duly acknowledged in the
thesis.

Place: Dhule

Ph.D. Supervisor

Date: 24/01/2013

Dr. S. M. Bhamare

(M Sc. Ph.D. B.Ed.)

Professor, P.G. And Research Dept. Of Geography
S.S.V.P.S L.K. Dr. P.R. Ghogrey Science College,
Dhule.424005

CANDIDATE’S DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the Ph.D. Thesis entitled ***“Hydrogeomorphic Analysis of Tittur Drainage Basin”*** submitted for the Ph.D. degree of the ***‘North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon’*** has not been previously submitted by me for the award of any other diploma or degree of this university or any other university.

CV. M. Agone.

Date: 24/01/2013

Agone Vikram Madhukar
(Research Scholar)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I wish to express my deep and sincere feeling of gratitude to my Ph.D. Supervisor, Dr. S.M.Bhamare, Professor, P.G. and Research Dept. of Geography, S.S.V.P.S. L.K. Dr. P.R. Ghogrey Science College, Dhule for constant supervision and unfailing interest, the present work was carried out. I am deeply indebted to him for his timely help, and encouragement during different stage of this research work.

My sincere thanks are also due to the Authorities of North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon providing a research opportunity in this esteemed University and also for approving the topic of research and granting me permission to work on such a diverse discipline of geography.

I wish to express my deep sense of gratitude to NASA, USGS, and Goddard Space Flight Center for provided Landsat and ASTER Satellite data for this research work. I also wish to express my sincere thanks toward the CGWB Nagpur, SDSC Nashik, from where the data and information was collected.

Constant encouragement from my parent Mrs. Pushpa and Mr. Madhukar Agone, Shubhangi help me a lot to carry out all the work in time right from the beginning. I wish to express my deep sense of gratitude to my wife Hemlata who was a source of inspiration and a good critique at every moment in completing this research work.

Finally, I thank everyone who helped me during the complication of this work.

Agone Vikram M.

CONTENTS

Chapter	Content	Page No.
1	INTRODUCTION	2
	1.1 Introduction	2
	1.2 Hydrogeomorphology	3
	1.3 Groundwater	5
	1.4 Occurrence of Groundwater in Deccan Trap Formation	7
	1.5 The Study Area	10
	1.6 Selection of the study area	11
	1.7 Aims and Objectives	13
	1.8 Literature Review	14
	1.9 Methodology	19
	1.10 Approach	21
	1.11 Research design/Outline of study	22
2	ENVIRONMENTAL PROFILE OF THE STUDY AREA	27
	2.1 Introduction	27
	2.2 Location and Extent	28
	2.3 Physiography	30
	2.4 Geology	33
	2.4.1 Deccan Trap Basalt	35
	2.4.2 Red Bole	36
	2.4.3 Dykes	37
	2.4.4 Alluvium	38

	2.4.5 Colluvium	38
	2.4.6 Structural Geology	40
	2.5 Climate	41
	2.5.1 Rainfall	41
	2.5.2 Temperature	44
	2.6 Land Surface Temperature	45
	2.7 Vegetation	49
	2.8 Soil	57
	2.9 Land use / Land cover	59
	2.10 Transport and Communication	62
	2.11 Population	64
	2.12 Geomorphology	64
3	DRAINAGE BASIN MORPHOMETRY	70
	3.1 Introduction	70
	3.2 Database and Methodology:	74
	3.3 Various Aspects of Drainage Basin Morphometry	75
	3.4 Linear Aspects of the Tittur Drainage Basin	83
	3.4.1 Stream Order and Stream Number	83
	3.4.2 Stream Order Vs Stream Number	87
	3.4.3 Bifurcation Ratio (Rb)	91
	3.4.4 Stream Length	93
	3.4.5 Sinuosity Index (SI)	99
	3.4.6 Length of Overland Flow	101
	3.4.7 Drainage Orientation	103
	3.5 Areal Aspects of the Tittur Drainage Basin	106
	3.5.1 Drainage Basin Area	106

	3.5.2 Basin Perimeter	106
	3.5.3 Length of the Basin	107
	3.5.4 Form Factor	107
	3.5.5 Circularity Ratio	108
	3.5.6 Elongation Ratio	108
	3.5.7 Stream Frequency	109
	3.5.8 Drainage Density	111
	3.5.9 Constant Channel Maintenance	114
	3.5.10 Area Ratio	114
	3.5.11 Law of Basin Area	115
	3.6 Relief Aspects of the Tittur Basin	119
	3.6.1 Total Basin Relief	119
	3.6.2 Relative Relief and Relief Ratio	121
	3.6.3 Ruggedness Number	122
	3.6.4 Dissection index	124
	3.6.5 Basin Slope	126
	3.6.6 Law of Channel Slope	128
	3.6.7 Longitudinal Profile of the Tittur River	131
	3.6.8 Valley Cross Profiles	134
	3.6.9 Superimposed, Projected and composite profile	140
	3.6.10 Percentage hypsometric curve	142
4	DRAINAGE BASIN HYDROLOGY	147
	4.1 Introduction	147
	4.2 Rainfall Regime	148
	4.2.1 Isohyetal method	153

4.2.2 Spatial Distribution of Rainfall using TRMM Satellite data and GIS	154
4.3 Runoff	164
4.3.1 Estimation of Runoff using SCS CN Method and ArcGIS ArcCN Runoff Tool.	166
4.4 Rainfall-runoff Relationship	176
4.5 Hydrologic Abstractions	189
4.6 Evaporation Loss	191
4.7 Evapotranspiration	193
4.8 Potential Evapotranspiration	197
4.9 Soil moisture Retention	201
4.10 Initial abstraction	204
4.11 Infiltration	206
4.12 Time of Concentration	211
4.13 Discharge	213
4.14 Flow Regimes	216
4.15 Water Balance Study of Tittur Basin	217
4.16 Groundwater Hydrology	221
4.17 Aquifer Characteristics	223
4.18 Lithology of Well Sections	232
4.19 Well Inventory	237
4.20 Water Table Contour Map	255
4.21 Groundwater Flow in Relation to Water Table Contour	260
4.22 Groundwater Quality of Tittur Basin	264

5	LANDFORM ANALYSIS	273
	5.1 Introduction	273
	5.2 Significance of Landform in Hydrogeomorphic Study	274
	5.3 Classification of Landforms in the Tittur Basin	275
	5.4 Structural Landform	280
	5.4.1 Structural Hill	281
	5.4.2 Lineaments	282
	5.4.3 Escarpment	284
	5.4.4 Dyke	286
	5.5 Denudational Landforms	287
	5.5.1 Pediment	288
	5.5.2 Pedepain	289
	5.5.3 Denudational Hill	291
	5.5.4 Dissected plateau	294
	5.5.5 Monadnock or Residual Hills	294
	5.5.6 Ridge	297
	5.5.7 Gully and Rill	299
	5.5.8 Tor	301
	5.6 Fluvial Landform	303
	5.6.1 Alluvial Plain	303
	5.6.2 Valley Fills	305
	5.6.3 Floodplain	306
	5.6.4 Fluvial Terraces	309
	5.6.5 Palaeochannel	310
	5.6.6 Plunge pool	311
	5.6.7 Stream pool	314

	5.7 Landforms associated with Hill Slope	314
	5.7.1 Talus	315
	5.8 Lineament Analysis	316
	5.8.1 Methodology and Data base for Lineament Analysis	320
	5.8.2 Lineament Mapping	321
	5.8.3 Result	324
	5.8.3.1 Lineament Density	325
	5.8.3.2 Lineament Intersection	328
	5.8.3.3 Orientation Analysis	330
	5.9 Identification of Groundwater Potential Zone using Geoinformatics	332
	5.9.1 Material and Methods for Identification of Groundwater Potential Zone using Geoinformatics	335
	5.9.2 Integration of remote sensing and GIS modeling for groundwater potential zone mapping	336
	5.9.3 Groundwater Potential Zones	342
	5.9.3 Conclusion	344
6	HYDROGEOMORPHIC PROBLEMS OF THE BASIN	347
	6.1 Introduction	347
	6.2 Problem of Exploitation of High Yielding Wells and Tube wells	348
	6.3 Problem Related to Deforestation & Removal of Vegetative Cover	350
	6.4 Growth of Impervious Surfaces	352
	6.5 Problem of High Water Table in Rainy Seasons	355
	6.6 Channel Morphological Constraints	356

	6.7 Quarrying and Dumping of Excavated Material	357
	6.8 Problem due to change in Land surface temperature	359
7	CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION	
	7.1 Conclusion	361
	7.2 Suggestion	377
	7.2.1 Terrain Classification and Rainwater harvesting	379
	7.3 Suggested Methods of Rain Water Harvesting	384
	7.3.1. Roof Top Rain Water Harvesting	384
	7.3.2. Watershed Ground Catchments rainwater harvesting systems in Overland flow and Runoff Zone	386
	7.3.3 The Rainwater Harvesting In Stream Line Zone	387
	REFERENCES	390
	PHOTOGRAPHIC PLATES	447
	1 to 25	

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Particulars of Figure	Page No.
Chapter I		
1.1	Concept of Groundwater	7
1.2	Location of Tittur River in Tapi Basin	12
Chapter II		
2.1	Location Map of the Tittur Basin	29
2.2	Physiography of the Tittur Basin	32
2.3	Geology of the Tittur Basin	34
2.4	Monthly Rainfall Distributions	42
2.5	Isohyetal Map of the Tittur Basin	43
2.6	Monthly Minimum and Maximum Temperature (°C) of the Tittur Basin	44
2.7	Pre Monsoon Land Surface Temperature	47
2.8	Post Monsoon Land Surface Temperature	48
2.9	NDVI Taxonomy of Year 1990	52
2.10	NDVI Taxonomy of Year 2010	53
2.11	NDVI Change Detection	54
2.12	Vegetation Density Map of Year 1990	55
2.13	Vegetation Density Map of Year 2010	56
2.14	Soil Map of the Tittur Basin	58
2.15	Land use Map of the Tittur Basin	61
2.16	Transportation and Communication Map of the Tittur Basin	63

Chapter III		
3.1	Sub Basin wise Catchment area of the Tittur Basin	82
3.2	Strahler Stream Order Drainage Network Map of the Tittur Basin	86
3.3	Tittur Drainage Basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number	88
3.4	Pimpri sub basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number	89
3.5	Dungri sub Basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number	89
3.6	Valjhari sub Basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number	90
3.7	Gadad sub Basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number	90
3.8	Tittur drainage basin Stream order vs mean stream length	96
3.9	Pimpri sub basin Stream order vs. mean stream length	97
3.10	Dungri sub basin Stream order vs. mean stream length	97
3.11	Valjhari sub basin Stream order vs. mean stream length	98
3.12	Gadad sub basin Stream order vs. mean stream length	98
3.13	Length of Overland Flow Map of the Tittur Basin	102
3.14	Surface Water Flow Direction Map of the Tittur Basin	105
3.15	Stream Frequency Map of the Tittur Basin	110
3.16	Drainage Density Map of the Tittur Basin	113
3.17	Tittur Basin Stream Order Vs Mean Basin area	116
3.18	Stream Order wise Cumulative Catchment Area Map	118
3.19	Digital Elevation Model of the Tittur Basin	120
3.20	Relative Relief Map of the Tittur Basin	123
3.21	Dissection Index Map of the Tittur Basin	125
3.22	Slope Map of the Tittur Basin	127
3.23	Tittur Basin Stream Order Vs Mean Channel Slope	129
3.24	Channel Slope Map of the Tittur Basin	130

3.25	Longitudinal Profile of the Tittur River	133
3.26. 1 to 3.26. 10	Valley Cross Profiles	135 to 139
3.27	Superimposed profile of the Tittur Basin	141
3.28	Projected Profile of the Tittur Basin	141
3.29	Composite profile of the Tittur Basin	141
3.30	Strahler Hypsometric curve of the Tittur Basin	144
Chapter IV		
4.1	Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite Data (Annual)	160
4.1a	Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite Data (Jan. – Apr.)	161
4.1b	Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite Data (May. – Aug.)	162
4.1c	Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite Data (Sept. – Dec.)	163
4.2	Flow chart of Arc GIS / Arc CN Runoff Methodology	170
4.3	SCS Curve Number Map of the Tittur Basin	171
4.4	Runoff Map of the Tittur Basin	174
4.5	Annual Rainfall Runoff Relationships	181
4.6	Monthly Rainfall Runoff Relationships	182
4.7	Monthly Rainfall Runoff Pattern	184
4.8	Rainfall and Runoff Map of the Pimpri Sub Basin	185
4.9	Rainfall and Runoff Map of the Dungri Sub Basin	186
4.10	Rainfall and Runoff Map of the Valjhari Sub Basin	187
4.11	Rainfall and Runoff Map of the Gadad Sub Basin	188

4.12	Monthly Evaporation, Evapotranspiration and Potential Evapotranspiration	200
4.13	Hydrologic Soil Group Map of the Tittur Basin	210
4.14	Stage and Discharge Relationship	214
4.15	Flow Regimes of Tittur Basin	216
4.16	Water Balance of Tittur Basin	220
4.17	Water passage from the surface to Fracture zone aquifer and ultimately to springs	230
4.18	3D Diagram of Spring Location	231
4.19	Litholog of Hilly Area	235
4.20	Litholog of Foot Hill Zone area	235
4.21	Litholog of Plain Area	236
4.22	Litholog of Alluvial Plain	236
4.23	Observation Well Location Map of the Tittur Basin	238
4.24	Depth of Water Level (May 2009)	241
4.25	Depth of Water Level (Nov 2009)	242
4.26	Depth of Water Level (May 2010)	243
4.27	Depth of Water Level (Nov 2010)	244
4.28	Groundwater Fluctuation of year 2009	245
4.29	Groundwater Fluctuation of year 2010	246
4.30	Pimpri Well hydrograph	248
4.31	Dungri Well hydrograph	248
4.32	Valjhari Well Hydrograph	249
4.33	Gadad Well Hydrograph	249
4.34	Sub Basin wise Average Fluctuation of Groundwater Level in Open Well	251

4.35	Drawdown (m) and Recuperation (m) Rate of Tittur Basin	254
4.36	Water Table Contour Map of the Tittur Basin	258
4.37	Water Table Contour Map of the Tittur Basin	259
4.38	Groundwater Flow direction of the Tittur Basin	263
Chapter V		
5.1	Geomorphology Map of the Tittur Basin	279
5.2	3D Diagram of Valley fill, Talus, Escarpment, Ridge (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	285
5.3	3D Diagram of Dyke (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	285
5.4	3D Diagram of Structural hill, Pediment and Pedepain Zone (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	293
5.5	3D Diagram of Denudational Hills (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	293
5.6	3D Diagram of Dissected plateau (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	295
5.7	3D Diagram of Monadnock or Residual Hills (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	295
5.8	3D Diagram of Dendritic ridge (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	298
5.9	3D Diagram of Fault Ridges (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	298
5.10	Satellite image of Gully (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	302
5.11	Tor (Source: Image on Field work)	302
5.12	3D Diagram of Alluvial Plain (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	308

5.13	3D Diagram of Flood plain (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	308
5.14	Satellite image of Palaeochannel (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	312
5.15	Satellite image of Plunge pool (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	312
5.16	Satellite image of Stream pool (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)	313
5.17	Stream pool (Source: Image on Field work)	313
5.18	Lineaments Map of the Tittur Basin	323
5.19	Lineament Density Map of the Tittur Basin	327
5.20	Lineament Intersection Density Map of the Tittur Basin	329
5.21	Rose Diagram	331
5.22	Flowchart for groundwater potential zone using Geoinformatics techniques	340
5.23	Groundwater Potential Zone of the Tittur Basin	341
Chapter VII		
7.1	Hydro-Geomorphic Zones for the Rainwater harvesting	380
7.2	Recharge pit for the Rainwater harvesting	385
7.3	Recharge Trench for the Rainwater harvesting	385

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Particulars of Table	Page No.
Chapter II		
2.1	Physiographic divisions of Tittur basin	31
2.2	15 year mean climatic data of Tittur basin	41
2.3	Spatio-Temporal distribution of Vegetation Cover of Tittur basin	51
2.4	Vegetation Change Detection during 1990 – 2010	51
2.5	Land use/Land cover of Tittur drainage basin	60
2.6	Transport and Communication	62
Chapter III		
3.1	Drainage Basin Morphometric Parameters Used for the Tittur Basin	76
3.2	Tittur Drainage Basin Morphometric Parameters	77
3.3	Morphometric Parameters of Tittur Basin	78
3.4	Pimpri catchment Morphometric data	79
3.5	Dungri catchment Morphometric data	79
3.6	Valjhari catchment Morphometric data	80
3.7	Gadad catchment Morphometric data	80
3.8	Sub Basin Wise Morphometric Parameters of the Tittur Basin	81
3.9	Sub basin wise stream order, stream no. and stream length of Tittur Drainage basin	85
3.10	Bifurcation ratio of Tittur Drainage basin	92
3.11	Sub Basin wise Bifurcation Ratio	93

3.12	Stream Order wise Total Length, Mean Stream Length, Stream Length Ratio of the Tittur River basin	94
3.13	Stream Order wise Total Length of sub basin	95
3.14	Stream Order wise Mean Stream Length and Stream Length Ratio of sub basin	96
3.15	Basin wise Length of Overland Flow	103
3.16	Drainage Orientation	104
3.17	Sub Basin wise Perimeter, Area and length	106
3.18	Sub Basin wise Stream Frequency	109
3.19	Sub Basin wise Drainage Density	112
3.20	Stream Order wise basin area and Area Ratio	116
3.21	Relative relief	121
3.22	Slope category	126
3.23	Mean channel slope of Tittur drainage Basin	128
Chapter IV		
4.1a	Annual rainfall of surrounding gauging station in mm	151
4.1b	Annual rainfall of surrounding gauging station in mm	152
4.2	Average Annual Rainfall of surrounding Rain gauge station	153
4.3	Mean areal Rainfall by Isohyetal Method	154
4.4	Rainfall Zone base on TRMM Satellite data	159
4.5	Monthly Rainfall base on TRMM Satellite data	159
4.6	Yearly Runoff of Tittur Basin	172
4.7	Monthly Rainfall base on TRMM Satellite data and Estimate Runoff using SCS CN method	172
4.8	Sub basin wise Mean Annual Rainfall and Runoff	175
4.9	Mean Monthly Evaporation data for Tittur basin	192

4.10	Monthly Evapotranspiration of Tittur basin	196
4.11	Monthly Potential Evapotranspiration of Tittur basin	199
4.12	Monthly Soil moisture Retention of Tittur basin	204
4.13	Hydrologic Soil Infiltration Rate	208
4.14	Actual Infiltration and Initial abstraction of Tittur basin	209
4.15	Sub basin wise Time of concentration	212
4.16	Monthly Mean Discharge and Mean Stage Height of Tittur basin	215
4.17	Water balance for Tittur basin	218
4.18	Lithological units of Tittur basin	234
4.19	Seasonal Water Levels and Fluctuation of Open Wells in the Tittur Basin	240
4.20	Drawdown and Recuperation Levels of Four Representative Wells's	252
4.21	Measured Drawdown (m) and Recuperation (m) Rate of Four Representative Wells's	252
4.22	Reduced Groundwater level of Open well in Tittur basin	262
4.23	W.H.O. and B.I.S. Specifications for Drinking Water	266
4.24	Water Quality at Different Locations	267
Chapter V		
5.1	Types of Landform and there Hydgeomorphic units	278
5.2	Lineament Category (Length and Direction) and No. of Lineament	325
5.3a	Thematic layers, their categories and weights	338
5.3b	Thematic layers, their categories and weights	339
5.4	Groundwater Potential Zone of Tittur Basin	344
7.1	Rainwater harvesting potential	379

LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHIC PLATES

Plate No.	Particulars of Photographs	Page No.
1	Escarpment near Patna Devi	447
2	Dhaval Tirtha waterfall near Patna Devi	447
3	Plunge pool at Kedar Kunda Waterfall near Patna Devi	448
4	Fluvial Terrace at Dungri River near Chalisgaon	448
5	Pothole at Dungri River near Pital Khora Caves, Chalisgaon	449
6	Pothole at Dungri River near Pital Khora Caves	449
7	Steep Slope and Dense vegetation in source area	450
8	Escarpment, Steep Slope and Dense vegetation in source area	450
9	developed Forest Soil Profile (Shallow Black Soil) near Saigavan	451
10	Structural Hills (Background), pediment and Pedepain (Foreground)	451
11	Colluviums Deposit near Patna Village	452
12	Alluvium deposit along Dungri River near Patna village	453
13	Balancing Stone at the top of Dyke	454
14	Mass movement on Dyke	454
15	Expose basalt at the Top of Dyke	455
16	Basalt with vertical joints at the Top of Dyke	455
17	Red Bole inter trap bed near Autrom Ghat area, Chalisgaon	456

18	Red Bole and Green Bole near Autrom Ghat area, Chalisgaon	456
19	Near surface water table (October) Neri open well	457
20	Near surface water table (October) Chalisgaon open well	457
21	Low water table (May) Lohatar open well	458
22	Escarpment and Talus near Patna Devi Temple	458
23	Landsat TM 5 Satellite Image (Band 123) Date: 09-10-2009	459
24	Landsat TM 5 Satellite Image (Band 234) Date: 09-10-2009	460
25	ASTER Satellite Image (Band 3b, 2, 1) Date: 26-05- 2010	461

CHAPTER I
INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

1.2 Hydrogeomorphology

1.3 Groundwater

1.4 Occurrence of Groundwater in Deccan Trap Formation

1.5 The Study Area

1.6 Selection of the study area

1.7 Aims and Objectives

1.8 Literature Review

1.9 Methodology

1.10 Approach

1.11 Research design/Outline of study

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Geomorphologist increasingly recognizes that the way, water is delivered to and moves through a hill slope, river, or landscape affects surficial processes and geomorphic form. Hydrogeologists recognize that geomorphology drives the spatial and temporal distribution of shallow groundwater. But both groups have sometimes seemed to lack the vocabulary and interdisciplinary tools to facilitate making advances truly at the intersection of geomorphology and hydrogeomorphology (Anne Jefferson, 2010). The drainage basin is a well-defined geomorphic unit of a fluvial landscape. It is defined as a catchment area, which contributes water to a particular channel or a set of channels in a network (Leopold, et al.1964). Drainage basins are created, shaped and structured by nature in some orderly manner, which exhibits the interdependence of meteorological, hydrological and geomorphologic factors. Hydrologists, earth scientists and geomorphologists have made their efforts to understand and synthesize hydrologic response of a drainage basin to morphologic, topographic features and established a relationship between fluvial geomorphology and hydrology to formalize the term 'Hydrogeomorphology'. The term Hydrogeomorphology can be divided into three terms hydro- means water including both surface and groundwater: geo- means the earth and morphology- is the surface expression of the features in the form of landforms. This means that the hydrogeomorphology is dealing with the aspects of water, rocks and earth's morphological features (land). Of these water and land are most important natural resources for human beings. Water is synonymous with

life. This is a natural resource and an absolute necessity for the survival of the living beings. Human beings have an organic relationship with water. For living and livelihood beings solely depend upon the availability of water. Water and land are the most important natural resources to human beings. For living and livelihood, human beings solely depend upon the availability of water. Most of the ancient culture of the world grew on the banks of the river. Rivers have been always the major source of water for different purposes.

1.2 Hydrogeomorphology

Hydrogeomorphology has been defined as “an interdisciplinary science that focuses on the interaction and linkage of hydrologic processes with landforms or earth materials and the interaction of geomorphic processes with surface and subsurface water in temporal and spatial dimensions (Sidle and Onda, 2004).”

The term 'hydro-geomorphology' designates the study of landforms caused by the action of water (Scheidegger, 1973). By this definition Hydro-geomorphology is inseparable part of geomorphology moreover fluvial geomorphology, because water is one of the most important agents in forming and shaping of landforms (Babar, 2005). From the groundwater point of view integration of geological, structural and hydrological data with hydro-geomorphologic data is very much useful in finding out the groundwater potential zones with fruitful results. The science relating to the geographical, geological, and hydrological aspects of water bodies and to changes to these aspects in response to low variations and to natural and human caused events, such as heavy rainfall or channel straightening is the hydro-geomorphology.

Hydrogeomorphology of a drainage basin is a function of rainfall kinematics, surface topography, morphology, basin shape, stream network and runoff etc (Magar, 2007). Hydrogeomorphology describes and evaluates the environment, in which water circulates, thus providing the information to understand the situation and to make the proper decisions (Verstappen, 1983). Quantitative study of drainage basin provides the theoretical base for the hydrogeomorphic approach, suggesting that certain unvarying drainage basin characters can be correlated to the hydrologic response of a basin. The measurable description of a drainage basin can be grouped in to linear aspect of channel network, areal aspect of drainage basin, relief aspect of channel system and basin form (Chorley, 1969). ***Hydro-geomorphology is science that deals with occurrences of water with respect to landform.*** All these aspects are regarded as the potential to describe hydrogeomorphic properties of the drainage basin. Because of non-availability of hydrological data, discharge data and sediment load data over a sufficient period of time in unguaged catchments, various investigators have used the drainage basin parameters to study the hydrogeomorphology of the drainage basin. Hydrogeomorphic studies of drainage basin often suffer a setback due to lack of long-term data. Therefore, there is need to extrapolate the results of few small subsystems to other hydrologically and geomorphologically similar basins, which mostly remain unguaged for want of enormous resource and time involved in instrumentation and monitoring them. Importance of hydrology for geomorphological purposes has been increasingly appreciated among geomorphologists in the last few decades. Earlier geomorphologists were bounded to use different unconventional approach to evaluate the characteristics of rivers and drainage basins to get proper idea of various aspects of the water

crisis. Horton pioneered the hydrologic and hydromorphometric analysis of basin and provided a rational and systematic base (Horton, 1945). He framed the geomorphic parameters with hydrologic parameters of the drainage system. Thus hydrological criteria not only assist the geomorphologists to evaluate the hydrogeomorphic characteristics of a drainage basin also facilitate their extrapolation in space and time.

1.3 Groundwater

Water flowing through streams, rivers, canals, stored in reservoirs, lakes and oceans is termed as surface water, while the soil, vadose and phreatic water lying below the surface is known as subsurface or groundwater (Chorley, 1969). Groundwater is water located beneath the earth's surface in soil pore spaces and in the fractures of rock formations. A unit of rock or an unconsolidated deposit is called an aquifer when it can yield a usable quantity of water. The depth at which soil pore spaces or fractures and voids in rock become completely saturated with water is called the water table. Groundwater is recharged from, and eventually flows to, the surface naturally; natural discharge often occurs at springs and seeps. Groundwater is also often withdrawn for agricultural, municipal and industrial use by constructing and operating extraction wells. Typically, groundwater is thought of as liquid water flowing through shallow aquifers, but technically it can also include soil moisture, permafrost (frozen soil), immobile water in very low permeability bedrock, and deep geothermal or oil formation water. Groundwater is hypothesized to provide lubrication that can possibly influence the movement of faults.

Groundwater constitutes about 30% of the world's total fresh water and 99% of its total stock of liquid fresh water (Shiklomanov & Sokolov,

1983). Groundwater is a crucial link in the hydrologic cycle because it is the source of most of the water in rivers and lakes. Groundwater is also important as the direct source of water withdrawn for domestic water use, irrigation and industrial uses worldwide (Dingman, 2002). It can be optimally used and sustained only when quality and quantity of groundwater is assessed. The lack of standard methods for estimating groundwater quality and quantity leads to false results of groundwater estimation. Therefore it is essential to maintain the proper balance between the groundwater quantity and its exploration. Large scale depletion of groundwater level has ultimately caused a serious problem for sustainable agricultural production. The surface water is mostly used by the urban population for domestic and industrial purposes. The groundwater is the main source for irrigation and domestic consumption in rural areas. Rural population largely depends on this groundwater source. In the state like Maharashtra, out of total cultivated land, only 8 percent of land is having canal irrigation and 70 percent of agricultural land gets water supply from open wells, dug wells and bore wells. In India approximately 40 percent of land is being irrigated by groundwater.

Naturally, hydrologists, geologists, engineers and geomorphologist need to concentrate their efforts to tap the groundwater. Tapping of groundwater is very difficult due to variation in the climatic, geologic, geomorphic conditions. In view, hydrogeomorphological investigations will help to locate and demarcate potential zones for groundwater to reduce the failure of bore wells, is of paramount importance in developing countries. The Deccan basaltic terrain in general and the Tittur drainage basin in particular, are no exception to these facts.

Fig. 1.1 Concept of Groundwater

1.4 Occurrence of Groundwater in Deccan Trap Formation

The 'Deccan Trap' , represents extensive horizontally bedded lava flows of Cretaceous-Eocene period, is the most extensive geologic formations of the Peninsular India, covering an area about 5,20,000 Sq. km and extends over most parts of Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra and in some parts of Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka (Dikshit, 1986). The Deccan Traps are a large igneous province located on the Deccan Plateau of west-central India (between 17°–24°N, 73°–74°E) and one of the largest volcanic features on Earth. They consist of multiple layers of solidified flood basalt that together are more than 2,000 m (6,562 ft) thick and cover an area of 500,000 km² (193,051 sq mi) and a volume of 512,000 km³ (123,000 cu mi). The term "trap", used in geology for such rock formations, is derived from the Swedish word for stairs and refers to the step-like hills forming the landscape of the region. The Deccan Traps

formed between 60 and 68 million years ago (Sheth, 2006) at the end of the Cretaceous period. The bulk of the volcanic eruption occurred at the Western Ghats (near Mumbai) some 65 million years ago. This series of eruptions may have lasted less than 30,000 years in total (CHENET, Anne-Lise et al, 2005). The original area covered by the lava flows is estimated to have been as large as 1.5 million km², approximately half the size of modern India. The Deccan Traps region was reduced to its current size by erosion and plate tectonics; the present area of directly observable lava flows is around 512,000 km² (197,684 sq mi).

It is postulated that the Deccan Traps eruption was associated with a deep mantle plume. The area of long-term eruption (the hotspot), known as the Réunion hotspot, is suspected of both causing the Deccan Traps eruption and opening the rift that once separated the Seychelles plateau from India. Seafloor spreading at the boundary between the Indian and African Plates subsequently pushed India north over the plume, which now lies under Réunion Island in the Indian Ocean, southwest of India. The mantle plume model has, however, been challenged (Sheth, 2006). Data continues to emerge which supports the plume model. The motion of the Indian tectonic plate and the eruptive history of the Deccan traps show strong correlations. Based on data from marine magnetic profiles, a pulse of unusually rapid plate motion begins at the same time as the first pulse of Deccan flood basalts, which is dated at 67 million years ago. The spreading rate rapidly increased and reached a maximum at the same time as the peak basaltic eruptions. The spreading rate then dropped off, with the decrease occurring around 63 million years ago, by which time the main phase of Deccan volcanism ended. This correlation is seen as driven by plume dynamics (Cande & Stegman, 2011). The Indian and African plate's motions have also been

shown to be coupled, with the common element being the position of these plates relative to the location of the Réunion plume head. The onset of accelerated motion of India coincides with a large slowing of the rate of counterclockwise rotation of Africa. The close correlations between the plate motions suggest that they were both driven by the force of the Réunion plume (Cande & Stegman, 2011).

Approximately 80 percent of total geographical area is occupied by Deccan Trap formation Maharashtra which is well known for its remarkable horizontality, characteristic flat topped hills and stepped like terraces. Groundwater in Deccan basalt mostly occurs under confined conditions, particularly in the broad river valleys. These valleys are characterized by thick weathered zones and alluvium deposits along the river banks. Occurrence of groundwater under confined conditions is a very rare phenomenon in Deccan Trap province. From the hydrogeological point of view, the frequency and extent of jointing, fracturing, flow contents and weathering along them are the most significant parameters imparting permeability and porosity for the formation of suitable groundwater reservoirs in the basaltic terrain. During the last three decades remarkable progress regarding groundwater exploration has been made in developed and developing countries of the world. Integration of hydrology, geology, geomorphology and geophysics in addition to conventional techniques has made it possible to explore the groundwater potentiality in hard rock terrain like Maharashtra.

Hydrogeomorphological study stresses the role of surface and subsurface features, geomorphological factors leading to get the knowledge about the environmental situation in which ground water occurs. Hydrogeomorphic conditions sometime vary within a short distance so that two adjacent wells also show a different yield of water.

Therefore it becomes a very difficult to formalize the groundwater scenario. These are the condition which provides a unique opportunity to a researcher for studying the problem of groundwater occurrence in the north Maharashtra. The present study attempts to analyze the hydrogeomorphic characteristics of the Tittur drainage basin. Tittur River is a Seventh order river basin of the Girna River, subsystem of Tapi river system in north Maharashtra. The hydrogeomorphic study of such a small basin can be applicable to any of other drainage basins with similar litho-climatic and geoenvironmental conditions for designing and development of watershed Planning and development activities in a drainage basin area can be efficiently implemented by following the hydrogeomorphological criterion. This study will provide a simple mean to compare it with other basin to regionalize the experimental results.

1.5 The Study Area

The Tittur River is a Seventh order river basin of the Girna River, subsystem of Tapi river system in north Maharashtra, rises in the Ajanta Satmala range hills. The total length of Tittur River is 76.67 km from its source at Motha Mahadev hill to confluence with its parent stream near Chalisgaon. It is a major right bank tributary of Girna River. The river drains an area about 970.10 sq. km. The Tittur River Basin is approximately elongated in shape having its broad base towards South and north. It extends in south-north direction for about 20 km and east-west for about 57.72 km. All geographical details about the study area have been discussed in the second chapter.

1.6 Selection of the study area

Criteria for the selection of the study area have been made on the basis of following characteristic features of Tittur basin.

1. The Tittur River Basin is located in the southern side of Tapi Graban, near foot hill of Ajanta Satmala range.
2. It is a non-perennial river, having discharge only during June to December every year.
3. Tittur Valley floor is more flat in northeastern and central part and southern part is steeper.
4. The shape of valley is asymmetrical. This asymmetry is evident from receiving large number of tributaries from right side and less numbers from left side.
5. The southern side of basin is characterized by hill range and steep escarpments.
6. The basin receives heavy monsoon rainfall in its source area that is in southern part, whereas the northern and western part receives moderate to low rainfall.
7. Depth of weathering varies from south to north and from west to east, which exhibits a variation in groundwater table.
8. Though the Tittur River is seventh order tributary of Girna River system, subsystem of Tapi basin, it exhibits its own identity in various erosional and depositional features within watershed.

Tittur River location in Tapi Basin

Fig. 1.2 Location of Tittur River in Tapi Basin

1.7 Aims and Objectives

Inadequate supply of water for domestic and agricultural purposes has become a challenging problem in semiarid regions. Therefore it is necessary to formulate a strategy for the optimum utilization of groundwater resources of the region concerned. In the present study, hydrogeomorphological investigation method has been used to evaluate groundwater resource of the Tittur Basin.

The basic aim of this study is to analyze the hydrogeomorphic characteristics of the Tittur Basin. In order to serve this aim, following objectives have been put forth.

1. To understand the environmental profile of the study area
2. To study basin hydrology of the Tittur Basin
3. To analyze the basin morphometry of the Tittur drainage basin
4. To study different fluvial landforms with reference to hydrogeomorphic significance.
5. To examine the hydrogeomorphic problem in the study area.
6. To demonstrate complex interdependence between drainage basin characteristics, geomorphic processes and hydrologic response of the drainage basin.
7. To carry out a detail literature survey particularly for understanding the drainage basin hydrology and morphometry of the Tittur Basin.

1.8 Literature Review

The term hydrogeomorphology has not been widely adopted by American geoscientists, although work at the intersection of hydrology and geomorphology is increasingly common and useful for identifying hazards and understanding the impacts of land use and climatic change. Japanese geologists have published a number of outstanding works examining the role of surface and subsurface flow regimes and flowpaths on fluvial erosion and mass wasting, and ecologists have found the concept of hydrogeomorphology useful to describe the linked water and geomorphic conditions that define habitats in wetlands, rivers, and other environments.

The study of subsurface water generally includes its chemical and physical properties, geologic environment, natural environment, recovery and utilization. For many years this subject has been called hydrogeology by many researchers from western world (De Wiest, 1965). The study of geomorphology and hydrology in analysis of drainage basin has become increasingly important since last two decades. Geomorphology is found to have very close links with both surface and subsurface water conditions. A main asset of geomorphology is that it aids to describe and evaluate the environment in which water circulates. Ample research has been done in hydrology and geomorphology separately with regards to surface and groundwater conditions in India and abroad. But hydrogeomorphology in general and river basin hydrogeomorphology in particular remained more or less unattended by the researchers in India. It is evidenced from the survey of literature on basin hydrogeomorphology for hard rock terrain or Deccan Trap region.

Meinzer (1942) and Mead (1950), authors of classical text books on hydrology have stressed the special character of the groundwater as geologic-geomorphic factors which forms and develops the rivers and drainage system. Chorley (1969) in his book 'Water Earth and Man' has made significant contribution towards occurrence and movement of groundwater as well as its geomorphic effect on rocks. The subject matter of this book is confined only to water and its movement through hydrologic cycle. Shukla and Verma (1973) studied morphometry in relation to slope development in sub Himalayan Siwalik ranges of Dehradun valley whereas Mithal et al. (1982) and Rawat (1982) carried out hydromorphometric studies in Garhwal Himalayas to mark the variations in morphometric parameters according to rock types. Bhamare (1983) studies Morphometric Analysis of Panzara River and its important Tributaries. Roohani and Gupta (1988) studied the relationships between hydromorphometric parameters and inferred that the channel network lacked morphometric similarity or steady state for which the hydromorphometric relations exhibited deviations from the widely accepted norms. Muley et al. (1988) attempted to study the geomorphological and hydrological properties of small watershed from Balaghat hills from the groundwater point of view to conclude that geological and hydrological characters of the watershed are suitable for increasing the groundwater potentiality. Similarly Bhamare (1990) studied Calcretes and Ground – Water Potentiality in the Panzara Basin to conclude that Calcretes formation has wide potential of Groundwater. Kulkarni (1991) analyzed a fourth order drainage basin from Deccan basaltic terrain and established a correlation between hydrogeological properties and drainage basin characters. Brown and Bradley (1995) book

on geomorphology and groundwater reflects an increasing convergence between recent research in geomorphology, groundwater hydrology and hydrogeology. All the chapters have concentrated on the role of geomorphology in the location, evaluation of groundwater resources. National Institute of Hydrology Report (1992) on hydrogeomorphological study of Tawi catchment states that in absence of sufficient network of hydrologic observation sites, the derived geomorphic parameters of the basin can be used for hydrologic studies. Bhamare (1996) studied Chemical characteristics of ground water in Burai Basin

As far as hydrogeomorphology of small basins or ungauged basins is concerned, there are very few studies from Deccan upland Maharashtra. No published literature is available directly on drainage basin hydrogeomorphology of small catchments on Deccan upland Maharashtra.

Recent Advances in Hydrogeomorphic Studies

A fair amount of literature is available on groundwater potential zone mapping, prioritization of watershed, geophysical surveys, integrated studies on remote sensing and geographical information system for groundwater exploration from southern states and Northern plains of India. Since 90's, several studies have attempted to identify and explain the spatial variability of groundwater occurrence in different terrain conditions using remote sensing and geographical information system. Horton, R.E. (1945) studied Erosional development of streams and their drainage basins: hydrophysical approach to quantitative morphology. Lohmann and Robinove (1964) mentioned the importance of landform evaluation in terms of lithology as a clue to the prevailing water bearing prospects. Bhamare (1985) attempt to studied Morpho Hydrological

Analysis of Panzara Basin. Howard, et al. (1992) studied Hydrogeologic evaluation of fracture permeability in crystalline basement aquifers of Uganda. G. Shankar Narayana (1996) studied Hydrogeomorphological study base on Remote sensing of Mulug Taluka. Y Srinivasa Rao et al. (1997) evaluated hydrogeomorphological conditions of Niva River in Andhra Pradesh by using satellite imagery for groundwater potential zonation; whereas Kumar and Tomar (1998) carried out geophysical and hydrogeomorphological survey to delineate groundwater potential zones from remotely sensed data of Godavari sub watershed of Bihar. Lineament studies have been carried out to delineate various hydrogeomorphic units for groundwater development by Raju et al. (1995) in Cuddapah, Andhra Pradesh. Another study by Sankar K (2000) study Hydrogeomorphological studies in the Trichirappalli environs, Tamil Nadu, India using Remote Sensing technology. Devi et al. (2001) reveals that integration of remotely sensed data, geomorphology and lineament study gives the best results to delineate groundwater prospect zones. Bajpai and Mahanta (2003) classified Gurgano-Sohna region of Haryana into different hydrogeomorphic units in relation to aquifer disposition with LANDSAT MSS images.

Similar attempts have been made by numerous scholars for mapping groundwater potential zones (Venkatachalan, et al, 1991; Krishnamurthy et al., 1996; Saraf and Chaudhary, 1998; Sankar, 2002; Khan and Mohorana, 2002; Murthy et al., 2003) as well as for generation of different thematic maps for the delineation of groundwater potential zones in different parts of the country (Gopinath and Seralathan, 2004; Chakraborty and Paul, 2004; Lokesh, et al., 2005; Vittala, et al., 2005; Nag, 2005). Kale (1980) has dealt with the evolution of slopes in Shivganga River Basin. M.D.Babar (2005) wrote a book entitle

Hydrogeomorphology: Fundamental application Techniques. Bhamare and Magar (2007) studied Hydro- geomorphic Analysis of Shivganga Basin Pune, Ground water Exploration GIS Approach. Bhamare and Agone (2011) studied on Land Surface Temperature change detection concern with hydrogeomorphich processes on Tapi river basin. Shukla Acharjee (2012) wrote book on Assam, A Remote Sensing and GIS Approach

As far as Tittur Basin is concerned, there is no detail investigation related to groundwater studies have been carried out so far, except few studies have been conducted on a totally different aspect such as Rainwater harvesting, Vegetation change detection, whereas the Bhamare (2010) studied Rain Water Harvesting & Water Resource Planning in Watershed: A GIS Application on Tittur basin. Bhamare and Agone (2011) studied change detection of Vegetation cover using NDVI Taxonomy of Tittur basin.

Hydrogeomorphology and Morphometry

Number of studies related to geomorphology and hydromorphometry has been carried out by different scholars. Large number of variables like basin shape, drainage density, stream length, stream ordering bifurcation ratio etc have been considered for the evaluation of hydrology, geology hydrogeomorphological parameters of drainage basins. A great amount of research has focused on drainage basin geometric characteristics to define hydrologic and geomorphic significance for groundwater studies. Horton (1945) pioneered the theoretical base for hydrogeomorphic approach by suggesting that certain unvarying basin characteristics can be correlated to the hydrologic response of a basin. Patton (1988) incorporated the unit hydrograph theory with basin topology to generate hydrograph and to

understand interrelationship between climate and morphometry. Bhamare (1992) studied Quantitative Measure of Drainage Development to modified Horton (1945) law of drainage composition. Morphometric properties of sub basins of Purna River were analyzed by Babar and Kaplay (1998) to explain their interrelationship on the basis of law of drainage composition. Raju et al. (2003) evaluated the geomorphic stage of a watershed from Andhra Pradesh by using remote sensing data to get sediment yield, erosion, intensity, land use and land cover.

It is evident from above discussion that geomorphological studies for hydrological purposes should not only stress subsurface water conditions but also the environment in which it occurs. It is also understand that in practice it is not feasible to separate the links between geomorphology and subsurface water resources completely but these two components are strongly interwoven.

1.9 Methodology

In order to understand hydrogeomorphic environment of the Tittur Basin, the methodology adopted for the present study is divided in five phases.

In the first phase, topographical maps published by Survey of India on 1:50,000 scale were obtained for delineation of drainage basin network as well as other physical and cultural aspects. Entire catchment of the Tittur River was drawn from SRTM DEM. All the wet and dry streams, water divides and contours (20 meter interval) were traced from topographical map No. 46 L/15, 46 P/2, 46 P/3, 46 P/6 and 46 P/7. Drainage basin morphometric parameters such as drainage density, basin area, basin shape, basin perimeter, stream length, elongation ratio, stream

frequency, hypsometric relationship were computed from derived basin morphometric map using Arc GIS 9.3.1. A slope map of the area under study was prepared with the help of SRTM DEM data. These basin morphometric data was then used for hydromorphometrical analytical purpose.

During the second phase, extensive field surveys were carried out to understand the basin morphology, structure and processes operating over it, during the field survey, well inventory data were collected for pre-monsoon and post-monsoon period from open wells and observation wells of the study area. Well cross sections, lithology, well depth, well diameter, groundwater level, yield of these wells has been recorded in well inventory during this phase of the study. Field data was then transferred on the base map in order to prepare a groundwater contour map of the Tittur Basin showing the groundwater flow direction.

Various geomorphic features, landforms evolved due to geomorphic processes were observed in the field. This information and observation data was used for the preparation of geomorphological map of the study area. Geological details such as dykes, lineaments, faults were also observed and recorded the field datasheet to understand the geology of the areas.

Total volume of water flowing at bankfull stage through the main river channel was computed by measuring river channel cross section area. For which channel cross section of main stream was surveyed at Chalisgaon, Patonda and Lohatar village. During the third phase, secondary data was obtained from various government departments, agencies and institutes for analysis purpose. It includes monthly rainfall

date of eight rainfall stations for 15 years period from India Meteorological department, Pune to know the spatial distribution of rainfall over the area. Groundwater levels, well log data of observation wells was obtained from Central Groundwater Board, Nagpur. This data was then integrated with the well inventory data and field investigation data.

In the fourth phase, all the primary data and secondary data collected from field as well as from government departments were analyzed by using appropriate numerical and statistical techniques.

Extensive literature review was carried out during the fifth phase in which published reports, research journals, reference books; district gazetteers were collected from various research institutes, libraries. In this phase, the generated, collected, processed and analyzed data was used for final, representation of results in the form of maps, charts, graphs and diagrams with the help of advanced and latest cartographic techniques using GIS and Remote sensing. These maps, charts, graphs and diagrams were used to write final draft of the report.

1.10 Approach

The approach of the study is systematic, analytical and regional for medium size watershed. The present investigation is micro level and oriented toward the GIS and Remote Sensing Technology.

1.11 Research design/Outline of study

Entire study has been represented through the following chapter system.

The first chapter deals with introduction of the topic, basic concept of hydrogeomorphology, its definition and relation hydrology, geology, geomorphology of the drainage basin to evaluate the environment in which water circulates. Occurrence of groundwater in general and occurrence of groundwater in Deccan Trap formation in particular have been also discussed briefly. A major component of this chapter is devoted to the introduction of the study area, criterions for the selection of the study area, aims and objectives and the literature Survey. Literature survey part of this chapter deals with the geomorphology, hydrology, and recent advances in hydrogeomorphic studies, relation of hydrogeomorphology and morphometry and review of modern techniques Methodology adopted for the study is also discussed in detail.

Second chapter highlights the environmental profile of the study area that gives a detail account of location, extent and area coverage of the Tittur Basin in the Tapi Basin of Peninsular India. Physiography, geology, geomorphology, soil, Land Surface Temperature and climate of the Tittur Basin elaborates some of the surface, subsurface and weather characteristics of the study area that are necessary for the hydrogeomorphic investigations. Vegetation, land use, transportation, communication and population characteristics of the basin are also discussed in the last part of the chapter to know about socioeconomic status of the Tittur drainage basin.

Third chapter contains drainage basin morphometric properties of the Tittur Basin and its hydromorphometric characters with reference to

groundwater. Methodological approach for the computation and measurement of drainage basin parameters are given in the beginning of the chapter. Linear, areal, relief and slope aspects with different morphometric parameters in general and the Tittur Basin morphometry in particular is well described in the remaining part of the chapter. The role played by these morphometric parameters in groundwater analysis is also given at end of every parameter.

Fourth Chapter is divided in two major parts. Surface water hydrology of the basin containing rainfall runoff relationship, sub basin wise runoff contribution to main channel has been assessed using SCS CN method, from the field data and the data supported by government offices, Total annual runoff, evaporation, evapotranspiration, Potential evapotranspiration, Soil moisture retention, initial abstract and infiltration are also calculated based on empirical formulae. Second half of this chapter deals with assessment of groundwater resources of the basin. Based on well inventory data collected from the field, the lithological characteristics, aquifer characteristics, seasonal groundwater fluctuation and movement of groundwater have been discussed in detail. Quality of groundwater in the Tittur Basin have been also discussed in brief on the basis of water samples collected from the open wells and there laboratory analysis. Nine important water quality parameters were taken into consideration to get idea about the water quality status of the Tittur Basin,

Fifth Chapter presents detailed hydrogeomorphic significance of various landforms identified in the study area, structural, landform associated with hill slope, denudational and depositional landforms play a vital role for demarcating groundwater potential zones. The landforms identified in the study area include structural bills, denudational lineaments, dyke, colluvial deposits, alluvial deposits, pediment,

pedeplain, valley fills, flood levees etc. This chapter also summarizes the groundwater potentiality of each landform unit. Based on lineament and Geoinformatics analysis, five groundwater potential zones are demarcated in the Tittur Basin.

The sixth chapter includes hydrogeomorphic problems of the Study area. Various anthrop geomorphic factor affecting movement, direction and depletion of groundwater in the study area have been discussed in this chapter. Gulley erosion at the base of steep hillside slopes, siltation of percolation tanks, K. T. weir, river bank erosion, construction of roads, paving of surface, deforestation, quarrying, embankments along the bridge culverts changing agricultural practices, conversion of agricultural land for non agricultural purposes are some of the major factors that has caused changing groundwater scenario of the Tittur Basin.

The chapter seventh gives summary, results and conclusions drawn from the study. It also focuses on the significance of hydrogeomorphic studies in unguaged basins. The concluding remarks of the study can be certainly taken into consideration while implementing watershed development projects, water resources planning; water conservation practices at micro watershed level any other basin having similar geo-environmental and litho climatic condition.

CHAPTER II

ENVIRONMENTAL PROFILE OF THE STUDY AREA

2.1 Introduction

2.2 Location and Extent

2.3 Physiography

2.4 Geology

2.4.1 Deccan Trap Basalt

2.4.2 Red Bole

2.4.3 Dykes

2.4.4 Alluvium

2.4.5 Colluvium

2.4.6 Structural Geology

2.5 Climate

2.5.1 Rainfall

2.5.2 Temperature

2.6 Land Surface Temperature

2.7 Vegetation

2.8 Soil

2.9 Land use / Land cover

2.10 Transport and Communication

2.11 Population

2.12 Geomorphology

CHAPTER II

ENVIRONMENTAL PROFILE OF THE STUDY AREA

2.1 Introduction

Availability and distribution of surface and subsurface water in arid and semi arid region is normally control by physical environment that includes physiographic, climate, geology, geomorphology and soil. Apart from these physical factors land use, vegetation cover also controls the spatio-temporal availability and distribution of groundwater. The concept of a groundwater regime is based on the fact that the occurrence and distribution of groundwater is not merely a product of chance, but the consequence of a finite combination of climatic, hydrologic, geologic, topographic, ecologic and soil-forming factors that together form an integrated dynamic system. These factors are interrelated in such a way that each provides some insight into the functioning of the total system and thus serves as an indicator of local conditions of groundwater occurrence.

Many scholars (Mithal et al. 1982; Rawat, 1982; Raju et al. 1995; Saraf and Chaudhary, 1998; Khan and Mohrana, 2002) have considered the physiography, climate, soil, vegetation, geology, geomorphology and other natural factors that directly or indirectly govern the spatio-temporal distribution of groundwater which is inseparable part of hydrogeomorphology. Hydrogeomorphology not only concerns to the groundwater but also the surface water. In the context of hydrogeomorphology it is necessary to understand the environmental profile of the Tittar watershed. Therefore, in this chapter a detailed

account of study area, its location and extent, physiography, geology, geomorphology, climate, vegetation, soil, landuse, transportation and groundwater situation have been discussed.

1.2 Location and Extent

The Tittur River is a Seventh order river of Girna River in Tapi river basin. Tapi itself is one of the major West flowing rivers of peninsular India. Tittur is located in the rain shadow zone of Ajanta Satmal range in the Jalgaon and Aurangabad districts of Maharashtra state. Geographically, the Tittur drainage basin extends between 20°16' 16.18 " north to 20°40' 13.27 " north latitude and 74° 52' 35.77 " east to 75° 17' 33.69 " east longitude. Its basin covers an area of 970.10 sq. km and included in Survey of India topographical map No. 46 L/15, 46 P/2, 46 P/3, 46 P/6 and 46 P/7. Administratively the Tittur Basin is located in Chalisgaon, Bhadgaon and Pachora tahsil of Jalgaon district and Kannad and Soygaon tahsil of Aurangabad district; it has a near elongated shape with its broad base coinciding with the Ajanta Satmala hill range which marks the boundary between Tapi valley on the north and Godavari valley to the south. The outlet of the basin extends eastward over a distance of 57.50 km. The basin has North-South width of 23.42 km. The Tittur Basin is bounded by east-west stretching under foot hill of Ajanta Satmal hill range. The northern divide of Tittur Basin runs parallel to Girna River.

The Tittur River originates in the Ajanta Satmal range hill particularly from Motha Maha-Dev hill at an elevation of 889.920 meters above sea level and debouches in Girna River after traversing a distance of 76.67 km at an elevation of 248.10 meters MSL. Major course of the

Location Map

Fig. 2.1 Location Map of the Tittur Basin

river Tittur flows towards east for a distance 36.089 km, From the Chalisgaon city, and the main river course gradually flow straight towards east follow lineament, up to its confluence with the River Girna.

2.3 Physiography

Physiographically, Tittur drainage basin is situated on the Deccan Trap upland region on North Maharashtra and near foot hill of Ajanta Satmal range. It has strong foundation of Deccan Trap Basaltic lava flows. The study area lies between the Tapi basin extends over an area of 65145 sq. km. which is nearly 2% of the total geographical area of the country. It is bounded on the north by the Satpura range, on the east by the Mahadeo hills, on the south by the Ajanata range and the Satmal hills and on the west by the Arabian Sea. Tittur drainage basin is nearly 1.48 % of the total geographical area of the Tapi basin.

There are three well-defined physiographic regions in the basin, namely, hilly region, Piedmont and the plains. The hilly regions comprising Ajanta Satmala hills are well forested. The Piedmont located at the foot hill of Ajanta Satmala range, Piedmont flat is slightly undulating, residual landscape like hill. The plain areas are broad and fertile suitable for cultivation. Primarily, the basin consists of black soils. The Tittur drainage basin is bounded by the high hill Ajanta Satmala ranges comprising of Deccan Trap Basaltic lava flows. The height of these hills varies from 790 to 942 meter; many peaks are above 850 meter in height. The highest peak is observed in the

Gautal Reserve forest (942m) which is the highest peak in Ajanta hilly range. Absolute relief of the Tittur Basin is 693.60 meter AMSL.

On the basis of terrain characteristics, the Tittur Basin is broadly grouped into three physiographic divisions. These are as follow.

Table 2.1 physiographic divisions of Tittur basin

Hills, Hill Ranges, Escarpments	942 m to 550 m
Piedmont/Rolling topography	550 m to 400 m
Valley Plain/Flat Surface	400 m to 250 m

Area lying above 550 meter elevation is a hilly terrain having steep escarpments and hill ranges constitute 9.37 % of total basin area. Approximately 15.54 % of the basin area lies between 550 to 400 meter altitude which is characterized by gently sloping land, dissected hills and dissected by streams and deep gullies. The plain surface or valley flat covers about 75.09 % of total basin area, characterized by veneer of alluvium.

The Tittur drainage basin has developed typical trappean topography which exhibits step like features formed by different rate of weathering and erosion. All these physiographic features are very important for identifying groundwater potential zones in the Tittur drainage Basin.

Fig. 2.2 Physiography of the Tittur Basin

2.4 Geology

The Tittur River Basin has located on thick pile of basaltic lava flows, which are commonly referred as Deccan Traps of Upper Cretaceous to Palaeogene period. The Deccan Traps are made up of several lava flows with the thickness of individual flow varying from few meters to as much as 30 meters (Deshpande, 1998). These lava flows exhibit the differential rate of weathering and erosion in the Tittur Basin. These lava flows are intruding by prominent dykes of varying thickness from 2-5 meters and trending NW-SE direction. A veneer of alluvium is observed along the mainstream and on valley floors, particularly in the northern-central part of the basin. The area of Tittur drainage basin forms part of the Deccan Trap region of Maharashtra. Secondary minerals such as jasper, chalcedony and other allied siliceous materials occur in abundance as veins or small lenticular patches in the traps, and these were mainly exploited in the Middle and Upper Paleolithic and Mesolithic periods (Sali, 1973). Since the landscape at Tittur basin, as elsewhere in the central Tapi basin, has been developed on the Deccan Trap, its evolution has to be trace to the origin of hills by the accumulation of lava-flows in the Cretaceous and Eocene epochs. After the formation of the Trap the landscape witnessed major earth-

Fig.2.3 Geology of the Tittur Basin

movements which culminated in the formation of the great Tapti rift (Deshpande, 1948), in which the Tittur drainage basin is now situated.

The spatial distribution of various geological features and lithological units observed in the study area is presented in a geological map of the study area and the brief descriptions of different geological characteristics are given below.

2.4.1 Deccan Trap Basalt

The close of the Mesozoic era was marked by the outpouring of enormous lava flows which spread over vast areas of Western, Central, and Southern India. They issued through long narrow fissures or cracks in the earth's crust, from a large magma basin and are therefore called fissure eruptions. The rocks formed from lava flows are called trap basalt because of the step-like or terraced appearance of their outcrops, the term being of Scandinavian Origin (Krishnan, 1982). The predominantly 'tholeiitic' lavas of the Deccan appear to have erupted some 65(+/- 4) million year ago when the Indian continent was rapidly migrating northward (Chatterjee and Rudra, 1992). Basaltic lava flows with remarkable horizontally and step like appearance is observed over a greater part of the Tittur drainage basin. Approximately 30 meters of thick pile of basaltic lava flows can be seen at Ajanta Satmala hill ranges. The thickness of each individual flow varies from few meters to more than 30 meters. The basaltic lava flows can be grouped in to two main types namely 'Pahoehoe' and 'aa' flows. The thickness of 'pahoehoe' flow varies from less than a meter to several meters. Pahoehoe weathers easily and gives rise to mature type of topography with smooth hill

slopes, conical peaks and broad valley bottoms. Such features are rarely seen in the Tittur Basin; especially some flows are exposed in southern part of the basin. “aa” flows on the contrary, are resistant to weathering and are simple in nature consisting of homogenous sections displaying up to five sets of vertical joints. It occurs near Bhildari, Saighavan village. (20° 21' 02.77'' N Lat and 75° 07' 36.15'' E Long)

2.4.2 Red Bole

These rocks have considered being the result of successive outpouring of lava eruption during Cretaceous-Tertiary extinction event (K-T event) 60 million years ago. Each lava flow ranges in thickness from few meters to 30 meters. Red bole is a feature commonly observed in the Deccan Trap country (Deshpande, 1998). It is reddish brown in color comprising hydrothermally baked angular fragments of weathered basalts. It separates two basalt flows. The individual lava flow is often separated by thin layer of red clay materials names as ‘Red Bole’. Beside Red Bole the fresh water sediments also occur in between two beds of lava during considerable interval of time which elapsed between successive eruptions of lava which began at the close of Mesozoic era are known as intertrappean beds. Usually these beds are 0.70 meter to 3.50 meter thick but occasionally they are only 15 cm in thickness. They are not more than 4 to 5 km in a lateral extent. The red boles occurring at shallow depth acts as a good water bearing horizons while deep seated boles are generally hard, compact and impervious to groundwater. These intertrappean beds occur at Outrom Ghat area and in famous Pitalkhora cave, some intertrappean beds occur near carve surface by Dhaval Tirtha and Kedarkunda waterfall. Amphitheatre like geomorphological features, boulder blocks are observed along the hill ranges of the basin.

2.4.3 Dykes

An intrusive dyke is an igneous body with a very high aspect ratio, which means that its thickness is usually much smaller than the other two dimensions. Thickness can vary from few centimeters to many meters, and the lateral dimensions can extend over many kilometers. A dyke is an intrusion into an opening cross-cutting fissure, shouldering aside other pre-existing layers or bodies of rock; this implies that a dike is always younger than the rocks that contain it. Dykes are usually high angle to near vertical in orientation. These Dykes are younger than Deccan Trap. Though the dykes are very common phenomenon in Deccan Volcanic Province, they are very rare in the study area Dykes are linear fissure eruption features, which have formed during late cretaceous age. Dykes are represented by narrow elongated, linear ridges at some places or by linear valleys at other places. The Tittur Basin shows presence of 4 dykes of dolerite composition. The dykes are cut by joints parallel to the walls and at right angles to the walls besides horizontal joints. The dyke rocks are fine to medium grained plagioclase. Both dykes are 3-5 meter thick and trending in NW-SE direction and can be traced for about 1.13 to 4.65 km distance running parallel to each other. These dykes can be easily recognized near foot hill of Ajanta Satmala range. The Dykes play a vital role in the controlling the movement of groundwater. Hard and compact dyke acts as underground check dams restricting the groundwater movement in downstream direction, whereas soft, jointed, fractured dykes allow free movement of groundwater. The dykes present hard, impermeable basalt acts as a conduit for water.

2.4.4 Alluvium

Alluvium is loose, unconsolidated (not cemented together into a solid rock) soil or sediments, which has been eroded, reshaped by water in some form, and redeposited in a non-marine setting. An unconsolidated accumulation of stream-deposited sediments, include sands, silts, clays or gravels. A relatively narrow, flat surface consisting of pebbles, sand, silt and clay found along the river bank is known as alluvium. Alluvium is typically made up of a variety of materials, including fine particles of silt and clay and larger particles of sand and gravel. When this loose alluvial material is deposited or cemented into a lithological unit, or lithified, it would be called an alluvial deposit.

In the Tittur river basin, the alluvium occurs along the banks of major tributaries and along the main river bank. The well developed sections of alluvium can be seen at near chalisgaon on Dungri River. Apart from these sections, the alluvium can be seen in different well sections at Patonda and Vaghali village along master stream of Tittur drainage basin and main stream of Valjhari and Gadad River. The thickness of alluvium varies from few meters to 10 m at the sections mentioned above. Alluvium deposits are highly permeable zone that contributes water to partial recharge along the river bank side area and to the sub surface flow.

2.4.5 Colluvium

Colluvium is the name for loose bodies of sediment that have been deposited or built up at the bottom of a low-grade slope or against a barrier on that slope, transported by gravity. The deposits that collect at

the foot of a steep slope or cliff are also known by the same name (Madigan, 2007). Colluvium often grades into alluvium (deposits transported down slope by water). Coarse deposits due to rock fall at a cliff base are called talus (scree) and if lithified are talus breccias. Avalanches, mudslides, and landslides are processes that deposit colluvium. This build-up process is called colluviation. Colluvium is a type of parent material that moved down slope due to gravitational forces (in some cases water may play a role in initiation of the movement). Colluvium is heterogeneous, unsorted material of all particle sizes (from boulders to clay) with angular or relatively little abrasion to round the particles. Consequently, colluvium consists of very sharp, angular rock fragments accumulated at the base of steep slopes. Colluvium normally forms humps at the base of mountains or fan-shaped deposits similar in shape to alluvial fans that cover former ground surfaces. The colluvial deposit includes talus, cliff debris, rockfalls and soil creep which occur along the hillslopes, at the base of hills and escarpments in the Tittur river basin. At many places the colluvium consists of heterogeneous material ranging from rock debris, boulders, angular rock fragments to silt and the thickness of colluvium varies from few meters to 10 meter at various locations, well developed colluvium deposits with thickness of more than 10 meters have been observed at near Patna Devi. Presence of less resistant mineral such as plagioclase in the basalt as well as semi arid climate appears to be factors responsible for physical and chemical weathering of parent rock which gives rise to thick colluvial deposits in the study area.

2.4.6 Structural Geology

The Tittur basin is not severely disturbed in its geological history since it is a part of rigid mass of the Deccan table land. However, the Tittur basin is not free from the influence of tectonic activities of adjoining area; like Faulting of Tapi valley associated with Himalayan Orogeny and faulting activity in the western Ghat. Beside this later intrusion in the Deccan plateau like dykes also have significant impact on the Tittur drainage basin. Obviously, the present drainage pattern and drainage network orientation are an outcome of the aforesaid activities. The structural details of the Tittur basin influence its drainage lines which become a clue to identifying Faults, fractures, joints in the rock. However, the orientation of the drainage alone is a conclusive evidence of Faults. Tectonic phenomena like faults, fracture, joints identify using Landsat ETM+, Geo Eye satellite imaginaries and 3D analysis of DEM which have prove a major fault line in the Tittur drainage basin, it well known as south side of Tapi graben. Its orientation is west to east. Still another important phenomenon is observed in the Tittur basin i.e. the southern tributaries of Tittur basin join the main channel of river at right angle. It leads to the consideration that southern slope of tittur basin is steeper than northern slope. In the upper part of Dungri sub basin mostly tributary join to main channel at acute angle, its follow the major joint and fracture in the basalt.

2.5 Climate

Being a part of tropical monsoon type of climate in general and semiarid climate in particular, the Tittur river basin is characterized by medium to low rainfall and moderate temperature conditions. Table 2.2 shows metrological data of Tittur drainage basin.

Table 1.2 15 year mean climatic data of Tittur basin

Month	Max. Temp. °C	Min. Temp. °C	Max. Humidity %	Min. Humidity %	Wind speed km/Day
January	33	8.5	55	28	110.4
February	36.9	10.4	42	21	124.8
March	40.6	13.8	35	18	146.4
April	43.7	20.1	32	17	172.8
May	45.1	23	39	18	295.2
June	42.4	22.3	67	43	333.6
July	36.5	22	81	66	278.4
August	34.3	21.8	84	68	266.4
September	35.7	20.9	80	60	208.8
October	36.2	15.2	65	40	112.8
November	33.8	11.6	57	34	91.2
December	32.4	9	58	33	88.8

(Source: IMD Pune)

2.5.1 Rainfall

The rainfall is major parameter and is a precious natural resource. Of all the resources, climate has the most direct significance, on the general characteristic and broad pattern of hydrological activities. As the basin is situated in the rain shadow zone of the foot hill of Ajanta Satmal range, it receives about 707.76 mm of rainfall annually, about 90 percent of which occurs during June to September. July and August are the rainiest

months. The southern part (Gautala Sanctuary, Ajanta Satmal Hill ranges) of the basin receives heavy rainfall as compare to northern part. The rainfall gradually decreases from east to west; the mean areal rainfall of the Tittur Basin is 707.76 mm which is calculated from the available monthly rainfall data of 15 years record from the surrounding rain gauging stations (Chalisingaon, Bhadgaon, Pachora, Kannad, Vaijpur, Sillod, Malegaon and Nandgaon). The graph from annual total rainfall of these rain gauge stations for 15 years (1997 to 2011) is shown figure 2.4.

The mean monthly rainfall data from eight surrounding rain gauging stations was collected and analyzed by isohyetal method of rainfall distribution (Fig. 2.4). These rain gauge stations namely Chalisingaon, Bhadgaon, Pachora, Kannad, Vaijpur, Sillod, Malegaon and Nandgaon are located at equi-spatial distance surrounding to the area.

Fig. 2.4 Monthly Rainfall Distributions

Fig. 2.5 Isohyetal Map of the Tittur Basin

2.5.2 Temperature

The wet rainy season is followed by winter. The Tittur river basin experiences very hot summer and medium winter temperature. The mean maximum temperature of the study area is 32°C. It reaches to 45°C during the month of April and May. During winter, mean minimum temperature decreases up to 10°C. The diurnal range of temperature is minimum during July and August because of cloud cover. Maximum diurnal variation in temperature is recorded in the month of January and February. December is the coldest month; Figure shows the maximum and minimum temperature of the study area.

Fig. 2.5 Monthly Minimum and Maximum Temperature

2.6 Land Surface Temperature

Land surface temperature (LST), controlled by the surface energy balance, atmospheric state, thermal properties of the surface, and subsurface mediums, is an important factor controlling most physical, chemical, and biological processes of the Earth (Becker and Li, 1990). Land surface temperature is how hot the “surface” of the Earth would feel to the touch in a particular location. From a satellite’s point of view, the “surface” is whatever it sees when it looks through the atmosphere to the ground. It could be snow and ice, the grass on a lawn, the roof of a building, or the leaves in the canopy of a forest. Thus, land surface temperature is not the same as the air temperature that is included in the daily weather report. The maps shown here were made using data collected during the daytime by the Landsat 5 TM. In the Tittur basin Pre monsoon seasonal Temperatures range from 26 degrees Celsius to 47 degrees Celsius and the Post monsoon seasonal Temperatures range have been from 21 degrees Celsius to 32 degrees Celsius. Use of Land surface temperature maps like these to evaluate water requirements for their crops or vegetation during the summer, when they are prone to heat stress.

Evapotranspiration (ET) is a fundamental variable in the hydrological cycle and in any investigation of water and energy balances at the surface of the Earth. The rate of evapotranspiration is mainly controlled by the available energy, the availability of water, the humidity gradient away from the surface and the wind speed at the surface (Stisen et al, 2007). Evapotranspiration varies in time and space and is difficult to estimate as it depends on many interacting processes. At the local scale ET may be accurately estimated from detailed ground observations. At the regional scale sufficient ground observations will never be available and instead spatially distributed of Land surface Temperature data can be

used as proxies for important controlling variables. Hence, information on the spatial distribution of ET requires Land surface Temperature data and a number of simplifying assumptions due to under parameterization at the regional scale. The Land surface Temperature impact on soil moisture too, that's why to study of LST is important aspect in hydro geomorphic analysis.

In the Tittur basin LST varies in spatial distribution, Water bodies has lowest temperature on surface, while on the northern side LST has also low because of forest land. In the central part on the Tittur basin surface Temperature is high due to bare land and rocky surface. Almost in valley plain surface temperature have been low where there is agricultural practices activity.

The spatio- temporal Land surface temperature change detection in response to climatic change can be analyzed through hydrological regime in hydro-geomorphic physical entity like river basin, which could be affected by climatic variations in recent decades and may be resulted from the global warming (Bhamare and Agone,2011). The hydrological regime covers the changing condition of water and sediment discharge positions in river channel as well as Tittur basin area. The prominent channel change is aggradations. Aggradations lead to the decreases of channel capacity causing high floods even in low to moderate rainfall. The Tittur basin also faces the problems of depletion of water level in channel as well as water table and salinization of basin soil due to accelerated rate of evaporation with increase of the Land surface temperature.

Fig. 2.7 Pre Monsoon Land Surface Temperature

Tittur Basin Post monsoon Land Surface Temperature

Legend

Fig. 2.8 Post Monsoon Land Surface Temperature

2.7 Vegetation

Vegetation intercepts surface and subsurface water flowing from drainage basins and forms a functionally important interface between terrestrial and hydrological system. Vegetation cover influences hydrological processes directly by intersecting precipitation and so modifying the amount and delivery of precipitation to the ground surface, by affecting the partitioning of water between infiltration and overland flow and by affecting the rate of water transmitted through rock, soil or overland flow to the river network (Gurnell and Gregory, 1995). Vegetation has direct influence on hydrogeomorphological processes and through the response of vegetation to these processes.

As pointed out earlier that the area under study experiences semi arid climate, hence it shows sparse to scanty vegetation in its northern part as compare to southern part where relatively dense vegetation occurs. It comprises of tress, herbs and shrubs, grasses occupying valley plain, colluvial slopes and hill tops where significant soil cover is formed (Dikshit, 1986). The area with relatively thicker soil cover shows dense forest cover near Patna Devi, Bhildari and part of Gautala reserve sanctuary. Tall trees are found along the river bank and stream courses. Most of the central and northern part of study area is under cultivation with different crops. The reserve forest at Tittur basin is of dry deciduous type. The most common trees are Anjan (*Hardwickia Binnata*), Khair(*Acacia catechu*), Dhavda(*Anogeissus latifolia*) and Bor (*Zyzyphus jujube*). The salai (*Boswellia serrata*), Chandan(*Santalum album*), Teak(*Tectona grandis*), kahu or arjuna (*Terminalia arjuna*) also grow sparsely. Of the above species the Arjuna is most dominant at present. Central valley plain of the Tittur Basin following plant species are observed during the field survey; Bor (*Zyzyphus jujube*), Mango

(Magnifera Indica), Anjir (Ficus Carica), Peru (Psidium Guava), Jambhul (Eugenia Jamolana).

Using NDVI Taxonomy detect change in vegetation cover year from 1990 to 2010. NDVI a spectral index namely Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is an emerging technique from Remote Sensing and GIS technology to detect spatio-temporal change of vegetation cover for micro regions on the earth surface. The analysis of spatio-temporal change in vegetation cover and its density has a greater significance in taxonomy and understanding overall nature of biodiversity with response to recent climatic change (Bhamare and Agone, 2012). This paper analyses the spatio-temporal change and adopted NDVI Taxonomy in a micro region like Tittur basin of Tapi system in northwestern part of Maharashtra state during 1990-2010 based on landsat TM and ETM+ imageries. (IR and NIR band) of 16 Oct.1990 and 15 Oct. 2010.The NDVI has been worked out for detection of spatio-temporal change in vegetation cover for Tittur basin which ranges between -0.39to 0.74 and 0.On the basis of NDVI-Taxonomy the Tittur basin can be classified into four categories. The NDVI Value below zero indicates water bodies. The NDVI value above zero is further classified into three groups. Viz. 0.0-0.20 (Bare surface), 0.20- 0.46 (vegetation cover of scrub and stunted brushwood) and 0.46 to 0.74 (dense forest and cropland vegetation) .The temporal variation reveal the –ve change, +ve change and no change. The major part of the basin reveal +ve change. All the NDVI Taxonomy groups reveals increasing trend from 1990 to 2010 except bare surface. Tittur basin experience considerable decrease of bare surface, which is brought, either in cultivation or under forest. The density of vegetation also increased .This fact attributed to the increase in rainfall and anthropogenic efforts towards the water conservation. The

rainfall is increased by 70 mm during this decade and water reservoirs are increased. This fact certainly proves conservation of biodiversity. Recently, Gavatala National forest is developed and biodiversity is well protected in this region (Bhamare and Agone, 2012). Table show Spatio-Temporal distribution of Vegetation Cover of Titter basin during years 1990 and 2010.

Table 2.3 Spatio-Temporal distribution of Vegetation Cover of Tittur basin

Vegetation Cover	Year 1990			Year 2010		
	NDVI Values	Area in Sq.Km	Area (%)	NDVI Values	Area in Sq.Km	Area (%)
Water Body	-0.74-0.00	10.59	1.08	-0.39-0.00	20.05	2.06
Bare Land	0.00-.20	361.71	37.21	0.00-.20	130.76	13.455
Scrub and Grassland	0.20-.46	444.86	45.96	0.20-.46	545.24	56.290
Dense Forest cover and Crop land	0.46-.0.69	152.94	15.73	0.46-.0.74	274.05	28.194
Total	-0.74-0.69	970.10	100	-0.39-0.74	970.10	100

Table 2.4 Vegetation Change Detection during 1990 - 2010

Vegetation Change Detection	Area (Sq Km)	Area (%)
Increase area	621.64	64.15 %
Decreased area	30.57	3.14 %
Unchanged area	317.89	32.71 %

Fig. 2.9 NDVI Taxonomy of Year 1990

Fig. 2.10 NDVI Taxonomy of Year 2010

Tittur Basin NDVI Change Detection

Legend

Fig. 2.11 NDVI Change Detection

Fig. 2.12 Vegetation Density Map of Year 1990

Tittur Basin
**Vegetation Density
Map of Year 2010**

Legend

Density in %

Fig. 2.12 Vegetation Density Map of Year 2010

2.8 Soil

Soil is a natural body that consists of layers (soil horizons), composed primarily of minerals, which differ from their parent materials in their texture, structure, consistency, color, chemical, biological and other physical characteristics (Birkeland, 1999). The end result, soil, is the end product of the influence of the climate (temperature, precipitation), relief (slope), organisms (flora and fauna), parent materials (original minerals), temperature, and time. Soil is composed of particles of broken rock (materials) that have been altered by chemical and mechanical processes that include weathering with associated erosion. Soil is altered from its parent material by the interactions between the lithosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere, and biosphere (Chesworth, 2008).

As mentioned in the above, that the Tittur Basin is underlined by Deccan basaltic lava flows. At some places it is overlain by alluvium and colluvium that is along the stream courses and at the base of hill slopes respectively. Southern part of the basin is dominated by shallow black soil with thick and mature profiles. In the western and south central part, well developed blackish grey or medium black soil is observed with mature soil profiles. Black cotton soil occurs in the valley plain in the eastern and northern part of the basin. These soils have strong swelling and shrinking effect with the changes in the moisture content. The thickness of soil ranges from 15 cm to more than a meter depending upon its development. In the Tittur drainage basin forest soil also occur in southern part of basin (Fig. 2.14). The soil profiles developed in the Tittur Basin show considerable variation in the color, maturity and thickness. Slope of the ground is most important controlling factor in the soil development of Tittur Basin. Highly immature, thin soil profiles have

Fig. 2.14 Soil Map of the Tittur Basin

been observed on the moderately steep to steep slope (14° to 29°). The degree of maturity of soil profile increases when the degree of slope becomes almost level (1° -7°).

2.9 Land use / Land cover

Land use is the human use of land. Land use involves the management and modification of natural environment or wilderness into built environment such as fields, pastures, and settlements. It has also been defined as "the arrangements, activities and inputs people undertake in a certain land cover type to produce, change or maintain it" (FAO, 1997a; FAO/UNEP, 1999). According to Meyer, 1999 every parcel of land on the Earth's surface is unique in the cover it possesses. Land use and land cover are distinct yet closely linked characteristics of the Earth's surface. The use to which we put land could be grazing, agriculture, urban development, logging, and mining among many others. While land cover categories could be cropland, forest, wetland, pasture, roads, urban areas among others. The term land cover originally referred to the kind and state of vegetation, such as forest or grass cover but it has broadened in subsequent usage to include other things such as human structures, soil type, biodiversity, surface and ground water (Meyer, 1995).

Knowledge of land use and for hydrogeomorphological studies is important as far as planning and management activities in the watershed are concerned (Babar, 2005). It also affects the quality of groundwater. The land use pattern in the Tittur Basin roughly coincides with the physiography of the area. The broad valley flat of the basin is almost occupied by agricultural crops. On the southern side narrow valley plain is partly occupied by agriculture as well as scanty natural vegetation. The

flat topped hill ridges in the southern part of the basin are covered by reserved forest consisting of tiny shrubs, bushes, and trees. At some places these ridges and hill slopes in the northern part are consisting open scrub and Stony waste. Near the hill slopes having some pasture land as well as barren land, in some part of hill slopes are almost barren with very thin and small patches of grass cover. The Urban built-up area in the basin is located along the central railway and Dhule-Solapur national highway no. 211. Due to rapid urbanization, growth of small scale industries, use of pesticides and fertilizers in agricultural practices and deforestation, the quality of groundwater in the region has been badly affected. Figure (2.14) shows the Land use/Land cover pattern of the Tittur Basin.

Table 2.5 Land use/Land cover of Tittur drainage basin

Landuse Category	Area in sq.km	Area in %
Deciduous Forest	203.50	20.97
Scrub Forest	68.35	7.045
Agriculture, Crop Land	558.9	57.61
Agriculture, Fallow Land	27.91	2.87
Barren rocky Land	58.42	6.02
Barren scrub Land	4.66	0.48
Water Bodies	14.92	1.53
River / stream	14.69	1.51
Urban Built-up Land	9.84	1.01
Rural Built-up Land	8.91	0.91

Fig. 2.15 Land use Map of the Tittur Basin

2.10 Transport and Communication

Tittur basin is well accessed by Dhule - Solapur national highway no. 211. Highway passes through the Tittur Basin. Patonda, Nagad, Nagardevla, Waghali, Hirapur and Kajgaon are some of the largest settlements in the study area. These are well connected with State highway no. 24 and state highway no. 25 as well as district highways. A fairly good network of metalled roads and foot tracks connect all other habitations of the Tittur valley. The other important habitations are Pimpri, Patna Devi, and Ranjangaon. Within Tittur basin central rail also pass and it length is 51.21 km. Following table shows Road, Railway and it totals length in Tittur basin.

Table 2.6 Transport and Communication

Roads / Railways	Length
Central Broad-gauge Railway	51.21 km
National Highway	23.48 km
State Highway	46.69 km
Other Metalled and unmetalled Roads	884.33 km

Tittur Basin Transport and Communication

Legend

- Railway
- National Highway
- State Highway
- Other Roads
- Settlement

Fig. 2.16 Transportation and Communication Map of the Tittur Basin

2.11 Population

According to Census 2001, and 2011 total population of the Tittur Basin is 91110 and 142220 respectively. Administratively Tittur Basin comes under Chalisgaon, Bhadgaon, Pachora, Soygaon and Kannad tehsils jurisdiction during last two decade (1991-2011) considerable growth of population have been recorded in the Tittur valley due to rapid urbanization, The density of population in Tittur valley is 166 persons per sq. km which is quite high. Ranjangaon, Patonda, Nagad, Nagardevla, Waghali, Hirapur and Kajgaon are some of the highly populated villages of the Tittur Basin. Near about 80 % population depend on agriculture, so it highly need to study hydrogeomorphich analysis for Tittur basin watershed management.

2.12 Geomorphology

Geomorphology is scientific study of scenery; it is therefore concern with the study of the form and nature of the land surface as whole and of its various parts (Dixey, 1960) like the mountain and valley, plain at plateaux, rift and scarps, Lake Basin and river channel and many other features that go to make up the landscape. Geomorphology is the science of landforms it is a description of features on land such as mountains, lakes, rivers, glaciers or dunes. It also includes measurement of features, understanding the processes that have shaped them, history of their formation and examination of their constituent material (Kale and Gupta, 2001). It is the scientific study of landforms and the processes that shape them. Importance of geomorphology for water resources study purpose has been increasing since last few decades. Geomorphological knowledge of the area provides essential data on surface topographic features, their

characters, processes which enables to understand the landforms to make proper decisions (Schumm, 1964). Landforms affects directly or indirectly on hydrogeomorphic condition of the area.

The Tittur River is a major right bank tributary of Girna River and Girna River is subsystem of Tapi River of Peninsular India. It rises at hills of Ajanta Satmal ranges at an elevation of 893.54 meter. The river flows eastward for a distance of 12.21 km and then takes a gradual turn towards north for a distance of 21.63 km to meet its parent stream, river Tittur. The Tittur Basin has near elongated shape like bird wing, exhibiting dendritic drainage pattern. The main river flows easterly along nothern edge of the valley. Much of the contributing drainage is from south and west. Parallel and sub parallel drainage pattern is observed in southern part of the basin near foot hill, indicating structural control over the drainage development.

The Tittur river basin exhibits a variety of geomorphological features, developed under the influence of semiarid climate. Therefore the basin shows erosional and depositional landforms from its source to mouth. On the basis of landform assemblage, nature of its drainage, slope characters, erosional and depositional environment, three geomorphic zones are identified in the Tittur Basin.

Zone of High Relief, Deep dissection

Zone of moderate relief and moderate to gentle slope

Zone of alluvial plain, gentle slope

Zone of High Relief- Presents well drained mature landscape with subdendritic to rectilinear drainage pattern. Interfluves are linear, short and fluves are deeply entrenched. This zone forms the area of sediment generation with a very little deposition. The basin is bordered by this zone from southern sides. The absolute relief of this zone varies from 942 meter in the northern part to 500 meter in the western part of the basin. Steep escarpments, steep slopes, debris slopes are some of the major geomorphic features of this belt which ends into piedmont belt running along this zone. Steep slopes and escarpments are the indicators of the potential energy available for fluvial erosion in all its 1st to 2nd order tributaries.

Zone of moderate Relief, Moderate to gentle slope- In this zone, the slope gradually decreases from steep slope to moderately sloping land. This zone is drained by widely spaced, north flowing, sub parallel drainage with poorly developed flood plain.

Zone of Alluvial Plain- It extends from the moderate relief zone and abuts in the river channel or tributary channel. The central and northern part of the basin is occupied by alluvial plain with very low relief of 250 to 400m. It slopes gently from south sides of the basin towards northern side flowing Tittur river channel. The flat areas of the basin are typically formed due to alluvium and colluvium brought from adjacent landform category. A very narrow belt of flood plain is observed along the main river and its main tributary streams such as Dungri stream, Valjhari stream, and Gadada stream.

Slope- The basin shows convex, concave as well as rectilinear slope profiles indicating the structural and lithological control over the terrain. Fig 3.26.1 to Fig 3.26.10 in chapter IIIrd shows the slope profiles drawn

from the ridge top to ridge bottom along the basin boundary and inner area. Figure 3.22 shows the slope distribution in the Tittur Basin. Mass wasting processes at many places have developed talus cones, rock debris at the base of escarpments and hills. The size of these deposits ranges from large boulders to weathered gravels. The upper reach of the Tittur River is characterized by many erosional features like knick points, potholes and rapids near Pitalkhora cave, Patnadevi, Nagad, Bhildari and Valjheri villages. The lower reach of the river exhibits the features developed during present cycle of erosion such as waterfall and large potholes at Patnadevi, narrow and deep gorge from Patna Devi Temple to Pimperkhed village and deeply entrenched channel (5-6 m) bedrock channel right up to confluence. The Tittur River shows typical valley in valley topography with broad and gently sloping valley and a very narrow, deeply incised channel.

CHAPTER III
DRAINAGE BASIN MORPHOMETRY

3.1 Introduction

3.2 Database and Methodology

3.3 Various Aspects of Drainage Basin Morphometry

3.4 Linear Aspects of the Tittur Drainage Basin

3.4.1 Stream Order and Stream Number

3.4.2 Stream Order Vs Stream Number

3.4.3 Bifurcation Ratio (Rb)

3.4.4 Stream Length

3.4.5 Sinuosity Index (SI)

3.4.6 Length of Overland Flow

3.4.7 Drainage Orientation

3.5 Areal Aspects of the Tittur Drainage Basin

3.5.1 Drainage Basin Area

3.5.2 Basin Perimeter

3.5.3 Length of the Basin

3.5.4 Form Factor

3.5.5 Circularity Ratio

3.5.6 Elongation Ratio

3.5.7 Stream Frequency

3.5.8 Drainage Density

3.5.9 Constant Channel Maintenance

3.5.10 Area Ratio

3.5.11 Law of Basin Area

3.6 Relief Aspects of the Tittur Basin

3.6.1 Total Basin Relief

3.6.2 Relative Relief and Relief Ratio

3.6.3 Ruggedness Number

3.6.4 Dissection index

3.6.5 Basin Slope

3.6.6 Law of Channel Slope

3.6.7 Longitudinal Profile of the Tittur River

3.6.8 Valley Cross Profiles

3.6.9 Superimposed, Projected and composite profile

3.6.10 Percentage hypsometric curve

CHAPTER III

DRAINAGE BASIN MORPHOMETRY

3.1 Introduction

Morphometric analysis is the measurement of the three dimensional geometry of landforms and has traditionally been applied to watershed, drainages, hill slopes, and other group of terrain features (Barber, 2005). The measurement and mathematical analysis of the configuration of the earth's surface and of the shape and dimensions of its landform provides the basis of the investigation of maps for a geomorphological survey (Bates & Jackson, 1980). This approach has recently been termed as Morphometry. The area, altitude, volume, slope, profile and texture of landforms comprise principal parameters of investigation. Dury (1952), Christian, Jenning and Tuidale (1957) applied various methods for landform analysis, which could be classified in different ways and their results presented in the form of graphs, maps or statistical indices.

Morphometry may be defined as the measurement and mathematical analysis of the configuration of the earth's surface, shape and dimensions of its landform. Morphometry has been used primarily to facilitate description of specific relief features-erosion surfaces, slopes, valleys and that of the character of relief as a whole (Clarke, 1970). Geomorphometry is the science of quantitative land-surface analysis (Pike, 1995, 2000a; Rasemann et al., 2004). It is a modern, analytical-cartographic approach to representing bare-earth topography by the computer manipulation of terrain height (Tobler, 1976, 2000). Geomorphometry is an interdisciplinary field that has evolved from

mathematics, the Earth sciences, and most recently computer science. Although geomorphometry has been regarded as an activity within more established fields, ranging from geography and geomorphology to soil science and military engineering, it is no longer just a collection of numerical techniques but a discipline in its own right (Pike, 1995). It is also used as direct or indirect evidence for the genesis and evolution of certain landforms. The aspects that can be examined through morphometry are, the area, altitude, volume, slope, profile and the texture of the land as well as the varied characteristics of rivers and drainage basins. Basin morphometric parameters have received a lot of attention from hydrologists and geomorphologists since watersheds have been used for analysis of various physical processes, including soil erosion, deposition, runoff, stream discharge, sediment yield (Barber, 2005).

Morphometry represents the topographical expression of land by way of area, slope, shape, length, etc. These parameters affect catchment stream flow pattern through their influence on concentration time (Jones, 1999). The significance of these landscape parameters was earlier pointed out by Morisawa (1959), who observed that stream flow can be expressed as a general function of geomorphology of a watershed. The assertion still stands valid following Jain and Sinha (2003), Okoko and Olujimi (2003) and Ifabiyi (2004) who reported that the geomorphic characteristics of a drainage basin play a key-role in controlling the basin's hydrology. Morphometric analysis of drainage basins thus provides not only an elegant description of the landscape, but also serves as a powerful means of comparing the form and process of drainage basins that may be widely separated in space and time (Easterbrook, 1993). In the early days, most basins were described as well-drained or poorly drained or they were connoted descriptively in the Davisian scheme as being youthful, mature

or old (Gregory and Walling, 1973). The mechanics of how river channels actually form within a basin and how water gets into the channels was only understood in vague terms by both geologist and hydrologists. Measurement and quantitative expression of drainage basin began with the work of James Hutton in 1775. Subsequently, a great step forward was made by Horton (1932) when he crystallized previous works added new measures and proposed general methods for the description of drainage basins characteristic (Gregory and Walling, 1973). Since then, mathematical analysis of drainage basin has been a subject of considerable analysis, both in temperate region (Schumm, 1954; Morisawa, 1959; Sokolov, 1969; Gregory and Walling, 1973; Gardiner, 1975) and in humid tropics (Hewlett and Hibbert, 1967; Ebisemiju, 1976; 1979; Nwa, 1979; Adejuwon et. al 1983; Ayandike and Phil-Eze, 1989; Ifabiyi, 2004). However, morphometric characteristics of drainage basin exhibit spatio temporal variation, hence the need for detail investigation of basin characteristics, not only from one area to another, but also from time to time. This is because, the form of a basin in terms of its morphometric characteristics determine the processes operating in such a basin. This form-process relationship according to Gregory and Walling (1973) produced a temporary dilemma in geomorphological investigation either in the study of form or process.

Morphometry is the measurement and mathematical analysis of the configuration of the earth's surface, shape and dimension of its landforms (Agarwal, 1998; Obi Reddy et al., 2002). A major emphasis in geomorphology over the past several decades has been on the development of quantitative physiographic methods to describe the evolution and behavior of surface drainage networks (Horton, 1945; Leopold & Maddock, 1953; Abrahams, 1984). The source of the

watershed drainage lines have been discussed since they were made predominantly by surface fluvial runoff has very important climatic, geologic and biologic effects e.g. Sharp and Malin, 1975; Pieri, 1976, 1980; Carr and Clow, 1981; Carr, 1999; Baker, 1982, 1990; Higgins, 1982; Mars Channel Working Group, 1983; Laity and Malin, 1985; Gulick and Baker, 1989; Haberle, 1998; Malin and Carr, 1999; Grant, 2000; Malin and Edgett, 2000; Goldspiel and Squyres, 2000; Williams and Phillips, 2001; Cabrol and Grin, 2001; Gulick, 2001; Craddock and Howard, 2002; Carr and Head, 2003; Hynek and Phillips, 2003; Craddock et al., 2003; Stepinski and Collier, 2004; Pareta, 2004; Howard et al., 2005. The morphometric characteristics at the watershed scale may contain important information regarding its formation and development because all hydrologic and geomorphic processes occur within the watershed (Singh, 1992). Morphometric analysis of a watershed provides a quantitative description of the drainage system, which is an important aspect of the characterization of watersheds (Strahler, 1964). A drainage basin, is well defined portion of the earth's surface within a physical boundary defined by topographic slopes that diverts all runoff to the same discharge outlet. The drainage basin can be thought of as a system that converts rainfall into runoff. Certain characteristics of a drainage basin reflect hydrologic behavior and are therefore useful when quantified in evaluating the hydrologic response of the basin (Singh, 1994). It also plays a vital role on the hydrogeomorphic performance and hydrologic behavior of a basin.

Horton (1932, 1945) pioneered the hydromorphometric analysis of drainage basin and provided a rational and systematic base, rather a framework of outline of geomorphologic characteristics to relate them to various hydrological properties of drainage basin. His works were

pursued by many investigators like Langbein (1947), Strahler (1952, 1957), Schumm (1956) and Chorley (1957). These pioneers put forwarded many laws of fluvial geomorphology in connection with hydrogeomorphic characteristics of river basins (NIH, 1990).

3.2 Database and Methodology

Tittur drainage basin is a seventh order tributary of Girna River in Tapi Basin. Its morphometric parameters have been measured and computed from Survey of India topographical maps on 1:50000 scale (46 L/15, 46 P/2, 46 P/3, 46 P/6 and 46 P/7) to bring out the detail picture of morphometric characteristics of the Tittur basin. The topographical maps of study area scanned and imported in Global Mapper 12.2 GIS Software. GPS ground truth data is used for geo-referencing of import map. All the imported and geo-referenced toposheets are compiled in to single mosaic for the sake of convenience. Streams network of Tittur basin has been digitized on the mosaic with the help of Global Mapper 12.2 GIS Software. Stream ordering has been generated using Strahler (1953) system, and ArcHydro 4 tool in ArcGIS 9.3.1 software. The entire catchment, water divides of sub basins of mainstream has been drawn from the SRTM DEM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Digital elevation model, NASA JPL 2000) and flow path grid using TAUDM and ARCGIS 9.3.1 for Digital watershed delineation (DWD).The morphometric parameters like stream order, order wise stream number, order wise length, basin length, basin area, basin perimeter, length of main stream, source height, confluence height, highest and lowest point of the basin and drainage orientation have been worked out for morphometric analysis .The basic data have been used for computation

morphometric parameter , bifurcation ratio, mean length ratio, mean area ratio and mean slope ratio in order to understand Horton laws of drainage composition. Apart from this drainage frequency, drainage density, sinuosity index, form factor, circularity ratio, elongation ratio, constant channel maintenance, ruggedness index, hypsometric integral have been estimated for understanding shape, size, drainage texture, surface roughness and stages of landscape development. The terrain analysis of Tittur basin have been attempted by using software device ArcHydro plug-in, Raster calculator and Spatial analysis extension in ArcGIS 9.3.1 The Length of overland flow have been estimated and mapped by using ILWIS 3.8. The data represented through chart, graph, maps and models in search of interpretative potentials.

3.3 Various Aspects of Drainage Basin Morphometry

The drainage basin morphometry of the Tittur basin has been grouped into

- Linear Aspects of the Drainage Network
- Areal Aspects of the Drainage Basin
- Relief Aspects and Drainage Basin form
- Slope Aspect of Drainage Basin

All the aspects are regarded to have potential to describe hydrological properties of the Tittur basin. The measured and computed parameters with their symbols and measures are shown in table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Drainage Basin Morphometric Parameters Used for the Tittur Basin

Parameter	Symbol	Unit of expression
A] Linear Aspects		
Stream Order	u	Enumerative
Number of streams of order u	N _u	Enumerative
Total no. of streams order u	($\sum N$) u	Enumerative
Bifurcation Ratio	R _b	Enumerative
Total stream Length of order u	L _u	Km
Mean Length of streams of order u	\overline{L}_u	Km
Total stream Length of order u	($\sum L$)u	Km
Length Ratio	R _L	Enumerative
Sinuosity Index	CL	Km
Channel Length	AL	Km
Length of Overland flow	L _g	Km
Drainage Orientation	D°	Degree
B] Areal Aspects		
Basin Area	A	Sq. km
Basin Perimeter	P	Km
Form Factor	F	Enumerative
Circularity Ratio	R _c	Enumerative
Elongation Ratio	E _c	Enumerative
Stream Frequency	F _u	No. of Streams/km ²
Drainage density	D _d	Km/ km ²
Constant Channel Maintenance	C _{cm}	Km/ km ²
Mean Basin Area of Stream order	\overline{A}_u	Sq. km
Area Ratio	R _a	Enumerative
C] Relief Aspects		
Maximum elevation of Basin	Z	Meter
Minimum elevation of Basin	z	Meter
Basin Relief	H	Meter
Relief Ratio	RL	Enumerative
Ruggedness Number	R _n	Enumerative
Slope	Φ _c	m/km or Degree

(Source and Modified from: Doornkamp and King, 1971)

Table 3.2 Tittur Drainage Basin Morphometric Parameters

Stream Order μ	No of Stream N_μ	Stream Length in km L_μ	Mean length $\bar{L}_\mu = L_\mu/N_\mu$	Bifurcation Ratio $N_\mu / N_{\mu+1}$	Length Ratio $\bar{L}_\mu / \bar{L}_{\mu-1}$	Basin Area in sq km A_μ	Mean Basin Area \bar{A}_μ	Area Ratio $\bar{A}_\mu / \bar{A}_{\mu-1}$
1	2163	1294.7	0.59	4.07	1.52	457.09	0.21	5.76
2	531	480.06	0.90	4.24	2.88	645.55	1.21	5.20
3	125	323.05	2.60	3.78	2.27	787.85	6.30	4.28
4	33	195.36	5.92	3.30	0.80	890.70	26.99	3.39
5	10	47.86	4.78	3.33	3.26	917.63	91.76	3.45
6	3	46.86	15.62	3.00	2.18	951.17	317.05	3.06
7	1	34.09	34.09			970.10	970.10	

Table 3.3 Morphometric Parameters of Tittur Basin

A] Linear Aspects	
Stream Order	7 th
Total no. of streams	2866
Total stream Length (km)	2334.34
Bifurcation Ratio	3.62
Mean streams Length	0.81
streams Length ratio	0.59
Length of Overland flow (Km)	0.20
B] Areal Aspects	
Basin Area (sq.km)	970.10
Basin Perimeter (km)	184.89
Basin Length (km)	182.31
Form Factor	0.28
Circularity Ratio	0.36
Elongation Ratio	0.60
Stream Frequency (stream / sq.km.)	2.95
Drainage density (km / sq.km.)	2.40
Constant Channel Maintenance (sq.km / 1 km length)	0.41
C] Relief Aspects	
Maximum elevation of Basin (m)	941.70
Minimum elevation of Basin (m)	248.10
Basin Relief (m)	693.60
Relief Ratio	3.80
Ruggedness Number	22.26

Table 3.4 Pimpri catchment Morphometric data

Stream Order	No of Stream N_{μ}	Stream Length in km L_{μ}	Mean length $\bar{L}_{\mu} = L_{\mu}/N_{\mu}$	Bifurcation Ratio $N_{\mu} / N_{\mu+1}$	Length Ratio $\bar{L}_{\mu} / \bar{L}_{\mu-1}$
1	203	166.384	0.819	3.75	0.43
2	54	71.550	1.325	4.15	0.60
3	13	43.517	3.347	3.25	0.48
4	4	21.310	5.327	2.00	0.26
5	2	5.738	2.869	2.00	1.32
6	1	7.627	7.627		

Table 3.5 Dungri catchment Morphometric data

Stream Order	No of Stream N_{μ}	Stream Length in km L_{μ}	Mean length $\bar{L}_{\mu} = L_{\mu}/N_{\mu}$	Bifurcation Ratio $N_{\mu} / N_{\mu+1}$	Length Ratio $\bar{L}_{\mu} / \bar{L}_{\mu-1}$
1	175	113.084	0.646	4.86	0.29
2	36	32.896	0.913	4.50	0.64
3	8	21.271	2.658	8	1.34
4	1	28.631	28.631		

Table 3.6 Valjhari catchment Morphometric data

Stream Order	No of Stream N_{μ}	Stream Length in km L_{μ}	Mean length $\bar{L}_{\mu} = L_{\mu}/N_{\mu}$	Bifurcation Ratio $N_{\mu} / N_{\mu+1}$	Length Ratio $\bar{L}_{\mu} / \bar{L}_{\mu-1}$
1	366	223.535	0.61	3.89	1.39
2	94	80.214	0.85	4.08	3.74
3	23	73.203	3.18	3.28	1.47
4	7	32.930	4.70	3.5	1.78
5	2	16.818	8.40	2	0.59
6	1	4.967	4.96		

Table 3.7 Gadad catchment Morphometric data

Stream Order	No of Stream N_{μ}	Stream Length in km L_{μ}	Mean Length $\bar{L}_{\mu} = L_{\mu}/N_{\mu}$	Bifurcation Ratio $N_{\mu} / N_{\mu+1}$	Length Ratio $\bar{L}_{\mu} / \bar{L}_{\mu-1}$
1	953	515.263	0.54	4.12	1.50
2	231	188.048	0.81	4.52	3.04
3	51	126.451	2.47	3.92	2.43
4	13	78.158	6.01	3.25	0.92
5	4	22.129	5.53	4	4.51
6	1	24.968	24.96		

Table 3.8 Sub Basin Wise Morphometric Parameters of the Tittur Basin.

Morphometric Parameters	Sub Basin			
	Pimpri	Dungri	Valjhari	Gadad
A] Linear Aspects				
Stream Order (u)	6	4	6	6
Total no. of streams	277	220	493	1253
Total stream Length	316.126	195.882	365.667	955.017
Bifurcation Ratio	3.03	5.78	3.35	3.96
Length of Overland	0.25	0.18	0.21	0.17
B] Areal Aspects				
Basin Area (km ²)	162.39	72.302	156.27	340.10
Basin Perimeter (km)	66.103	64.714	67.72	96.64
Basin Length (km)	23.048	21.373	21.77	30.40
Form Factor	0.30	0.15	0.32	0.36
Circularity Ratio	0.46	0.21	0.42	0.45
Elongation Ratio	0.62	0.44	0.64	0.68
Stream Freq.	1.70	3.04	3.15	3.68
Drainage Density	1.94	2.70	2.33	2.80
Constant Channel Maintenance	0.51	0.37	0.42	0.35
C] Relief Aspects				
Ht. of Highest Point	799.486	892.838	907.305	938.056
Height of Basin	338.701	337.811	315.120	274.742
Basin Relief (m)	460.785	555.027	592.185	663.314
Relief Ratio (m/km)	6.97	16.39	21.42	16.75
Ruggedness Number	0.017	0.100	0.024	0.005

Fig. 3.1 Sub Basin wise Catchment area of the Tittur Basin

3.4 Linear Aspects of the Tittur Drainage Basin

3.4.1 Stream Order and Stream Number

Stream ordering is the first step of quantitative analysis of the watershed. The stream ordering systems has first advocated by Horton (1945), but Strahler (1952) has proposed this ordering system with some modifications. The total of order wise stream segments is known as stream number. Horton (1945) states that the numbers of stream segments of each order form an inverse geometric sequence with order number.

Strahler's (1952) stream order system is a simple method of classifying stream segments based on the number of tributaries upstream. A stream with no tributaries (headwater stream) is considered a first order stream. A segment downstream of the confluence of two first order streams is a second order stream. Thus, an n^{th} order stream is always located downstream of the confluence of two $(n-1)^{\text{th}}$ order streams.

Classification of streams in a hierarchical manner, measurement of number of streams, length of streams and branching of streams etc. may be used for numerical quantification of stream. These linear parameters can be used as predictive tools to understand streamflow behavior. According to Strahler (1957) system of stream ordering, the Tittur Basin is 7^{th} ordered stream, covers an area of 970.10 Sq. km. The drainage pattern of the Tittur River is mostly dendritic. The dendritic pattern itself indicates that the drainage is over the homogenous lithostructure. The drainage pattern over the Deccan Trap country is almost dendritic in nature like Tittur Basin. For the sake of convenience the entire Tittur Basin is further classified in to four sub basins namely

1) Pimpri, 2) Dungri, 3) Valjhari and 4) Gadad. The drainage map (Fig.3.2) of the Tittur Basin shows the network of streams of different orders and lengths. The entire network is composed of 2866 streams in which 93.99 % streams are of lower order. i.e. first and second order. The higher order streams successively reduced to unity until finally. It has been observed that the total length of lower order stream constitute 76.04 % (1774.85 km length of I and II order streams) of the total 2334.34 km length of entire network. Table 3.9 shows proportion of order wise streams and number to total streams of each sub basin.

Table 3.9 Sub basin wise stream order, stream no. and stream length of

Tittur Drainage basin

Stream Order	Sub Basin								Tittur Drainage Basin	
	Pimpri		Dungri		Valjhari		Gadad		No of Stream	Stream Length
	No of Stream	Stream Length	No of Stream	Stream Length	No of Stream	Stream Length	No of Stream	Stream Length		
1	203	166.384	175	113.08	366	223.535	953	515.263	2163	1294.79
2	54	71.550	36	32.896	94	80.214	231	188.048	531	480.06
3	13	43.517	8	21.271	23	73.203	51	126.451	125	323.05
4	4	21.310	1	28.631	7	32.930	13	78.158	33	195.36
5	2	5.738			2	16.818	4	22.129	10	47.86
6	1	7.627			1	4.967	1	24.968	3	46.86
7									1	34.09
Total	277	316.126	220	195.88	493	365.667	1253	955.017	2866	2334.34
Correlation	-0.790		-0.872		-0.788		-0.781		-0.741	
Fitness Value R²	0.624		0.760		0.620		0.609		0.549	

Fig. 3.2 Strahler Stream Order Drainage Network Map of the Tittur Basin

3.4.2 Stream Order Vs Stream Number

The relationship between stream Order and number of streams is in inverse geometric proportion for all sub basins (fig3.4 to Fig.3.7). The regression equations, correlation coefficient between stream order and number also have been worked out. The values of correlation coefficient and goodness of fit are depicted in table 3.9 this clearly indicates the significant inverse correlation ship. Corresponding values of their significant fitness are (R^2) 0.624, 0.760, 0.620, 0.609 respectively for Pimpri, Dungri, Valjhari and Gadad sub basin. The regression lines of all four sub basin do not coincides as they shows some deviations in either higher or lower order streams. This fact clearly indicates the disproportionate number of higher and lower order streams. This disproportionate increase or decrease of stream numbers is always associated with different degree of drainage development in such homogenous litho-structure like Deccan basalt. This may be attributed to the different degree of resistance of the rock or to the structural control of drainage basin like lineaments, dykes etc. as the basin is traversed by two dykes and many lineaments. While in some parts of the basin represent parallel types indicating that the topographical features are dipping and highly jointed in the hilly terrains. A parallel drainage pattern consists of tributaries that flow nearly parallel to one another and all the tributaries join the main channel at approximately the same angle. Parallel drainage suggest that the area has a gentle, uniform slopes and with less resistant bed rock. The properties of the stream networks are very important to study the landform making process (Strahler and Strahler, 2002).

Fig 3.3 shows the variation of stream number with stream order of the Tittur Basin on semi log plot with the number of Streams plotted on

log scale along vertical axis and stream order is plotted on arithmetic scale along the horizontal axis. The curve of Tittur Basin between stream order and number showing almost uniform steepness. The curve of all sub basin's between stream order and number dose not showing uniform steepness. The gentler slope of higher order i.e. from fourth order, the drainage might be extended in nature.

Fig. 3.3 Tittur Drainage Basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number

Fig. 3.4 Pimpri sub basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number

Fig. 3.5 Dungri sub Basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number

Fig. 3.6 Valjhari sub Basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number

Fig. 3.7 Gadad sub Basin Stream Order Vs Stream Number

3.4.3 Bifurcation Ratio (Rb)

The term bifurcation ratio was introduced by Horton (1945) to express the ratio of number of streams of a given order to the number of streams of next higher order and is expressed as

$$\mathbf{Rb} = \mathbf{N_u} / (\mathbf{N_{u+1}})$$

Horton (1945) considered the bifurcation ratio as index of relief and dissertation. Strahler (1957) demonstrated that bifurcation shows a small range of variation for different regions or for different environment except where the powerful geological control dominates. It is observed from the Rb is not same from one order to its next order these irregularities are dependent upon the geological and lithological development of the drainage basin (Strahler, 1964). The bifurcation ratio is dimensionless property and generally ranges from 3.0 to 5.0. The lower values of Rb are characteristics of the watersheds, which have suffered less structural disturbances (Strahler, 1964) and the drainage pattern has not been distorted because of the structural disturbances (Nag, 1998).

The behavior of bifurcation ratio depends upon lithological and geological control to the development of drainage basin. According to Horton (1945), bifurcation ratio fairly ranges between 3.0 and 5.0 under normal environmental circumstances. The extreme value clearly indicates abnormal environmental circumstances. The abnormalities are frequently associated with either rejuvenation or strong structural control over the drainage basin development. Apart from these, the bifurcation ratio also reflects the hydrological conditions of drainage basin especially the flood discharge conditions. The elongated basin with high value of bifurcation ratio yields a low but extended peak flow, which in turn contributes more infiltration of water along the streams, while basin with near circular

shape with low bifurcation ratio produces a sharp peak flow giving very less time for infiltration of water in the soil layers along the streams.

If the bifurcation ratio of a river network is low, there is a higher chance of flooding, as the water will be concentrated in one channel rather than spread out, as a higher bifurcation ratio would indicate. The bifurcation ratio can also show which parts of a drainage basin is more likely to flood, comparatively, by looking at the separate ratios. In the present study of Tittur Basin, the values of bifurcation ratios obtained are given in table 3.10.

Table 3.10 Bifurcation ratio of Tittur Drainage basin

Stream Order μ	No of Stream N_μ	Bifurcation Ratio $N_\mu / N_{\mu+1}$	Average Bifurcation Ratio
1	2163	4.07	3.62
2	531	4.24	
3	125	3.78	
4	33	3.30	
5	10	3.33	
6	3	3.00	
7	1		

Table 3.10 indicates that the bifurcation ratio of the Tittur Basin ranges between 3.00 to 4.24 with average value of 3.62 and hence clearly indicates normal environmental circumstances for the drainage development. However, at some places faults, fractures or weaker strata's controlled the drainage lines. Sub basin wise bifurcation ratio values also range between 3.03 and 5.78 (Table 3.11) but values of are close to lower extremity indicating that there is lower degree of control in drainage

development. In Dungri sub basin values are indicating that there is rejuvenation because of faulting activity.

Table 3.11 Sub Basin wise Bifurcation Ratio

Stream Order μ	Sub Basin							
	Pimpri		Dungri		Valjhari		Gadad	
	N_{μ}	Rb	N_{μ}	Rb	N_{μ}	Rb	N_{μ}	Rb
1	203	3.75	175	4.86	366	3.89	953	4.12
2	54	4.15	36	4.50	94	4.08	231	4.52
3	13	3.25	8	8.00	23	3.28	51	3.92
4	4	2.00	1		7	3.50	13	3.25
5	2	2.00			2	2.00	4	4
6	1				1		1	
Avg.Rb		3.03		5.78		3.35		3.96

3.4.4 Stream Length

Stream length is one of the most significant hydrological features of the basin as it reveals surface runoff characteristics streams of relatively smaller lengths are characteristics of areas with larger slopes and finer textures. Longer lengths of streams are generally indicative of flatter gradients. Generally, the total length of stream segments is maximum in first order streams and decreases as the stream order increases. The numbers of streams of various orders in the basin are counted and their lengths from mouth to drainage divide are measured with the help of GIS software. Stream Length involves the measurement of the length of different orders of streams. Horton's law of stream length states that the average length of streams of each of different order in a drainage basin tends closely to approximate a direct geometric series in which the first term is the average length of stream of the first order (Strahler, 1957).The

length of stream is a dimensional property indicating the hydrologic nature of the contributing surface of the drainage network. In more permeable strata, the stream follows reduction in number and extension in length.

Table 3.12 depicts the total length of streams in each order with mean stream length and length ratio. The stream length is the ratio of mean length of the streams of a given order to the mean length of the streams of the next lower order. It gives a general idea about the relative permeability of the rock formation in a basin.

Table 3.12 Stream Order wise Total Length, Mean Stream Length, Stream Length Ratio of the Tittur River basin.

Stream Order μ	No of Stream N_μ	Stream Length in km L_μ	Mean Stream length $\bar{L}_\mu = L_\mu/N_\mu$	Length Ratio $\bar{L}_\mu / \bar{L}_{\mu-1}$
1	2163	1294.79	0.59	1.52
2	531	480.06	0.90	2.88
3	125	323.05	2.60	2.27
4	33	195.36	5.92	0.80
5	10	47.86	4.78	3.26
6	3	46.86	15.62	2.18
7	1	34.09	34.09	

It is evident from the figures of the length ratio of 1st order to 2nd order is strikingly greater than (1.88) the values of remaining orders of streams. This can be attributed to higher permeability wherein drainage follows colluvial formation. Total length of 1st order streams is more than the successive higher orders. About 59 % of total length of all streams in the Tittur Basin is occupied by 1st order streams indicating strong resistance to the permeability in the upper reaches of the basin. It also indicates that

a higher impermeability in the source areas of all 1st order streams can be related to the talus slopes.

The plot of stream order wise mean stream length (fig.3.8) also follows Horton's IInd law or law of stream length. The curve is positive exponential indicating comparative higher infiltration in the higher order streams is lengthened. Sub basin wise plot of stream order vs mean stream length have been workout.

Table 3.13 Stream Order wise Total Length of sub basin.

Stream Order μ	Sub Basin							
	Pimpri		Dungri		Valjhari		Gadad	
	N_{μ}	L_{μ}	N_{μ}	L_{μ}	N_{μ}	L_{μ}	N_{μ}	L_{μ}
1	203	166.384	175	113.084	366	223.535	953	515.263
2	54	71.550	36	32.896	94	80.214	231	188.048
3	13	43.517	8	21.271	23	73.203	51	126.451
4	4	21.310	1	28.631	7	32.930	13	78.158
5	2	5.738			2	16.818	4	22.129
6	1	7.627			1	4.967	1	24.968

Table 3.14 Stream Order wise Mean Stream Length and Stream Length Ratio of sub basin.

Stream Order μ	Sub Basin							
	Pimpri		Dungri		Valjhari		Gadad	
	Mean length \bar{L}_μ	Length Ratio $\bar{L}_\mu / \bar{L}_{\mu-1}$						
1	0.819	0.43	0.646	0.29	0.61	1.39	0.54	1.50
2	1.325	0.60	0.913	0.64	0.85	3.74	0.81	3.04
3	3.347	0.48	2.658	1.34	3.18	1.47	2.47	2.43
4	5.327	0.26	28.63		4.70	1.78	6.01	0.92
5	2.869	1.32			8.40	0.59	5.53	4.51
6	7.627				4.96		24.96	

Fig. 3.8 Tittur drainage basin Stream order vs mean stream length

Fig. 3.9 Pimpri sub basin Stream order vs. mean stream length

Fig. 3.10 Dungri sub basin Stream order vs. mean stream length

Fig. 3.11 Valjhari sub basin Stream order vs. mean stream length

Fig. 3.12 Gadad sub basin Stream order vs. mean stream length

3.4.5 Sinuosity Index (SI)

Sinuosity deals with the degree of deviation of its actual path from expected theoretical straight path (Singh, 2004). It explains hydrological and topological characteristics of a drainage basin. Thus channel sinuosity is an important parameter used in the hydromorphometric studies to distinguish the various types of terrain to ascertain the degree of drainage line establishment in the area of influence (Babar, 2005). Sinuosity may help considerable in studying the effect of terrain characteristic on the river course and vice versa, the degree of sinuosity many give a vivid picture of the stage of basin development as well as landform evaluation. It may be give fruit full result for hydro geomorphic analysis.

S.A.Schumm's (1963) suggested that sinuosity index is ratio between actual path of stream and expected straight path of stream.

$$\text{Sinuosity index (SI)} = O_L / E_L$$

Where, O_L is actual path of stream and E_L is expected straight path of stream

Generally when sinuosity index is with in 1.25, the river is in between the straight to the regular stage. When the sinuosity index is more than 1.5, the river is in the Meander stage. When it is above 2.5 the river is in the tortuous stage.

Sinuosity Index as classified by Rosgen (1994):

I- Strong when sinuosity index ratio > 1.4 ; stream has numerous closely spaced bends, very few straight sections.

II- Moderate when sinuosity index ratio $>1.2 < 1.4$; stream has good Sinuosity with some straight sections.

III- Weak when sinuosity index ratio $>1 < 1.2$; stream has very few bends, and mostly straight sections.

IV- Absent when sinuosity index ratio $=1$; stream is completely straight with no bends.

In the present work, S.A.Schumm's (1963) technique of Sinuosity Index has been adopted to determine O_L and E_L from source to mouth as sinuosity attributes.

O_L	E_L	SI
76.67	58.12	1.31

The Sinuosity Index (SI) for the Tittur River channel is 1.31. The sinuous channel are prone to valley bottom plain location or flood plains, indicating that it contributes more water to subsurface flow and recharging the water table during peak flows. It can be said that the sinuosity of Tittur River is attributed to its hydraulic gradient and topography.

3.4.6 Length of Overland Flow

The term length of overland flow refers to the length of the course of the rainwater on the surface before it gets localized into a definite channel (Horton, 1945) or the mean horizontal length of flow path from the divide to the first order stream. It is a measure of stream spacing and degree of dissection and is approximately half of the reciprocal of the drainage density (Chorley, 1969). It is one of the important morphometric variables affecting the hydrologic and topographic development of the basin. Early stage of basin development is generally marked with maximum length of overland flow and mature and old stage registers the decrease of overland flow.

The Overland Flow Length operation calculates for each pixel the overland distance towards the 'nearest' drainage according to the flow paths available in the Flow Direction map. As input is required the output raster map of the Drainage network ordering operation and its linked attribute table, the output raster map of the Flow direction operation. The operation produces a raster map that contains the overland down-flow distances towards the drainage into which a pixel will drain according to the flow direction map.

Length of overland flow calculated for the Tittur Basin is 0.20 km. Table 3.15 shows sub basin wise length of overland flow.

Fig. 3.13 Length of Overland Flow Map of the Tittur Basin

Table 3.15 Sub Basin wise Length of Overland Flow

Sub Basin	Length of overland Flow (km)	Average Length of Overland Flow (km)
Pimpri	0.25	0.20
Dungri	0.18	
Valjhari	0.21	
Gadad	0.17	

The lower value of overland flow indicates that surface runoff quickly enters into 1st order streams. However, under such circumstances significant volume of surface runoff can occur during less rainfall event over the area.

3.4.7 Drainage Orientation

The drainage orientation is a key to understand the way in which a drainage network follows path over the available surface area. It also reflects dip of the structures like fold, and strikes of faults, joints etc. (Jarvis, 1976). The direction of drainage line or network orientation is so greatly influenced by the geologic structure and lithology that it gives clues to interpret nature of structure and rock type. Over lithologically homogenous areas, the drainage orientation is random and lack of directional control wherein a dendritic pattern results.

In order to understand the structural details of the Tittur Basin drainage orientation have been measured and drawn using GIS and DEM. Fig. 3.14 shows drainage orientation of the Tittur Basin. In a (sink-free) Digital Elevation Model (DEM), the Flow direction operation determines into which neighboring pixel any water in a central pixel will flow

naturally. Flow direction is calculated for every central pixel of input blocks of 3 by 3 pixels, each time comparing the value of the central pixel with the value of its 8 neighbors. The output map contains flow directions.

Most of the drainage lines of the basin are oriented towards three major axes i. e. North (N), North-East (NE), North-West (NW). It is observed that basins more or less oriented towards S, SE and SW direction, indicating that geologically the basin has structural and dip direction of fault, escarpment, dykes and lineaments, in N,NE and NW direction. Table 3.16 shows direction wise drainage orientation of the Tittur Basin.

Table 3.16 Drainage Orientation

Drainage Direction	Area in sq km
N	216.61
NE	176.61
E	115.12
SE	79.35
S	40.45
SW	45.53
W	101.03
NW	189.31
Flat	8.1

Fig. 3.14 Surface Water Flow Direction Map of the Tittur Basin

3.5 Areal Aspects of the Tittur Drainage Basin

3.5.1 Drainage Basin Area (A)

Drainage basin area represents the area enclosed within the boundary of the watershed divide. The entire geographical area drained by a river and its tributaries; an area characterized by all runoff being conveyed to the same outlet. The drainage area is probably a single most important basin characteristic for hydrologic design. It reflects the volume of water that can be generated from rainfall. The total basin area and sub basin wise area have been measured from topographical map by using ARC GIS 9.3.1 the total drainage basin area of the Tittur Basin is 970.10 sq. km. Sub basin wise area are indicate in table 3.17

3.5.2 Basin Perimeter (P): Basin perimeter is the total length of the basin boundary or the length measured along the drainage divide of the basin and may be used as an indicator of basin size and shape. The Tittur Basin has a perimeter of 184.89 km covering an area 970.10 sq. km. Table 3.17 shows sub basin wise drainage basin perimeter and basin area.

Table 3.17 Sub Basin wise Perimeter, Area and length

Sub Basin	Perimeter (km)	Area (Sq. km)	Length (km)
Pimpri	66.103	162.39	23.04
Dungri	64.714	72.302	21.33
Valjhari	67.720	156.27	21.76
Gadad	96.640	340.10	30.36

Gadad sub basin has greater perimeter (96.640 km) as compare to the other sub basins. It indicates that amongst four sub basin it is large in size, contributing large amount of discharge to its parent catchment.

3.5.3 Length of the Basin (L)

Several people defined basin length in different ways, such as Schumm (1956) defined the basin length as the longest dimension of the basin parallel to the principal drainage line. Gregory and Walling (1973) defined the basin length as the longest in the basin in which are end being the mouth. Gardiner (1975) defined the basin length as the length of the line from a basin mouth to a point on the perimeter equidistant from the basin mouth in either direction around the perimeter. In the present study basin length has been determined in accordance with the definition of Schumm (1956) that is 58.25 Km, Sub basin wise Basin length are given in table 3.17

3.5.4 Form Factor (F): Form factor is the ratio of the basin area to the squared value of basin length (Horton 1932; Selby 1985).

$$F = A / L^2$$

According to Horton (1932), form factor may be defined as the ratio of basin area to square of the basin length. The value of form factor would always be less than 0.754 (for a perfectly circular watershed). Smaller the value of form factor, more elongated will be the watershed. The watershed with high form factors have high peak flows of shorter duration, whereas elongated watershed with low form factor ranges indicating them to be elongated in shape and flow for longer duration

It is a dimensionless quantity which expresses the basin shape. The shape of a drainage basin is influencing factor on the discharge of a basin. In an elongated basin, flood takes longer time to travel through outlet as compare to a basin having circular shape. 'F' value computed for the

Tittur Basin is 0.28, indicating that it is elongated in shape. Sub basin wise Form Factor shows in Table-3.8.

3.5.5 Circularity Ratio (R_C): Circularity ratio is the ratio of basin area to the area of circle with same perimeter as basin (Miller 1953; Selby 1985). Circularity (R_C) = basin area / area of circle with same perimeter as basin

$$R_C = 4\pi A / P^2$$

For the out-line form of watershed (Strahler, 1964, and Miller, 1953) used a dimensionless circularity ratio as a quantitative method. Circularity ratio is defined as the ratio of watershed area to the area of a circle having the same perimeter as the watershed and it is pretentious by the lithological character of the watershed. Miller (1953) has described the basin of the circularity ratios range 0.4 to 0.5, which indicates strongly elongated and highly permeable homogenous geologic materials.

The value of ' R_C ' for the Tittur Basin is 0.36 indicates that it is not a circular shape. This indicates that the watershed is elongated in shape, low discharge of runoff and highly permeability of the subsoil condition.

3.5.6 Elongation Ratio (E_R): Elongation ratio is the ratio of diameter of the circle with the same area as basin and the length of the basin (Schumm 1956; Selby 1985).

Elongation (E) = diameter of circle with same area as basin / basin length

$$E_R = 2(A / \pi)^{0.5} / L$$

According to Schumm (1965), 'elongation ratio is defined as the ratio of diameter of a circle of the same area as the basin to the maximum basin

length. Strahler states that this ratio runs between 0.6 and 1.0 over a wide variety of climatic and geologic types. The varying slopes of watershed can be classified with the help of the index of elongation ratio, i.e. circular (0.9- 1.0), oval (0.8-0.9), less elongated (0.7-0.8), elongated (0.5-0.7), and more elongated (< 0.5). The computed value of E_R of the Tittur Basin is 0.60. This means, it is an elongated basin.

3.5.7 Stream Frequency

Stream frequency is the measure of number of streams per unit area (Horton, 1945). A higher stream frequency indicates the higher surface runoff and steep ground surface. The values of stream frequency obtained from the Tittur Basin is 2.95 streams per sq. km and sub basin wise, values of stream frequency are given in table 3.18

Table 3.18 Sub Basin wise Stream Frequency

Sub Basin	Total No. of Streams	Basin Area (Sq. km)	Stream Frequency (Stream/ Sq. km)
Pimpri	277	162.39	1.70
Dungri	220	72.302	3.04
Valjhari	493	156.27	3.15
Gadad	1253	340.10	3.68

Sub basin wise stream frequency ranges from 1.70 to 3.68 streams per sq.km indicates that Gadad basin contributes higher surface runoff with steep ground surface as compare to Valjhari and other sub basins. Because of steep valley side slopes in Gadad sub basin, rain water flows directly to trunk stream with very low infiltration and less permeability of rocks. Pimpri basin has more infiltration than another sub basin.

Fig. 3.15 Stream Frequency Map of the Tittur Basin

3.5.8 Drainage Density (D_D): Horton (1945) defined drainage density as the ratio of total channel segment length of all orders within a basin to the area of the drainage basin projected to horizontal.

$$D_D = \sum L/A$$

Drainage density characterizes the textural measure independent of basin size and considered to be a function of climate, lithology, stage of development etc. it is a measure of drainage dissection that reflects the competing effectiveness of overland flow and infiltration. Horton (1945) reasoned that basins of low drainage density are the product of runoff processes dominated by infiltration and subsurface flow, whereas basins of high drainage density are the product of erosion and dissection by overland flow. Higher drainage density also indicates the decrease in the length of overland flow with increase in angle of hill slope (Schumm, 1956). For the basins of comparable relief, the hydrologic response of stream network is directly related to drainage density. Drainage density is the total length of all the streams and rivers in a drainage basin divided by the total area of the drainage basin. It is a measure of how well or how poorly a watershed is drained by stream channels. It is equal to the reciprocal of the constant of channel maintenance and equal to the reciprocal of two times the length of overland flow.

Drainage density depends upon both climate and physical characteristics of the drainage basin. Soil permeability and underlying rock type affect the runoff in a watershed; impermeable ground or exposed bedrock will lead to an increase in surface water runoff and therefore to more frequent streams. Rugged regions or those with high

relief will also have a higher drainage density than other drainage basins if the other characteristics of the basin are the same.

Drainage density can affect the shape of a river's hydrograph during a rain storm. Rivers that have a high drainage density will often have a more 'flashy' hydrograph with a steep falling limb. High densities can also indicate a greater flood risk. The Tittur Basin has a drainage density of 2.40 km per sq. km. Table 3.19 shows sub basin wise drainage density, of four sub basins, ranging from 1.94 km per sq. km to 2.80 km per sq. km.

Table 3.19 Sub Basin wise Drainage Density

Sub Basin	Drainage Density (Km/Sq. km)
Pimpri	1.94
Dungri	2.70
Valjhari	2.33
Gadad	2.80

It is observed that Pimpri sub basin has lowest drainage density of 1.94 km/ sq. km, indicating higher rate of infiltration greater subsurface flow, high moisture retentive capacity and relatively low relief, and Gadad sub basin has highest drainage density of 2.80 km/ sq. km, indicating lower rate of infiltration and more runoff than other sub basin's, because in Gadad sub basin most part are rocky barren land which has less permeability that's why in this area groundwater table is not well developed. Dungri, Valjhari and Gadad basin are having drainage density of 2.70, 2.33 and 2.80 km per sq. km indicating that these basins are dominated by erosion, comparable relief, low infiltration and higher surface runoff as well as steep side hill slopes with decreased overland flow.

Fig. 3.16 Drainage Density Map of the Tittur Basin

3.5.9 Constant Channel Maintenance (Ccm.)

Schumm (1956) defined the constant channel maintenance as the ratio between the area of a drainage basin and the total length of all the channels, and is expressed in square kilometer per km. The constant of channel maintenance indicates the relative size of landform units in a drainage basin and has a specific genetic connotation (Strahler, 1957).

$$Ccm = Basin\ Area / \sum L$$

It is equal to the reciprocal of the drainage density. The value of constant channel maintenance of the Tittur Basin comes to 0.41 sq. km per km. it means that 0.41 sq km surface of the basin is required to maintain a stream length of 1 km. This can be attributed to higher surface runoff and low infiltration rate of the basin.

3.5.10 Area Ratio

The area ratio (Ra) is the proportion of increase of mean basin area between two successive orders of a given basin. It is derived on the basis of the following formula (Strahler, A.N. 1969):

$$R a = \overline{A\mu} / \overline{A\mu}_1$$

Where $\overline{A\mu}$ is the mean area of given order of a basin.

When $\overline{A\mu} = A\mu / N_{\mu}$

Where N_{μ} = number of stream segments of a given order

$A\mu$ = the total area of all segments of the same order

On the basis of the above formula mean basin areas (Table 3.17) have been obtained and thus with the help of $\overline{A\mu}$, mean Ra of Tittur basins have been derived. The mean Ra of the basins is 4.19. This rule holds good in Tittur basins of the region.

3.5.11 Law of Basin Area

Strahler has formulated the law of positive geometric progression of drainage basin area wherein "the mean basin areas of successive higher stream orders tend to form a geometric series beginning with mean area of the 1st order basin and increasing according to constant area ratio." (Strahler, 1969) It is appropriate to point out that the basin area becomes cumulative from 1st order to the successively higher orders and thus the area of a higher order (the entire basin area) stream includes the total area covered by all the streams of lower order. There are positive relationships between stream order and basin area. The basin area increases with increases in order of stream segments (Table 3.20). The mean basin area of successive higher order stream tend to form geometric series beginning with mean ratio of the first order basin and increase according to constant area ratio. Following equation of the law of basin area.

$$\overline{A\mu} = A_1 \text{ Ra}^{(\mu-1)}$$

Where A_1 = the mean basin area of the 1st order; and

Ra = area ratio.

Fig. 3.17 Stream Order Vs Mean Basin area

Table 3.20 Stream Order wise basin area and Area Ratio

Stream Order μ	No of Stream N_{μ}	Basin Area in sq km A_{μ}	Mean Basin Area $\overline{A_{\mu}}$	Area Ratio $\overline{A_{\mu}} / \overline{A_{\mu-1}}$
1	2163	457.09	0.21	
2	531	645.55	1.21	5.76
3	125	787.85	6.30	5.20
4	33	890.70	26.99	4.28
5	10	917.63	91.76	3.39
6	3	951.17	317.05	3.45
7	1	970.10	970.10	3.06

On the basis of Table 3.20 it may be point out that the basins which are developed over flat surfaces or partly over highly dissected hilly terrain and partly over flat. Thus, relief regularity accelerates the areal coverage but minimizes the stream segments with their orders.

The correlation coefficient between orders and mean basin areas are obtained on the basis of the following regression equation:

$$\mathbf{Log\ y = Log\ a + bx}$$

Where y = the mean basin area;

x = order of the streams;

a = constant;

b = regression coefficient.

Regression lines (Fig. 3.17) are drawn on the basis of the above equation to test the linear relationship between drainage orders and mean basin areas. Above law almost good in the case of Tittur drainage basin as the coefficient of correlation is 0.78 and percentage of variance explained is 53.66 %.But the fitted function show (Fig.3.17) considerable underestimation in the case of basin area of 1st, 2nd and 7th order stream and an overestimation in case of 3rd, 4th, 5th and 6th stream order basin area.

Fig. 3.18 Stream Order wise Cumulative Catchment Area Map

3.6 Relief Aspects of the Tittur Basin

A relief aspect of a river basin describes the elevation of surface from surrounding common surface. It is always measured in terms of difference in elevation of highest and lowest elevation in an aerial unit. Relief is the measure of the energy head from which potential energy can be determined. Relief is also a measure of slope in respect of length which governs the flow dynamics. Rainfall is also influenced by relief. This is significant to study the flow phenomenon in the watershed. The potential energy of flowing water from high altitude gets converted into kinetic energy which is related to slope. Various losses of water like storage, infiltration, evaporation and travel time are inversely related to the slope. The various parameters of relief aspects of the Tittur Basin are discussed below.

3.6.1 Total Basin Relief

Total basin relief is the difference in elevation between the highest point on the source and the mouth of the river in a basin. For the area under study, the elevation of highest and lowest Points is 941.70 meter and 251.19 meter respectively and the value of total relief is computed as 590 meter (fig.3.19). The relief of 590 meter within a distance of 58.25 km clearly indicates higher amount of potential energy available for water to flow in downstream reaches with high velocity, low infiltration and flashy discharge at the basin outlet.

Fig. 3.19 Digital Elevation Model of the Tittur Basin

3.6.2 Relative Relief and Relief Ratio

To show spatial variation from one place to another calculation of relative relief (Rao et al, 2011) is paramount. The vertical difference in elevation between the highest and lowest points of a land surface within a specified horizontal distance or in a limited area also known as relative relief. With the help of ARC GIS raster calculator and DEM calculate special relative relief. (fig.3.20). Relative relief has various regions and is classified into 5 categories, as show in fig (3.20). An appraisal of figure reveals that relative relief range between 0 m to 198.60 m the basin. The maximum frequency lies in low relief category of 0 m to 39.72 m. The frequency decrease as the relative relief become higher and higher.

Table 3.21 Relative relief

Relative Relief in km	Total Area In km²	% Area
0 – 39.72	885.11	91.24
39.72 -79.44	41.31	4.25
79.44 -119.16	29.42	3.03
119.16 – 158.88	11.51	1.18
158.88 – 198.60	2.92	0.30

Difference in the elevation between the highest point of a watershed and the lowest point on the valley floor is known as the total relief of the river basin. The relief ratio may be defined as the ratio between the total relief of a basin and the longest dimension of the basin parallel to the main drainage line (Schumm, 1956). The possibility of a close correlation between relief ratio and hydrologic characteristics of a basin suggested by Schumm who found that sediments loose per unit area is closely correlated with relief ratios. Relief ratio is the ratio of maximum basin relief to the catchments longest horizontal

straight distance measured parallel to the principal axis of drainage line. It has been observed that areas with low to moderate relief and slope are characterized by moderate value of relief ratios. Low value of relief ratios are mainly due to the resistant basement rocks of the basin and low degree of slope.

$$R_L = \text{Basin Relief (Z)} / \text{Longest Catchment Length (L)}$$

The relief ratio gives the overall steepness of the drainage basin and is a measure of shear stress applied on the surface of the basin. It is the dimensionless property of drainage basin. The computed relief ratio for the Tittur Basin is **11.907**, which is an indication low steepness of slopes contributing moderate surface runoff and moderately low infiltration in the Tittur **Basin**.

3.6.3 Ruggedness Number (Patton and Baker 1976):

The topographic ruggedness index to indicates the extent of instability of land surface (Strahler, 1956). Ruggedness number is defined as the product of the basin relief and drainage density and is a dimensionless number. It provides an idea of overall roughness of a basin. It is observed that ruggedness number for the Tittur Basin is 22.26. It indicates gentle and short slopes. It also shows a subdued relief with moderately rugged to old stage of terrain development.

Fig. 3.20 Relative Relief Map of the Tittur Basin

3.6.4 Dissection index

For better understanding of morphometry as well as physiographic attribute, dissection index analysis is performed (Schumm, 1956). Dissection index is defined as a ratio between actual dissection made by the rivers and potential dissection up to base levels. Relative relief and maximum altitude are used to compute the dissection index. Higher the value of dissection index, larger is the undulation and instability of the terrain. Dissection index is a parameter implying the degree of dissection or vertical erosion and expounds the stages of terrain or landscape development in any given physiographic region or watershed (Singh and Dubey 1994). On average, the values of Dissection index vary between '0' (complete absence of vertical dissection/erosion and hence dominance of flat surface) and '1' (in exceptional cases, vertical cliffs, it may be at vertical escarpment of hill slope or at seashore). Maximum dissection index is calculated as 0.27 in the southern and south east part of the watershed (Figure 3.21).

Fig. 3.21 Dissection Index Map of the Tittur Basin

3.6.5 Basin Slope

Slope is defined as an angular inclination of terrain between hill tops and valley bottoms, resulting from the combination of many constituent factors like geological structure, absolute and relative relief, climate, vegetation cover, drainage texture and stream frequency etc. It is one of the major dimensions of landforms in a drainage basin. Slope is the most important and specific feature of the earth's surface form. Maximum slope line is well marked in the direction of a channel reaching downwards on the ground surface. There are many contributions to slope-geomorphology and various methods of representing the slope, but the contributions made by Rich (1916), Wentworth (1930), Raisz and Henry (1937), Smith (1938-39), Robinson (1948), Calef (1950), Calef and Newcomb (1953), Strahler (1956), Miller and Summerson (1960), Eyles (1965) and Pity (1968), are very important.

In the present study, using ArcGIS 9.3.1 slope tool in spatial analysis extension has been adopted to determine the slope of the Tittur Basin. The average spatial slope of Tittur Basin has been prepared as shown in figure 3.22. The average regional slope of Tittur Basin ranges between 0° and 1°. This entire slope is distributed into six categories show in table 3.22.

Table 3.22 Slope category

Slope in Degree	Slope category	Area in km ²	Area in %
0 to 1	Level Slope	773.36	79.72
1 to 7	Pediment slope	106.35	10.96
7 to 14	Moderate Slope	37.1	3.82
14 to 22	Moderately steep slope	26.38	2.71
22 to 29	Steep Slope	19.94	2.05
More than 29	Escarpment	6.87	0.74

Fig. 3.22 Slope Map of the Tittur Basin

The slope map of the Tittur Basin reveals that maximum area of the basin i.e. 773.36 sq.km ,its cover 79.92 % to total lies under Level slope category of 0° to 1°. The pediment slope area i.e. above 1° to 7° covers 10.96% area. The Level and Pediment slope has a greater significance to enhance infiltration. The remaining 9.32 % areas which under lie's Moderate slope to escarpment are mostly runoff zone area; this area has not favorable for infiltration because in this area there is mostly first and second order stream with higher gradient.

3.6.6 Law of Channel Slope

The mean channel slope (gradient) is defined as the ratio of vertical drop to horizontal distance, measured from the upper end to the lower end of a single stream segment of a given order. The vertical leg of the triangle is the average vertical drop of that order the horizontal leg is the average horizontal distance of that order and is identical with mean stream length (Strahler, 1969). Mean channel slope of each order is then derived and tabulated.

Table 3.23 Mean channel slope of Tittur drainage Basin

Stream Order	Mean channel slope (Degree)
1	5.01
2	2.25
3	0.81
4	0.35
5	0.22
6	0.15
7	0.11

Fig. 3.23 Stream Order Vs Mean Channel Slope

The law of channel slope as propounded by R.E. Horton (1945) and applied by M.Morisawa (1959) and Leopold and Miller (1956) states that mean channel slope decreases with increasing successive orders in geometric series with constant slope ratio. The exponential function fitted to mean channel slope and stream order (fig.3.23) the Tittur drainage basin, reveals a perfect relationship as is evident from high coefficient of -0.83.

Fig. 3.23 Tittur Basin Stream Order Vs Mean Channel Slope

3.6.7 Longitudinal Profile of the Tittur River

The most striking phenomenon related to longitudinal profiles is their form. The plotting of these profiles shows altitude against distance downstream. The resulting form is a curve, more or less regular, the concavity of which increases towards the headwater area. This is their most obvious and persistent feature regardless of the climatic conditions, the length of the river or the rock cut by the riverbed. The attention here is focused on stream profile concavity, partly because it is assumed to be “...so common as to be almost universal” (Rubey, 1933, quoted by Wheeler, 1979).

We owe the first pertinent explanation of the form of the longitudinal profile to Gilbert (1877) who, on the basis of numerous laboratory experiments, showed that the slope of the longitudinal profile is inversely proportional to the discharge. Further studies were concerned with an even greater number of variables which could explain the form of the profile as well as its evolutionary tendencies. Special attention is paid to the effect that the discharge, the characteristics of the riverbed material, the sediment discharge (suspended or bed load), and the type of rock in situ have on the form of the stream bed profile. The conclusion was that the variation of the discharge (Q), the riverbed material diameter (D_{mm}), and the sediment load (Q_s) are the most important in explaining the shape of the profile. All other factors such as rocks of different hardness, tributaries, neotectonic movements, and its continuities caused by the different stages in the evolution of the profile, account for deviations from the general form of the profile, without fundamentally modifying it

Longitudinal stream profiles are conventionally illustrated as elevation plotted against distance downstream (Kale and Gupta, 2001). A

section of the longitudinal course of a river from head to mouth, showing only vertical changes. The theoretically smooth curve shown by such a profile may be interrupted by breaks of slope which can result from bands of resistant rock or from rejuvenation.

Downstream pattern of change in channel gradient and stream power are fundamentally related to the landforms and processes operating within a river basin. Analysis of downstream changes in channel gradient provides a key element for understanding, explaining, quantifying and predicting the variations in river basin forms and processes (Knighton, 1999). The Tittur River profile exhibit overall concave profile (fig.3.25). The stream gradient from DEM data is measured with the help of Globalmapper GIS software to generate longitudinal profile for 76.67 km length of the River Tittur.

There are two prominent breaks in the profile, one at 560 m elevation in upper reach and another at 366 m in middle reach. First break having a waterfall of 70 m height. It is near Patnadevi Kedarkund waterfall and another near at Valjhari, there is a rapid height upto 10 m. Below Kedarkund waterfall, a long narrow gorge and a hug circular pothole are carved into the basaltic rock. Within in Tittur basin there is several waterfall various magnitude, Dhaval Tirtha height is 50m, Junpani fall height is 60 m. All these Waterfalls experience change in magnitude and direction of flow and exhibits associated features like potholes, abrasion Platforms etc.

The Tittur River exhibits gradual downstream reduction in channel gradient except at 560 m elevation (Kedarkund) where a major waterfall is observed. Gradual decrease in gradient indicates the longer transfer of surface and groundwater along the channel in downstream direction. Gentler stream gradient has produced comparatively less dynamic

landscape characterized by a stable, bedrock controlled, incised channel in which a narrow alluvial flood plain have been built by lateral deposition. It is more pronounced to the downstream of along Chalisgaon.

The high relief, medium rainfall and medium size catchment area of the Tittur River together with gradient maxima in upper catchment, combined had produced Old stage topography.

The occurrence of a 70m waterfall at Kedarkunda, the natural amphitheatre clearly suggests a past rejuvenation of the stream, and the encroachment of the Tittur drainage system into the northern watershed of the Godavari.

Fig. 3.25 Longitudinal Profile of the Tittur River

3.6.8 Valley Cross Profiles

Profiles drawn from the DEM data are of greater importance to Geomorphologists who are primarily concerned with the analysis of relief and surface of a terrain because it provides a visual perception of the actual nature of terrain and the levels of planation surfaces.

The cross valley profiles have been studied at numerous locations (Fig.3.26.1 to Fig. 3.26.10) in the Tittur Basin from west to east as the basin has general trend of slope towards North. All the profiles have been constructed for western divide to eastern drainage divide. All profile show Asymmetrical valley form. Whereas asymmetrical valley forms profiles reveals that the rain water takes longer time to reach at main stream from the southern divide as compare to nothern divide with the steep valley side slopes. Water contributed by the Southern side tributaries flows with greater velocity with very low infiltration. The stream flow by northern side streams contributes much of its water to infiltration as well as to soil moisture. The weathered rock material formed on southern slopes from foot hill of Ajanta-Satmala goes directly to mainstream channel whereas the sediment load from these tributaries are deposited along the banks of the streams giving rise to high moisture retentive capacity and higher groundwater holding capacity.

The profiles of the valley floor appear to be flat with graded valleys in their lower reaches. Thus, all the profiles of Tittur Basin indicate that upper and lower reaches of the basin are having moderate to steep sided valley walls, while the valley floors are quite flat.

From Pos: 20° 12' 42.3867" N, 74° 59' 30.0411" E

To Pos: 20° 24' 23.2154" N, 74° 50' 40.1462" E

Fig. 3.26.1

From Pos: 20° 14' 31.7843" N, 75° 02' 17.5562" E

To Pos: 20° 26' 19.4504" N, 74° 53' 27.6614" E

Fig. 3.26.2

From Pos: 20° 16' 14.3446" N, 75° 04' 34.3033" E

To Pos: 20° 28' 12.2667" N, 74° 56' 11.7578" E

Fig. 3.26.3

From Pos: 20° 18' 3.7423" N, 75° 07' 11.5624" E

To Pos: 20° 29' 51.4083" N, 74° 58' 35.3423" E

Fig. 3.26.4

From Pos: 20° 19' 39.4652" N, 75° 09' 41.9842" E

To Pos: 20° 31' 30.5499" N, 75° 00' 55.5080" E

Fig. 3.26.5

From Pos: 20° 21' 18.6068" N, 75° 11' 55.3126" E

To Pos: 20° 33' 6.2729" N, 75° 03' 15.6737" E

Fig. 3.26.6

From Pos: 20° 22' 47.4924" N, 75° 14' 8.6409" E

To Pos: 20° 34' 38.5771" N, 75° 05' 25.5834" E

Fig. 3.26.7

From Pos: 20° 24' 16.3780" N, 75° 16' 18.5506" E

To Pos: 20° 36' 10.8814" N, 75° 07' 38.9118" E

Fig. 3.26.8

From Pos: 20° 26' 2.3570" N, 75° 18' 45.5537" E

To Pos: 20° 37' 53.4417" N, 75° 09' 59.0776" E

Fig. 3.26.9

From Pos: 20° 27' 31.2426" N, 75° 20' 58.8821" E

To Pos: 20° 39' 22.3273" N, 75° 12' 15.8246" E

Fig. 3.26.10

3.6.9 Superimposed, Projected and composite profile

The purpose of a profile is to show with precision, the form of the land (Miller, 1953). They present the variation of altitudes of the surfaces and the magnitude of the summit levels, etc. within the region besides profiles established then as erosion surface. The superimposed, projected and composite profiles are frequently used in the geomorphological interpretation of the terrain as they are useful in depicting the nature of the general relief's and different surfaces having different slopes at various altitudes.

Superimposed profile help in determining the difference level of planation surfaces. It shows not only the surfaces (of some morphological unity, as an erosion surface) by the general uniformity of level of various profiles but also reflect depth of the valleys and amplitude of relief. It is evident from fig.3.27 that there are three planation surfaces in the Tittur basin, that's Kannad surface, Patna Devi surface and Chalisgaon surface. Former erosion surface can be identified from the general uniformity levels of various profiles at different level. The peak rising over 580 m above sea level are clearly seen in the sets of superimposed profile (fig.3.27). The highest peak height is 942 m. It is very interesting to note that this peak is highest in Ajanta-Satmal range.

Projected profile provides a panoramic view of the whole landscape of the region as if seen from above and they also present a vivid picture of the magnitude of relief and general nature of dissection of region. (Fig.3.28)

Composite profile (fig.3.29) represents the highest parts of the summit level as if seen from a distance place.

Fig. 3.27 Superimposed profile of the Tittur Basin

Fig. 3.28 Projected Profile of the Tittur Basin

Fig. 3.29 Composite profile of the Tittur Basin

3.6.10 Percentage hypsometric curve (Strahler, 1952)

Hypsometric analysis (or area-altitude analysis) is the study of the distribution of horizontal cross-sectional area of a landmass with respect to elevation (Strahler, 1952). Classically, hypsometric analysis has been used to differentiate between erosional landforms at different stages during their evolution (Strahler, 1952, Schumm, 1956). It involves two ratios of relative height plotted on the ordinate and relative area plotted on the abscissa in terms of percentage, which has proved fruitful in providing a basis for recognizing stages of the cycle of erosion in a drainage basin (Savidndra Singh and R. Srivastava, 1975). Strahler (1952) introduced the hypsometric integral to determine stages of landscape development. According to Strahler (1952) topography produced by stream channel erosion and associated processes of weathering, mass-movement, and sheet runoff is extremely complex, both in the geometry of the forms themselves and in the inter-relationships of the processes which produce the forms. The form of the hypsometric curve and the value of the integral are important elements in topographic form. It shows marked variations in regions differing in stage of development and geologic structure, because in the stage of youth the hypsometric integral is large but it decreases as the landscape is denuded towards a stage of maturity and old age (Strahler, 1952).

The hypsometric integral (HI) is a geomorphological parameter classified under the geologic stages of watershed development. It assumes importance in estimation of erosion status of watershed and subsequent prioritization for taking up soil and water conservation activities. The hypsometric integral is also an indication of the 'cycle of erosion' (Strahler 1952; Garg 1983). Hypsometric analysis aims at developing a relationship between horizontal cross-sectional area of the watershed and

its elevation in a dimensionless form that permits comparison of watersheds irrespective of scale issues (Dowling et al. 1998). Hypsometric curves (HC) and hypsometric integrals are important indicators of watershed conditions (Ritter et al. 2002). Differences in the shape of the curve and the hypsometric integral value are related to the degree of disequilibria in the balance of erosive and tectonic forces (Weissel et al. 1994). Hypsometric analysis was first time introduced by Langbein (1947) to express the overall slope and the forms of drainage basin. The hypsometric curve is related to the volume of the soil mass in the basin and the amount of erosion that had occurred in a basin against the remaining mass (Hurtrez et al. 1999a). It is a continuous function of non-dimensional distribution of relative basin elevations with the relative area of the drainage basin (Strahler 1952). This surface elevation distribution have been extensively used for topographic comparisons because of its revelation of three-dimensional information through two-dimensional approach (Harrison et al. 1983; Rosenblatt and Pinet 1994)

The hypsometric integral helps in explaining the erosion that had taken place in the watershed during the geological time scale due to hydrologic processes and land degradation factors (Bishop et al. 2002). Besides this, it also provides a simple morphological index with respect to relative height of the elevation distribution within the area considered, which can be use in surface runoff and sediment yield prediction from watersheds (Sarangi and Bhattacharya 2000).

The hypsometric integral is the area beneath the curve which relates the percentage of total relief to cumulative percent of area. This provides a measure of the distribution of landmass volume remaining beneath or above a basal reference plane. Hypsometric curves and integrals can be interpreted in terms of degree of basin

dissection and relative landform age: Convex-up curves with high integrals are typical for youth, undissected (disequilibrium stage) landscapes; smooth, s-shaped curves crossing the center of the diagram characterize mature (equilibrium stage) landscapes, and concave-up with low integrals type old and deeply dissected landscapes (Strahler, 1952). Hypsometric integral and percentage of mass removed calculated by mathematically as well as graphically on hypsometric curve. The area below the curve is Hypsometric integral and above curve is percentage mass removed. The Hypsometric integral has been accepted as an important morphometric indicator of the stage of basin development. The Hypsometric integral of Tittur basin is 19 % indicating old stage of landscape development. The hypsometric of Tittur basin is shown in fig 3.30.

Hypsometric curve

Fig. 3.30 Strahler Hypsometric curve

Chapter IV
DRAINAGE BASIN HYDROLOGY

4.1 Introduction

4.2 Rainfall Regime

4.2.1 Isohyetal method

4.2.2 Spatial Distribution of Rainfall using TRMM Satellite data and GIS

4.3 Runoff

4.3.1 Estimation of Runoff using SCS CN Method and ArcGIS ArcCN Runoff Tool.

4.4 Rainfall-runoff Relationship

4.5 Hydrologic Abstractions

4.6 Evaporation Loss

4.7 Evapotranspiration

4.8 Potential Evapotranspiration

4.9 Soil moisture Retention

4.10 Initial abstraction

4.11 Infiltration

4.12 Time of Concentration

4.13 Discharge

4.14 Flow Regimes

4.15 Water Balance Study of Tittur Basin

4.16 Groundwater Hydrology

4.17 Aquifer Characteristics

4.18 Lithology of Well Sections

4.19 Well Inventory

4.20 Water Table Contour Map

4.21 Groundwater Flow in Relation to Water Table Contour

4.22 Groundwater Quality of Tittur Basin

Chapter IV

DRAINAGE BASIN HYDROLOGY

4.1 Introduction

Water is among the most essential requisites that nature provides to sustain life for plants, animals and humans. The total quantity of fresh water on earth could satisfy all the needs of the human population if it were evenly distributed and accessible. (Stumm, 1986) Quite literally hydrology is ‘the science or study of’ (‘logy’ from Latin logia) ‘water’ (‘hydro’ from Greek hudor). However, contemporary hydrology does not study all the properties of water. Modern hydrology is concerned with the distribution of water on the surface of the earth and its movement over and beneath the surface, and through the atmosphere (Davie,2002).Hydrology is the science of water, and deals with the occurrence, movement, distribution, circulation, storage of water of the earth (Mutreja, 1990). Hydrology determines the volume of water to be stored to achieve the desired objective. Drainage basin can be considered as the natural laboratory for hydrology (Garg, 1977). It provides a well defined physical unit for hydrological studies having input in the form of precipitation and output by evaporation and stream flow (Petts and Foster, 1985). Therefore, for all hydrologic analyses, a watershed constitutes the spatial unit, and all hydrologic problems are solved in the context of this spatial unit (Singh, 1994). There are number of indices, which can be defined to illustrate variability of hydrologic behavior such as rainfall, runoff, evaporation, infiltration, peak discharge, unit hydrograph, groundwater table and its fluctuation, movement to name but a few (Shaw, 1988). The drainage basin can be thought of a system that converts rainfall into runoff. The basin itself governs the runoff volume

from a given rainfall, the shape and magnitude of runoff hydrograph including discharge resulting from this runoff volume (Viessman et al., 1980).

The present chapter incorporates the fundamental principles of drainage basin hydrology. The results obtained by analyzing basin hydrological parameters such as rainfall, runoff, evaporation, evapotranspiration and infiltration. Groundwater, groundwater quality as well as groundwater fluctuation also have been presented in detail on the basis of field data and the data obtained from various government agencies and institutes.

4.2 Rainfall Regime

Rain is liquid water in the form of droplets that have condensed from atmospheric water vapor and then precipitated that is, become heavy enough to fall under gravity. Rain is a major component of the water cycle and is responsible for depositing most of the fresh water on the planet. Water budget is important measure in hydrological studies and deals with water as input in the form of precipitation and water loss or abstractions in the form of evaporation, evapotranspiration and infiltration. This measure helps to identify the water surplus and water deficiency in the drainage basin. A water budget is the scientific method for measuring the amount of water entering, stored within, and leaving a watershed and it is also called a hydrologic budget or a water balance.

Rainfall Regime is a term that comprises many components, including: mean and other statistical measures of annual rainfall total, its temporal distribution, the length of the rainy season, distribution of rain-spells and their yields, distribution of dry-spells, etc., the chief

rainfall regimes, as defined by W. G. Kendrew (1953), are equatorial, tropical, monsoonal, oceanic and continental westerlies, and Mediterranean. The Tittur Basin is situated in typical monsoon regime. The Tittur drainage basin receives input in the form of rainfall and excess input flows through streams and main river channel and further flows out of the basin in the form of runoff. Generally, the basin receives rain from mid-June with the onset of southwest monsoon. The monsoon period accounts for a large proportion of the mean annual rainfall over the basin. 90% of rainfall occurs in the months of July and August. This proportion of rainfall decreases towards the west part of the basin. July is the rainiest month throughout the basin, and accounts for 25% to 30% of the total annual rainfall.

Rainfall is often defined as being the key variable in hydrological systems. Considering the question how the spatial variability of rainfall influences the hydrological state, most studies have focussed on the effect on catchment discharge (e.g. Obled et al., 1994; Arnaud et al., 2002; Bell and Moore, 2000; Shah et al., 1991). Obled et al. (1994) conclude from their study (using TOPMODEL for a rural catchment of 71 km²) that the 25spatial variability must be taken into account more because it improves the estimation of the basin average incoming volume, rather than because of some dynamic interactions with flow-generating processes. Arnaud et al. (2002) (using 3 different rainfall-runoff models for 4 fictitious catchments of 20–1500 km²) however, found that rainfall variability can lead to significant different discharge, not for extreme events but for the more frequent events. This was also concluded by Shah et al. (1991): under “wet” 5 conditions, good predictions of runoff can be obtained with a spatially averaged rainfall input but under “dry” conditions; spatial variability of rainfall has a significant influence. They suggest this is

caused by the spatial distribution of soil moisture which controls the runoff production. Bell and Moore (2000) also show the importance of taking into account the spatial variability of rainfall, especially in case of convective rainfall events, 10 which show much more spatial variability. O'Connell and Todini (1996) point out the need to study the influence of space-time rainfall variability on the hydrological system in real catchments, but up to now not much attention has been given to the influence of rainfall variability on groundwater level and soil moisture content within the catchment.

In absence of rainfall data from the Tittur Basin, the mean areal rainfall figures have been estimated from the surrounding and within basin rain gauge sites (Chalisingaon, Bhadgaon, Pachora, Kannad, Vaijpur, Sillod, Nandgaon and Malegaon). Since, the areal distance of these sites from the basin centre is 20 to 30km (fig.2.6). Table 4.1a and 4.1b shows annual total in the respective wet years (1997-2011) for above rain gauge stations, and table 4.2 shows the average annual rainfall for eight rain gauge stations of the surrounding area of the basin. Isohyetal method and The Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) data has been used to estimate rainfall yield of the Tittur Basin

Table 4.1a Annual rainfall of surrounding gauging station in mm

Year	Chalisgaon	Bhadgaon	Pachora	Kannad
1997	960.2	920.5	1110.1	756.2
1998	1183	1137.9	1215.5	800.6
1999	632	659	553	699.7
2000	336.4	480	384	412.8
2001	666	644.3	588	567.5
2002	925.8	605.1	587.2	594.7
2003	1158	1067	985.6	440.82
2004	506	628	566	496.2
2005	379.4	662.2	588.9	506.35
2006	1039	1033.8	984	971.1
2007	531.6	481.6	536.36	537.72
2008	649.8	699.2	587.1	672.67
2009	747	689	716.6	967.1
2010	823.2	773.8	886.6	967.1
2011	695.8	631.8	657.2	694.6

(Data source: IMD; Based on 15 years of Record)

Table 4.1b Annual rainfall of surrounding gauging station in mm

Year	Vaijpur	Sillod	Malegaon	Nandgaon
1997	680.8	892.6	602.1	840.5
1998	754	924.5	647.6	882
1999	666.6	465.6	797.9	736
2000	258.8	338.6	408.6	696
2001	394.7	440.2	383.4	382
2002	405	758.6	552.9	584
2003	255.04	648.94	394.9	400
2004	484.4	624.7	672.2	517.4
2005	445.84	482.22	422.4	413
2006	843.08	1085.6	851	877.5
2007	538.03	644.54	739.1	629.2
2008	614.73	501.82	558	780
2009	635.6	750.8	763.5	792
2010	868.5	961.7	872	790
2011	523.6	709.6	396	571

(Data source: IMD; Based on 15 years of Record)

4.2.1 Isohyetal method

Isohyetal method is more appropriate for computing the mean areal rainfall in hilly and rugged topographical area (Suresh, 2005). As per IMD recommendations, in a regions of average elevation (500 to 1000m ASL) and in a hilly areas one rainguage station should be available for the area of 130 to 260 sq. km (Suresh, 2005). Isohytes have been drawn for Tittur Basin on the basis of rainfall data available from surrounding stations. In the isohyetal method, the point rainfalls are plotted on a suitable base map and the lines of equal rainfall (isohyets) are drawn giving consideration to orographic effects and storm morphology. The average rainfall between the succesive isohyets taken as the average of the two isohyetal values are weighted with the area between the isohyets added up and divided by the total area which gives the average depth of rainfall over the entire basin. The mean areal rainfall for study area has been determined by measuring the area of successive Isohytes. Thus the mean areal rainfall values obtained for Tittur Basin are shown in table 4.3.

Table 4.2 Average Annual Rainfall of surrounding Rain gauge station

Rain gauging Station	Average Annual Rainfall (mm)
Chaliskaon	748.88
Bhadgaon	740.88
Pachora	729.74
Kannad	672.34
Vaijpur	557.91
Sillod	682.00
Malegaon	604.10
Nandgaon	659.37

(Data source: IMD; Based on 15 years of Record)

Table 4.3 Mean areal Rainfall by Isohyetal Method

Isohyets (mm)	Area Enclosed (Sq. km)	Mean isohyetal value	Rainfall Volume (Cu. M) (Area Enclosed X Mean isohyetal value)	Mean Areal depth of Rainfall (mm)
	A		B	
650-675	95.65	662.5	63368.125	$\Sigma B / \Sigma A$ 707.76 mm
675-700	168.10	687.5	115568.75	
700-725	530.60	712.5	378052.50	
725-750	175.75	737.5	129615.62	
	970.10		686604.99	

(Data source: IMD; Based on 15 years of Record)

Average areal rainfall computed from Isohyetal method is 707.76 mm. Fig 2.5 in IInd chapter shows the distribution of mean areal rainfall in the basin.

4.2.2 Spatial Distribution of Rainfall using TRMM Satellite data and GIS

The Tropical Rainfall Measurement Mission (TRMM) is a joint space mission between NASA and the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) designed to monitor and study tropical rainfall. The term refers to both the mission itself and the satellite that the mission uses to collect data. TRMM is part of NASA's Mission to Planet Earth, a long-term, coordinated research effort to study the Earth as a global system. The satellite was launched on November 27, 1997 from the Tanegashima Space Center in Tanegashima, Japan. These data, recorded at 3-h intervals allow the identification of extreme events and their spatiotemporal context. Whereas these data cover only the last 14 years (1998–2011),

several distinctive rainfall patterns help to delineate general relationships between rainfall, topographic relief and extreme-rainfall events.

Instruments aboard the TRMM

Precipitation Radar (PR)

The Precipitation Radar is the first space borne instrument designed to provide three-dimensional maps of storm structure. The measurements yield information on the intensity and distribution of the rain, on the rain type, on the storm depth and on the height at which the snow melts into rain. The estimates of the heat released into the atmosphere at different heights based on these measurements can be used to improve models of the global atmospheric circulation.

TRMM Microwave Imager (TMI)

The TRMM Microwave Imager (TMI) is a passive microwave sensor designed to provide quantitative rainfall information over a wide swath under the TRMM satellite. By carefully measuring the minute amounts of microwave energy emitted by the Earth and its atmosphere, TMI will be able to quantify the water vapor, the cloud water, and the rainfall intensity in the atmosphere. It is a relatively small instrument that consumes little power. This, combined with the wide swath and the quantitative information regarding rainfall make TMI the "workhorse" of the rain-measuring package on Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission.

Visible and Infrared Scanner (VIRS)

The Visible and Infrared Scanner is one of the three instruments in the rain-measuring package and serves as a very indirect indicator of rainfall. VIRS, as its name implies, senses radiation coming up from the Earth in

five spectral regions, ranging from visible to infrared, or 0.63 to 12 micrometers. VIRS is included in the primary instrument package for two reasons. First is its ability to delineate rainfall. The second, and even more important reason, is to serve as a transfer standard to other measurements that are made routinely using POES and GOES satellites. The intensity of the radiation in the various spectral regions (or bands) can be used to determine the brightness (visible and near infrared) or temperature (infrared) of the source.

Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System (CERES)

CERES measures the energy at the top of the atmosphere, as well as estimates energy levels within the atmosphere and at the Earth's surface. Using information from very high resolution cloud imaging instruments on the same spacecraft, CERES also will determine cloud properties, including cloud-amount, altitude, thickness, and the size of the cloud particles. All of these measurements are critical for understanding the Earth's total climate system and improving climate prediction models.

Lightning Imaging Sensor (LIS)

The Lightning Imaging Sensor is a small, highly sophisticated instrument that detects and locates lightning over the tropical region of the globe. The lightning detector is a compact combination of optical and electronic elements including a staring imager capable of locating and detecting lightning within individual storms. The imager's field of view allows the sensor to observe a point on the Earth or a cloud for 80 seconds, a sufficient time to estimate the flashing rate, which tells researchers whether a storm is growing or decaying.

4.2.2.1 Methodology

Tropical Rainfall Measurement Mission (TRMM) product 3B42 is used for analysis (Huffman et al. 2007). The data is obtained in a gridded format with a spatial resolution of 0.2586 degree (approximately 30 km) and a temporal resolution of 3 h. Data access and detailed algorithm information are available on the web (http://disc.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov/precipitation/documentation/TRMM_README/TRMM_3B42_readme.shtml/). In short, input for the 3B42 dataset comes from two main sources: first, sensors on board several low-earth-orbit satellites measuring indicators related to hydrometeors that ultimately result in surface precipitation. These sensors are the TRMM Microwave Imager (TMI), Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I), Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer-Earth Observing System (AMSR) and Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit-B (AMSU). Second, data from a geosynchronous satellite in the infrared spectrum are calibrated with the low-Earth-orbit satellites to provide high temporal observations of large parts of the Earth. In a final step, these datasets are combined through continuously improved and re-calibrated algorithms (Huffman et al, 2007). Several studies suggest that the TRMM 3B42 surface-rainfall rate is comparable to the other surface observation (e.g. Koo et al, 2009, Sapiano and Arkin, 2009), although the spatial scale of the rainfall data makes direct comparison to gauge data difficult. In addition, it has been argued that the TRMM 3B42 product is useful for creating a global landslide-hazard assessment (e.g. Hong et al, 2006). After successful compilation of TRMM Satellite data using Arc GIS spatial analysis extension prepare spatial distribution map.

Result:

The rainfall in Tittur basin is characterized by highly irregular distribution, seasonality and high annual variability in successive years. Main stream of the Tittur River originates in the lowest rainfall zone wherein rainfall is up to 700 mm. Valjhari and Dungri sub basins head's belongs to the moderate rainfall zone. Gadad sub basin source lies in very high rainfall zone on the south eastern part of the basin. The orographic effect of the Ajanta Satmala hill range in the southern part is responsible for enhancing the higher monsoon rainfall. Besides, the east-west orientation of the Tittur Basin also determines the amount and distribution of rainfall over the entire basin. Thus spatial variation of rainfall is controlled by Orographic barrier on one hand and the east west orientation of basin on the other. This fact is reflected in the TRMM data and on the isohyetal pattern of the map of Tittur basin (Fig. 2.5).

The source areas of Gadad and Valjhari sub basin receive more than 1000 mm and 700 mm rainfall respectively. The amount of rainfall gradually decreases towards west side of the basin where Dungri and Pimpri sub basins are situated (i. e. less than 700 mm rainfall.) However, in this part, the drainage area is less. The area of lowest rainfall (477 to 709 mm) is also observed in small patch on eastern side of Tittur basin.

More than 90% of the annual rainfall is concentrated in the month of June, July, August, September and October months. This period is defined as rainy monsoon season. The spatial distribution and Mean monthly rainfall and have been shown in table 4.4 and 4.5 respectively. Table 4.4 Mean monthly rainfall base on TRMM Satellite data

Table 4.4 Rainfall Zone base on TRMM Satellite data

Rainfall in mm	Category	Area in sq. km.	Area in %
477 - 709	Very Low Rainfall Zone	162.85	16.76
709 - 816	Low Rainfall Zone	239.33	24.67
816 - 919	Moderate Rainfall Zone	240.79	24.82
919 - 1036	High Rainfall Zone	178.19	18.36
1036 - 1185	Very High Rainfall Zone	148.94	15.39

Table 4.5 Monthly Rainfall base on TRMM Satellite data

Month	Maximum Rainfall	Minimum Rainfall	Mean Rainfall in mm
January	11	0	5.5
February	13	0	6.5
March	42	0	21
April	14	0	7
May	26	0	13
June	326	24	175
July	475	48	261.5
August	351	7	179
September	437	68	252.5
October	202	0	101
November	16	1	8.5
December	9	0	4.5

Fig. 4.1 Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite Data (Annual)

Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite

Fig- 4.1a Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite Data (Jan. – Apr.)

Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite

Fig. 4.1b Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite Data (May. – Aug.)

Rainfall Spatial Distribution using TRMM Satellite

Fig. 4.1c Spatial Rainfall Distribution using TRMM Satellite Data (Sept. – Dec.)

The average monthly rainfall of 15 years (1997 to 2011) for 8 rain gauge stations surrounding the Tittur basin shows wide variation of rainfall in every month. The intensity of rainfall gradually increases from the July to October, and suddenly decreasing from November and December. The July and August are the peak rainfall months. The mean annual rainfall of the Tittur basin is 831.2 mm (based on TRMM Satellite data). The rainfall distribution of Tittur basin is influenced by the Ajanta-Satmal hill ranges. The windward side of the Ajanta-Satmal hill ranges receives maximum rainfall in the range of 1036 - 1185 mm. Similar rainfall pattern is observed in the south-east part. This part of the basin is referred to as Gautala reserve forest. Very small pockets of high rainfall are also observed in the vicinity of the mouth. The western side of the basin receives minimum rainfall in the range of 477 - 709 mm.

4.3 Runoff

Surface runoff is the water flow that occurs when the soil is infiltrated to full capacity and excess water from rain, melt water, or other sources flows over the land. This is a major component of the water cycle, and the primary agent in water erosion (Beven, 2004). Runoff that occurs on surfaces before reaching a channel is also called a nonpoint source. A land area which produces runoff that drains to a common point is called a drainage basin. Surface runoff occurs when the rate of rainfall on a surface exceeds the rate at which water can infiltrate the ground, and any depression storage has already been filled. This is called infiltration excess overland flow, Hortonian overland flow (after Robert E. Horton), or unsaturated overland flow. The Hortonian overland flow is more

commonly occurs in arid and semi-arid regions, where rainfall intensities are high and the soil infiltration capacity is reduced because of surface sealing by disaggregated soil particle under the impaction of raindrop. In urban areas the concrete pavements prevents water infiltration.

When the soil is saturated, the depression storage filled, and rain continues to fall, the excess rainfall is converted into surface runoff. The saturation of soil is influenced by level of antecedent soil moisture. This runoff is also called as saturation excess overland flow or saturated overland flow or Hewlettian runoff. Soil retains some degree of moisture after a rainfall. This residual water moisture is called as antecedent soil moisture and affects the soil's infiltration capacity. The higher the level of antecedent soil moisture, the more quickly the soil becomes saturated. Once the soil is saturated, runoff occurs.

Oftenly on up hill slopes, some portion of infiltrated water may flow laterally through the soil and appears on the surface or exfiltrate (flow out of the soil) closer to a channel in the form subsurface return flow or through flow. The volume and intensity of runoff may be reduced in a several ways due to evapotranspiration, surface stricking or storage in microtopographic depressions; infiltration and generation of overland flow. The remaining surface water eventually flows into a receiving water body such as a river, lake, estuary or ocean (Nelson, 2004).

4.3.1 Estimation of Runoff using SCS- CN Method and ArcGIS ArcCN Runoff Tool.

In hydrology a curve number (CN) is used to determine how much rainfall infiltrates into soil or an aquifer and how much rainfall is available for surface runoff. The CN value is directly proportional to runoff and inversely proportional to infiltration. As higher the curve number higher will be the runoff and lower infiltration (especially for urban areas), whereas a lower the curve number lower would be the runoff and higher the infiltration (e.g. over dry soils). Hence the curve number is a function of land use and hydrologic soil group. The US Soil Conservation Service (SCS; now Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS)) introduced curve-number method for predicting storm runoff volume. Many watershed models such as AGNPS (Young et al., 1987), EPIC (Williams, 1995), SWAT (Arnold et al., 1996), and WMS have used this method to determine surface runoff. The transported Sediment and nutrient are also estimated from the runoff. Recently it was reported from some applications of this method with watershed models in Kansas (Bhuyan et al., 2002, 2003; Tsou and Zhan, 2004; Misgna et al., 2004).

Traditionally, an area weighted average curve number for the entire watershed is used to study the runoff of a watershed. The details of the spatial variation in the watershed are often lost. An ArcGIS tool, named ArcCN-Runoff, is therefore developed to facilitate watershed-modeling work. Unlike raster mode, ArcCN-Runoff is designed for any shape of polygon in order to keep irregular boundaries unaltered. Application of dissolving techniques reduces processing time significantly. The curve-number database implemented provides a flexible way to use a reference table for the curve number based on soil and land use information. Users can also develop their own database as simply as to editing an Excel file.

The tool can be used to design and manage hydraulic structures and projects, to estimate future discharges, and to predict watershed response associated with changes in topography, soil, land use, and land cover (e.g. urbanization).

4.3.2 Application

Soil and land use data are needed as inputs. The land use and Soil data of Tittur basin generated using supervised classification image processing method on Landsat ETM+ Satellite data in ERDAS 2011 Remote Sensing software. After generate raster of these layers it is converted in to vector layer using Spatial Analysis extension.

After loading the ArcCN-Runoff tool into ArcMap, soil and land use data were processed through the following three steps:

- (1) To focus on an interesting area or a watershed, the soil and land data for the watershed were clipped using a polygon feature from the overlay layer such as a watershed-boundary layer.
- (2) To reduce processing time, the soil and land use layers were dissolved before intersection, based on the attributes in soil and land use.
- (3) Soil and land use layers were intersected to generate new and smaller polygons associated with soil hydro group and land use cover name. This step keeps all the details of the spatial variation of soil and land use, and therefore it is considered more accurate than using raster grid to calculate runoff than any average or dominant methods to determine curve number.

The curve number for each polygon was determined from the soil and landuse information. All input and output are stored in the newly

generated layer after intersection and the operation was performed through the panel. An important step is to match the covername of landuse to the landuse of index table in the curve-number database. The curve number database was built based on the similar curve number databases of SCS CN. The map showing spatial variation of the curve number is generated automatically after clicking on the button called “finish match” on the working panel. Using the statistics functions in ArcMap, users can report immediately some statistical results of the curve number for the watershed.

4.3.3 Calculation of Runoff

The runoff is calculated based on the SCS curve number-runoff method. The SCS curve-number method assumes that, for a rainfall of storm event, the ratio of actual soil retention after runoff begins to the potential maximum retention of soil is equal to the ratio of direct runoff to rainfall. This simplified assumption (Ponce and Hawkins, 1996) results in the following runoff equation where the curve number ($0 < CN < 100$) represents a convenient representation of the potential maximum soil retention (S). The runoff is calculated by the SCS curve number-runoff method on the basis of soil permeability, surface cover, hydrologic condition, and antecedent moisture.

The basic assumption of the SCS curve number method is that, for a single storm, the ratio of actual soil retention after runoff begins to potential maximum retention is equal to the ratio of direct runoff to available rainfall. This relationship has been simplified after assumptions have been simplified after is relationship is simplified, after, algebraic manipulation with consideration of assumptions and results in the following equation. (Which is found in Section 4 of the National

Engineering Handbook (NEH-4) (USDA-SCS, 1985), where curve number (CN) represents a convenient representation of the potential maximum soil retention, S (Ponce and Hawkins, 1996).

$$Q = \frac{(P - 0.2S)^2}{P + 0.8S} \text{ ----- (4.1)}$$

Where

- Q is runoff in mm
- P is rainfall in mm
- S is the potential maximum soil moisture retention after runoff begins
- The runoff curve number, CN, is then related

$$S = (25400 / CN) - 254 \text{ ----- (4.2)}$$

Lower curve numbers indicate low runoff potential and higher numbers indicates higher runoff potential. (The table of CS curve values is given in Chapter 9 of NEH-4 for various land covers and soil textures.) These values are applicable to variety of watershed to estimate runoff from rainfall data (USDA-SCS, 1985). The entire process of estimation of runoff is represented with help of following flow chart. Thus spatial map of CSC Curve number for Tittur basin has been prepared.(as shown fig.4.3) and annual as well as monthly runoff values estimated for Tittur basin as given in Table 4.6 and Table 4.7.

Fig. 4.2 Flow chart of Arc GIS / Arc CN Runoff Methodology

Fig. 4.3 SCS Curve Number Map of the Tittur Basin

Table 4.6 Yearly Runoff of Tittur Basin

Year	Rainfall in mm	Runoff in mm
1997	845.37	671.40
1998	943.13	766.52
1999	651.22	484.47
2000	414.40	263.34
2001	508.26	349.60
2002	626.66	461.08
2003	668.78	501.24
2004	561.86	399.78
2005	487.53	330.36
2006	960.63	783.59
2007	579.76	416.65
2008	632.91	467.03
2009	757.70	586.60
2010	867.86	693.23
2011	609.95	445.21

Table 4.7 Monthly Rainfall base on TRMM Satellite data and Estimate Runoff using SCS CN method

Month	Rainfall in mm	Runoff in mm	Month	Rainfall in mm	Runoff in mm
January	5.5	00	July	261.5	198.2
February	6.5	00	August	179	120.3
March	21	00	September	252.5	189.5
April	7	00	October	101	51.3
May	13	00	November	8.5	00
June	175	116.6	December	4.5	00

4.3.4 Seasonal Variation of Runoff in Tittur basin

In the Tittur basin rainfall is not uniformly distributed throughout the year. It varies with space and time; consequently the runoff is also not uniform. To understand seasonal variation of runoff, the monthly average data have been collected for the period of 15 year. Table No.4.7 reveals that rainfall is concentrated in a particular period of the year, i. e. June, July, August, September and October, commonly known wet monsoon season. The monthly average data of runoff and their proportion to the average annual runoff have been computed using SCS CN method for entire Tittur basin. The high percentage of runoff is mostly concentrated in June, July, August and September. The highest percentage of runoff occurs in the month of July (198.2 mm). July and August are the core months of wet monsoon season of Tittur basin. The spatial map of runoff distribution has been prepared for Tittur basin (fig.4.4).The runoff map of Tittur basin similar pattern like rainfall distribution map. It clearly indicates the strong associations between rainfall and runoff for Tittur basin. The sub-basinwise mean annual runoff and its volume also have been estimated and compared to Tittur basin as shown in Table No 4.8. In order to understand Runoff regime of the Tittur basin, intended as the sequence of mean monthly runoff values, is a useful indicator of the seasonality of runoff, to be used for the development of water management strategies.

Fig. 4.4 Runoff Map of the Tittur Basin

Table 4.8 Sub basin wise Mean Annual Rainfall and Runoff

Sub Basin	Pimpri	Dungri	Valjhari	Gadad	Tittur
Rainfall(mm)	733.9	734.8	868.6	860.9	831.2
Runoff(mm)	627.8	623.9	704.8	664.1	705.5
Runoff Volume (m ³)	1.01 x 10 ⁸	4.5 x 10 ⁷	1.10 x 10 ⁸	2.25 x 10 ⁸	6.85 x 10 ⁸

Total available annual runoff in the Tittur Basin after evaporation and infiltration loss is about 705.5 mm and runoff volume is 6.85 x 10⁸ m³. Results obtained for four sub basin reveals that Valjhari sub basin generates 704.8 mm of surface runoff as compare to 664.1 mm of Gadad basin, 623.9 mm of Dungri and 627.8 mm of Pimpri basin. Valjhari basin is located in central part of the Tittur Basin having more rainfall than other sub basin, precipitous slope with thin soil cover and rocky surface resulting low infiltration and greater runoff. Pimpri and Dungri basin contributes greater rainwater towards groundwater in the form of infiltration as compare to that of Gadad and Valjhari basin, because of total infiltration in to the soil owing to the large catchment availability as well as factors favorable infiltration such as gentle slope, comparatively deep weathering, fractured and jointed basalt rock. Therefore it can be said that Pimpri and Dungri sub basins have enough groundwater potential than Valjhari and Gadad sub basin.

4.4 Rainfall-runoff Relationship

A rainfall-runoff model is a mathematical model describing the rainfall runoff relations of a catchment area, drainage basin or watershed. More precisely, it produces the surface runoff hydrograph as a response to a rainfall hydrograph as input. In other words, the model calculates the conversion of rainfall into runoff. A rainfall runoff model can be really helpful in the case of calculating discharge from a basin. The transformation of rainfall into runoff over a catchment is known to be very complex hydrological phenomenon, as this process is highly nonlinear, time-varying and spatially distributed. Over the years researchers have developed many models to simulate this process. Based on the problem statement and on the complexities involved, these models are categorized as empirical, black-box, conceptual or physically-based distributed models. Physically based distributed models are very complex and required too many data and tedious for the application purpose. The conceptual models attempt to represent the known physical process occurring in the rainfall-runoff transformation in a simplified manner by way of linear or nonlinear mathematical formulations but their implementation and calibration is complicated and time consuming. While black-box models, which establish a relationship between input and the output functions without considering the complex physical laws governing the natural process such as rainfall-runoff transformation. The unit hydrograph, which is a linear rainfall-runoff model, is one well-known example of such a relationship.

Rainfall-Runoff Models

The development of computer models to simulate rainfall-runoff relationships has been a prime focus of hydrological research for at least since the 1960s (Crawford and Linsley, 1966) and has resulted in a proliferation of models. Following Beck (1991), the following sections describe metric, conceptual, and physically based rainfall-runoff models to note how the methods investigated in this study are related.

Metric models

Metric (or empirical) models are directly based on observations to characterize runoff and are formulated with little or no consideration of the hydrologic cycle (Kokkonen and Jakeman, 2001) so that the model has no theoretical basis. Strictly limited to the range of data used to formulate the model, empirical models have two basic uses. Firstly, interpolations over the range of data used to derive the model are feasible in that the computer codes serve to estimate a response between observations. Secondly, the form and structure of metric models provide insight into the formulation of conceptual models or the derivation of physically based models, making extrapolation beyond the original observations possible. The unit hydrograph (Sherman, 1949), formulated as a linear relationship between rainfall excess and stream flow, is one of the first metric rainfall-runoff models developed (Kokkonen and Jakeman, 2001). Although the curve number method can be classified as an empirical model (Kokkonen and Jakeman, 2001) based on infiltrometer, plot, and watershed data used to derive the table of curve numbers (NRCS, 2001), the curve number was derived from the principle that water is conserved on a watershed during a storm. Hence, semi-empirical is a better categorization for the curve number method.

Conceptual models

These models incorporate the important hydrological processes using mathematical approximations. Conceptually these types of models usually involve interconnected storage volumes receiving recharge and discharge as appropriate for representations of component processes of the hydrological cycle (Kokkonen and Jakeman, 2001). Good examples of conceptual watershed models include

- (1) The Stanford Watershed Model (Crawford and Linsley, 1966)
- (2) The Tank model (Sugawara et al., 1983)
- (3) The Boughton (1984) model
- (4) MODHYDROLOG (Chiew and McMahon, 1994)
- (5) Hydrologiska Bryäns Vattenbalansavdelning (Bergström, 1995).

The more component processes that are represented in the conceptual model the larger the risk of over-parameterization. Freer et al. (1996), Johnston and Pilgrim (1976), and Speare et al. (1994) document the associated effects of parametric uncertainty in conceptual hydrologic modeling.

Physically based models

Models with a theoretical basis simulate hydrological responses based on the governing hydrodynamics and transport equations. A physically based model is one for which parameters and variables of the governing equations are measurable in the field (Beven, 1983). In hydrology, however, some parameter estimation using empirical relationships is necessary to solve the governing equations for the complex flows that occur (Wilcox et al., 1990). Freeze (1972) developed the first physically

based model to solve the Richards equation for unsaturated flow in two dimensions to represent hill slope processes. Later, Abbott et al. (1986) and Bathurst (1986) developed the *Système Hydrologique Européen* model and Beven et al. (1987) developed the Institute of Hydrology Distributed Model using similar mathematical formulations. Physically based models are appealing because of the mathematical approximations of the real phenomenon are derived from first principles. However, these models can require difficult-to-obtain data and may have large computational demands. Beven (1989), Binley and Beven (1989), and Grayson et al. (1992) discuss the applicability of physically based models. This method (Beck, 1991) of classifying rainfall-runoff models is not complete. Some models may have a strong empirical origin, but also have some conceptual basis so that these cannot be clearly classified as empirical or conceptual models. These types of models can be classified as semi-empirical.

The SCS curve number method is the best example of a semi-empirical model. Because of spatial variability within a watershed, the conceptual or the physically based rainfall-runoff models can also be classified as lumped, semi-distributed, or fully distributed. Rainstorms generate runoff, and its occurrence and quantity are dependent on the characteristics of the rainfall event, i.e. the intensity, duration and distribution. Apart from these rainfall characteristics, there are number of catchment specific factors, which have a direct effect on the occurrence and volume of runoff. They include soil type, vegetation cover, and slope and catchment type. SCS-CN provides an empirical relationship for estimating initial abstraction and runoff as a function of soil type and land use. Rainfall runoff relationship can be visualized by the factors such as initial

abstraction (Ia), direct runoff (Q), and actual retention (F). The Curve Number (CN) is an index developed by the Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS), to represent the potential for storm water runoff within a drainage area. The CN for a drainage basin is estimated using a combination of land use, soil, and antecedent soil moisture condition (AMC). There are four hydrologic soil groups: A, B, C and D. Group A have high infiltration rates and group D have low infiltration rates.

Group A Soils: High infiltration (low runoff) for Sand, loamy sand, or sandy loam_ Infiltration rate ranges from 762— 11.43 mm/hr. when wet.

Group B Soils: Moderate infiltration (moderate runoff) for Silt loam or loam. Infiltration rate ranges from 3.81 - 7.62 mm/hr. when wet.

Group C Soils: Low infiltration (moderate to high runoff) for Sandy clay loam. Infiltration rate ranges from 1.27 - 3.81 mm/hr. when wet.

Group D Soils: Very low infiltration (high runoff) for Clay loam, silty clay loam, sandy clay, silty clay, or clay. Infiltration rate ranges from 0.00 - 1.27 mm/hr. when wet.

The mean annual rainfall and the mean annual runoff have been estimated for Tittur basin and plotted to establish rainfall -runoff relationship as shown in fig.4.5.

Annual rainfall and runoff Relationship of Tittur basin

Fig. 4.5 Annual Rainfall Runoff Relationships

A general principal or relationship between mean annual rainfall and runoff has been proposed by estimating the correlation coefficient between mean annual runoff and mean annual rainfall. The estimated correlation coefficient is 99.99 %.The linear regression equation is also worked out and expressed as follows..... (4.3). the runoff is a function of rainfall.

$$Y = -136.8 + 0.9562 x \text{ ----- (4.3)}$$

Where Y = Runoff in mm,

And X = Rainfall in mm.

Monthly Rainfall and runoff Relationship of Tittur basin:

The relationship between mean monthly rainfall and mean monthly runoff also have been established for Tittur basin as shown in fig.4.6

Fig. 4.6 Monthly Rainfall Runoff Relationships

The correlation coefficient (98.99 %) has been worked out between monthly rainfall and runoff which is significantly high. The linear regression equation is also established between monthly rainfall and runoff. (Fig.4.4).The runoff is a function of rainfall. This can be expressed with the help of a liner regression equation.

$$Y = -9.162 + 0.7593 x \text{ ----- (4.4)}$$

Where Y = Runoff in mm,

And X = Rainfall in mm.

Out of the total mean annual rainfall of Tittur basin (i.e. 675.9 mm.) 65.30 % is converted into runoff. The remaining 34.70 % of rainfall is lost by evaporation and percolation underground.

The Mean Monthly Rainfall-Runoff Patterns:

Water resources engineers are primarily concerned with catchment yields and usually study hydrometric records on a monthly basis. Most rainfall measurements are made daily, and a day's rain may be part of a continuous storm that can be related to resulting stream flow by means of the unit hydrograph method. With the summation of daily values to give a monthly total, periods of both wet and dry days are included, and the relationship of the rainfall with stream flow is indirect. Monthly mean discharges from a catchment area are converted to volumes of water produced and then to equivalent depths over the catchment area. Rainfall and runoff in the same units can then be compared.

The nature of the relationship of rainfall to runoff over longer periods again depends primarily on the structure and composition of the catchment area, but it can also be affected by the climate of the area. In the Tittur basin rainfall occurs in 5 months within year. Taking average monthly values over 15 years, regional variations in the rainfalls of the wettest and driest months can be identified. Resultant effects on runoff are dependent on the time factor; the rainfall-runoff relationship is distinctly modified by the occurrence of sequences of wet or dry months.

Fig 4.7 reveals seasonal pattern of rainfall and runoff. The runoff of Tittur basin is concentrated in the rainy monsoon season during June-october. The runoff is almost absent during remaining month during November- May.

Fig. 4.7 Monthly Rainfall Runoff Pattern

The mean monthly rainfall pattern as shown in Fig.4.7 for the catchment area of the Tittur drainage basin reveals long duration aridity. This arid period is attributed to various losses of rainfall like evaporation, and transpiration or the combined process known as evapotranspiration. The potential evapotranspiration is a measure of water need of plant during the arid period. Therefore potential evapotranspiration is also one of the important parameters of hydrological concerns.

Pimpri Sub basin

Fig. 4.8 Rainfall and Runoff Map of the Pimpri Sub Basin

Dungri Sub basin

Fig. 4.9 Rainfall and Runoff Map of the Dungri Sub Basin

Valjhari Sub basin

Fig. 4.10 Rainfall and Runoff Map of the Valjhari Sub Basin

Gadad Sub basin

Fig. 4.11 Rainfall and Runoff Map of the Gadad Sub Basin

4.5 Hydrologic Abstractions

Amount of precipitation, which does not appear as overland flow or runoff, is considered as hydrologic abstractions. Evaporation and infiltration are the most important abstractions in the hydrologic-budget equation. Hydrologic Abstractions include Interception, Evaporation, Transpiration, Depression storage, Surface Detention and Infiltration.

A portion of the rainfall is intercepted by plant foliage, buildings, and other objects. This water is not available for runoff. Interception typically removes about 0.5 mm during a single storm event. Maximum Values is reported 1.5 mm.

Evaporation is the change of the state of water from liquid to vapor as a result of heat addition. The air is saturated when relative humidity is 100%. The evaporation process continues until the air completely saturated.

Transpiration is the transfer of soil moisture from the soil to the atmosphere by the action of vegetation. Plants transpire water vapor through their foliage. Transpiration has minimal effect on individual storms and is usually only taken into account in long-term hydrologic budgets. Evaporation and transpiration are commonly lumped in one variable called evapotranspiration.

Depression storage accounts for the water that becomes ponded in land surface irregularities. Depression storage depends on the land use of the watershed and typically amounts to 0.5 to 8 mm during a single rain event. It is inversely proportional to the slope of watershed.

Detention storage is the volume of water that moves as overland flow (sheet flow). This volume is temporarily detained in transit to the

stream. Sheet flow storage depends on watershed parameters including land use, vegetation, slope, and rainfall intensity. Typical values range between 2.5 mm and 10 mm.

Infiltration takes place as part of the rain percolates through the soil pores. The rate of infiltration depends on the soil type, slope, vegetation, soil moisture content, temperature, and the precipitation intensity. Infiltration usually is the largest abstraction and therefore has the most significant effect on runoff. Infiltration rates generally decrease with time as the rainfall proceeds and the soil becomes saturated. Many infiltration models have been developed from very simple to very complex.

The abstraction is very small as compare to runoff event hence can be neglected. The bulk of evaporation takes place before runoff events is usually long. Whereas infiltration occurs or commences as soon as overland flow initiates. These losses have significant influence in the available volume of water in the basin. Therefore abstractions i. e. evaporation and infiltration losses must be considered in order to understand the total surface runoff generated from the rainfall.

4.6 Evaporation Loss

Evaporation or vaporization is the process by which water changes from liquid state to vaporous state. Two main factors influencing the evaporation from an open water surface are the supply of energy to provide latent heat of vaporization and the ability to transport the vapor away from the evaporating surface. Solar radiation is the main source of heat energy. The ability to transport the vapor away from the evaporating surface depends on the wind velocity over the surface and the specific humidity gradient in the air above it

Evaporation may occur directly from open water surfaces, from the soil or as transpiration from plants. Potential evaporation (PE) is the maximum evaporation that would occur from a continuous vegetative cover supplied with ample moisture. Temperature, particularly during the summer, is the primary influence on evaporative demands, but wind speed, sunshine hours, humidity and patterns of land use are all contributory factors (Hough and Jones, 1997).

Evaporation losses from small reservoirs affect their water storage efficiency. Because water that evaporates is water that cannot be used, one can also speak about unproductive water losses. Many planners and decision makers feel that small reservoirs are unsuitable for rural water supply because they assume that evaporation losses are extremely high (Jones, 1991). Evaporation losses in tropical region is high because of intense solar radiation, greater number of sun shine hour and day of clear skies, High wind speed and long rainless period.

Evaporation is an important hydrologic loss that affects the hydrological output or runoff of a river basin. Evaporation over the entire drainage basin varies with season and is inversely related to rainfall. In

order to know about evaporation losses of the Tittur Basin, mean monthly pan evaporation data from Chalisgaon station has been used. Mean monthly average pan evaporation values for the year 2011 have been considered to obtain average annual evaporation for the entire area. Table 4.9 shows monthly pan evaporation values for the year 2011.

Table 4.9 Mean Monthly Evaporation data for Tittur basin

Month	Pan Evaporation (mm/Day)	Month	Pan Evaporation (mm/Day)
Jan	3.1	Jul	4.2
Feb	4.0	Aug	4.0
Mar	5.3	Sep	4.3
Apr	8.2	Oct	4.9
May	10.7	Nov	3.2
Jun	5.8	Dec	3.0

(Data Source: Chalisgaon Tahsil office 2011)

On the basis of above values, average daily pan evaporation of the Tittur Basin fluctuates around 5.0 mm per day. Fig 4.12 reveals that summer months experience higher evaporation losses because of high temperatures, and negligible rainfall. The graph also shows drastic reduction of evaporation during monsoon season (June to September) whereas in winter also declines after October maxima and gradual rise after January.

As per the statistics with Groundwater Survey and Development Agency, Pune (Sarbukan, 2001), nearly 40% of the total rainfall loss is due to evaporation and 15% infiltration loss enhances the groundwater storage. Considering these 55% losses, net 45% rainfall is available only for runoff.

4.7 Evapotranspiration

Evapotranspiration (ET) is the sum of evaporation and plant transpiration from the Earth's land surface to atmosphere. Evaporation accounts for the movement of water to the air from sources such as the soil, canopy interception, and water bodies. Transpiration accounts for the movement of water within a plant and the subsequent loss of water as vapor through stomata in its leaves. Evapotranspiration is an important part of the water cycle. An element (such as a tree) that contributes to evapotranspiration can be called an evapotranspirator (Swank and Douglass, 1974). Evapotranspiration is a significant water loss from drainage basins. Types of vegetation and land use significantly affect evapotranspiration, and therefore the amount of water leaving a drainage basin. Because water transpired through leaves comes from the roots, plants with deep reaching roots can more constantly transpire water. Herbaceous plants generally transpire less than woody plants because they usually have less extensive foliage. Conifer forests tend to have higher rates of evapotranspiration than deciduous forests, particularly in the dormant and early spring seasons. This is primarily due to the enhanced amount of precipitation intercepted and evaporated by conifer foliage during these periods (Swank and Douglass, 1974). Factors that affect evapotranspiration include the plant's growth stage or level of maturity, percentage of soil cover, solar radiation, humidity, temperature, and wind.

The term evapotranspiration (ET) is commonly used to describe two processes of water loss from land surface to atmosphere, evaporation and transpiration. Evaporation is the process where liquid water is converted to water vapor (vaporization) and removed from sources such as the soil surface, wet vegetation, pavement, water bodies, etc. Transpiration consists of the vaporization of liquid water within a plant

and subsequent loss of water as vapor through leaf stomata. Evaporation and transpiration occur simultaneously and both processes depend on solar radiation, air temperature, relative humidity (i.e. vapor pressure deficit) and wind speed. Transpiration rate is also influenced by crop characteristics, environmental aspects and cultivation practices. Different kinds of plants may have different transpiration rates. Not only the type of crop, but also the crop development, environment and management should be considered when assessing transpiration. For example, when the crop is small, water is predominately lost by soil evaporation because little of the soil surface is covered by the plant, but once the crop is well developed and completely covers the soil, transpiration becomes the main process (Allen et al, 1998). Reference evapotranspiration (E_{To}) is defined as the rate at which readily available soil water is vaporized from specified vegetated surfaces (Jensen et al, 1990). Then, reference evapotranspiration is defined as the ET rate from a uniform surface of dense, actively growing vegetation having specified height and surface resistance, not short of soil water, and representing an expanse of at least 100 m of the same or similar vegetations (Allen et al, 2005). The concept of the E_{To} was introduced to study the evaporative demand of the atmosphere independent of crop type, crop development and management practices. If water is abundantly available at the reference surface, soil factors do not affect ET; however, ET may decrease overtime as soil water content decreases. Relating ET to a specific surface provides a reference to which ET from other surfaces can be related. It obviates the need to define a separate ET level for each crop and stage of growth and is referred to as crop ET (E_{Tc}). E_{To} values measured or calculated at different locations or in different seasons are comparable as they refer to the ET from the same reference surface. The only factors affecting E_{To}

are climatic parameters and ET_c can be determined from ET_o using a crop specific coefficient (K_c). The use of K_c with specific crops is the subject of other EDIS documents: Basic Irrigation Scheduling in Florida (Smajstrla et al., 1997), Outline for Managing Irrigation of Florida Citrus with High Salinity Water (Boman and Stover, 2002), A Web-Based Irrigation Scheduling Model to Improve Water Use Efficiency and Reduce Nutrient leaching for Florida Citrus (Morgan et al, 2009), Irrigation Scheduling for Tropical Fruit Groves in South Florida (Migliaccio and Li, 2000), Smart Irrigation controllers: Programming Guidelines for Evapotranspiration-Based Irrigation Controllers (Dukes et al, 2009) and Principle and Practices of Irrigation Management for Vegetables (Simonne et al, 2010).

A large number of empirical methods have been developed over the last 50 years to estimate evapotranspiration from different climatic variables. Evapotranspiration of Tittur basin derived from updated equation was recommended by FAO (Allen et al. 1998) with the Penman-Monteith Equation, Metrologic data collect from NASA GISS (**Goddard Institute for Space Studies**) (Hansen and Lebedeff, 1987) and IMD Pune.

$$ET_o = \frac{0.408\Delta(R_n - G) + \gamma \frac{900}{T + 273} u_2 (e_s - e_a)}{\Delta + \gamma (1 + 0.34u_2)} \text{-----4.6}$$

Where

ET_o = reference evapotranspiration [mm day⁻¹],

R_n = net radiation at the crop surface [MJ m⁻² day⁻¹],

G = soil heat flux density [MJ m⁻² day⁻¹],

T = air temperature at 2 m height [$^{\circ}\text{C}$],
 u_2 = wind speed at 2 m height [m s^{-1}],
 e_s = saturation vapor pressure [kPa],
 e_a = actual vapor pressure [kPa],
 $e_s - e_a$ = saturation vapor pressure deficit [kPa],
 Δ = slope vapor pressure curve [$\text{kPa } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$],
 γ = psychrometric constant [$\text{kPa } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$].

Thus estimated monthwise values of evapotranspiration are given in the Table 4.10.

Table 4.10 Monthly Evapotranspiration of Tittur basin

Month	ET(mm)	Month	ET(mm)
Jan	34.2	Jul	40.7
Feb	43.5	Aug	35.2
Mar	55.1	Sep	41.4
Apr	69.3	Oct	44.2
May	81.1	Nov	37.2
Jun	59.6	Dec	32.1

On the basis of above table 4.10, it reveals that April and May months experience higher evapotranspiration losses because of high temperatures, dry air, vegetation require more water for transpiration and negligible rainfall. The graph (Fig. 4.12) also shows drastic reduction of evapotranspiration during winter season (November to February).

4.8 Potential Evapotranspiration

Evaporation is the primary process of water transfer in the hydrological cycle. The water is transformed into vapour and transported to the atmosphere. The combined process of evaporation and transpiration from a vegetated surface is known as *potential evaporation* or *potential evapotranspiration* (PET) and it constitutes the maximum possible rate due to the prevailing meteorological conditions. PET is also known as water need of the plants. Potential evapotranspiration is defined as “the rate of evapotranspiration from an extensive surface of 8 to 15 cm tall, green grass cover of uniform height, actively growing, completely shading the ground and not shortage of water” (Doorenbos and Pruitt,1977). PET is s equal to the actual evaporation (ET): $PET = ET$ when water supply is unlimited.

Thornthwaite (1948) suggested that soil moisture may have considerable effect on evapotranspiration and potential evapotranspiration was equal to actual evapotranspiration that would occur when there was an adequate supply of soil moisture at all the times. Penman (1956) defined potential evapotranspiration as the amount of water transpired in unit time by a short green crop, completely shading the ground, of uniform height and never short of water. Van Ba.vel (1966) defined potential evapotranspiration as the evapotranspiration that occurs when the vapour pressure at the evaporating surface is at the saturation point. Gangopadhyaya et. al. (1970) defined potential evapotranspiration as the maximum quantity of water capable of being lost as water vapour in a given climate by a continuous, extensive stretch of vegetation covering the whole ground when the soil is kept saturated. Jensen (1973) defined potential evapotranspiration as the rate at which water, if available, would

be removed from the soil and plant surfaces, expressed as the latent heat transfer per unit area or its equivalent depth of water per unit area.

Potential evapotranspiration (PET) is defined as the amount of evaporation that would occur if a sufficient water source were available. If the actual evapotranspiration is considered the net result of atmospheric demand for moisture from a surface and the ability of the surface to supply moisture, then PET is a measure of the demand side. Surface and air temperatures, insolation, and wind all affect this. A dry land is a place where annual potential evapotranspiration exceeds annual precipitation. PET is a measure of the ability of the atmosphere to remove water through the process of evaporation and transpiration. The FAO introduced the definition of PET as the evapotranspiration of a reference crop under optimal conditions, having the characteristics of well watered grass with an assumed height of 12 centimeters, a fixed surface resistance of 70 seconds per meter and an albedo of 0.23 (Allen et al,1998).

Various research workers defined and discussed many ways for measurement of potential evapotranspiration. Thornthwaite (1948) assumed that an exponential relationship exists between mean monthly temperature and mean monthly consumptive use. The relationship was based largely on experience in the central and eastern United States. No allowance was made for different crops on varying land uses. The formula was originally developed for the purpose of a rational classification of the broad climatic patterns of the world. Suitable coefficients should therefore be developed locally for reliable estimation of crop ET values. Thornthwaite (1948) proposed the following formula:

$$PET = 16 \left(\frac{L}{12} \right) \left(\frac{N}{30} \right) \left(\frac{10T_a}{I} \right)^\alpha \text{----- (4.7)}$$

Where

PET = the estimated potential evapotranspiration (mm/month)

T_a = the average daily temperature (degrees Celsius) of the month being calculated

N = the number of days in the month being calculated

L = the average day length (hours) of the month being calculated

$$\alpha = (6.75 \times 10^{-7})I^3 - (7.71 \times 10^{-5})I^2 + (1.792 \times 10^{-2})I + 0.49239$$

$I = \sum_{i=1}^{12} \left(\frac{T_{ai}}{5} \right)^{1.514}$ is a heat index which depends on the 12 monthly mean temperatures T_{ai} (Thornthwaite, 1948)

Table 4.11 Monthly Potential Evapotranspiration of Tittur basin

Month	PET(mm)	Month	PET(mm)
January	86.9	July	40.7
February	98.6	August	35.2
March	118.2	September	41.4
April	167.4	October	44.2
May	195.9	November	95.4
June	59.6	December	82.6

Fig. 4.12 Monthly Evaporation, Evapotranspiration and Potential Evapotranspiration

4.9 Soil moisture Retention

The role of soil in retaining water is significant in terms of the hydrological cycle; including the relative ability of soil to hold moisture and changes in soil moisture over time. Soil water that is not retained or used by plants may continue downward through the profile and contribute to the water table, the permanently saturated zone at the base of the profile – this is termed recharge. Soil that is at field capacity may preclude infiltration so to increase overland flow. Both effects are

associated with ground and surface water supplies, erosion and salinity. Soils can process and contain considerable amounts of water. They can take in water, and will keep doing so until they are full, or the rate at which they can transmit water into, and through, the pores is exceeded. Some of this water will steadily drain through the soil (via gravity) and end up in the waterways and streams. But much of it will be retained, away from the influence of gravity, for use of plants and other organisms to contribute to land productivity and soil health.

The spaces that exist between soil particles, called pores, provide for the passage and/or retention of gasses and moisture within the soil profile. The soil's ability to retain water is strongly related to particle size; water molecules hold more tightly to the fine particles of a clay soil than to coarser particles of a sandy soil, so clays generally retain more water (Leeper and Uren, 1993). Conversely, sands provide easier passage or transmission of water through the profile. Clay type, organic content and soil structure also influence soil water retention (Charman & Murphy 1977).

The maximum amount of water that a given soil can retain is called field capacity, whereas a soil so dry that plants cannot liberate the remaining moisture from the soil particles is said to be at wilting point (Leeper & Uren 1993). Available water is that which the plants can utilize from the soil within the range of field capacity and wilting point. Soil moisture has an effect on the thermal properties of a soil profile, including conductance and heat capacity, explains Oke (1987); the association of soil moisture and soil thermal properties has a significant effect on temperature-related biological triggers, including seed germination, flowering and faunal activity.

Recent climate modelling by Timbal et al. (2002) suggests a strong linkage between soil moisture and the persistence and variability of surface temperature and precipitation; further, that soil moisture is a significant consideration for the accuracy of “inter-annual” predications regarding the Australian climate.

Estimation of Soil moisture Retention using SCS CN method

The SCS-CN method is based on the water balance equation and two fundamental hypotheses. The first hypothesis equates the ratio of the actual amount of direct surface runoff (Q) in the total rainfall (P) (or minimum potential surface runoff) to the ratio of the amount of actual infiltration (F) to the amount of the potential maximum retention (S). The second hypothesis relates the initial abstraction (Ia) to the potential maximum retention. Thus, the SCS-CN method consists of

$$\text{Water balance equation: } P = Ia + F + Q$$

$$\text{Proportional equality hypothesis: } Q \setminus P - Ia = F \setminus S$$

Where

P = total rainfall;

Ia = initial abstraction,

F = cumulative infiltration excluding Ia,

Q = direct runoff, and

S = potential maximum retention or infiltration, also described as the potential post initial abstraction retention (McCuen, 2002).

The SCS runoff equation (SCS, 1972) that is an empirical model was developed to provide a consistent basis for estimating the amounts of runoff under varying land use and soil types (Neitsch, 2001).

$$Q = \frac{(P - I_a)^2}{(P - I_a) + S}$$

Where Q is the accumulated runoff or rainfall excess (mm), P is the rainfall depth for the day (mm), I_a is the initial abstractions which includes surface storage, interception and infiltration prior to runoff (mm), and S is the retention parameter (mm). The retention parameter varies spatially due to changes in soils, land use, management and slope and temporally due to changes in soil water content. The retention parameter is defined as

$$S = (25400 / CN) - 254$$

Where CN is the SCS curve number.

Parameter S of the SCS-CN method depends on the soil type, land use, hydrologic condition, and antecedent moisture condition (AMC). The

initial abstraction accounts for the short-term losses, such as interception, surface storage, and infiltration (Ramasastrri and Seth, 1985).

Table 4.12 Monthly Soil moisture Retention of Tittur basin

Month	S (mm)	Month	S (mm)
January	27.5	July	63.5
February	32.5	August	63.5
March	105	September	63.6
April	35	October	63.6
May	65	November	42.5
June	63.5	December	22.5

S = Soil moisture Retention in mm

4.10 Initial abstraction (Ia)

SCS-CN method constitutes a popular empirical approach for the estimation of direct runoff for a given rainfall event from small agricultural, forest, and urban watersheds and is capable of incorporating several watershed runoff producing characteristics; soil type, land cover and practice, hydro-logic condition, and (AMC) antecedent moisture condition (Mishra and Singh, 2003; Mishra et al., 2004, 2005; Jain et al., 2006). It was developed by the U.S. Department of Agriculture (SCS, 1956) Soil Conservation Service (SCS), now called Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS). Due to its low input data requirements and its implementation within GIS, it has been incorporated in many widely used hydrological models.

The initial abstraction (Ia) includes all losses before runoff begins, and includes water retained in surface depressions, water taken up by

vegetation, evaporation, and infiltration. This value is related to characteristics of the soil and the soil cover. The initial abstraction includes water captured by vegetation, depression storage, evaporation, and infiltration. For any Rainfall, this abstraction must be satisfied before any runoff is possible. The universal default for the initial abstraction is given by the equation:

$$I_a = 0.2S$$

Where

I_a = Initial abstraction (includes interception, surface storage, and infiltration)

S = Potential maximum soil retention after runoff begins

The determined values of the initial abstraction are close to the suggested the highest initial abstraction is 21 mm in the March month due to not sufficient rainfall for runoff in the Tittur basin. In the month June to October initial abstraction values are same due to Rainy season and wet soil. In the month of November to May total rainfall account to initial abstraction. The human intervention, in the form of urban development and the impervious geological formations contribute to the decrease in the initial abstraction. Runoff from these impervious areas reaches the outlet at the early stages of the storm and thus leads to low initial abstraction. On the contrary, the initial abstraction is higher in the foot hill of Ajant satmala range due to the lack of impervious areas and occurrence of colluviums. Monthly Initial abstraction show in table 4.14

4.11 Infiltration

Infiltration process is one of the most important components of the hydrologic cycle. The ability to quantify infiltration is of great importance in watershed management. Prediction of flooding, erosion and pollutant transport all depend on the rate of runoff which is directly affected, by the rate of infiltration (Zolfaghari et al, 2012). Infiltration has an important role in land-surface and sub-surface hydrology, runoff generation, soil erosion, irrigation rate. In addition, the infiltration rate of the soil is influence by various factors depending on the condition of soil surface, its chemical and physical properties (Siyal et al., 2002). Also water infiltration is an index of soil compaction (Younesi Alamouti and Navabzadeh, 2007).

Infiltration is the process by which water on the ground surface enters the soil. Infiltration rate in soil science is a measure of the rate at which soil is able to absorb rainfall or irrigation. It is measured in inches per hour or millimeters per hour. The rate decreases as the soil becomes saturated. If the precipitation rate exceeds the infiltration rate, runoff will usually occur unless there is some physical barrier. It is related to the saturated hydraulic conductivity of the near-surface soil. The rate of infiltration can be measured using an infiltrometer. Infiltration is governed by two forces: gravity and capillary action. While smaller pores offer greater resistance to gravity, very small pores pull water through capillary action in addition to and even against the force of gravity.

The rate of infiltration is affected by soil characteristics including ease of entry, storage capacity, and transmission rate through the soil. The soil texture and structure, vegetation types and cover, water content of the soil, soil temperature, and rainfall intensity all play a role in controlling

infiltration rate and capacity. Vegetation creates more porous soils by both protecting the soil from pounding rainfall, which can close natural gaps between soil particles, and loosening soil through root action. This is why forested areas have the highest infiltration rates of any vegetative types. Once water has infiltrated the soil it remains in the soil, percolates down to the ground water table, or becomes part of the subsurface runoff process.

The process of infiltration can continue only if there is room available for additional water at the soil surface. The available volume for additional water in the soil depends on the porosity of the soil and the rate at which previously infiltrated water can move away from the surface through the soil (Hogan, 2010). The maximum rate that water can enter a soil in a given condition is the infiltration capacity. If the arrival of the water at the soil surface is less than the infiltration capacity, all of the water will infiltrate. If rainfall intensity at the soil surface occurs at a rate that exceeds the infiltration capacity, ponding begins and is followed by runoff over the ground surface, once depression storage is filled. This runoff is called Horton overland flow.

The minimum or ultimate value of infiltration capacity, (in/hr or mm/hr) this parameter is essentially the saturated hydraulic conductivity, or "permeability", of soils. The table 4.14 lists ranges of this parameter for various soil groups (Musgrave, 1955).

Table 4.13 Hydrologic Soil Infiltration Rate

Hydrologic Soil Group	Minimum Infiltration Rate (mm/hr)
A	7.6 - 11.4
B	3.8 - 7.6
C	1.3 - 3.8
D	0.0 - 1.3

Infiltration calculation methods

Infiltration is a component of the general mass balance hydrologic budget. There are several ways to estimate the volume and/or the rate of infiltration of water into a soil. The SCS CN is based on the water balanced equation.

$$P = Ia + F + Q$$

The water balance equation, simple algebra solves the infiltration question. There for

$$F = P - Q - Ia$$

Where

F =is Cumulative infiltration excluding Ia,

P = is total rainfall,

Ia = is initial abstraction,

Q =is direct runoff

Table 4.14 Actual Infiltration and Initial abstraction of Tittur basin

Month	Rainfall (mm)	Runoff (mm)	Initial abstraction (Ia) (mm)	Infiltration F (mm)
January	5.5	00	5.5	00
February	6.5	00	6.5	00
March	21	00	21	00
April	7	00	7	00
May	13	00	13	00
June	175	116.6	12.7	45.7
July	261.5	198.2	12.7	50.6
August	179	120.3	12.7	46
September	252.5	189.5	12.7	50
October	101	51.3	12.7	37
November	8.5	00	8.5	00
December	4.5	00	4.5	00

Fig. 4.13 Hydrologic Soil Group Map of the Tittur Basin

4.12 Time of Concentration

Time of concentration is a concept used in hydrology to measure the response of a watershed to a rain event. It is defined as the time needed for water to flow from the most remote point in a watershed to the watershed outlet (Haan et al, 1994). It is a function of the topography, geology, and land use within the watershed.

The time of concentration is the time required to a drop of water in remote part of the drainage basin so as to reach the basin outlet or gauge (Singh, 1992). It consists of the time required for all portions in the drainage basin to contribute runoff. After saturation, it is assumed that uniform rainfall continues over the entire drainage basin for a period at least equal to the time of concentration. The time of concentration also affects the amount of water to be available for infiltration in the soil of the watershed. It also represents the maximum discharge that can occur from a rainfall over the drainage basin. Kirpich (1940) method of time of concentration has been used to obtain the time of concentration for the Tittur Basin. It is as follows:

$$***T_c = 0.0078(L/S^{0.5})^{0.77}***$$

Where

T= is the time of concentration in minutes,

0.0078 is Kirpich's constant based on physiography, soil, vegetation factors,

L= is the length of travel in meters from the most remote point on the drainage basin along the river channel to the basin outlet, and

S= is the slope in meters per meter determined by the difference in elevation of the most remote point and that of the outlet divided by distance.

As per 76.6 km length and slope is 0.012 m/m , the time of concentration of the Tittur River is 616.70 minutes (10 Hour 27 minutes). It means that runoff requires 616.70 minutes to approach from periphery of Tittur Basin. Thus by adopting Kirpich method, time of concentration have been estimated for sub basin as shown table 4.15

Table 4.15 Sub basin wise Time of concentration

Sub basin	Time of concentration in Minutes	Time of concentration in Hours
Pimpri	263.29	4.38
Dungri	244.33	4.07
Valjhari	205.17	3.41
Gadad	294.63	4.91
Tittur	616.70	10.27

Table 4.15 reveals a general fact that the time of concentration is irrespective of elevation and distance, e.g. Gadad basin has maximum time of concentration with comparatively Valjhari sub basin. It means that other factors like infiltration, lithology, intensity and duration of rainfall might be influencing the time of concentration. Similarly, Different travel time of the sub basin reveals that Gadad and Pimpri sub basin takes larger path from its point of source to travel up to basin outlet as compare to Valjhari and dungri sub basin, this indicates that rain occurring over this area has greater chance for infiltration by natural process. In contrast Valjhari and dungri sub basin take short time of concentration, this fact clearly indicates that the rainfall after initial

losses, rapidly contributes to the main river discharge without considerable infiltration, though the basin has sufficient slope.

4.13 Discharge

In hydrology, discharge is the volume rate of water flow, including any suspended solids (i.e. sediment), dissolved chemical species and/or biologic material (i.e. diatoms), which is transported through a given cross-sectional area (Buchanan and Somers, 1969).

The discharge of a river is the volume of water which flows through it in a given time. It is usually measured in cubic meters per second. The volume of the discharge will be determined by factors such as climate, vegetation, soil type, drainage basin relief and the activities of man. The catchment of a river above a certain location is determined by the surface area of all land which drains toward the river from above that point. The river's discharge at that location depends on the rainfall on the catchment or drainage area and the inflow or outflow of groundwater to or from the area, stream modifications such as dams and irrigation diversions, as well as evaporation and evapotranspiration from the area's land and plant surfaces.

The discharge is a significant hydrological attribute related to stream flow. It represents the runoff in the river or stream at a given cross section and time. Discharge generally includes surface runoff as well as ground water flow (Bhamare, 1978). The discharge data of the Tittur basin have been obtained from the gauging stations near Lohatar. The correlation coefficient between stage and discharge is 0.8799.

The rating equation also has been estimated owing to the significantly high correlation ship between stage height and discharge, which can be expressed as

$$Y = 1.327 + 34.09 X$$

Where Y = discharge in cumes,

And X = stage height in meter.

Fig. 4.14 Stage and Discharge Relationship

This rating equation has been used for measurement of discharge in one case and the stage height in another.

Besides the stage, velocity of flow is also correlated with discharge. Very high correlation coefficient is also observed between velocity and discharge which is 0.9221. The relation between velocity and discharge can be predicted with the help of the following regression form:

$$Y = 5.9100x - 0.4211$$

Where Y = discharge in cumes,

And X = velocity in meter per second.

Table 4.16 Monthly Mean Discharge and Mean Stage Height of Tittur basin

Months	Discharge(m³/s)	Mean Stage Height (m)
January	1	0.05
February	0	0
March	0	0
April	0	0
May	0	0
June	21	0.18
July	71	0.95
August	87	2.5
September	41	1.5
October	6	0.85
November	2	0.15
December	1	0.1

(Source: SDSC, Hydrology Project, Nashik)

4.14 Flow Regimes

Fig. 4.15 Flow Regimes of Tittur Basin

The flow of the river is not uniform throughout the year. Particularly, rivers in tropical monsoon regions commonly display a seasonal pattern of runoff which reflects the interaction of rainfall and evaporation in wet and dry periods during the year. Such a pattern of flow of a river is called flow regime or runoff regime (Bhamare, 1978). The Tittur basin lies in a tropical monsoon climate region. The basin receives high rainfall inputs during the post summer monsoon (June, July, August and September). The winter and pre-summer period (March, April and May) experience a marked dry season.

Figure 4.15 shows the flow regions of river Tittur at Lohatar gauging stations. The monthly date of discharge is available for a period of 5 years (2007-2011). The Tittur basin displays a more complex flow regime that is related to several factors. The discharge is exceptionally high during the monsoon i.e. July, August and September. This is the

rainiest part of the year. June is also a month of heavy rains, but in this month evaporation is higher than the rest of the monsoon months. May and June, both record high temperature. Wind speed is also very high in the month of June. High velocity winds accelerate the rate of evaporation; consequently, the runoff is low in June, despite good rains. In the month of October, transpiration is more from plants besides a decrease in rainfall as a result of recession of the monsoons. The flow regime has generally followed the rainfall pattern.

4.15 Water Balance Study of Tittur Basin

The input items into a basin are essentially precipitation (P) and subsurface inflow (Gi) while the water losses are evaporation (E), evapotranspiration (ET) and subsurface outflow (Go). The balance goes to recharge ground water (Gr), increase the soil moisture (SMA) and as surface runoff (stream flow, R). The water balance equation can be written as

$$***P + G_i = E + ET + G_o + SMA + G_r + R***$$

The monthly normal water balance for the whole year for the Tittur River basin is given in Table 4.17

Table 4.17 Water balance for Tittur basin

Month	PET	P	ET	SMU	SMD	SMA	R + Gr
Jan	86.9	5.5	34.2	28.7	52.7	—	—
Feb	98.6	6.5	43.5	37	55.1	—	—
Mar	118.2	21	55.1	34.1	63.1	—	—
Apr	167.4	7	69.3	62	98.1	—	—
May	195.9	13	81.1	68.1	114.8	—	—
Jun	59.6	175	59.6	—	—	115.4	—
Jul	40.7	261.5	40.7	—	—	170.8	50
Aug	35.2	179	35.2	—	—	—	143.8
Sep	41.4	252.5	41.4	—	—	—	211.1
Oct	44.2	101	44.2	—	—	—	56.8
Nov	95.4	8.5	37.2	28.7	58.2	—	—
Dec	82.6	4.5	32.1	27.6	50.5	—	—
Total	1066.1	1035	573.6	286.2	442.0	286.2	461.7

PET = potential evapotranspiration (mm/month) when there is unlimited water in the root zone, i.e., $P \geq PET$.

P= precipitation (mm/month)

ET =actual evapotranspiration (mm/month) limited to the availability of water by precipitation and soil moisture stored; $ET \leq PET$

SMU = Soil moisture utilization (mm/month) from storage = $ET - P$

SMD = Soil moisture deficit (mm/month) = PET – ET

SMA = Soil moisture accretion (mm/month) when $P > PET$

$$= P - PET - (R + Gr)$$

$R + Gr$ = Rainfall excess (stream flow + Ground water accretion)

(mm/month)

$R + Gr = P - PET - SMA$; after soil recharge = $P - PET$

The water balance study shows that the water need (1066.1 mm) is higher than the water supply by precipitation (1035 mm), though an amount of 461.7 mm of water is recorded as rain-fall excess (stream flow plus ground water storage (in underground formations)), on account of concentration of rainfall from June to October compared to the lower values of water need during these months. Water deficiency (SMD) obtained from the water balance studies indicates the amount of water (442 mm) needed for supplemental irrigations in agricultural operations, adjustment of crop calendar (so that harvest will precede drought) and crop rotation to improve the soil structure and increase the soil moisture storage capacity. Crop yields can increase if the moisture deficiency could be avoided. Water surplus is 286.2 and deficit is 442 mm, *since annual water deficit is more than water surplus, Tittur basin is under drought.*

Fig. 4.16 Water Balance of Tittur Basin

Thus, estimation of evaporation, evapotranspiration, infiltration, runoff and discharge of the Tittur Basin is based on the data collected from field survey, empirical formulae and conventional methodologies adopted by different scholars in different regions. Therefore exact estimation of these hydrological indices gives appropriate picture of surface water hydrology.

4.16 Groundwater Hydrology

Next to the surface water hydrology, groundwater hydrology also plays a significant role in watershed hydrological studies. Ground-water hydrology is the subdivision of the science of hydrology that deals with the occurrence, movement, and quality of water beneath the Earth's surface. It is interdisciplinary in scope in that it involves the application of the physical, biological, and mathematical sciences. It is also a science whose successful application is of critical importance to the welfare of mankind. Because ground-water hydrology deals with the occurrence and movement of water in an almost infinitely complex subsurface environment, it is, in its most advanced state, one of the most complexes of the sciences (Thomas, 2004). Groundwater is a dynamic and replenishes able natural resource. But in hard rock terrain, availability of groundwater is of limited extent. Its occurrence is essentially confined to fractured and weathered zones, fills the cracks, porous and void spaces in soils and rock formations (Fetter, 2000). The occurrence of groundwater largely depends upon climatic conditions, characters of soils, vegetation cover, land use and geology of the area. The infiltration or precipitation falling over the surface is the main source of groundwater. Out of total rainfall receipt, some part is lost through evapotranspiration from soil and plants. A major portion of rainfall loss through runoff, only small amount of rainwater infiltrates through the soil and reaches to underlying strata or aquifers (Babar, 2005).

Hydrological and geomorphological investigation helps to locate and demarcate potential zones for groundwater to reduce the failure of bore wells. Deccan basaltic terrain in general and the Tittur Basin in particular, are no exception to these facts. As mentioned earlier that the

study area is the part of Deccan Basaltic Province characterized by extensive horizontally bedded lava flows of Cretaceous-Eocene period. Groundwater in Deccan Trap province mostly occurs under unconfined conditions, particularly in the broad river valleys. These valleys are characterized by thick weathered zones and alluvium deposits along the river banks (Dikshit, 1985). Occurrence of groundwater under confined conditions is a very rare phenomenon in Deccan volcanic province. From the hydro- geological point of view, the frequency and extent of jointing, fracturing, flow contacts and depth of weathering are the most significant factors imparting permeability and porosity for the formation of suitable groundwater reservoirs in the basaltic terrain (Deshpande, 2004). During the last three decades remarkable Progressess regarding groundwater exploration has been developed and developing countries of the world. Hydrology, geology, geomorphology and geophysics in Progressess regarding groundwater exploration has developed and developing countries of the world. Hydrology, geology, geomorphology and geophysics in conventional techniques have made it possible to explore the groundwater potentiality in hard rock terrain of Maharashtra. In the Tittur Basin, most of the villages, wadis and hamlets, the groundwater is the chief source for domestic and agricultural needs.

Therefore by considering these factors that are responsible occurrence, movement, direction and availability of groundwater, the groundwater condition of the Tittur drainage basin have analyzed by studying aquifer characteristics, well inventory lithology of open wells, pre-monsoon and post-monsoon water table condition and natural recharge conditions etc. In order to understand water table condition and groundwater flow direction, 19 wells from the Tittur Basin were selected. Pre-monsoon and post-monsoon (October-November) water level of

these as recorded continuously for the year 2009 and 2011 to know their recharge condition and water table fluctuation. On the basis of groundwater fluctuation and water table condition, groundwater contour maps were prepared to know the groundwater flow direction.

4.17 Aquifer Characteristics

An aquifer is an underground layer of water-bearing permeable rock or unconsolidated materials (gravel, sand, or silt) from which groundwater can be usefully extracted using a well. An aquifer is a formation that contains sufficient saturated permeable material to yield significant quantity of water to wells and springs (Todd, 1980). An aquifer is a naturally occurring formation that contains sufficient amount of water and permeable materials to yield significant amount of water to wells and springs. Geo materials that serve as aquifers are gravels, sand, fractured crystalline and other fractured rocks. Aquifers can also be grouped into confined-, unconfined-, perched- and leaky aquifers (Sen, 1995).

An aquifer is a layer of porous substrate that contains and transmits groundwater. When water can flow directly between the surface and the saturated zone of an aquifer, the aquifer is unconfined. The deeper parts of unconfined aquifers are usually more saturated since gravity causes water to flow downward. The upper level of this saturated layer of an unconfined aquifer is called the *water table* or *phreatic surface*. Below the water table, where generally all pore spaces are saturated with water is the zone. Substrate with low porosity that permits limited transmission of groundwater is known as an aquitard. An aquiclude is a substrate with porosity that is so low it is virtually impermeable to groundwater.

Aquiclude have capable of absorbing water slowly, but not capable of transmitting it fast enough to yield reasonable quantity of water to a well. These are confining formations like crystalline rocks, clays and shales (Sen, 1995). Aquitards has insufficient permeability to act as an aquifer, but can still serve as source or interchange medium between neighbouring aquifers. These contain usually silt or shale (Singhal and Gupta, 1999).

The characteristics of aquifers vary with the geology and structure of the substrate and topography in which they occur. Generally, the more productive aquifers occur in sedimentary geologic formations. By comparison, weathered and fractured crystalline rocks yield smaller quantities of groundwater in many environments. Unconsolidated to poorly cemented alluvial materials that have accumulated as valley-filling sediments in major river valleys and geologically subsiding structural basins are included among the most productive sources of groundwater. Aquifers are generally aerially extensive and may be overlain or underlain by a confining bed which is relatively impermeable. Many aquifers are large in areal extent and they can act as underground reservoirs. The detailed study of subsurface lithology of selected open wells from Tittur Basin (GSI, 1976) indicates the presence of two different aquifers. These are:

1. Alluvial Aquifers

2. Weathered Basaltic Aquifers

3. Fracture Zone Aquifers

Alluvial Aquifers

Alluvial aquifers are composed of alluvial deposits like gravel, sand, silt or clay in alluvial formations of river basin or the watersheds in the form of channels fill and floodplains. They occur mostly in lower reach and in isolated pockets in middle reach of the Tittur basin. The alluvial aquifers are the prime source water for irrigation, drinking and domestic uses. About 15 percent bore well out of total bores and dug wells in Tittur basin found in alluvial aquifers. They account for 25 percent of Tittur basin groundwater extraction. Alluvial aquifers are generally shallower than Weathered Basaltic Aquifers and water levels often fluctuate due to varying recharge and pumping rates. Due to their shallow and unconfined nature, alluvial aquifers are susceptible to contamination and pollution. The alluvial aquifer of Tittur basin composed of fluvial sediments in the range from clay to coarse gravel. The disposition of aquifer sediments forms a grade. The finer members lie on the top and coarser at bottom. The alluvium in the area is composed of coarse-grained silt and gravelly sand of alluvial and colluvial origin found along the river bank and Ajanta Satmala foot hills respectively. It is normally located in the valley floor and valley plain in the downstream part of Tittur River along the villages Chitegaon, Waghali, Kajgaon, Neri, Nagardeola, and Lohatar. The thickness of alluvial aquifer as evident from open well data varies from place to place and from South to North. From open well lithological data, it is evident that the thickness of alluvial aquifer ranges from 1 meter to 3 meters at places where it is overlain with very recent alluvium. This coarse grained material is highly transmissive and most productive aquifer in the area. Yields of the wells from this aquifer vary from 25 to 50 cubic meters per day depending upon the recharge from the surrounding and adjacent rock porosity as

well as permeability. The open wells are normally fitted with 3 to 5 H.P. pumps which discharges 15m^3 to 35m^3 of water per hour depending upon the capacity of well and drawdown of 1 to 2 m. Wells that are located close to or within the stream channel usually support high discharge. These wells are pumped for 5 to 7 hours a day. The groundwater from this aquifer is being extensively exploited and utilized for irrigation and some quantity for domestic purpose.

Weathered Basaltic Aquifers

Geologically the study area is underlain by hard rock basalt with 'Aa' flows with rare Pahoehoe' flows (G.S.I., 1976). The whole terrain is marked by Aa flows with dense and open vertical jointing pattern which is observed along the well sections and at places where quarrying, mining is carried out. These joints are forming good aquifers in the study area. Weathering of basalt has helped in the development of weathered basaltic aquifers. Red bole, a feature with reddish brown angular fragments of basalt is also observed in between two flows at some of the wells and along the steep vertical slopes that are studied for basaltic aquifers. In basaltic aquifers, red bole occurs at shallow depth and acts as aquitard. It is noteworthy that from Antur, Saigavhan villages located in the Southern part of the basin, SE- NW oriented dyke running across the River Tittur is forming a good aquifer in the upstream part of the river. The porosity of Weathered Basaltic Aquifers is 10 to 34 % and transmissivity is 10 to $140\text{ m}^2/\text{day}$ (Rao, 1975). The wells located in around these villages are having good enough water in the basaltic aquifers. Yield, drawdown and recuperation of wells in basaltic aquifer show wide range of variation on account of variations in fracture, porosity which is solely responsible for the movement and storage of

groundwater. Pumping test performed in some of the selected wells show an average yield of 10 to 20 cubic meters per day. Yield values were found to be higher along the main stream course of the basin with gradual reduction towards the basin boundary.

Fracture Zone Aquifers

Faults and fractures develop at various scales from faults that cross continents to fractures that are only visible microscopically. These discontinuities in the rock fabric are located and oriented according to the internal properties of the rock and the external stresses imposed on it (Morency, 1994). Fractures at various scales represent zones of increased porosity and permeability. They may form networks and, therefore, are able to store and carry vast amounts of water.

The concept of fracture zone aquifers explains (Bisson and El-Baz, 1990) the behavior of groundwater in large fault-controlled watersheds. Fault zones in this case serve as collectors and transmitters of water from one or more recharge zones with surface and sub-surface flow strongly controlled by regional tectonism.

Both the yield and quality of water in these zones are usually higher than average wells in any type of rock. High-grade water for such a region would be 250 gallons per minute or greater (Larsson, 1984). In addition, the total dissolved solids measured in the water from such high-yielding wells will be lower than the average for the region.

The fracture zone aquifer concept looks at the variations in groundwater flow as influenced by secondary porosity over an entire watershed. It attempts to integrate data on a basin in an effort to describe

the unique effects of secondary porosity on the processes of groundwater flow, infiltration, transmissivity, and storage (Bisson and El-Baz, 1990).

The concept includes variations in precipitation over the catchment area. One example is orographic effects wherein the mountainous terrain precipitation is substantially greater than at lower elevations. The rainfall is collected over a large catchment area, which contains zones with high permeability because of intense bedrock fracturing associated with major fault zones. The multitude of fractures within these highly permeable zones “funnel” the water into other fracture zones down gradient. These funnels may be in a network hundreds of square kilometers in area (Bisson and El-Baz, 1990).

The fault and fracture zones serve as conduits for ground-water and often act as channel ways for surface flow. Intersections form rectilinear drainage patterns that are sometimes exposed on the surface but are also represented below the surface and converge down gradient. In some regions, these rectilinear patterns are not always visible on the surface due to vegetation and sediment cover. The convergence of these groundwater conduits increases the amount of water available as recharge. The increased permeability, water volume, and ratio of water to minerals within these fault/fracture zones help to maintain the quality of water supply. These channels occur in fractured, nonporous media (crystalline rocks) as well as in fractured, porous media (sandstone).

At some point in the groundwater course, after convergence, the gradient decreases. The sediment cover over the major fracture zone becomes thicker and acts as a water storage unit with primary porosity. The major fracture zone acts as both a transmitter of water along conduits and a water storage basin along connected zones with secondary (and/or

primary) porosity. Groundwater within this layer or lens often flows at accelerated rates. The result can be a pressurization of groundwater both in the fracture zone and in the surrounding material. Rapid flow in the conduit may be replenished almost instantaneously from precipitation. The surrounding materials are replenished more slowly but also release the water more slowly and serve as a storage unit to replenish the conduit between precipitation events.

The concept of fracture zone aquifers is particularly applicable to areas underlain by crystalline rocks and where these rocks have undergone a multiple deformational history that includes extensional tectonics. It is especially applicable in areas where recharge is possible from seasonal and/or sporadic rainfall on mountainous regions.

Fracture zone aquifers are distinguished from horizontal aquifers in that: (a) they drain numerous streams in extensive areas and many extend for tens of kilometers in length; (b) they constitute conduits to mountainous regions where the recharge potential from rainfall is high; (c) some may connect several horizontal aquifers and thereby increase the volume of accumulated water.

The characteristics of fracture zone aquifers make them an excellent source of groundwater in arid and semiarid environments. Fracture zone aquifers are located by seeking major faults. The evaluation of the groundwater potential of Tittur basin is to study the structures displayed in satellite images to map the faults, fractures, and lineaments.

Tittur basin located near foot hill zone of Ajanta Satmala Ranges, which is formed because of a major Fault activity within in Tapi basin. Several Fracture and lineament situated in the southern side of the Tittur basin.

Fig. 4.17 Water passage from the surface to Fracture zone aquifer and ultimately to springs 230

Fig. 4.18 3D Diagram of Spring Location

4.18 Lithology of Well Sections

The details of the lithological units of four location according to Physiographic unite in the study area were accurately observed viz. Hilly area, Alluvial plain, plain of the basin and near Ajanta Satmala foot hill zone. The variation in the thickness of the lithological units with their material composition was also recorded during the well inventory. From this data the detailed well lithologs were prepared. A generalized litholog obtained by inventory of 9 open wells (Patne, Rideshare, Saigvhan, Hirapur, Pimpri, Chalisgaon, Neri, Nagardavela, Lohatar) of Tittur basin show mostly three to four lithological units as soil, weathered basalt, hard and jointed basalt, massive basalt. The thickness of each litholog unit depends upon the physiographic location. Chalisgaon well located along the right bank of the Tittur river shows four lithological units as alluvium, weathered and fractured basalt, hard and massive but partly weathered basalt, whereas Saigvhan well has four distinct lithologs from the colluvium, Clayey and gravelly sand, weathered and jointed basalt and hard massive basalt, this well located near foot hill of Ajanta Satmala Range.

Wells situated in the hilly area were inventoried to obtain litholog information. Wells from this area show four lithological units upper thin forest soil, weathered basalt, jointed and partly weathered basalt and hard massive basalt.

Near foot hill zone 3 open wells were inventoried (Patne, Rajdehare, Saigvhan) to obtain litholog information. Wells from this area show four lithological units depends the well location. Wells situated along and near the river channel, foothill zone shows colluvium (comprising mostly clay, silt, sand), clayey and gravelly sand, weathered

and jointed basalt with massive basalt at the base. The most distinct character of this litholog unit is the presence of thick colluvial deposits (2 to 4m) along the wells that are located at the foothills.

Wells situated on the plain area of the basin were inventoried (Hirapur, Pimpri, Neri) to obtain litholog information. Wells from this area show four lithological units upper soil, weathered basalt, Hard & Jointed Basalt and hard massive basalt.

Well inventory of Alluvial plain area (Lohatar, Chalisgaon) also reveals three distinct lithologs which are more or less similar but distinct from other location in the case of their thickness. These are alluvium, Weathered and fractured basalt, hard and massive but partly weathered basalt at the base. The most distinct character of this litholog unit is the presence of thick Alluvium deposits (2 to 3m) along the wells and presence of thick alluvium at the top unit of the wells that are located within or close to the river channel.

Table 4.18 shows different lithological units of selected open wells of the Tittur Basin. Study of lithologs indicates that different units can independently act as an aquifer for that well. Alluvium is found along major tributary and in the lower part of the Tittur Basin constitutes good water retentive lithological unit.

Table 4.18 Lithological units of Tittur basin

Physiographic Unite	Average Depth (m)	Depth from the Ground surface (m)	Lithological unit
Hilly Area	6 to 9	0 to 2	Soil
		2 to 5	Weathered Basalt
		5 to 8	Hard & Jointed Basalt
		> 8	Massive Basalt
foot hill zone	6 to 11	0 to 4	Colluviums
		4 to 6	Clayey and gravelly sand
		6 to 8	Weathered and jointed basalt
		> 8	Hard massive basalt
Plain area	8 to 11	0 to 2	Soil (Clayey)
		2 to 6	Weathered Basalt
		6 to 8	Hard & Jointed Basalt
		> 8	Massive Basalt
Alluvial plain	11	0 to 3	Alluvium
		3 to 7	weathered and fractured basalt
		> 7	hard and massive but partly weathered basalt

(Data Source: Based on field Work Data and CGWB, Nagpur)

Fig. 4.19 Litholog of Hilly Area

Fig. 4.20 Litholog of Foot Hill Zone area

Fig. 4.21 Litholog of Plain Area

Fig. 4.22 Litholog of Alluvial Plain

4.19 Well Inventory

In order to understand the groundwater regime of the area under investigation, well inventory of open wells was prepared. Well inventory data helps to understand the relationship between the topography and the movement of groundwater. The data also provides useful information about the depth, volume of water in different seasons. A total of 18 wells were inventoried in the study area. Out of these, 3 wells are located in Pimpri sub basin, 2 wells are located in Dungri sub basin, 3 wells are located in Valjhari sub basin and 7 wells are located in Gadad sub basin. Pre-monsoon and post-monsoon water levels from these wells were measured continuously from pre-monsoon season of the year 2009 i.e. from May 2009 to November 2010. Central Ground Water Board periodically monitors the National Hydrograph Network Stations (NHNS) stations in the Tittur basin, Two times a year i.e. in May (Pre monsoon) and November (Post monsoon).Some well's water level data collect within field survey.

Fig. 4.23 Observation Well Location Map of the Tittur Basin

Depth of Water Level – Pre monsoon (May-2009)

The depth to water levels in the Tittur basin during May 2009 ranges between 2.62 (Rajdehare) and 9.25 (Neri) m bgl. Depth to water levels during pre monsoon (May 2009) has been depicted in Figure Shallow water levels, within 3.43 to 5.11 m bgl are seen in the southern parts of the basin. Deeper water levels of more than 7.94 to 9.63 m bgl are observed in northern side but very few part cover deeper water levels. The central part of the basin shows water level between 5.11 and 7.94 m bgl.

Depth of Water Level – Postmonsoon (Nov-2009)

The depth to water levels during post monsoon (Nov 2009) ranges between 0.40 (Rajdehare) and 4.9 (Patna). Spatial variation in post monsoon depth to water levels is shown in Figure. Shallow water levels within 1.10 to 1.92 m bgl are observed in southeastern and western part of the basin. Water levels are between 1.92 and 2.47 m bgl in central parts. North western, central and eastern parts of the basin have water levels between 2.47 to 2.90 m bgl and 2.90 to 3.36 m bgl. Deeper water levels of 3.36 to 4.05 m bgl are observed as isolated patches near outlet of the basin.

Fig 4.23 shows the location of open wells in the Tittur Basin. Table 4.19 shows pre-monsoon and post-monsoon water level, fluctuation of these wells. The groundwater levels measured for each well was then plotted with respective depth to observe seasonal changes in water level.

Table 4.19 Seasonal Water Levels and Fluctuation of Open Wells in the Tittur Basin

Well Location	Water level below ground level (m) with Fluctuation					
	May 09	Nov 09	Fluctuation	May 10	Nov 10	Fluctuation
Pimpri Sub basin						
Rajdehare	2.62	0.4	2.22	5.8	4.3	1.50
Shinde	5.05	1.57	3.48	4.1	2.3	1.80
Hirapur	8.85	4.8	4.05	7.27	5.9	1.37
Average	5.50	2.25	3.25	5.72	4.16	1.55
Dungri Sub basin						
Chaliskaon	4.8	0.75	4.05	3.15	1.4	1.75
Patna	7.42	4.9	2.52	3.82	1.85	1.97
Average	6.11	2.825	3.28	3.485	1.625	1.86
Valjhari Sub basin						
Bodhra	7.05	3.69	3.36	5.45	2.7	2.75
Lonja	5.7	3.15	2.55	3.83	1.85	1.98
Vakdi	5.45	1.4	4.05	4.8	2.2	2.60
Average	6.06	2.74	3.32	4.69	2.25	2.44
Gadad Sub basin						
Saigvhan	6.87	2.14	4.73	5.55	1.85	3.70
Nagardavela	5.58	2.73	2.85	6.66	4.5	2.16
Haraswadi	3.4	0.6	2.80	3.7	2.65	1.05
Kinhi	4.37	1.04	3.33	6.75	6.1	0.65
Vadgaon	7.47	2.12	5.35	9.7	3.95	5.75
Neri	9.25	4.5	4.75	9.5	5.6	3.90
Nagad	5.52	1.24	4.28	6.80	2.15	4.65
Average	6.06	2.05	4.01	6.95	3.82	3.12
Other well located in Tittur basin						
Kajgaon	7.65	2	5.65	5.45	2.7	2.75
Galan	7	3.6	3.40	4.6	4.15	0.45
Lohatar	7.3	4.9	2.40	5.73	4.83	0.90
Average	7.31	3.50	3.81	5.26	3.89	1.36
(Data Source: Based on field Work Data and CGWB, Nagpur)						

Fig. 4.24 Depth of Water Level (May 2009)

Fig. 4.25 Depth of Water Level (Nov 2009)

Fig. 4.26 Depth of Water Level (May 2010)

Fig. 4.27 Depth of Water Level (Nov 2010)

Tittur Basin Groundwater Fluctuation of year 2009

Fig. 4.28 Groundwater Fluctuation of year 2009

Fig. 4.29 Groundwater Fluctuation of year 2010

It is observed that majority of the wells are excavated in the tributary channel, at the foothill and along the river bank to get the advantage of stream flow seepage. All the wells inventoried are circular in shape. The wells located in the valley plain are lined depending upon the thickness of the soil cover or alluvium and degree of basalt weathering.

Seasonal Water Level Fluctuation (May-Nov. 2009)

In the Tittur basin rise in water level in the range of 2.22 (Rajdehare) to 6.33 m (Pasardi) is observed. In entire Tittur basin rise in water level has been observed. Rise in water level in the range of 2.44 to 3.21 m is observed in Southern part of the Tittur basin. Rise of 3.21 to 4.24 m is observed in most of the part of the Tittur basin covering. Rise of 4.24 to 4.75 m is observed in the northern part of the basin covering along main channel of Tittur basin. Rise of more than 4.75 m to 5.44 m is observed in isolated in northern side of the basin.

Fig. 4.30 Pimpri Well hydrograph

Fig. 4.31 Dungri Well hydrograph

Fig. 4.32 Valjhari Well Hydrograph

Fig. 4.33 Gadad Well Hydrograph

Sub Basin wise well hydrographs has been also prepared to observe the trend of water level in the selected wells. Figure (4.30 to 4.33) shows Sub basin wise water level of open wells in the Tittur Basin for the period of May 2009 to November 2010. From the figure 4.34 it is evident that Valjhari sub basin has greater groundwater potential because of natural recharge by all means of various natural sources such as precipitation, runoff, base flow etc. The wells from this basin on an average do not show much of water level fluctuation from May 2009 to November 2010. On the contrarily, Dungri basin show greater water level variation as increasing trend, indicating that this basin has very low potential of groundwater recharge by naturally and artificially. All four sub basin wells show increasing trend of groundwater level is evidence from the figure 4.35. Within all sub basins in the upper reaches the water table is situated at greater depth owing to high hydraulic gradient towards adjoining valley plain. On an average 4 to 5 meters of fluctuation is recorded in some wells. On the other hand, the valleys and valley flats has low hydraulic gradient. Therefore, subsurface flow is very slow. As a result, very low fluctuation is noted from these wells Level 2 to 3 meters (Table 4.19).

Fig. 4.34 Sub Basin wise Average Fluctuation of Groundwater Level in Open Well

In order to evaluate the impact of pumping on the groundwater regime, and on aquifer storability, the static water level, total drawdown level for three hours and total recuperation level for three hours was continuously observed and measured from the wells representing each sub basin. Drawdown is the drop in level of water in a well when water is being pumped. Drawdown measurements record the difference (in feet or meters) between the static level and the pumping level. One of the aim of carrying out pumping test on a well is to assess the yield of the well or the capacity of well to supply water through pumping. The static water levels (SWL) for four wells from the Tittur basin were measured after ascertaining that the well has not been pumped on the previous day. Representative time- drawdown-recuperation curve (Fig 4.35) for these wells was prepared to know about their recharge potential. Table 4.20 and Table 4.21 show depth, diameter, static water levels, total drawdown level and recuperation level and the total observation time for four representative wells.

Table 4.20 Drawdown and Recuperation Levels of Four Representative Wells

Well Location	Depth (m)	Diameter (m)	Static water level (m)	Total Drawdown (m)	Total Recuperation (m)	Time Observed (minutes)	
						Drawdown	Recuperation
Bodhra	10.5	4.5	3.28	2.0	1.0	180	180
Neri	15.0	11.5	7.21	1.67	1.25	180	180
Chalishaon	10.0	3.35	2.52	0.98	0.75	180	180
Lohatar	9.8	8.0	5.69	1.2	0.92	180	180

(Data Source: Based on field Work Data)

Table 4.21 Measured Drawdown (m) and Recuperation (m) Rate of Four Representative Wells

Time in Hour	Bodhra	Neri	Chalishaon	Lohatar
0	0	0	0	0
0.5	0.33	0.27	0.16	0.18
1	0.66	0.54	0.32	0.36
1.5	0.99	0.81	0.48	0.54
2	1.32	1.08	0.64	0.72
2.5	1.65	1.35	0.80	0.90
3	2.00	1.67	0.98	1.20
3.5	1.80	1.60	0.93	1.16
4	1.60	1.53	0.89	1.12
4.5	1.40	1.46	0.86	1.08
5	1.20	1.39	0.83	1.04
5.5	1.10	1.32	0.79	0.98
6	1.00	1.25	0.75	0.92

(Data Source: Based on field Work Data)

Rate of drawdown obtained for Chalisgaon and Lohatar wells is 0.98 and 1.2 meter respectively with recuperation rate of 0.30 m per hour. This can be attributed to the location of the wells in alluvial aquifers that hold the water in porous spaces of soil for longer duration. As the hydraulic head of water in the well decreases, water from these spaces is released under the gravity. Bodhra and Neri wells indicates slightly greater recuperation rate as compare to Chalisgaon and Lohatar wells though they are located in upper reaches of the Tittur Basin. This can be attributed to the higher degree weathering and fracturing of basalt rock beneath the surface that is responsible for higher permeability for the higher recharge and recuperation of 0.33 m to 0.41 meter per hour. The average recuperation level of the Tittur Basin comes to 0.32 meter per hour. The wells that are located in alluvial aquifers have greater recuperation compare to the wells in basaltic aquifers. The recuperation rate of Bodhra well more than Neri well. In general, the groundwater fluctuation in the Tittur Basin can be attributed to higher hydraulic gradient resulting low permeability of partially weathered basalt in upper reaches, excess draft of groundwater from open wells which also results the lowering of hydrostatic pressure of adjacent wells, which in turn results in depletion of water in a very short period. The analysis also reveals less variation in post-monsoon water level. This indicates that zone of saturation in hard rock area has a definite and limited storage capacity with dependable saturation and thickness of aquifer available for the extraction of groundwater.

Fig. 4.35 Drawdown (m) and Recuperation (m) Rate of Tittur Basin

4.20 Water Table Contour Map

The upper surface of the zone of saturation in ordinary permeable soil or rock has been termed the ground-water table, or simply the water table. Where the upper surface is intersected by impermeable material, the water table is interrupted, and artesian conditions are said to exist. The water table is not a plane surface but has irregularities comparable with and related to those of the land surface, although the water table is less rugged. The water table does not remain in a stationary position, but fluctuates up and down. The irregularities are caused chiefly by local differences in geology and topography, and the fluctuations are due to gain or loss of water. A map of the water table Contour is a good tool for understanding the patterns of horizontal flow in aquifers. These Contours represent the horizontal distribution of hydraulic head in the aquifer. Since water always flows towards lower hydraulic head, horizontal flow directions can be inferred from these maps. If the aquifer materials have isotropic hydraulic conductivity in the horizontal plane, then flow will be perpendicular to the contours of hydraulic head.

Surface water elevations are another source of useful data for water table maps. If the aquifer and surface water are in direct contact, the water table will intersect the surface water at an elevation close to the elevation of the surface water. Along steep stream banks, there is often seepage because the water table is slightly higher than the stream surface. The elevation of the water table can differ from the elevation of a surface water body if there is a layer of low-conductivity sediment on the bottom of the surface water body. On the other hand, the inferred groundwater flow directions near the larger stream indicate that groundwater is

discharging into it from both sides. This is a gaining stream, one that picks up groundwater discharge.

In order to ascertain the behavior and flow direction of groundwater movement in the Tittur Basin, the systematic water level measurements of the inventoried wells given in table 4.19 well inventoried data were used for the preparation of groundwater table contour map.

The spacing of groundwater contours gives a good indication of variation in aquifer permeability values. Closely spaced contours imparts higher runoff and low permeability because of steep hydraulic gradient through the aquifer, whereas widely spaced groundwater contours indicate moderate to good permeability, higher infiltration in the soils (Brassington, 1999). Contour map of groundwater level, together with flow line, is useful data for locating new wells. Convex contours indicate regions of groundwater recharge, while concave contours are associated with groundwater discharge (Todd and Mays, 2005).

The trend of groundwater contour is across the basin; however depth decreases towards the downstream direction of the river. The groundwater contours becomes more and more concentric around the mouth of the river.

The Static groundwater levels were converted to reduced groundwater levels with reference to actual topographic elevation of the wells for plotting the groundwater contours (Table 4.22). GPS have been used to record the altitude of each well. These values of the reduced groundwater levels have been used for the preparation of water table contour map at an interval of 5 m, (Fig. 4.36) In order to ascertain the groundwater movement, a few representative flow lines were drawn at

right angles to the water table contours and prepare groundwater flow direction map.

From the fig 4.36 it is revealed that the water table contours closely spaced on the western and Southern part of the Tittur Basin. Due to rugged topography and steep hydraulic gradient, this part of the basin having very poor ground water potentiality.

On the other hand, widely spaced contours are coinciding with the valley flats and valley plain in the central belt. This belt runs parallel to the main tributary channels, indicating low hydraulic gradient and higher permeability of the underlying geological formations. In the central and northern part of the basin widely spaced water table contours indicating gentle hydraulic gradient supporting higher permeability of subsurface strata.

Spacing of water table contours in the lower part of the basin becomes compact whereas sparse in the south west part of the basin. This unusual phenomenon of closely spaced contours is the indication of increase in hydraulic gradient. As a result, the subsurface flow of groundwater has greater speed as compare to the middle reaches of the basin which ultimately reduces groundwater recharge. During the field investigation, the presence of fractured, jointed as well as hard massive basalt rock close to the surface. These fractures and joints are more prone to sub surface flow of Water rather than holding it into their void spaces. It results in lowering of groundwater, increase in base flow contribution to main stream channel.

Fig. 4.36 Water Table Contour Map of the Tittur Basin

Fig- 4.37 Water Table Contour Map of the Tittur Basin

4.21 Groundwater Flow in Relation to Water Table Contour

Groundwater flow is defined as the "...part of stream flow that has infiltrated the ground, has entered the phreatic zone, and has been discharged into a stream channel, via springs or seepage water" (Chorley, 1978). Like surface water, groundwater also moves towards the decreasing head, but the rate of movement of groundwater is very slow as compared to the surface water movement and its path is more complex (Raghunath, 1996).

Because no flows cross an impermeable boundary, flow line must parallel it. Similarly if no flows cross the water table of an unconfined aquifer, it becomes a bounding flow surface. The energy head (h_E) or fluid potential at any point on the water table can be approximated by,

$$h_E = \frac{P}{\gamma} + z$$

Where p = Pressure,

γ = Specific weight of water,

z = elevation

So that by letting the atmospheric pressure referred by Zero, $p = 0$ and $h_E = z$, Therefore under steady state condition, the elevation at any point on the water table equal the energy head and as consequence, flow lines lie perpendicular to water table contours (Todd and Mays, 1980). As long as no flow crosses a water table, it served as a groundwater boundary; however if flow, such as percolating water, reaches the water

table, flow line no longer parallel the surface as an impermeable boundary (Hubbert, 1956).

Spacing of contours also indicates groundwater flow direction. In upper reaches of the Tittur Basin, groundwater follows topographic gradient. From south west and from central part of the basin, it flows towards north east. In the central zone direction of groundwater flow is slightly different. From the eastern part, groundwater flows towards south direction, and from western divide groundwater flow towards north east approaching main channel due to steeper topographic as well as hydraulic gradient. These two flows converge in the central belt of main stream, result the increase in groundwater level. In the lower reaches of the basin, overall direction of groundwater flow is from south to north and south west to north east which coincides with the surface water flow direction. In the figure 4.36, groundwater flow direction is depicted by arrows perpendicular to groundwater table contours. In the central south part near foot hill zone a groundwater basin occur that's why in this zone grounder water flow toward depression from all direction. Fig 4.38 shows groundwater flow direction in eight directions.

Table 4.22 Reduced Groundwater level of Open well in Tittur basin

Well Location	Elevation of Well ASL (m)	Static Water level (m)	Reduced Level (m)
Chalisingaon	344.65	2.52	342.13
Bodhra	381.58	4.72	376.86
Hirapur	376.87	6.70	370.17
Vakdi	330.43	3.46	326.97
Pasardi	283.14	6.24	276.9
Lohatar	256.89	5.69	251.2
Nagardavela	291.31	4.86	286.45
Saigvhan	385.35	4.10	281.25
Kajgaon	294.39	4.45	289.94
Neri	306.44	7.21	299.23
Nagad	330.24	3.92	326.32
Shinde	401.17	3.25	397.92
Rajdehare	462.69	3.28	459.41
Galan	281.76	4.83	276.93
Patna	405.96	4.49	401.47
Vadgaon	317.75	5.81	311.94
Kinhi	338.84	4.56	334.28
Haraswadi	358.52	2.58	355.94
Lonja	366.72	3.63	363.09

(Data Source: Based on field Work Data and CGWB, Nagpur)

Fig. 4.38 Groundwater Flow direction of the Tittur Basin

4.22 Groundwater Quality of Tittur Basin

Water obtained from different sources is associated with a large number of impurities and gets contaminated with sewage and industrial waste or effluents when they are allowed to flow into running water or through percolation (Sarbhukan, 2001). In recent years, an increasing threat to ground water quality due to human activities has become of great importance. The adverse effects on ground water quality are the results of man's activity at ground surface, unintentionally by agriculture, domestic and industrial effluents, unexpectedly by sub-surface or surface disposal of sewage and industrial wastes. The quality of ground water is of great importance in determining the suitability of particular ground water for a certain use (public water supply, irrigation, industrial applications, etc.). The quality of ground water is the resultant of all the processes and reactions that have acted on the water from the moment it condensed in the atmosphere to the time it is discharged by a well. Therefore, the quality of ground water varies from place to place, with the depth of water table, and from season to season and is primarily governed by the extent and composition of dissolved solids present in it.

A vast majority of ground water quality problems are caused by contamination, over-exploitation, or combination of the two. Most ground water quality problems are difficult to detect and hard to resolve. The solutions are usually very expensive, time consuming and not always effective. Ground water quality is slowly but surely declining everywhere. Ground water pollution is intrinsically difficult to detect, since problem may well be concealed below the surface and monitoring is costly, time consuming and somewhat hit-or-miss by nature.

The intensive use of natural resources and the large production of wastes in modern society often pose a threat to ground water quality and have already resulted in many incidents of ground water contamination. Pollutants are being added to the ground water system through human activities and natural processes. Solid waste from industrial units is being dumped near the factories, which is subjected to reaction with percolating rain water and reaches the ground water level. The percolating water picks up a large amount of dissolved constituents and reaches the aquifer system and contaminates the ground water. The problem of ground water pollution in several parts of the country has become so acute that unless urgent steps for detailed identification and abatement are taken, extensive ground water resources may be damaged.

The quality of ground water depends on a large number of individual hydrological, physical, chemical and biological factors. Generally higher proportions of dissolved constituents are found in ground water than in surface water because of greater interaction of ground water with various materials in geologic strata. The water used for drinking purpose should be free from any toxic elements, living and nonliving organism and excessive amount of minerals that may be hazardous to health. Some of the heavy metals are extremely essential to humans, for example, cobalt; copper, etc., but large quantities of them may cause physiological disorders.

The quality of water could be in terms of physical, chemical and biological qualities. All these parameters can be measured by using different equipments at levels of the water quality ascertained. The groundwater of the Tittur Basin has been analyzed in order to know its quality for different uses. Results obtained from the analysis of 06 water samples collated from the study area, have been discussed. For the

present study only nine important chemical parameters were selected by having discussion with the expert in this field and availability of data. These are pH, Electric Conductivity (EC), Alkalinity, Hardness, Chloride, SO₄, Fluoride, NO₃ and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS). Table 4.25 gives the standard specifications of the groundwater water quality parameters considered for the analysis.

Table 4.23 W.H.O. and B.I.S. Specifications for Drinking Water

Sr. No	Parameters (Except otherwise indicated all in mg/L or ppm)	Permissible Limits			
		W.H.O.		B.I.S.	
		Highest Desirable	Maximum Permissible	Highest Desirable	Maximum Permissible
1	pH	7.0 - 8.5	6.5 - 9.2	7.0 - 8.5	6.5 - 9.2
2	Electric Conductivity (EC)	---	---	---	---
3	Alkalinity	< 100 mg/L for domestic purpose			
4	Hardness	100	500	300	600
5	Chloride (Cl)	200	600	200	1000
6	Sulphate (SO ₄)	200	400	150	400
7	Fluoride	0.6 - 0.9	0.8 - 1.78	0.6 - 1.2	1.5
8	Nitrate(NO ₃)	---	45	45	No Relaxation
9	Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	500	1500	500	1500

(Source: WHO, 1992 and Tomar, 1999)

The study is entirely based on the water samples from open wells that are used for drinking, domestic and agricultural purpose. The water samples collected to gauge their quality and the same have been analyzed in laboratory using standard analytical procedures.

In Tittur basin seven water samples were collected from Rajdehare, Patna, Bodhra , Saigvhan, Neri , Chalisgaon ,and Lohatar open wells. The results obtained from the analysis are presented in Table 4.26

Table 4.24 Water Quality at Different Locations

Well Location	pH	Electric Conductivity (EC)	Alkalinity	Hardness	Chloride	SO ₄	Fluoride	NO ₃	Dissolved Solids (TDS)
Rajdehare	7.29	238	92	90	18.8	15.3	0.11	1.58	96
Patna	7.49	136	97	126	13.0	12.5	0.12	2.02	161
Bodhra	7.29	122	83	45	18.90	10.6	0.24	2.05	72
Saigvhan	7.33	149	97	70	13.50	12.4	0.21	2.02	90
Neri	7.22	236	88	60	15.33	15.3	0.32	1.85	173
Chalisgaon	7.81	270	70	65	14.05	12.1	0.18	1.85	141
Lohatar	7.62	193	76	64	13.50	11.6	0.27	1.59	126

(Data Source: Based on Labrotory Analysis)

The analysis of water samples collected from open wells reveals, pH is a measure of the concentration of hydrogen ions (H⁺) and indicates the degree of acidity or alkalinity of the water. $pH = \log_{10} 1/(H^+)$ and on the scale from 0 to 14 a pH of 7 is indicative of a neutral solution. If the pH is less than 7 then the water is acidic, and if the pH is greater than 7,

the water is alkaline. pH value ranging from 7.22 to 7.81 that is within the range of permissible limit.

Electrical conductivity (EC) is a physical property of water that is dependent on the dissolved salts. Thus its measurement in micro-Siemens per centimeter ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) gives a good estimate of the dissolved solids content of a river. The electric conductivity (EC) denotes the characteristics feature of water as a medium of the passage of electricity. The EC measured for all the samples at ambient temperature, ranges from 122 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ to 238 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ indicating that the water can be used for drinking purpose in the Tittur Basin.

In case of Alkalinity, the value ranges from 70 to 97 mg/L. It indicates that salts like carbonates, bicarbonates, phosphates along with hydroxyl ion are in a free state which is not so hazardous to drinking purpose.

As regards the hardness of the water, the value doesn't exceed desirable and maximum permissible limit of 500 mg/L. All the values range from 45 to 126, indicating that the water possesses temporary hardness and are suitable for drinking purpose. Chlorides, most often occurring in the NaCl common salt form, are found in brackish water bodies contaminated in groundwater aquifers with high salt content. The presence of chlorides ($\text{mg l}^{-1} \text{Cl}$) in a river is also indicative of sewage pollution from other chloride compounds. Chloride, Sulphate, and Nitrate content in all samples is also within the range of permissible limits. Quantity of total dissolved solids in all samples is below highest desirable limit of BIS.

Majority of the samples analyzed fall in the permissible range with the exception of doubtful to unsuitable groundwater occurring in the alluvial tracts of lower reaches of the Tittur Basin. The analyzed data also reveals that the upper reaches of Tittur basins can be categorized in moderate to good quality of water. The low lying valley plains, lower reaches of the rivers and the wells located near to alluvium may be getting polluted from the pesticides and fertilizers used by farmers.

Chapter V

LANDFORM ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

5.2 Significance of Landform in Hydrogeomorphic Study

5.3 Classification of Landforms in the Tittur Basin

5.4 Structural Landform

5.4.1 Structural Hill

5.4.2 Lineaments

5.4.3 Escarpment

5.4.4 Dyke

5.5 Denudational Landforms

5.5.1 Pediment

5.5.2 Pedepain

5.5.3 Denudational Hill

5.5.4 Dissected plateau

5.5.5 Monadnock or Residual Hills

5.5.6 Ridge

5.5.7 Gully and Rill

5.5.8 Tor

5.6 Fluvial Landform

5.6.1 Alluvial Plain

5.6.2 Valley Fills

5.6.3 Floodplain

5.6.4 Fluvial Terraces

5.6.5 Palaeochannel

5.6.6 Plunge pool

5.6.7 Stream pool

5.7 Landforms associated with Hill Slope

5.7.1 Talus

5.8 Lineament Analysis

5.8.1 Methodology and Data base for Lineament Analysis

5.8.2 Lineament Mapping

5.8.3 Result

5.8.3.1 Lineament Density

5.8.3.2 Lineament Intersection

5.8.3.3 Orientation Analysis

***5.9 Identification of Groundwater Potential Zone using
Geoinformatics***

***5.9.1 Material and Methods for Identification of Groundwater
Potential Zone using***

***5.9.2 Integration of remote sensing and GIS modeling for
groundwater potential zone mapping***

5.9.3 Groundwater Potential Zones

5.9.3 Conclusion

Chapter V

LANDFORM ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

Landforms are the configurations of the land surface taking distinctive forms and produced by natural processes of erosion, denudation and deposition (Strahler and Strahler, 1996). Landforms are the result of geologic and geomorphologic processes that occur on the earth's surface. The term 'landform' as used by geoscientific modelers denotes a portion of the earth that unites the qualities of homogeneous and continuous relief due to the action of common geological and geomorphological processes (Crevenna et al, 2004). The study of landforms, in a drainage basin with reference to hydrology and geomorphology context has become increasingly important for understanding the surface and subsurface water conditions. In fact geomorphology is found to have very close links with both surface and subsurface water conditions (Verstappen, 1983). Geomorphological features of a terrain, generally controls the distribution of precipitation and amount of precipitation that is contributed as runoff as well as for groundwater recharge. A specific asset of geomorphology is that it aids to describe and evaluate the environment in which water circulates, thus providing the hydrologists working in areas where essential data are lacking (Zaporozec, 1979; Verstappen, 1983). According to Lohmann and Robinove (1964), evaluation of landforms is of lithology is an important clue to the prevailing water searing property of any particular landform. Schumm (1964) emphasized this role of

landforms for hydrogeomorphological analyses by evaluating various landform units of fluvial, structural, denudational and depositional origin.

Groundwater generally escapes direct observation where it emerges in springs or is tapped by wells. In geomorphology context, a landform may give a clue to subsurface water conditions. Therefore, a complete terrain classification is often required to evaluate the groundwater conditions, its availability and for this, geomorphological surveying of landforms becomes essential. Integration of hydrological, geomorphological, geological data minimizes the area for the detailed survey by sophisticated method. For example Geographical Information System (GIS) in finding out the groundwater potential zones. Among all available techniques, GIS, a computer based information system provides accurate information for analyzing drainage basin hydrogeomorphology. GIS also makes it possible to identify and outline various landforms and geomorphic units and their characters that may serve as direct or indirect indicators of the presence of groundwater (Todd, 1985).

5.2 Significance of Landform in Hydrogeomorphic Study

It is a well established fact that geological and geomorphological factors have direct influence on the occurrence and movement of groundwater in any terrain. Hydrogeomorphic classification of landform in a drainage basin provides information on the hydrologic characteristics of the morphological units developed in an area in relation to the geology of the terrain (Bajpai and Mahanta, 2003). A detailed study of lithology and geologic structure of different morphological units would enable one to understand the distribution of surface and subsurface water situation and hence the overall location of surface water and groundwater reservoirs.

Therefore, for assessing groundwater potential it is necessary to understand different types of landforms and their characteristics, rock types, geological structures and how they have been evolved with respect to each other as these landforms have definite control over the movement and localization of groundwater.

Considering the fact that hydrology is actually the combined effect of climate, landforms, geology, soils and vegetation on the natural regime of water and the effect of man on the water balance, it is evident that hydrogeomorphological studies should not only stress the structure of landforms, but also the spatio-temporal environment in which the surface and subsurface water is stored and retained by that landform.

With this approach, in the present chapter, an attempt has been made to delineate the study area into different landforms and hydrogeomorphic units. Based on the nature of origin, these units can be grouped into structural landforms, denudational landforms and depositional landforms.

5.3 Classification of Landforms in the Tittur Basin

The delineation of hydrogeomorphic units in the Tittur Basin has been made after a detailed consideration of spatial-distribution of aforesaid mode of origin of different landforms. The landforms identified for the present study, have been named after a thorough literature survey, i.e. abbreviations used by different scholars for different units on the basis of their topographic character, process of formation in particular area. Some modifications and changes with these abbreviations have been made accordingly so as to facilitate the author to show them at their respective

locations in hydrogeomorphic map of the Tittur Basin, as well as and wherever they are required to write in the text while describing them.

Field investigations, on site observation of various landforms in the study area has been carried out to classify these landforms for better understanding of groundwater situation. Some of the features like dyke (positive and negative dykes) and lineaments are not visible over the surface due to their subsurface occurrence. But the resultant topography of these geologic units can be easily trace with in ASTER Satellite Images and the field in the form of more or less straight channel for lineaments and linear grass vegetation or tree line over the barren surface or on the slope which is an indication of presence of positive or negative influence of dyke.

In order to delineate hydrogeomorphological and lineament maps, the geo-coded Landsat ETM (Enhanced Thematic Mapper 30 m Resolution), Geo Eye (0.5 m Resolution) and ASTER (15 m Resolution) satellite imagery have been used. Basic image characteristics like tone, texture, shape, color, associations, etc were used, along with field parameters such as topography, relief, slope factor, surface cover, soil and vegetation cover were considered while delineating hydrogeomorphic and lineament maps. Different thematic layers such as drainage, geology, geomorphology, Lineament and slope have been generated by using above Satellite Images and SOI toposheets on 1:50000 scale. Arc GIS 9.3.1, ERDAS 2011 and Global Mapper 13 has been used for the generation of individual layers and for overlay analysis. The database used for identifying various hydrogeomorphic units includes,

1. Drainage data from SOI topographical map number 46 L/15, 46 P/2, 46 P/3, 46 P/6 and 46 P/7 (1:50000 scale).

2. Digital Elevation Models (DEM) data generate from ASTER Satellite Images using DEM Extraction method.
3. Field investigation includes Well Inventory (Pre-monsoon) & Post-monsoon groundwater levels).
4. Geological Map of Tittur watershed from GSI, Calcutta.
5. Landsat ETM + (Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus, 30 m Resolution), Geo Eye (0.5 m Resolution) and ASTER (15 m Resolution) satellite imagery.

Ground truth verification was carried out in the field and necessary modifications were made in the thematic maps. The methodology adopted to generate hydrogeomorphic unit wise groundwater potential zone map involves generation of thematic layers and overlay analysis Fig. 5.22 shows the methodology adopted for generating groundwater potential zone map. All these landform units are not have exact boundaries as well as exact length (except lineaments and dykes), width, depth, height because as they coalesces with next or neighboring unit with a very gradual or imperceptible change. Table 5.1 illustrates their material composition and fig. 5.2 to Fig. 5.17 shows a schematic diagram of various landforms identified in the Tittur Basin. The diagram presents a much generalized picture of these landform units, 3D Diagram and during the field investigation.

The specific characteristic of each of the landforms varies greatly in terms of shape, size, dimension, thickness as well as permeability and porosity of the overburden material, underlying, structural control and vegetative cover.

Table 5.1 Types of Landform and there Hydgeomorphic units

Landforms	Hydrogeomorphic Unit	Area km²	Area %	Surface Material, Lithology
Structural Landforms	Structural Hills	126.93	13.08	Thin soil, bare rock surface, sparse grass cover
	Escarpment	20.59		Bare rock surface
	Lineament	463.87 km		Expressed in terms of topography
	Dykes	12.05 km		Expressed in terms of topography
Denudational Landforms	Pediment	197.35	20.34	Medium soil thickness, Veneer of detritus, sparse shrubs & Grass cover
	Pedeplain	360.15	37.12	Thick soil, fractured and weathered basalt, thick vegetation
	Monadnock	0.55	0.05	Bare rock surface
	Dissected plateau	26.60	2.74	Thin soil, sparse grass cover, Agriculture
	Tor			Rocky Outcrop, Basalt
	Ridge	47.54	4.90	Thin soil, bare rock surface
	Gully and Rill			Soil, Alluvium, Colluviums
	Denudational Hill	21.90	2.25	Medium soil thickness, sparse shrubs & Grass cover
Fluvial Landforms	Braided river	0.92		Sand, Silt, Gravel
	Floodplain	15.27	1.57	Alluvium, Colluviums
	Fluvial terraces	0.65	0.06	Alluvium, Colluviums
	Valley fills	26.90	2.77	Alluvial & colluvial deposits, Crop plantation
	Paleo-channel	0.20	0.02	Alluvium, Sand, Silt, Clay
	Plunge pool	0.10		Boulder, Cobble, Pebble
	Stream pool	0.25		Sand, Silt
	Alluvial Plain	100.99	10.41	Alluvial soil, Agriculture Crops
Landforms associated with Hill Slope	Talus	43.80	4.51	Boulder, Clay, Silt, Broken rock fragments, thick vegetation

Tittur Basin Geomorphology Map

Legend

- Braided River
- Fluvial Terraces
- Paleo-channel
- Denudational Hill
- Dissected plateau
- Monadnock
- Plunge pool
- Stream pool
- Tor
- Dyke
- Pedeplain
- Pediment
- Ridge
- Talus
- Escarpment
- Alluvial Plain
- Valley fills
- Floodplain
- Waterfall

Fig. 5.1 Geomorphology Map of the Tittur Basin

5.4 Structural Landform

Application of the principal of geomorphology provides information, which will be of value in predicating the geometry of aquifers. On weathering and erosion, many geological formations develop landforms that are distinctive in respect of slope continuity of outcrops and symmetry of valley flanks. The surface topographic features of bedrocks can sometimes be extrapolated to reasonable depths to predict the thickness of alluvium or aeolian sands occurring as valley fill deposits, by treating slope profile as mathematical curves for which equations similar to regression equations can be found (Doornkamp and King, 1971).

The influence of tectonic movements and resultant structural features on landform is of paramount importance for hydrogeomorphologists. The control of structure on landforms and hydrogeological processes are being discussed here. The structural geology concerns with the features such as folds, faults and joints. Of these the structural features like faults, fractures; joints etc appear as linear feature.

Many features are formed due to the tectonic readjustments that take place within the crust of the earth (Nath et al, 2000). This tectonic readjustment plays an important role in the formation and evolution of landscape and landforms. The most important features of this category found in the study area are structural hills and lineaments.

5.4.1 Structural Hill

Structural Hill are massive linear or accurate hills exhibiting definite trend lines dominated by hard unweathered basalt rock (Vittala, et al., 2005). These hills are structurally controlled with complex folding faulting criss-crossed by number of joints and fractures which facilitates infiltration and acts as runoff zone. A complex erosional process shapes the structural hills predominantly by erosion, circumdenudation, weathering and mass wasting. The dip of the strata controls the rate of denudation processes in these structural hills. These hills are linear to arcuate exhibiting definite trends composed of varying lithology. This unit is structurally controlled by numerous joints, fractures and lineaments which facilitate some infiltration and mostly act as runoff zones. From the satellite imagery, the structural hills are interpreted by dark green tonal variation and by thick vegetation. There are few lineaments running on the structural hills. These have been identified in the imagery by the streams flow along them. These hills are found all along the southern side basin boundary which accounts about 13.08 % of total basin area (470 - 943 meter altitude).

In the Tittur Basin, structural hills are observed prominently in the southern part. These hills have linear as well as arcuate pattern. In the Tittur basin structural hills are running in a NE-SW trend with an average elevation of 750 m ASL, 115-480 m relief. Southern boundary of the Tittur Basin coalesces to form a linear structural hill range steeply descending to river channel. Being subjected to the stream action, these hill ranges are interspersed with well defined narrow valleys of sub watersheds. Slope angle is very steep along the escarpments.

Structural hills found in the Tittur Basin are devoid of water bearing aquifers due to highly jointed and fractured basalt with thin soil cover at the hill top and on the slopes. Generally, the groundwater potential is very poor in structural hills owing to their poor permeability where surface runoff is greater. Only limited groundwater potential is expected along faults, joints, fractures present in structural hills ranges. Linear hill ranges are found in the southern part of the basin with northeast southwest trend.

5.4.2 Lineaments

A lineament is a linear feature in a landscape which is an expression of an underlying geological structure such as a fault. Typically a lineament will comprise a fault-aligned valley, a series of fault or fold-aligned hills, a straight coastline or indeed a combination of these features. Fracture zones, shear zones and igneous intrusions such as dykes can also give rise to lineaments (Attoh and Brown, 2008). Lineaments are the linear features of tectonic origin then are identified as long narrow and relatively straight tonal alignments visible in satellite images. A lineament may be a fault, fracture, master joint, a long and linear geological formation, the straight course of streams, vegetation served may be the result of faulting and fracturing and hence it is inferred that they are the areas and zones of increased porosity and permeability in hard rock areas. These have more significance in the ground water studies. Lineaments are any features that can be picked out as lines (appearing as such or evident because of contrasts in terrain or ground cover on either side) in aerial or space imagery or geophysical data. Geologically, these are usually faults, fractures (joints), or boundaries

between stratigraphic formations. The human eye tends to single out both genuine and deceitful linear features, so that some, thought to be geological origin may, in fact, be of other origins. A fracture (or joint) is just a crack or break in the rock in which the rock on either side springs apart some small distance. A fault is a break in which the rock on one side slides or slips against the rock on the other side so that each side is displaced some distance from the other. As seen from the air or space, in a photo/image, a fracture is just a linear mark in which the tone of the rocks is the same on both sides. Most faults cause enough movement for individual layers or even formations to be displaced, so that there may be a sharp discontinuity in tonal pattern, where one type of rock is brought against another. Lineaments are often apparent in geological or topographic maps and can appear obvious on aerial or satellite photographs.

Groundwater is known to be concentrated in fracture zones found in many different rock types. The fracture traces are located by studying linear features such as straight alignment of trees, straight stream courses, straight valleys, aligned surface depressions (Murthy et al, 2003). These linear features more than 300 meters are termed as lineaments. Lineaments are large scale linear feature, which expresses itself in terms topography, which is itself, in expression of underlying structural features. Lineaments provide pathway for groundwater movement and hydrogeologically they are significant to form an interlaced network of high transmissivity and serve as groundwater conduits.

On the basis of GIS analysis many lineaments have been observed in the Tittur Basin most prominently in the southern and central part of the basin. Most prominent lineaments having south to North trend are running. Some Lineament have been running almost parallel to main

stream, these lineament had given an advantage of groundwater convergence from Western and eastern part of the basin.

5.4.3 Escarpment

An escarpment is a steep slope or long cliff that occurs from erosion or faulting and separates two relatively level areas of differing elevations. Usually escarpment is used interchangeably with scarp (from the Italian *scarpa*, shoe). But some sources differentiate the two terms, where escarpment refers to the margin between two landforms, while scarp is synonymous with a cliff or steep slope (Easterbrook, 1999). The surface of the steep slope is called a scarp face. Scarps are generally formed by one of two processes: either by differential erosion of sedimentary rocks, or by vertical movement of the Earth's crust along a fault (faulting). Less resistant rocks will erode faster, retreating until the point they are overlain by more resistant rock. When the dip of the bedding is gentle, a *cuesta* is formed. Steeper dips (greater than 30-40°) form *hogbacks* (Easterbrook, 1999). Escarpments are also frequently formed by faults. When a fault displaces the ground surface so that one side is higher than the other, a *fault scarp* is created. This can occur in *dip-slip* faults, or when a *strike-slip* fault brings a piece of high ground adjacent to an area of lower ground.

Escarpments have been observed in the Tittur Basin most prominently in the southern part of the basin. Most prominent Escarpments having SW to NE trend are running. Generally Escarpments have runoff zone that's why there is very low groundwater potential.

Fig. 5.2 3D Diagram of Valley fill, Talus, Escarpment, Ridge (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

Fig. 5.3 3D Diagram of Dyke (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

5.4.4 Dyke

A dike or dyke in geology is a type of sheet intrusion referring to any geologic body that cuts discordantly across planar wall rock structures, such as bedding or foliation, massive rock formations, like igneous/magmatic intrusions. Dikes can therefore be either intrusive or sedimentary in origin. An intrusive dike is an igneous body with a very high aspect ratio, which means that its thickness is usually much smaller than the other two dimensions. Thickness can vary from sub-centimeter scale to many meters, and the lateral dimensions can extend over many kilometers. A dike is an intrusion into an opening cross-cutting fissure, shouldering aside other pre-existing layers or bodies of rock; this implies that a dike is always younger than the rocks that contain it. Dikes are usually high angle to near vertical in orientation, but subsequent tectonic deformation may rotate the sequence of strata through which the dike propagates so that the latter becomes horizontal. Near horizontal or conformable intrusions, along bedding planes between strata are called intrusive sills.

Dikes can vary in texture and their composition can range from basaltic to granitic or rhyolitic, but on a global perspective the basaltic composition prevails, manifesting ascent of vast volumes of mantle-derived magmas through fractured lithosphere throughout Earth history. Dykes are discordant or cross-cutting, tabular intrusion into the country rock. Most dykes are vertical or near vertical, having pushed their way through the overlying country rock. This unit appears as dark tone in the satellite imagery. They occur in linear, narrow, low-lying relief and are barren. These dykes act both as conduits and barriers for groundwater flow. The groundwater prospects in this hydrogeomorphic unit are poor; but in the study area these dykes act as subsurface barriers

for groundwater movement within the weathered mantle making the prospect of groundwater good.

In the Tittur basin there is 4 Dykes, two dykes originate from southern side of the basin and is running almost perpendicular to main Fault line. The narrow linear valley formed by this Dykes has resulted in moderate to good groundwater potential zone. Remain two Dykes has been observed as they cross the straight stream course of Gadad sub basin. Along this Dykes, high moisture zone and dense vegetation is noted during field check. This Dyke is trending in NW-SE direction and traceable of about 3.5 km.

A subsurface dyke is a barrier impermeable to water that is placed underground to control the groundwater flow in an aquifer, and to raise the water table. Subsurface dyke is a structure that is built in an aquifer with the intention of obstructing the natural flow of ground water, thereby raising the ground water level and increasing the amount of water stored in the aquifer. Subsurface dyke had given an advantage of groundwater partition from Western and eastern part of the basin in upper reaches of Tittur basins. Consequently the dug wells in this stretch have greater groundwater potential as well as higher recuperation level.

5.5 Denudational Landforms

The surface of the earth is constantly being acted upon by different kinds of exogenetic forces like wind, water and ice. These forces tend to bring physical and chemical weathering of bed rock and also transport and deposit the weathered debris in certain locations on the earth (Nath et al., 2000). This complete phenomenon is referred to as a denudational

process and this gives rise to many denudational landforms such as pediment, pedepain, insulberg, tors etc. among- these, pediment and pedepain observed in study area are discussed with reference to their groundwater.

5.5.1 Pediment

Pediment is a gently sloping landform with erosional bedrock situated between hills and plains consisting of veneer of detritus and undulating rock floor (Gopinath and Seralathan, 2004), groundwater condition in pediment zone is expected to vary depending upon the type of underlying folds, fractures and the degree of weathering. Generally pediments do not favor much infiltration and therefore, these areas are not favorable for groundwater explorations. Pediment as the term suggests, is a feature usually formed at the foot of a mountain. Pediments occur as gently undulating plains with moderate slope dotted with outcrops of gneisses with thin layers of soil (Sethupathi et al, 2012). The pediment is a terrestrial erosional foot slope surface inclined at a low angle and lacking significant relief in all three dimensions. It usually meets the hill slope at an angular neck line, and may be covered by transported material. The low moisture content of this unit gives a bright signature in the satellite imagery, especially around the hills.

The term 'pediment' is defined, as an eroded rock surface of considerable extent at the foot of a mountain slope or a face formed under arid to semi-arid climate erosion. The pediments have very thin cover of soil, but its thickness may increase away from the pediment junction. The pediment overlies all the litho units with gentle to moderate slopes (1° to 7°), and is generally characterized by rugged

appearance with number of small outcrops and supports scanty vegetation. The zone of weathering is highly variable on different lithological units varying between 20cm and 50cm; and it extends to a depth of 10 meters along the fractures and joints. Sheet erosion and gulleying are very active in the zone of dissociated pediment exposing the underlying weathered mantle of bedrock at number of places. The areas of dissected pediment with shallow cover of red and brown sandy and gritty soil are under intense dry cultivation of groundnut, millets, jowar etc.

In the study area, pediments are observed along the villages viz Saigavan, Nipane, Bodhra, and Rajdehare as a narrow strip and are confined to adjoining the foothill zone found all along the periphery of the basin. Average elevation of pediment zone ranges from 480 to 410 m ASL and moderate slope of 1° to 7° occupying 20.34 percent (197.35km²) of the total basin area. This unit consists of fairly thick weathered zone underlain by partly weathered basalt. Thickness of weathered zone ranges from 5-10 meter as observed by open well lithology. From the groundwater Point of view this unit falls in poor to moderate groundwater Potential zone. In this zone most of irrigation depends on dug wells. Water table fluctuation ranges from 3-5 meter.

5.5.2 Pedepain

Pedepain is the gently sloping undulating plain of large area extent. These are formed as a result of continuous process of pedimentation with intensive weathering under semiarid climatic conditions (Knig, 1950 and Spark, 1960). These are identified in the imageries grey tone on false colour composite (Ghose, 1993). Groundwater prospects in this unit good

due to the moderate thickness (4 to 10 m) weathering materials (Prakash and Mishra 1993).

The pediplains are formed as a result of weathering under arid and semi-arid conditions, representing the end stage of cyclic erosion (King, 1950; Sparks, 1960). A Pediment is developed by a combination of process including stream erosion, weathering, sheet wash and lateral plantation. When the sediment developed over a large area as a result of continuous process of pedimentation, it is normally termed as a pediplain (Agarwal and Garg, 2000). Pediplains are the result of coalescence of pediments, predominantly occupying large area. There are three pediplains observed in the study area, which are shallow buried pediplain, moderate buried pediplain and deep buried pediplain. The pediplains are characterized by the presence of relatively thicker weathered material. The extent and thickness of weathering depends on the slope, resistance of the underlying rock to weathering, presence of joints and fractures and precipitation and climatic conditions of the area. Depending upon the thickness of the weathered zone, the groundwater potential is moderate to good and eligible for construction of a well.

Pedeplain, are located between pediment and alluvial plains in the northern and central part of the Tittur Basin, whereas in linear valley of Gadad sub basin, they are observed between pediments and valley fills. Pedeplain have fairly weathered thick mantle underlain by weathered and fractured basalt locally known Murum, indicates high porosity and permeability. In the study area, pedeplain unit has an average elevation of 444 to 258 m AST- with the slope ranging from 0° to 1°. This unit is observed along Chalisgaon, Nagardeola, Patonda, Vaghli villages. The area occupied by pedeplain is 37.12 % (360.15 sq km) of total basin area.

The thickness of these plains varies from 4 to 10 m in the northern and central part of the basin, whereas in the south, thickness varies from 2 to 5 m. The occurrence of groundwater is in unconfined condition with weathered mantle. Pedepain have moderate to good groundwater potential.

5.5.3 Denudational Hill

Denudational hills are the remnants of the natural dynamic process of denudation and weathering. The geomorphic forms of denudational hills occur as exfoliation domes, linear ridges, mesas, low mounds and Tors with partial scree or debris covered at the foot slopes. The geomorphic expression and shape of the denudational hills are controlled by lithology, and spacing of structural features like joints and fractures occurring in them. The denudational hills in basic intrusives occur as narrow linear ridges within the pediplain where dykes are seen.

These hills are essentially rocky, composed of basaltic with very little soil cover and mostly barren of vegetation. These are characterized by rugged surface and occur as hill ranges. All the hill ranges are under Gautala reserve forest. These denudational hills are characterised by horizontal, curvilinear and vertical joints, which accelerate the process of weathering. These have given rise to the typical semi-arid type of tropical weathering geomorphic forms such as exfoliation domes, domed inselbergs and Tors with steeper slopes along with the sliding of the bigger boulders. The depth of weathering in these denudational hills is shallow, hardly about a meter thick.

Denudational hills are marked by sharp to blunt crest lines with rugged tops indicating that the surface run off at the upper reaches of the hills has caused rill erosion. Denudational hills, with an average height of 360 m above mean sea level occupy the South East part of the study area. They are exposed as a group of massive hills with resistant rock bodies , flat top, some hills have rounded summits and are formed due to differential erosion and weathering. Denudational hills are identified in the satellite imagery by their massive size and domal to elliptical shape. They appear as dark green in color in the satellite imagery. These hills are covered with big boulders and sparse vegetation in contrast to structural hills. This landform, in general, act as high runoff zone, due to its moderate to steep slope (7° to 22°). Denudational hills due to their relief acts as watershed boundary also. The total coverage of this unit is 21.90 sq km and it occupies 2.25 % of the study area. They are mostly exposed to the south to southwest. These are found to be south-central to southwest. A few pockets of denudational hills exist in the north eastern parts of the study area are mostly covered with forest leaving no common tonal characteristics for their identification. But that could be interpreted from their massive size and dome to elliptical shape. The rugged topography of this region is due to the erosion of the denudational hills to the plain region, leaving the rock exposed. The groundwater potential of this landform in general is moderate to poor.

Fig. 5.4 3D Diagram of Structural hill, Pediment and Pediplain Zone (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

Fig. 5.5 3D Diagram of Denudational Hills (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

5.5.4 Dissected plateau

A dissected plateau is a plateau area that has been severely eroded so that the relief is sharp. Such an area may be referred to as mountainous, but dissected plateaus are distinguishable from orogenic mountain belts by the lack of folding, metamorphism, extensive faulting, or magmatic activity that accompanies orogeny. Such a plateau may be level or gently sloping but may be distinguished by the till caps on its hills.

Dissected Plateaus cover small area of flat upland bounded by an escarpment on western sides but some part enclosed by hill. The essential criteria for plateaus are low relative relief and some altitude. In Tittur basin Dissected Plateaus are not much extensive but together with enclosed basins they cover about 2.74 percent (26.60 sq km) of the Tittur basin. Although plateaus stand at higher elevation than surrounding terrain, they differ from mountain ranges in that they are remarkably flat. The groundwater potential of this landform in general is moderate to poor.

5.5.5 Monadnock or Residual Hills

The residual hills are the end product of the process of pediplanation, which reduces the original mountain masses into a series of scattered knolls standing on the pediplains (Thornbury, 1990). The residual hills have geomorphic expression in the form of inselbergs, tors, linear and curvilinear ridges, exfoliated domes with partially debris cover at the foot slope (Tripathy et al. 1996). These

Fig. 5.6 3D Diagram of Dissected plateau (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

Fig. 5.7 3D Diagram of Monadnock or Residual Hills (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

are the resistant isolated, steep sided, usually smoothed and rounded hill of circumdenudation rising abruptly above the surroundings over the level plains in tropical regions (Gary et al., 1972). These residual hills exhibit conical to rounded forms with steep to very steep slopes. King (1948) termed those residual hills as inselbergs. The residual hills are more resistant formation standing out prominently differential erosion and weathering. It's occurring as isolated patches are found at lower altitudes complex to the denudational hills. In spite of their isolated occurrence, their continuity in a linear or curvilinear fashion gives indication that they are structurally controlled. The shape of the residual hills, controlled by the different lithological composition, distribution and spacing of joints and fractures. In the imageries dark grey tone and coarse texture in black and white images and dark reddish colour in false colour composite with radial drainages pattern (Gupta, 1980).

The residual hills are isolated hillocks being formed as remnants of weathering and denudation processes and this unit is present in a scattered manner in the central part of the study area and along east of Chalisgaon. They are mostly barren, rocky, usually smooth, rounded small hills abruptly rising above the surrounding plains. Monadnocks in the study area are made up of basalt rocks. Slope ranges are moderate to very steep slope.

In the study area, the residual hills are composed of massive rock with a height average of 365 m mean sea level. The residual hills are more resistant formation from differential erosion and weathering. This unit occurs as isolated patches and found at lower altitudes. In spite of their isolated occurrence, their continuity in a linear or curvilinear fashion gives indication that they are structurally controlled.

In the satellite imagery they appear as isolated patches and with dark green color tone with radial drainage pattern. Due to steep slope most of the rain water is washed off immediately without much infiltration and hence the groundwater prospect in this unit is poor. Its coverage is 0.55 sq.km area and it occupies 0.05% of the study area. This unit is acting as surface runoff zone due to steep slope and groundwater prospects are very poor.

5.5.6 Ridge

A ridge is a geological feature consisting of a chain of mountains or hills that form a continuous elevated crest for some distance. There are two types of Ridges in the Tittur basin.

Dendritic ridge: In typical dissected plateau terrain, the stream drainage valleys will leave intervening ridges. These are by far the most common ridges. These ridges usually represent slightly more erosion resistant rock, but not always – they often remain because there were more joints where the valleys formed, or other chance occurrences. This type of ridge is generally somewhat random in orientation, often changing direction frequently, often with knobs at intervals on the ridge top.

Fault ridges: Faults often form escarpments. Sometimes the tops of the escarpments form not plateaus, but slope back so that the edges of the escarpments form ridges. This type of ridge occurs at southern divide of the Tittur basin. Its coverage is 47.54 sq.km areas and it occupies 4.90 % of the study area. This unit is acting as surface runoff zone due to steep slope, bare rocky surface and groundwater prospects are very poor.

Fig. 5.8 3D Diagram of Dendritic ridge (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

Fig. 5.9 3D Diagram of Fault Ridges (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

5.5.7 Gully and Rill

A gully is a landform created by running water, eroding sharply into soil, typically on a hillside. Gullies resemble large ditches or small valleys, but are meters to tens of meters in depth and width. When the gully formation is in process, the water flow rate can be substantial, which causes the significant deep cutting action into soil.

Gullying or gully erosion is the process by which gullies are formed. Hillsides are more prone to gullying when they are cleared of vegetation, through deforestation, over-grazing or other means. In the Tittur basin near foot hill zone of the Ajanta Satmal Range several gullies occur. The eroded soil is easily carried by the flowing water after being dislodged from the ground, normally when rainfall falls during short, intense storms such as during thunderstorms. Gullies reduce the productivity of farmland where they incise into the land, and produce sediment that may clog downstream water bodies. In the Tittur basin Gully length measured from 100 meter to 1100 meter. This unit is acting as runoff zone due to steep slope and groundwater prospects are low as compare to stream.

Rill is a narrow and shallow incision into topsoil layers, resulting from erosion by overland flow or surface runoff. Rills are most common on slopes of unvegetated ground and agricultural land. However, they can occur on a variety of surfaces. Rills may even be found on the surface of certain soluble rocks (Ford and Lundberg, 1987). Rills are often seen as the first signs of major soil erosion, and if left to grow, may evolve into larger fluvial features like gullies, streams, or rivers. Rills are often seen as the first signs of major soil erosion, and if left to grow, may evolve into larger fluvial features like gullies, streams, or rivers.

Rills are created when water erodes the topsoil on hillsides, and so are significantly affected by seasonal weather patterns. They tend to appear more often in rainier months (Fullen and Reed, 1987). Rills begin to form when the runoff shear stress, the ability of surface runoff to detach soil particles, overcomes the soil's shear strength, the ability of soil to resist force working parallel to the soil's surface. This begins the erosion process as water breaks soil particles free and carries them down the slope (Torri et al, 1987). These forces explain why sandy, loamy soils are especially susceptible to the formation of rills, whereas dense clays tend to resist rill formation (Loch and Thomas, 1987).

Rills cannot form on every surface, and their formation is intrinsically connected to the steepness of the hillside slope. Gravity determines the force of the water, which provides the power required to start the erosional environment necessary to create rills. Therefore, the formation of rills is primarily controlled by the slope of the hillside. Slope controls the depth of the rills, while the length of the slope and the soil's permeability control the number of incisions in an area. Each type of soil has a threshold value, a slope angle below which water velocity cannot produce sufficient force to dislodge enough soil particles for rills to form (Planchon et al, 1987). For instance, on many non-cohesive slopes, this threshold value hovers around an angle of 2 degrees with a shear velocity between 3 and 3.5 cm/s (Rauws, 1987).

In the Tittur basin several rills occurs on hill slope. This unit is acting as runoff zone due to steep slope and groundwater prospects are low, rills are not much affect on groundwater prospects because they are seasonal in nature.

5.5.8 Tor

A Tor is a large, free-standing residual mass (rock outcrop) that rises abruptly from the surrounding smooth and gentle slopes of a rounded hill summit or ridge crest. Tor is usually composed of granite or metamorphic rocks, but they can also develop in volcanic rocks and occasionally other hard rock's such as quartzite. They are the result of millions of years of weathering. Further chemical attack by circulating water and later by acidic rainwater caused further weathering along the lines of these joints, resulting in the more or less complete decomposition of the basalt into its constituent crystals in regions where the joints were closely spaced. Finally majority of the basalt was stripped away and leaved away larger blocks, leaving them scattered around the now-exposed Tor. Tor exposed rock mass of jointed and broken blocks.

In the Tittur basin Tors are seldom more than 5 meters high and often occur as residues at the summits of Dykes and at the highest points of pediments. Tors usually overlies unaltered bedrock and are thought to be formed either by freeze–thaw weathering or by groundwater weathering before exposure. There is often evidence of spheroidal weathering of the squared joint blocks. Due to the lack of moisture content, groundwater prospects are very poor.

Fig. 5.10 Satellite image of Gully (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

Fig. 5.11 Tor (Source: Image taken on Field work)

5.6 Fluvial Landform

Fluvial is a term used in geography and Earth science to refer to the processes associated with rivers and streams and the deposits and landforms created by them. Fluvial processes comprise the motion of sediment and erosion or deposition (geology) on the river bed (Charlton, 2008). Fluvial Landform is associated with fluvial process on earth surface.

Fragments of soil, regolith, and bed rock that are remained from the parent rock mass transported by the fluvial agent and deposited elsewhere to make an entirely different set of surface features the depositional landforms. Alluvial plain and flood plain constitute the main forms of fluvial origin in addition to valley fills and channel bars. These are characterized by very gentle sloping, thick deposits of river alluvium mainly pebbles, cobbles, boulders, sand, silt and clays. These units form the main source of ground water in the region. These hydrogeomorphic units that have come in to existence due to fluvial depositional processes in the Tittur Basin, These features occupy the valley part and are composed of loose deposits of permeable material like sand, silt, clay.

5.6.1 Alluvial Plain

Alluvial plain" is "a large assemblage of fluvial landforms (braided streams, terraces, etc.,) that form low gradient, regional ramps along the flanks of mountains and extend great distances from their sources. Use of "alluvial plain" as a general, informal term for a broad flood plain or a low-gradient delta is explicitly discouraged. The NCSS glossary instead suggests "flood plain"(NRSC, 2001).A level or gently sloping tract or a

slightly undulating land surface produced by extensive deposition of alluvium, usually adjacent to a river that periodically overflows its banks; it may be situated on a flood plain, a delta, or an alluvial fan. Alluvial plains are level to gently sloping plains with undulating topography composed of unconsolidated sediments or partly consolidated sediments such as sand, silt and clay (Nagarale et al., 2007).

These fluvial depositional plains are developed on either sides of the river and their tributaries. From the river banks it extends from few hundred meters to 1-2 km laterally. It is highly permeable zone helping in partial bank recharge and subsurface flow. Groundwater in alluvial plain occurs under semi confined to perched water table conditions with shallow water levels.

Alluvial plains in the Tittur River are observed along the main river course downstream to Chalisgaon, Patonda and Lohatar villages occupies about 10.41 % (100.99 sq km) of the total basin area. The alluvial material comprises of gravel, sand, silt and clayey silt. The alluvial Plain patches are narrow and restricted as the river flows over the hard and resistant basalt. The thickness of the alluvium ranges from 2 to 5 meters over the basalt. Lateral spreading of alluvial deposits in the flood plain is also noticed. The low thorny trees and Babul are seen along the course of Dungri and Tittur River. Groundwater prospects in alluvial plain is invariably found to be good and it is a promising zone for the same through which groundwater has been tapped by digging numerous wells and tube wells, giving high yield of water. Ground water can be tapped through shallow and deep tube wells in alluvial plains and flood plains. The wells tapping the flood plains generally give high yield with good quality of water.

5.6.2 Valley Fills

Valley Fills are those valley courses which are controlled by lineaments and are filled with colluvial and alluvial material deposited or dumped by the natural process of transportation as well as decrease in flow velocity or obstruction to the transported material. They are confined to narrow linear depressions. Lithologically valley fills comprises weathered and erosional products of surrounding rock consists of cobbles, pebbles, sand, silt, clay and gravels (Magar et al., 2007). Valley fills are low linear areas occurring between hills. These units occupy the lowest reaches in topography with nearly level slope. The valley fill deposits are colluvio-fluvial in origin derived from weathering and deposited by the action of streams at the floor of valleys. Depending upon the parent rock, the valley fills deposits vary in composition and texture (Agarwal and Garg, 2000). Normally, they are covered with red, brown and black coarse gravel to sandy and clayey soils. In the study area, the valley fills are identified between the structural hills on the Southern part of the study area. The drainage pattern over the valley fills is parallel to sub-parallel indicating that the drainage is by and large controlled by the lineaments. They exhibit dark reddish tone and medium texture in the satellite imagery, which indicates high moisture content due to intensive cultivation.

Valley fills are observed in the southern part of the Tittur Basin occupying approximately 2.77 % (26.90 sq km) of the total basin area. This unit is typically located in between structural hill ranges near Patna, Saigavan, Rajdehare, Kinhi villages trending in North to South direction. Very fine to medium grain unconsolidated sediments varying in thickness, either continuous or disconnected strips are noticed. Generally the thickness of this colluvio-fluvial sediment varies from 5 to 12 meter

depending upon the width of the valley bottom and the stage of stream course that is draining the valley. Most of the valley fills observed in the basin is aligned to lineaments having straight stream courses.

This hydrogeomorphic unit is characterized by high porosity and high permeability resulting in high infiltration rate. Most of the wells have been dugged in this zone to get the high yield of water. In the Tittur Basin valley fills zone is mostly occupied by cultivation. Owing to large amount of recharge from both valley side slopes, they are most favorable groundwater zone. Groundwater prospects in valley fills are good to excellent because of the topographical location at the bottom of the hill and geological composition consisting of highly porous materials. Subsurface water potential is also good to excellent in the valley fills (Murthy and Rao, 1999).

5.6.3 Floodplain

A relatively level area bordering a river, subject to periodic flooding and made up of sediments deposited by the river, which bury the rock-cut valley to a variable depth (Smith, 2006). Floodplains are a natural feature of rivers. They are the mostly flat land adjacent to the river and form due to the actions of the river. Rivers erode their own banks and redeposit the eroded material downstream. Material is added to the floodplain during floods, a process called overbank deposition. The material that underlies floodplains is a mixture of thick layers of sand and thin layers of mud.

A floodplain is a flat or nearly flat land adjacent a stream or river that stretches from the banks of its channel to the base of the enclosing valley walls and experiences flooding during periods of high discharge

(Goudie, 2004). It includes the floodway, which consists of the stream channel and adjacent areas that carry flood flows, and the flood fringe, which are areas covered by the flood, but which do not experience a strong current. In other words, a floodplain is an area near a river or a stream which floods when the water level reaches flood stage. Flood plains are made by a meander eroding sideways as it travels downstream. When a river breaks its banks and floods, it leaves behind layers of rock and mud. These gradually build up to create the floor of the flood plain. Floodplains generally contain unconsolidated sediments, often extending below the bed of the stream. These are accumulations of sand, gravel, loam, silt, and/or clay, and are often important aquifers. The water drawn from Flood Plain area being pre-filtered compared to the water in the river.

Flood Plain is observed in the Northern part of the Tittur Basin occupying approximately 1.57 % (15.27 sq km) of the total basin area. This unit is typically located along the main stream course near Patna, Chalisgaon, Patonda , Kajgaon, Nagardeola, Lohatar villages trending in South to North and SW to NE direction Very fine to medium grain unconsolidated sediments varying in thickness. This hydrogeomorphic unit is characterized by high porosity and high permeability resulting in high infiltration rate. Most of the wells have been dugged in this zone to get the high yield of water. Owing to large amount of recharge that's why this zone has been most favorable groundwater zone. Groundwater prospects in Flood Plain are good to excellent.

Fig. 5.12 3D Diagram of Alluvial Plain (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

Fig. 5.13 3D Diagram of Flood plain (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

5.6.4 Fluvial Terraces

Fluvial terraces are elongated terraces that flank the sides of floodplains and fluvial valleys all over the world. They consist of a relatively level strip of land, called a “tread,” separated from an adjacent floodplain, other fluvial terraces, or uplands by distinctly steeper strips of land called “risers.” These terraces lie parallel to and above the river channel and its floodplain. Because of the manner in which they form, fluvial terraces are underlain by fluvial sediments of highly variable thickness (Fairbridge, 1968, Blum and Tonqvist, 2000). Geologically ancient floodplains are often represented in the landscape by fluvial terraces. These are old floodplains that remain relatively high above the present floodplain and indicate former courses of a stream.

Fluvial terraces are the remnants of earlier floodplains that existed at a time when either a stream or river was flowing at a higher elevation before its channel down cut to create a new floodplain at a lower elevation. Changes in elevation can be due to changes in the base level (elevation of the lowest point in the fluvial system, usually the drainage basin) of the fluvial system, which leads to head ward erosion along the length of either a stream or river, gradually lowering its elevation. For example, down cutting by a river can lead to increased velocity of a tributary, causing that tributary to erode toward its headwaters. Terraces can also be left behind when the volume of the fluvial flow declines due to changes in climate, typical of areas which were covered by ice during periods of glaciation, and their adjacent drainage basins (Blum and Tonqvist, 2000, Leet et al, 1982).

Fluvial Terraces is observed in the Northern part of the Tittur Basin occupying approximately 0.06 % (0.65 sq km) of the total basin area.

This unit is typically located along Dungri River course near Chalisgaon trending in SW to NE direction Very fine to medium grain unconsolidated sediments varying in thickness. This hydrogeomorphic unit is characterized by high porosity and high permeability resulting in high infiltration rate. Groundwater prospects in this zone are good to excellent.

5.6.5 Palaeochannel

A palaeochannel or paleochannel is a remnant of an inactive river or stream channel that has been either filled or buried by younger sediment. The sediments that the ancient channel is either cut into or buried by can be either unconsolidated, semi-consolidated, consolidated, or lithified (Anand and Paine, 2007). A palaeochannel is distinct from the overbank deposits of currently active river channels, including ephemeral water courses which do not regularly flow. A palaeochannel is distinct from such watercourses because the river bed is filled with sedimentary deposits which are unrelated to the normal bed load of the current drainage pattern.

Paleochannels or old river courses, buried by subsequent sedimentation, are generally potential reservoirs for groundwater and hence useful for groundwater exploration. In addition to that, the paleochannel identification useful in flood mitigation. In the identification of paleochannel contrasting dark tone in a characteristics winding fashion in association with cropping pattern and linearly oriented vegetation. Soils in this region more moisture content as compared to the surrounding areas due to the groundwater flow zones.

The paleochannels are observed mainly in the south west side of the basin, occupying approximately 0.02 % (0.20 sq km) of the total basin

area. This area falls under the low-lying topography. The origin of the paleochannels may be due to the frequent changes in the Dungri River. In the Tittur basin paleochannels are arranged on old drainage patterns which are distinct from the current drainage system of a catchment. These paleochannels drained West to East and the current drainage direction is south to north. Groundwater prospects in buried channels are excellent because of the hydrophilic nature of alluvial and colluvium deposits, retention of foot waters, location contiguous to the river mainly responsible for recharge.

5.6.6 Plunge pool

A plunge pool (or plunge basin or waterfall lake) can be a natural hydrologic fluvial landform feature. It is a stream pool, lake, or pond that is small in diameter, but deep. Plunge pools are formed under the force of a natural source, such as a waterfall or rapids. The swirling water, sometimes carrying rocks within it, erodes the riverbed into a basin, often featuring irregular and rough sides. Plunge pools can remain after the waterfall has ceased to exist or the stream has been diverted. Plunge pools are erosional features which occur in the youthful stage of a river. When soft rock has been eroded back to a knickpoint, water constantly bombards its base, because this rock is often less dense than surrounding strata, the water from the higher grade continues eroding downward.

The plunge pools are observed mainly in the south west side of the basin, occupying approximately 0.10 sq km area. Plunge pool is a significant feature in Tittur basin because Kedar Kunda Waterfall has the most prominent plunge pool feature and due to the occurrence of a fracture zone this plunge pool is working as a groundwater recharge zone.

Fig. 5.14 Satellite image of Palaeochannel (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

Fig. 5.15 Satellite image of Plunge pool (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

Fig. 5.16 Satellite image of Stream pool (Source: Geo Eye Satellite Imaginary and ASTER DEM)

Fig. 5.17 Stream pool (Source: Image taken on Field work)

5.6.7 Stream pool

A stream pool, in hydrology, is a stretch of a river or stream in which the water depth is above average and the water velocity is quite below average (Matthew,2004).A stream pool may be portion of the stream bed that is bedded with sediment or armoured with gravels, and in some cases the pool formations may have been formed as basins in exposed bedrock formations.

The stream pools are observed mainly in the south side of the basin, occupying approximately 0.25 sq km area. Stream pool is significant feature in Tittur basin because this landform working as ground water recharge zone.

5.7 Landforms associated with Hill Slope

Hillslopes are an important part of the terrestrial landscape. The basin landscape can be thought of as being composed of a mosaic of slope types, ranging from steep mountains and cliffs to almost flat plains. On most hillslopes large quantities of soil and sediment are moved over time via the mediums of air and water often under the direct influence of gravity. The form a hillslope takes is dependent on the various geomorphic processes acting on it. Hillslopes are also the source of materials that are used to construct a number of depositional landforms such as Talus.

5.7.1 Talus

Talus is defined as a pile of rock fragments lying at the bottom of the cliff or steep slope from which they have broken off. Talus is accumulation of broken rock fragments at the base of crags, mountain cliffs, or valley shoulders. Landforms associated with these materials are sometimes called scree slopes or talus piles. These deposits typically have a concave upwards form, while the maximum inclination of such deposits corresponds to the angle of repose of the mean debris size. Formation of talus deposits results from physical and chemical weathering and erosional processes acting on a rock face. The predominant processes that degrade a rock slope depend largely on the regional climate (temperature, amount of rainfall, etc.).

Talus, or Scree, is the loose rock created by physical weathering. It typically lies on a steep mountainside or at the base of a cliff. Mechanical weathering breaks down exposed bedrock into steep piles and talus slopes like this before the minerals in the rock can alter into clay minerals. That comes much later, after the talus is washed and tumbled downhill, turning to alluvium, colluviums and eventually into soil. In the Tittur basin mostly after Talus slope there is colluviums deposit near foot hill zone.

The Talus has been observed mainly in the south side of the basin, occupying approximately 43.80 sq km (4.51 %) area. Talus is significant feature in Tittur basin because this landform working as ground water recharge zone.

5.8 Lineament Analysis

Linear features on surface of the earth have attracted attentions of geologists for many years. This interest has grown most rapidly since the introduction of aerial photographs and satellite image into geological studies. In the early and middle of 1900s, several geologists, Hobbs (1904, 1912), O'Leary et al. (1976), recognized the existence and significance of linear geomorphic features that were the surface expression of zones of weakness or structural displacement in the crust of the earth. Lineaments have been used in many applications: petroleum and mineral exploration, nuclear energy facility sittings, and water resource investigations. Previous studies have revealed a close relationship between lineaments and groundwater flow and yield (Lattman and Parizek, 1964; Mabee et al., 1994; Magowe and Carr, 1999; Fernandes and Rudolph, 2001). Generally lineaments are underlain by zones of localized weathering and increased permeability and porosity. Meanwhile, some researchers studied relationships between groundwater productivity and the number of lineament within specifically designated areas or lineament density rather than the lineament itself (Hardcastle, 1995). Therefore mapping of lineaments closely related to groundwater occurrence and yield is essential to groundwater surveys, development, and management. These lineament maps are constructed as an annexed thematic map of a hydro geological map in Korea (MOCT and KOWACO, 1998).

Lineaments are defined as map-able linear surface features, which differ distinctly from the patterns of adjacent features and presumably reflect subsurface phenomena (O'Leary et al., 1976). The subsurface effect is valid if the origin of the lineament is controlled by geological structures such as faults and fractures. Other types of lineaments resulted

from morphological effects (stream channels or drainage divides) can also exist in the region. Satellite images and aerial photographs are extensively used to extract lineaments for different purposes. Since satellite images are obtained from varying wavelength intervals of the electromagnetic spectrum, they are considered to be a better tool to discriminate the lineaments and to produce better information than conventional aerial photographs (Casas et al., 2000). Lineaments usually appear as straight lines or “edges” on the images which in all cases contributed by the tonal differences within the surface material. The knowledge and the experience of the user is the key point in the identification of the lineaments particularly to connect broken segments into a longer lineament (Wang et al., 1990).

Lineaments are natural, linear surface elements, interpreted directly from satellite imagery and geo-physical map and have been called fracture traces, and many other names (Parizek, 1976; Garza and Slade, 1986; O’leary et al, 1976) and also used for water resource investigations (Boyer and McQueen, 1964; Brown, 1994; Lattman and Parizek, 1964; Peterson, 1980; Mah et al, 1995; Dhakate et al, 2007) and structural geologic studies (Blanchet, 1957; Henderson, 1960; Hodgson, 1961; Lattman and Segovia, 1961; Caran et al, 1982; Acharya et al, 2007; Rahiman and Pettinga, 2008; Kazemi et al, 2009), considering lineaments as the surface expressions of joints/fractures or zone of joint concentration. Practical experiences of many hydrogeologists and petroleum geologists were that suggesting locations for dug wells, tube wells and drill wells in crystalline metamorphic and igneous terrain, based on lineament data, did not always yield a good success rate. Several studies show a significant deviation of lineaments from dominant joint/fractures (Lattman and Matzke, 1961; Matzke, 1961; Lipfert et al,

2001; De'gnan and Clark, 2002), demanding more investigations to analyze the lineaments in Precambrian metamorphic rocks.

Caponera (1989) interpreted the remote sensing image for groundwater surveying and extracted the morphology, lineaments, structural features, vegetation, and drainage from the image. His study concluded that the tensional fractures by tectonism are related to the groundwater storage or movement in bedrock. Travaglia (1989) also studied the fracture and groundwater exploration in two areas, the Bayhan Al Qasab area (Yemen) and the Philippines. He also revealed that the tensional fractures are related with groundwater exploration in the Karst region, Philippines. Sidle and Lee (1995) concluded that anisotropic hydraulic conductivity was related to the orientation of geologic structures. Larson (1972) indicated that wells located in fractures which were interpreted as extensional fractures were much more productive than wells located in shear fractures.

A lineament is defined as a large-scale linear feature, which expresses itself in terms of topography, which is in itself, an expression of the underlying structural features. From the groundwater point of view such features may include, valleys controlled by faulting and jointing, hill ranges and ridges, displacements and abrupt truncation of rocks, straight streams and right angles off setting of stream courses etc., (Merh et.al., 1989 and Ramesh, 1990). A lineament is a regional scale linear or curvilinear feature, pattern or changes in pattern that can be identified in a data set and attributed to a geologic formation or structure (Qureshy and Hinze, 1989). The linear features can be measured and treated quantitatively like measurements of other geological properties, but it is necessary to use formal statistics that reflect the circular nature of the directional data (Cheeney, 1983; Gaile and Burt, 1980 and Gumbel et al,

1953; Mardia, 1972). Lineaments are linear fractures commonly associated with dislocation and deformations. They provide the pathways for groundwater movement and are hydrogeologically very important (Sankar et.al, 1996). Lineaments are important in rocks where secondary permeability and porosity dominate and inter-granular characteristics combine in secondary openings influencing weathering, soil water and groundwater movements. The fracture zone forms an interlaced network of high transmissivity and serves as groundwater conduits in massive rocks in inter-fracture areas. The lineament intersection areas are considered as good groundwater potential zones. The combination of fractures and topographically low grounds can also serve as the best aquifers horizons (Karanth, 1989; Rao, 1992). In hard rocks, the amount of groundwater available is entirely dependent on the storage and rate of infiltration in the faults and fractures. This, in turn, depends on whether the fracture is open or tight. It can be said quite simply that a tight fracture contains no water while an open one may produce a considerable yield of groundwater. In most cases this can be related to tension or shear phenomena in the ruptural deformation of the rocks (Larsson, 1977). The common assumption in lineament mapping is that these features are closely related to fractured zones and lineaments studies have therefore been one of the most important and common approaches in groundwater explorations in hard rock terrain. It has been shown that wells located on or close to fractured zones are often more productive than wells positioned farther away from the fracture zone (Singhal and Gupta, 1999). Lineaments are often visual on remote sensing data as topographic, drainage, vegetation, or soil tonal anomalies. Determining the hydrological importance of different fractures is however very difficult. The most common criteria are lineaments associated with

prominent vegetation, straight segments of drainage and topographic relief. Other criteria are length, width, continuity along strike and parallelism with other lineaments (Sander et al, 1997). Since faults usually have similar directions, an important means to determine the significance of the lineament is to check if the direction of the lineament is systematic and similar to known fault zones (Drury, 1993).

Lineament maps such as lineament density map are important to reveal the groundwater recharge, flow and development. Especially, groundwater flows and yields in mountainous areas composed of crystalline rocks with many fractures and faults are governed mainly by the lineaments comprised of fractures, joints and faults. Furthermore, the distribution of lineaments is closely related to well productivity or yield. That is to say, these lineaments may give important information on the distribution of well development and management. Therefore, the lineament and related maps are considered as essential maps in basic groundwater surveys in Tittur Basin.

5.8.1 Methodology and Data base for Lineament Analysis

The imagery used comprised subsets from an original scene of path 146 and row 046 and path 147 and row 046 of the Landsat 7 Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+) of 2010 respectively. Landsat 7 ETM+ has an extra 15-m panchromatic (Pan) band. Using ENVI RS software removes Scan Line Corrector Problem. The imagery was geo-referenced using the identifiable features such as road junctions and bends on the topographical map of the study area.

5.8.2 Lineament Mapping

Lineaments were delineated by visual interpretation of the false colour composite (FCC) 471. The FCC was fused with the 15-m Pan imagery to enhance the interpretation. Hung et al. (2005) showed that the application of higher-resolution 15-m resolution Advanced Space borne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) imagery yielded better results in lineament interpretation compared to Landsat imagery due to improved spatial resolution. FCC RGB 471 was used after examining various band combinations. The application of higher-resolution 0.5 m resolution Geo Eye Satellite image also provides potential of lineament mapping for subsurface lineament and paleochannels. Visual interpretation was improved by using a 99% linear contrast stretch, in which 1% of the lower and higher digital number (DN) values in the histogram were assigned to black and white (0,255) respectively, and the remaining values were distributed linearly between these values (Arlegui and Soriano 1998). Lineament mapping is normally undertaken based on geomorphological features such as aligned ridges and valleys, displacement of ridge lines, scarp faces and river passages, straight drainage channel segments, pronounced breaks in crystalline rock masses and aligned surface depression (Koch and Mather 1997 and Hung et al. 2005). For the study area, the main interest was topographically negative lineaments, which may represent joints, faults and probably shear zones (Juhari and Ibrahim 1997, Koch and Mather 1997, Solomon and Ghebreab 2006). To eliminate the non-geological elements such as paths, roads, power cables and field boundaries in the study area, geographical map and field checking were undertaken by the method suggested by Yassaghi (2006). The interpreted lineaments from the fused imagery of 2010 have been digitized on-screen. The interpretation underwent further

checking to eliminate any unnecessary lineaments using the topographical features of the study area. Only features that resemble lineaments in both imagery were delineated. Although Suzen and Toprak (1998) suggested that Landsat 7 ETM+ band 7 should be used, upon inspection of both imageries, band 4 was found to be the best in showing the textural features. Use of band 4 was also suggested by Juhari and Ibrahim (1997), Pradeep et al. (2000) and Syed and Saied (2004) for lineament interpretation. This suggestion is based on the good overall contrast and sharpest definition of linear geological features compared to other bands. Band 4 was also subjected to a non-directional edge-enhancement filter prior to further interpretation (Juhari and Ibrahim 1997). After all the lineaments were interpreted, they were draped over the DEM derived from the ASTER imagery. Only lineaments that were consistent with the topographically features were digitized

Fig. 5.18 Lineaments Map of the Tittur Basin

5.8.3 Result

In the study area, 291 lineaments have been mapped through visual interpretation of satellite imagery and most are cross checked during the field investigation. They are having varying dimension and the smallest of them is 0.99 Km long and the longest of them is 22.64 km. In the present study, lineaments were classified based on their length into three categories as Major (>15km); Medium (5-15km) and Minor (<5km). Lineament map shows that there are three predominant sets of lineaments, one set trending SW – NE and second set trending SE - NW and last set trending south - North. Total cross lineaments have been 94. Details on lineament interpretation as follows;

1. Two long prominent lineaments were interpreted in the satellite imagery, which starts from Gautala reserved forest in the southwestern side of the study area and ends with in North eastern side of the study area. Remain one major lineament is northern side of the Tittur basin. The Tittur main river course is flowing exactly along this major lineaments and this infers that Tittur main river course is structurally controlled. These major lineaments lengths are 22.64 Km, 21.52 Km and 15.78 Km respectively.
2. There are lot of criss-cross lineaments in the south and southwestern part of the study area.
3. Central part of the study area, from South to North, there are 2 parallel running discontinuous lineaments run along with dykes.
4. Non criss-cross lineaments occupy the top northern portion, northwestern portion, and North east portion of the study area.

5. From the lineament map, the lineament density and lineament intersection maps are prepared.

Table 5.2 Lineament Category (Length and Direction) and No of Lineament

Lineament Category (Length)	No of Lineament	Lineament Category (Direction)	No of Lineament
Minor (<5km)	281	South - North	24
Medium (5-15km)	7	SW – NE	61
Major (>15km)	3	SE - NW	206

5.8.3.1 Lineament Density

Analysis of the lineament length density is useful guide for interpreting the lineament map. Calculating lengths of lineaments more accurately gives the image of lineament density, since the total length per unit area depends on the lines or segment of lines completely contained within the cell. This analysis is also known as “lineament-length density” (Greenbaum, 1985) and is defined as the total length of all recorded lineaments divided by the area under consideration. Lineament density is one of the important thematic maps prepared from the lineaments, which are critically used in groundwater studies related to hard rock terrain (Rao, 1992; Krishnamurthy et al, 1996; Rao et al, 2001). According to Edet et al, (1998) the zones of relatively high lineament density are identified as zones of high degree of rock fracturing, which are prerequisite for groundwater conduit development in an area. Presence of lineaments may act as a conduit for groundwater movement which results in increased secondary porosity and therefore, can serve as groundwater potential zone (Reddy et al. 2000). Lineament

density map is a measure of quantitative length of linear feature expressed in a grid. Lineament density of an area indirectly reveals the groundwater potential of that area since the presence of lineaments usually denotes a permeable zone. Areas with higher lineament density are good for groundwater development. The lineament density maps are very important in groundwater exploration especially in areas underlain by basement rocks and other hard rocks. High lineament density areas usually imply areas with high fracture density. Many researcher (Bala, 2001; Bassey et al, 1999; Drahovzal et al, 1973; Edet et al, 1994; Gelnnett and Gardner, 1979; Larsson, 1968; Moore and Hinkle, 1977; Odeyemi et al, 1985; Woodruff et al, 1974), have shown that groundwater accumulation and water well production or yields increase with increasing lineament density. As a result, areas having high lineament density represent areas with relatively high groundwater potentials. Therefore groundwater exploration in the study area should be concentrated on areas with high lineament density.

Based on the length of lineaments, a lineament density map was prepared. The lineament density map was generated in Arc GIS 9.3.1 software using Kriging method (ESRI, 2001), a lineament density map have been prepared. The lineament density zone was classified into five classes which are very high density lineament zone (4.57 to 5.72 km per sq km), high density lineament zone (3.43 to 4.57 km per sq km), moderate density lineament zone (2.28 to 3.43 km per sq km) and low density lineament zone (1.14 to 2.28 km per sq km), very low density lineament zone(0.0 to 1.14km per sq km) (Fig.5.19). The very low density lineament occupied 836.85 sq.km areas, the low density lineament

Tittur Basin Lineament Density Map

Legend

km / sq. km

Fig. 5.19 Lineament Density Map of the Tittur Basin

occupied 105.89 sq.km areas, the moderate density lineament occupied 22.27 sq km, the high density lineament occupied 4.43 sq.km areas and the very high density lineament occupied 0.66 sq.km areas. The very high density lineament zone occupied as patches throughout the study area, the other lineament density zone are well distributed throughout the study area.

5.8.3.2 Lineament Intersection

The lineament intersection map provides interpretation of hidden subsurface tectonic configuration in the form of linear feature intersection / cross cutting geological structures, which are indicators of deep seated fracture / fault medium (Mogaji et al, 2011). The lineament intersections are plotted as points and a high density of points corresponds to a more fractured zone (Singhal and Gupta, 1999). The zones of high lineament intersection over the study area are feasible zones for groundwater targeting in the study area. There are some springs occurred on lineament intersection zone in the study area.

The total numbers of lineaments intersected in square kilometer area is Digitize in the respective grid center for generating contour map (Fig. 5.20). The lineament intersection in the study area varied from 7 to nil. Lineament intersections classified in to three classes as; high lineament intersection zone(4 to 7 per sq km), medium lineament intersection zone (2 to 4 per sq km) and low lineament intersection zone (0 To 2 sq km) using the Kriging method in ArcGIS 9.3.1 software, a lineament intersection density map have been prepared. The high and medium lineament intersection zones are distributed as patches in the study area.

Fig. 5.20 Lineament Intersection Density Map of the Tittur Basin

5.8.3.3 Orientation Analysis

The rose diagram (Fig. 5.21) shows the directional frequency of the mapped lineaments over the area of study. It was interpreted as a statistical means of representing the anisotropy of the fractured environment, as well as fissure development tendency on a regional scale. The rose diagram of the detected lineaments show three prominent trends in the directions of the S-N, SW-NE and SE - NW axes, which are also the principal directions of the regional structures in basement complexes.

Orientation of the lineaments is usually analyzed by rose diagrams in all applications in the literature. These diagrams display frequency of lineaments for regular intervals. The diagram is prepared by counting each lineament as an element regardless of its length. Therefore, the resultant diagram is not length-weighted. The rose diagram indicates that the most dominant lineament direction is SE - NW.

The two prominent lineament trends (SE-NW and S-N) are correlated with high density variation zones of the study area. This can be an indication of the directions of groundwater movement in the studied area. The research findings of Owoade and Moffat (1989) in determining the groundwater prospects corroborate the above hydrogeological deduction which emphasized that groundwater movement and its accumulation always explored the fissures / fractural / weathered column of the basement rocks. Therefore, the fracture anisotropy of the detected lineaments trends presented in (Fig. 5.21) can be investigated for groundwater potential of the study area.

Fig. 5.21 Rose Diagram

5.9 Identification of Groundwater Potential Zone using Geoinformatics

The occurrence of groundwater at any place on the earth is not a matter of chance but a consequence of the interaction of the climatic, geological, hydrological, physiographical and ecological factors. Groundwater exploration operation is essentially a hydrogeological and geophysical inference operation and is dependent on the correct interpretation of the hydrological indicators and evidences (Ravindran et al, 2012). The movement of groundwater is controlled mainly by porosity and permeability of the surface and underlying lithology. The same lithology forming different geomorphic units will have variable porosity and permeability thereby causing changes in the potential of groundwater. This is also true for same geomorphic units with variable lithology. The surface hydrological features like topography, geomorphology, drainage, surface water bodies, etc. play important role in groundwater replenishment. High relief and steep slopes impart higher runoff, while the topographical depressions help in an increased infiltration. An area of high drainage density also increases surface runoff compared to a low drainage density area. Surface water bodies like rivers, ponds, etc. can act as a recharge zones enhancing the groundwater potential in the vicinity. Hence, identification and quantization of these features are important in generating groundwater potential model of a particular area (Jensen, 1986).

A Geoinformatics can be used effectively for this purpose to combine different hydrogeological themes objectively and analyze those systematically for demarcating the potential zone. Chi and Lee (1994) and Krishnamurthy et al. (1996) successfully used remote sensing and GIS in a diverse geological setup for the demarcation of groundwater potential zones in Kochang, Korea, and Marudaiyar river basin,

Tamilnadu, India, respectively. Geoinformatics technology, with its advantages of spatial, spectral and temporal availability of data covering large and inaccessible areas within a short time, has emerged as a very useful tool for the assessment, monitoring and management of groundwater resources (Jha et al., 2007). The hydrogeologic interpretation of satellite data has been shown to be a valuable survey tool in areas of the world where little geologic and cartographic information exists or is not accurate, as well as in inaccessible regions of the world (Engman and Gurney, 1991). As remote sensors cannot detect groundwater directly, the presence of groundwater is inferred from different surface features derived from satellite imagery such as geology, landforms, soils, land use/ land cover, surface water bodies, etc., which act as indicators of groundwater existence (Todd, 1980; Jha and Peiffer, 2006). Moreover, Geoinformatics have emerged as powerful tools for handling spatial data and decision making in several areas including engineering and environmental fields (Stafford, 1991; Goodchild, 1993). Since the delineation of groundwater prospect zones and groundwater modeling involve a large volume of multidisciplinary data, an integrated application of Geoinformatics techniques has become a valuable tool.

In the past, several researchers have used Geoinformatics techniques for the delineation of groundwater potential zone with successful results (Krishnamurthy et al., 2000; Shahid et al., 2000; Khan and Moharana, 2002; Jaiswal et al., 2003; Rao and Jugran, 2003; Sikdar et al., 2004; Sener et al., 2005; RaviShankar and Mohan, 2006; Solomon and Quiel, 2006). In these studies, the commonly used thematic layers are lithology, geomorphology, drainage pattern, lineament density, soil and topographic slope. On the other hand, some researchers have integrated Geoinformatics techniques to delineate groundwater potential zone

(Sreedevi et al., 2001; Shahid and Nath, 2002; Hadithi et al., 2003; Rao, 2003; Sreedevi et al., 2005; Israil et al., 2006; Srivastava and Bhattacharya, 2006). All the studies have been carried out in India; the majority of which focus on hard-rock terrains. The details about the applications of Geoinformatics technology in groundwater hydrology, including groundwater prospecting, can be found in the type and number of themes used for the assessment of groundwater resources by Geoinformatics techniques varies considerably from one study to another. In most studies, local experience has been used for assigning weights to different thematic layers and their features. Only (Shahid and Nath, 2002) used Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) for normalizing the assigned weights.

Remote sensing is an excellent tool for hydrologists and geologists in understanding the “perplexing” problems of groundwater exploration. In recent years, Satellite remote sensing data has been widely used in locating groundwater potential zones (Srivastav and Bhattacharya, 2000; Manimaran, 2012). Satellite remote sensing data is not only cost-effective, reliable and timely but also meets the essential requirements of data in the geographical Information System (GIS) domain, which are “current, sufficiently accurate, comprehensive and available to a uniform standard” (Phukan, 1999). Integration of the information on the controlling parameters is best achieved through GIS which is an effective tool for storage, management and retrieval of spatial and non-spatial data as well as for integration and analysis of this information for meaningful solutions. The technique of integration of remote sensing and GIS has proved to be extremely useful for groundwater studies (Saraf and Choudhary, 1998; Sankar, 2002).

Satellite remote sensing provides an opportunity for better observation and more systematic analysis of various geomorphic units, landforms, lineaments due to the synoptic and multi-spectral coverage of a terrain. Investigation of remotely sensed data for drainage map, geological, geomorphological and lineament characteristics of terrain in an integrated way facilitates effective evaluation of ground water potential zones. Similar attempts have been made in the generation of different thematic maps for the delineation of groundwater potential zones in different parts of the country (Reddy, 2000). Analysis of remotely sensed data along with Survey of India Topographical and collateral information with necessary ground check helps in generating the base line information for ground water targeting.

Integrated remote sensing and GIS can provide the appropriate platform for convergent analysis of diverse data sets for decision making in groundwater resource mapping and planning. This work aims to develop and apply integrated methods combining the information obtained by analyzing multi-source remotely sensed data in a GIS environment for better understanding the groundwater resource of the Tittur basin.

5.9.1 Material and Methods for Identification of Groundwater Potential Zone using Geoinformatics

Data Collection: The Landsat TM data (Path-146/ Row-046 and Path-147/ Row-046), ASTER and GEO EYE Satellite image and ASTER (30 m DEM) have been used in the present study. Survey of India (SOI) Toposheet (No. 46 L/15, 46 P/2, 46 P/3, 46 P/6 and 46 P/7) at 1:50,000 scales have also been used. Secondary data on hydrology and ground

water well data have been collected from Central Ground Water Board, Nagpur and from the field to support mapping. Geographic Information System and Image Processing (ARC GIS 9.3.1, ARC INFO environment and ERDAS IMAGINE 2011 software) have been used for analysis and mapping of the individual layers as described in the flow chart (fig 5.22).

5.9.2 Integration of remote sensing and GIS modeling for groundwater potential zone mapping

The groundwater potential zones were obtained by overlaying all the thematic maps in terms of weighted overlay methods using the spatial analysis tool in ArcGIS 9.3.1. During the weighted overlay analysis, the ranking has been given for each individual parameter of each thematic map and the weightage were assigned according to the influence of the different parameters and was presented in Table 5.2 These weightage have been taken considering the works carried out by researchers such as Srinivasa & Jugran (2003), Krishnamurthy et al. (1996), Saraf & Choudhary (1998). All the thematic maps were converted into grid (raster format) and superimposed by weighted overlay method (rank and weightage wise thematic maps and integrated with one another through GIS (Arc / Info grid environment). As per this analysis, the total weights of the final integrated grids were derived as sum of the weights assigned to the different layers based on suitability (Environment System Research Institute Inc.'s ArcView GIS Software, 1997). The full potential of remote sensing and GIS can be utilized when an integrated approach is adopted. Integration of the two technologies has proven to be an efficient tool in groundwater studies (Krishnamurthy et al., 1996). In models derived through integration of various thematic maps using a GIS approach,

several parameters are commonly involved to assess groundwater potential in the study area Fig. 5.22. The modeling involves delineation of zones of varying groundwater potential based on integration of Eight thematic maps in a raster based GIS. The Eight parameters considered are: Hydrological soil Group, Runoff Zone, Geomorphology, Geology, Slope, Land use/ Land Cover, Lineament Density and Drainage Density. Every class in the thematic layers was placed into one of the following categories viz. (i) Very Good (ii) Good (iii) Moderate (iv) Poor (v) very poor, depending on their level of groundwater potential. Considering their behavior with respect to groundwater control, the different classes were given suitable values, according to their importance relative to other classes in the same thematic layer. The spatial distribution of the various zones of groundwater potential obtained from the model generally shows regional patterns related to lithology, soils, drainage, geomorphology, Lineament and Land use patterns.

Table 5.3a Thematic layers, their categories and weights

Thematic Layers	Categories	Weight
Geology	Alluvium and Colluvium	5
	Basalt	2
Hydrological soil Group	A	5
	B	4
	C	3
	D	1
Slope	0° – 1°	5
	1° – 7°	4
	7° – 14°	3
	14° – 22°	1
	22° – 29°	1
	More than 29°	1
Geomorphology	Escarpment	1
	Pediment	3
	Pedeplain	5
	Denudational Hill	3
	Dissected plateau	3
	Monadnock /Residual Hills	1
	Ridge	2
	Alluvial Plain	5
	Valley Fills	5
	Floodplain	5
	Palaeochannel	5
	Talus	3

Table 5.3b Thematic layers, their categories and weights

Thematic Layers	Categories	Weight
Lineament Density	Very High	5
	High	4
	Moderate	3
	Low	2
	Very Low	1
Land use	Agriculture	5
	Forest	4
	Bare land	1
	Settlement	1
	Water Bodies	5
Drainage Density	Very low	5
	Low	4
	Moderate	3
	High	2
	Very high	1
Runoff Zone	Very low	5
	Low	4
	Moderate	3
	High	2
	Very high	1

Fig. 5.22 Flowchart for groundwater potential zone using Geoinformatics techniques

Fig. 5.23 Groundwater Potential Zone of the Tittur Basin

5.9.3 Groundwater Potential Zones

By integration of all the maps (Hydrological soil Group, Runoff Zone, Geomorphology, Geology, Slope, Land use/ Land Cover, Lineament Density and Drainage Density), groundwater potential zones were delineated and classified as: very high potential, high potential, moderate potential, low potential and very low potential (Table 5.4) . Only 28.86 % (279.81 km²) of the study area was classified as having very high potential at southeast, southwest and central regions, 19.44 % (188.66 km²) was of high potential at northeast, western and central regions of the Tittur basin and 21.81 % (211.60 km²) was classified as having moderate potential (Table 5.4). Hence, a total of 29.89 % of the area (290.03 km²) can be classified as Low to very Low potential. Very high groundwater potential zones cover an area of only 279.81 km², where nearly Alluvium plain, very near distance to drainage channel, very near distance to lineament and Lineament intersection zone , very shallow water table levels (< 3 m), very deep weathered zone thickness (>10 m) and very high well yields have been present in alluvium zones. High groundwater potential zones cover an area of 188.66 km², where very gentle to gentle slopes, near distance to drainage channel, near distance to lineament, deep weathered zone thickness (6–8 m), high well yields and shallow water table levels (4–6 m) have been present in alluvium to moderately weathered pediplains. Moderate groundwater potential zones cover an area of 211.60 km², where very gentle to gentle slopes, near to moderately far distance to drainage, lineament, and moderate to deep weathered zone thickness. Low groundwater potential zones cover an area of 160.53 km² where moderate to steep slope, extremely far to farthest distances to drainage, lineament, deep to very deep water table levels, shallow to very shallow weathered zone thickness, and low to very

low well yields are present as pockets spread over the whole study area. Very low groundwater potential zones are present in the central part of the study area and comprise an area of 129.50 km² where mostly area occupy rocky surface. The flat surfaces are observed in pediplain and valley fill units having high density of dug wells. The lineaments are acting as pathways of groundwater movement. As a result, the groundwater level is increasing considerably during monsoon period. From the study it is concluded that nearly level, very gentle slopes are better than the much steeper hilly areas from the groundwater point of view. The hydrogeomorphological units such as flood plain, valley fill and deeply buried pediplain are prospective zones for groundwater exploration and development in the study area. Presence of faults and lineaments in the area enhance the potential of these units. Groundwater potential map clearly indicate that alluvial plain which is composed of sand, silt and clay with nearly level slope and very low drainage density has excellent potentiality. Piedmont plain with gentle slope and low drainage density poses High to very High potential while in some area Structural hills and linear ridges with steep slope and high drainage density but due to presence of high lineament density offer High to very high potential. Residual hills and parts of structural hills with low lineament density, very steep slope and very high drainage density lie in very Low potential zones. Thus the generated groundwater potential map serves as a base line for future exploration in the Tittur basin.

Table 5.4 Groundwater Potential Zone of Tittur Basin

Groundwater Potential Zone	Area in sq km	Area in %
Very Low	129.50	13.35
Low	160.53	16.54
Moderate	211.60	21.81
High	188.66	19.44
Very High	279.81	28.86

5.9.3 Conclusion

In the present study, multi-criteria evaluation technique using raster based GIS analysis is attempted to delineate the groundwater potential zones. Remote sensing and GIS have proved as vital tools in delineating groundwater potential zones based on the integration of various thematic maps. Occurrence of groundwater has a direct relationship with the geomorphology, Runoff Zone and slope of the area. In hard rock area potentiality for groundwater occurrence is influenced by the presence of lineaments. Study area is dominated by weathered basalt Geo material with nearly level slope. Consequently about 21.81 percent area has Moderate Potential and 48.30 percent area has very High to High potential for groundwater occurrence. Residual hills, structural hills and ridges with steep slope and high drainage density have either very Low to Low groundwater potential which is influenced by the presence of lineaments.

Overall, the results of this study demonstrated that the Geoinformatics technology is a powerful tool for assessing groundwater potential zone, based on which suitable locations for groundwater withdrawals could be identified. Consideration of an adequate number of

thematic layers and proper assignment of weights are keys to the success of Geoinformatics techniques in identifying groundwater prospects. Based on the results of this study, concerned decision makers can formulate an efficient groundwater utilization plan for the study area so as to ensure long-term sustainability of this vital resource.

CHAPTER VI

HYDROGEOMORPHIC PROBLEMS OF THE BASIN

6.1 Introduction

6.2 Problem of Exploitation of High Yielding Wells and Tube wells

6.3 Problem Related to Deforestation & Removal of Vegetative Cover

6.4 Growth of Impervious Surfaces

6.5 Problem of High Water Table in Rainy Seasons

6.6 Channel Morphological Constraints

6.7 Quarrying and Dumping of Excavated Material

6.8 Problem due to change in Land surface temperature

CHAPTER VI

HYDROGEOMORPHIC PROBLEMS OF THE BASIN

6.1 Introduction

Drainage basin forms an essential element in man's use of the environment, and man's way of life may be geared to use the river water for drinking, domestic, fishing, navigation or as a means of waste disposal (Cooke and Doornkamp, 1974). Man is the most effective agents of change in a watershed (Morisawa, 1985). Drainage basins are thought to be a dynamic system, in which hydrological and geomorphological processes are governed not only by external factors such as evaporation, amount of rain falling in a drainage basin, but also by anthropogenic and anthrop geomorphic factors such as alterations in the channel system, hill side slopes, land reclamation and land use changes etc.

Any interference by man in a drainage basin, whether it is deliberate or accidental, can set sequence of events that may extend throughout the basin (Ruhe, 1971). For example, straightening of a channel leads to channel deepening and widening, large urbanization over agricultural land leads to high sediment yield further down valley, decrease in infiltration, lowering of groundwater level etc.

These factors all together are responsible for the change in the natural behavior of hydrological and geomorphological member parameters of a drainage basin system (Hart, 1986). The hydrology and geomorphology of the Tittur Basin have been altered dramatically in many ways throughout the system, through combined effects of four

laning of National Highway No. 211, increase in small scale and medium scale industries, heavy pumping of wells and land use changes.

Present chapter discusses some of the anthrop geomorphic factors that have created hydrogeomorphic problems in the Tittur Basin. Results obtained from morphometric analysis, basin hydrology, occurrence and movement of groundwater, knowledge of various landforms identified in the Tittur Basin have been considered to identify hydrogeomorphic problems of the basin. Each of this has led to significant impact on the occurrence, movement, distribution of surface as well as subsurface water in the Tittur Basin.

6.2 Problem of Exploitation of High Yielding Wells and Tube wells

Through human interaction, groundwater is subject to artificial discharge that is the process of pumping of groundwater from an aquifer to satisfy a socioeconomic need. In some instance, groundwater is subject to artificial recharge by way of various recharge method like construction of large size tank in the agriculture field, percolation tank along the stream. Excessive pumping can lead to groundwater depletion where in groundwater is extracted to rate faster than the rate of replenishment. The impacts of groundwater depletion are many and varied. The first and most direct impact is the loss of base flow. Shallow groundwater flow nearly horizontally, in the direction of the closest depression crust usually towards a stream or river draining a valley. An initially influent (gaining) stream becomes partially effluent (losing) towards the pumping well, reducing its base flow.

In the study area such type of overexploitation of groundwater occurs in the zone of moderate to good potential in which the rate of extraction is greater. Especially the wells located in Chalisgaon, Saigavan, Nagad, Nagardeola, Lohatar villages have been heavily pumped for agricultural needs. The groundwater levels in this zone decreases considerably during March, April and May. The wells which are adjacent to and or upstream to the heavily pumped wells result drastic lowering of water table due to decrease in hydraulic head underground. Such type of depletion has significant effects surface and unsaturated subsurface (vadose) waters, and on the terrestrial, and other ecosystems which depend on groundwater.

Over-exploitation of aquifers is a common occurrence especially when the abstracted water is used for irrigation. Submersible pumps in deep tube wells are capable of drawing substantial quantities of water from aquifers; the Quantity of water withdrawn may be far greater than there charge. Over-exploitation may continue for a number of years without serious consequences but eventually the yield of the tube wells is likely to show as ever decline. Originally, dug wells were used, with the water with-drawn using animal power, but once deep tube wells were drilled, the yield increased significantly and the area of irrigated crops also increased .However, this resulted in a decline in both the piezometric heads and the water table. The decline in the former became so severe that a number of the earlier tube wells were abandoned. Furthermore, there is a serious concern about the continuing fall in the water table. The heavy pumping of the deeper aquifers causes water to be drawn vertically through the less permeable zones.

6.3 Problem Related to Deforestation & Removal of Vegetative Cover

Deforestation, clearance or clearing is the removal of a forest or stand of trees where the land is thereafter converted to a non-forest use. Vegetation cover is perhaps the greatest deterrent to soil erosion. It tends to protect the surface from raindrop impact, reduces the amount of water available for runoff by consuming it and by improving infiltration capacity, and decreases the velocity of runoff (Cooke and Doornkamp, 1974). Deforestation, understood as the net conversion from forest to non-forest land cover. The removal of trees and other vegetation leads to a decrease in transpiration and interception and a lessening of infiltration, and hence increase in surface runoff, high sediment yield in downstream reaches causing aggradations of channel. It is generally believed that in a forest, the ground is protectable against splash erosion during intensive rainfall. The protective value of trees is rather related to development of a porous, well structured, litter layer which favors infiltration and percolation of water to sub surface layers.

The water cycle is also affected by deforestation. Trees extract groundwater through their roots and release it into the atmosphere. When part of a forest is removed, the trees no longer transpire this water, resulting in a much drier climate. Deforestation reduces the content of water in the soil and groundwater as well as atmospheric moisture. The dry soil leads to lower water intake for the trees to extract. Deforestation reduces soil cohesion, so that erosion, flooding and landslides ensue (Daniel, 1999). Due to Deforestation, the presence or absence of trees can change the quantity of water on the surface, in the soil or groundwater, or in the atmosphere. This in turn changes erosion rates and the availability of water for either ecosystem functions or human services. The forest may have little impact on flooding in the case of large rainfall events,

which overwhelm the storage capacity of forest soil if the soils are at or close to saturation.

Deforestation generally increases rates of soil erosion, by increasing the amount of runoff and reducing the protection of the soil from tree litter. This can be an advantage in excessively leached tropical rain forest soils. Forestry operations themselves also increase erosion through the development of roads and the use of mechanized equipment. Forest cover observed in the study area has been cut at unprecedented rates by farmers, ranchers, and by fuel wood collectors. Particularly in the southern part of the basin, deforestation has intensified soil erosion, removal of thin soil cover along the slopes. Along the Saigavan, Vadgaon, Bahadarpur and Haraswadi, due to absence of vegetative cover and forest cover, bare slopes have been heavily denuded by the erosional and denudational agents. Presence of large fragmented boulders and rock fragments along the steep slopes as well as at the foot hills clearly indicates the intensive erosion of structural hills by the intense rainfall during monsoon. As explained earlier in fifth chapter, that structural hills and steep escarpments observed along the southern side of the Tittur Basin has poor groundwater potential as compare to alluvial plains and valley fills. Area occupied by the structural hills in the study area is devoid of vegetation and forest cover along the northern slopes. Therefore wherever the forest cover has been removed completely or in part, in the Tittur Basin are hydrogeomorphologically not significant from the groundwater exploration point of view. Absence of vegetative cover has also similar impact on the water bearing of the landform unit. Pediment and pedepain unit possesses sparse to very sparse vegetation in their upslope region. This intensifies the rill erosion over the pediment and pedepain surface. Rill erosion in turn accelerates evaporation of sub

surface soil moisture from the steep banks the gullies causing lowering of groundwater table along these gullies.

Study of the production, transport, and storage of surficial sediment in drainage basins is essential for understanding their evolution and geomorphic behavior. Fluvial regimes are intimately related to hillslope sediment delivery and storage systems (Dietrich and Dunne, 1978). Extensive precipitation patterns result in a dynamic geomorphic system characterized by seasonal flooding, slope failure, and debris flow activity. As such, forested area in Tittur drainage basins export sediment by colluvial and alluvial processes in high-gradient channel systems. Understanding the controls for routing and storage of sediments in this region are a critical component of habitat management plans.

6.4 Growth of Impervious Surfaces

Impervious surfaces are mainly constructed surfaces rooftops, sidewalks, roads, and parking lots covered by impenetrable materials such as asphalt, concrete and stone. These materials effectively seal surfaces, repel water and prevent precipitation to infiltrating soils. Surfaces covered by such materials are hydrologically active, meaning they generate surface runoff. According to Novotny and Chesters (1981), impervious surfaces are nearly 100 percent hydrologically active, and high percentages of such surfaces occur within urbanized areas containing commercial, industrial, transportation, and medium to high density residential land uses. Other impervious, hydrologically active surfaces include compacted soils, high clay content soils, frozen soils, saturated soils, and soils with high groundwater tables (Novotny and Chesters, 1981). With the last three, imperviousness and hydrological activity is usually seasonal or

temporary, in marked contrast to urbanized areas, which are permanently impervious and hydrologically active.

Paving watershed areas with asphalt and concrete makes these surfaces “desert like” in terms of hydrology and climate. Storm water washes over paved, sparsely vegetated urban surfaces in much the same manner as it does over a desert landscape. Intense storms over urban and desert areas can quickly generate large volumes of runoff, even flash floods, followed by relatively dry conditions a short time later (Christopherson, 2001). Rapid runoff and the paucity of vegetation over these surfaces also reduce the amount of water available for evapotranspiration. Therefore, much of the incoming solar energy that could have been utilized to evaporate water is instead transformed into sensible heat. This effectively raises the temperatures of these surfaces and of the overlying atmosphere. Moreover, impervious urban surfaces behave like rocky desert surfaces in that they tend to have high thermal conductivities and heat storage capacities in comparison to vegetated, pervious surfaces (Douglas, 1983; Christopherson, 2001). The differences in the thermal characteristics of surface materials that overlie urban areas versus those that overlie natural pervious areas have profound implications not only for microclimates, but also for stream and watershed health. From a hydrological perspective, the impervious areas of a watershed can be differentiated between total impervious area and effective impervious area. The former refers to all areas within a watershed that are “covered by constructed, non-infiltrating surfaces,” whereas the latter is “impervious surfaces with direct hydraulic connection to the downstream drainage (or stream) system” (Booth and Jackson, 1997).

Under natural conditions a part of the water from rainfall infiltrates into the soil, either finding its way to groundwater storage or reappearing as springs that feed the natural drainage system. The amount of rainfall that does not enter the soil by infiltration becomes surface runoff. Obviously, the amount of runoff varies with the permeability of the surface. If a previously permeable soil is covered with an impermeable surface, the amount of water from rainfall which had previously infiltrated into the soil thereafter becomes surface runoff.

Concentration of population and commercial activities in a watershed considerably alters the land from natural state of pervious surfaces to artificial impervious surfaces (Carter, 1961). Impervious surfaces create and aggravate surface drainage problems, speeds up the water flow and maximize runoff volumes, Construction of impervious surfaces also interferes with the recharge of groundwater supplies. As man changes an area of watershed from a natural state to a more artificial state, the buildings streets, paving's, constructs cover land, waterproofing the soil where water once percolated in to the soil (Leopold, 1968).The continuous growth of population, small scale industries, commercial complexes, highway resorts and motels in the Tittur valley plain in recent years has created complex physical problems in watershed hydrology and hydraulics. The permeable soils have become waterproofed so greatly that local water table have been reduced through lack of infiltration and increased runoff in lower order streams (IVth and Vth order streams) than in higher order streams (1st and IInd order tributaries).

Most prominent impervious surfaces in the Tittur valley are located along the Dhule Solapur National Highway No 211. Construction of road side hotels, motels, resorts, petrol pumps, parking lots, non residential and commercial complexes in Chalisgaon and near city area has been

largely converted into paved surfaces by cement concrete, interlocking concrete blocks, and concrete platforms. Along the Ranjangaon, Bodhra patch of the national highway, Central Broad gauge Railway, Dhule Broad gauge Railway line, numerous small scale industries, many Petroleum and many other commercial and non commercial complexes have converted large natural surface into concrete paved surface. Some of these firms have also modified the natural behavior of streams flowing across their premises by reducing channel size in to small rivulet, and or by diverting the channel from its natural flow direction.

In the villages, Nagardeola, Kajgaon, Patonda, Hirapur most of land has been converted into impervious surfaces for various commercial and non agricultural economic activities. Because of impervious surfaces the rain water is directly contributed as surface runoff thereby increasing peak flows in downstream channel, and is also responsible for decreased infiltration, blockage of natural surface flow in natural direction of slope.

6.5 Problem of High Water Table in Rainy Seasons

Seasonal high water table may occur as a result of internal soil characteristics or it may occur due to local Conditions of impeded horizontal drainage. Temporary high water tables are due to internal conditions within the soils themselves. Usually as layer is impermeable or slowly permeable Water or of shallow depth of soil over the impermeable rock. Where such layer occurs within less than 2-3 feet of the surface, a high water table can develop and persist during rainy season (Leopold, 1968). A water table at or near the soil surface creates conditions for the pollution of both groundwater and surface water from any contaminant located in or the soil. In rural environment, the most probable occurrence

of contamination is from cow-dung composting pits. These pits themselves often will be under water with such conditions.

In the Tittur valley, problem of high water table is noted during the months of July to September that is in monsoon season. It is highly localized phenomenon especially observed in lowland or in valley flats where hydraulic gradient as well as surface gradient is very low. Middle reaches of the Tittur Basin are more prone high water table phenomenon in July-August as a result of high rainfall, compaction of black cotton soil (2 to 3 feet thickness) present over the impervious hard and massive bsalt rock. Field survey carried out during July, August months reveals that Ner, Vaghali, Ghusardi, and valley flats of Nachankhada and Sangameshwar villages are more prone to high water table conditions. Prevalence of this situation causes swelling, lithification, of black cotton soil ultimately results in water logging situation in low lying valley fiats of the Tittur basin.

6.6 Channel Morphological Constraints

The channel pattern of Tittur River is showing the changes from wide and shallow meandering bed rock channel in the upper reaches to narrow, deep but horizontal bedded channel in downstream direction, specifically downstream to Belwadi and further downstream up to Ghusardi. The sinuosity of the Tittur River channel varies from 1.05 to 1.31 with increase in sinuosity in the middle reaches that is an indicative of sinuous shape of the channel. This implies that sinuous channels in the middle reaches contribute water to aquifers adjacent to the channel only during peak flows. Consequently during low flows the base low contribution also gets minimized due to low recharge during peak flows.

Tittur River basin is prone to erosion and sediment generation in its upper reaches only during monsoon season: Especially 1st order tributaries flowing across steep slopes and hills are more susceptible to erosion. Weathered rock fragments, loose soil along the steep slopes is removed by first rain of the season resulting quite high amount of Sediment supply to downstream reaches of Valjhari and Gadad sub basins, load is further added from middle stream region due to soil pipes of agricultural fields. Increase in wash load and reduction in stream power is responsible for deposition of sediment within channel in the middle stream region (Ghusardi, Sangameshwar, Nachankhada-Main Stream., Ner, Vaghali Stream)making the channel shallower and prone to avulsion and flooding.

6.7 Quarrying and Dumping of Excavated Material

Excavation of hard massive rock for various construction purposes is a major economic activity in hard rock terrain. Quarrying and excavation of rock results in the removal of large volume of parent rock along the hill slopes and from barren surface. In the Tittur, quarries are located along the hill slopes of Bodhra, and Vadala villages. Numerous springs have emerged due to this vertical cutting of rock. This influences indirectly to the subsurface supply of water to downstream reach the foot hill area of pedepain present along these quarries.

Construction of national highway, major Roads and Central Railway Line has also influenced surface and subsurface flow of water. Approximately 4 to 5 feet deep and 50 feet wide linear trenching along the highway was carried out to have better foundation for the highway. This excavated linear trench was then filled with rubble and dabber

(crushed fragments of rock) and further by concrete material. Hydro compaction to this filled material was done in order to have asphaltting over it.

Approximately 5 to 6 feet deep and 50 feet wide and 23.48 km length of compact foundation of national highway running north to south and 51.21 km Central Railway Line has significantly modified the surface and subsurface flow regimes of the Tittur valley, particularly, the surface and subsurface flow of water from northern slopes to valley flat present in the central part of the basin. National highway is acting as an artificial surface dyke to these flows causing the low recharge of wells located to east of highway and north of Railway line and downstream to the flowing reach.

Besides these hydrogeomorphic and anthropogenic problems, there are other common problems such as structural alterations that includes fragmentation of riverine morphology due to construction of roads, bridges, culverts and other barriers, sediment accumulation behind percolation tanks located at Shindol and Beldarwadi villages, degradation of water quality in the wells present along the channel., numerous screened and unscreened diversion of natural flow of tributaries which are flowing through agricultural fields and paddy fields that are not directly connecting to nearby river channels. Process alterations includes increased sedimentation from surrounding channel system to master stream system, alteration of natural hydrology below small check dams, K. T. weirs and percolation tanks due to storage, diversion and later the release of seasonal high flows.

Thus under natural conditions a river basin seeks to establish a morphology and hydraulics. However, man can easily upset the natural

equilibrium of the watershed by altering either the catchment surface or the river channel itself, by channeling, dredging or damming it. A man must understand the results of such alterations in collaboration with hydrogeomorphological principles governing the basin.

6.8 Problem due to change in Land surface temperature

The spatio- temporal Land surface temperature change detection in response to climatic change can be analyzed through hydrological regime in hydro-geomorphic physical entity like river basin, which could be affected by climatic variations in recent decades and may be resulted from the global warming (Bhamare and Agone, 2011). The hydrological regime covers the changing condition of water and sediment discharge positions in river channel as well as basin area. The prominent channel change is aggradations. Aggradations lead to the decreases of channel capacity causing high floods even in low to moderate rainfall. The basin also face the problems of depletion of water level in channel as well as water table and salinization of basin soil due to accelerated rate of evaporation with increase of the temperature This sort of change can be detected, monitored and predicted using GIS with renewed satellite information from remote sensing data (Bhamare and Agone, 2011).

The average annual summer temperature for previous 60 years (1950-2010) recorded data is 23.95 °C and average summer month Land surface temperatures for previous two decades (1990-2010) is 25.65 °C. The net rise of temperature is 1.6 °C in previous sixty years. However, in the previous two decades remote sensing data in summer reveals the rise in temperature by 2 °C (Bhamare and Agone, 2011). This rate is certainly accelerated during previous two decades. This fact is certainly attributed to the global warming (Bhamare and Agone, 2011). There are several

causes of global warming in Tittur Basin like deforestation, over exploitation of river and ground water, saline older alluvium aquifer characteristics and technogenic anthropogenesis. They all are responsible for increase in green house gases like CO₂, CFC, SO₂, NO₂ and various salt accumulations due to high rate of evaporation in the soil.

Considering dry summer months in which intensity of temperature is high and accumulated surface temperature responsible for accelerated rate of evaporation and transpiration. The water rises upward by osmotic pressure from beneath the water table and water table falls. The raised water evaporates out and leaving salt accumulation in the surface soils. The summer irrigated crops also aids in accumulation of salts from direct evaporation of water. This problem of salinization especially found in alluvial soils along the main River channel. The deep older alluvium aquifer along the Dungri river region is comparatively more saline. The saline soils absorb more heat than any other residual surface soils. This fact of Tittur basin is an added asset of the global warming. The major consequence of fall in water table and over exploitation of water for irrigation is drying up of Tittur river channel in summer. The consequent effect is the aggradations of channels and reduction of channel cross section area. This fact leads to increase in magnitude and frequency of floods in the Tittur basin. The spill over water during the peak flood stage of high magnitude flood on the both side banks of river for a considerable distance and rebound water during falling stage of flood bellow bank discharge stage responsible for accelerated gully erosion on both the banks of river Tittur. The tremendous soil loss is experienced during high magnitude floods.

CHAPTER VII

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

An attempt has been made in this thesis to present some general considerations governing the application of hydrogeomorphological analysis of the Tittur drainage basin in southern part of Tapi Basin, covered Jalgaon and Aurangabad district of Maharashtra.

7.1 Conclusion

The study is purely based on extensive field surveys, numerous seasonal and field observations of different parts of the basin. Basin morphometry has been obtained from topographical maps, Digital Elevation Model, Landsat and ASTER Satellite Imaginary whereas geological details of the area have been obtained from the previously published geological maps with the help of Landsat and ASTER Satellite Imaginary. Basin hydrological analysis has been carried out on the basis of climatological parameters such as rainfall, temperature and evaporation, evapotranspiration data. It is also supported by empirical formulae to estimate runoff, evaporation and net recharge of the Tittur Basin. Groundwater hydrology of the basin has been studied by using filed inventory data of open wells. Different parameters of the sample wells were considered to obtain the seasonal groundwater scenario of the basin. Apart from the field data and collected field information, the data and information was also obtained from various government offices and institutes.

GIS analysis of the Tittur drainage basin had given significant results about structural, denudational and depositional landforms that are

directly or indirectly controlling occurrence, movement and distribution of groundwater. Based on this, the Tittur Basin has been categorized in different groundwater potential zones; Hydrogeomorphic problems raised due to anthropogenic interference are the major obstacles in maintaining the natural hydrology and geomorphology of the basin. This concluding chapter gives precise summary of results obtained, and the conclusions drawn on the basis of morphometric, hydrological and GIS analysis.

The Tittur drainage basin is located in the rain shadow zone of Ajanta Satmala Range and extends between 20°16' 16.18 " north to 20°40' 13.27 " north latitude and 74° 52' 35.77 " east to 75° 17' 33.69 " east longitude. Tittur Basin has a perimeter of 184.89 km covering an area 970.10 sq. km and basin length is 58.25 Km.

Being the part of tropical monsoon type of climate in general and semiarid climate in particular, the area under study receives 707 mm average annual rainfall, 90 percent of which occurs during June to September. April-May are the hottest months with the monthly maximum temperature of 43.7°C to 45.1°C, and December- January are the coldest months with monthly minimum temperature of 9°C to 8.5°C. As the area under study experiences semiarid climate and hence, it shows sparse scanty natural vegetation relatively dense natural vegetation depending upon slope, soil cover, available groundwater for plant growth.

On the basis of landform assemblage, nature of its drainage, slope characters, erosional and depositional environment, three geomorphic zones are identified in the Tittur Basin viz. 1) Zone of High Relief, Deep dissection, 2) Zone of moderate relief and moderate slope, 3) Zone of alluvial plain, gentle slope. Geologically the basin has strong foundation of horizontally bedded basaltic lava flows (Aa flows, and Pahoehoe

flows), commonly referred as 'Deccan Traps', and exhibits the differential rate of weathering and erosion. Aa flows which are resistant to weathering occur near Kinhi, Saigavan hills. These lava flows are intruded by two prominent dykes trending North to South direction and can be traced for about 4.5 km distance. Red boles occurring at shallow depth (1m to 3m) acts as a good water bearing horizons while deep seated boles are generally hard, compact and impervious to groundwater. Red boles are observed along the foot hills in the southern part near Patna Devi, Dhaval Tirtha Waterfall and Autrom Ghat area and can be traced laterally for a considerable distance. A veneer of alluvium with thickness ranging from few meters to 8 meters is observed along the mainstream and on valley floors, particularly in the northern-central and southern part of the basin. Alluvium deposits are highly permeable zone that contributes water to partial recharge along the river bank side area and to the subsurface flow. Colluvium occurs along the foothills and at the base of escarpments in the Tittur river basin. Presence of less resistant mineral such as plagioclase in the basalt as well as semi arid climate appears to be factors responsible for physical and chemical weathering of parent rock which gives rise to thick colluvial deposits in the study area. The soil profiles developed in the Tittur Basin show considerable variation in the color, maturity and thickness. Highly immature, thin soil profiles have been observed on the moderately steep to steep slopes (10° to 29°). The degree of maturity of soil profile increases when the degree of slope becomes almost level (1° to 2°).

The land use pattern in the Tittur Basin roughly coincides with the physiography of the area. The central, Northern valley flat is almost occupied by agriculture and scanty natural vegetation. Ridges and hill tops covered with Gautala reserved forest consisting of tiny shrubs,

bushes, and trees as well as open scrub, stony waste, pasture land and barren land at some places. The built-up- area in the basin is located at Chalisgaon City area and along the national highway no. 211 at Ranjangaon, Bodhra village and along state highway no. 19 and 25 roads (Hirapur, Patonda, Kachgaon, Nagardeola Village). The population density of the Tittur Basin is 166 persons per sq. km which is - quiet high density of population.

It is evident from the drainage map that two main types of drainage patterns prevail in the Tittur Basin area viz, the dendritic and subdendritic. Ist and IInd order stream constitute almost 93.99 % of the total number of streams. The total length of all Ist and IInd order tributaries of the Tittur River constitutes about 73.28 % (1774.85 km) of the total stream length of all orders that is 2422.07 km. Horton's law of stream number Vs stream order is confirmed as the total number of streams and stream order in four sub basins forms an inverse geometric sequence by decreasing systematically with increasing order.

The average bifurcation ratio of the basin is 3.62, which indicates the general, absence of structural control on the development of the drainage. The greater length ratio of Ist order to IInd order than further higher order streams indicates higher permeability of the rock formation in the area drained by IInd order streams. 53.45 % of total length of all streams occupied by Ist order streams indicates strong resistance to the permeability, highly impermeable rock stratum in the source areas of all Ist order streams.

The Sinuosity Index (SI) for the Tittur River channel is 1.31. The sinuous channel are prone to valley bottom plain location or flood plains, indicating that it contributes more water to subsurface flow and

recharging the water table during peak flows. It can be said that the sinuosity of Tittur River is attributed to its hydraulic gradient and topography. Length of overland flow 200m reveals that the surface runoff quickly enters into 1st order streams. It also indicates that even moderate to low rainfall can generate a significant volume of surface runoff.

South to North stream orientation of all four sub basins indicates that geologically the basin has structural and dip direction of faults and lineaments in NE and NW direction.

Most of the drainage directions of the basin are oriented towards three major axes i. e. North (N), North-East (NE), North-West (NW). It is observed that basins more or less oriented towards S, SE and SW direction, indicating that geologically the basin has structural and dip direction of fault, escarpment, dykes and lineaments, in N,NE and NW direction.

Form factor value of the Tittur Basin is 0.28, indicating that it is elongated in shape, while circularity ratios of the Tittur Basin is 0.36 indicates that basin is not in a circular shape. Elongation ratio of the Tittur basin is 0.60, this fact indicate that, it is an elongated basin.

Greater stream frequency of Gadad sub basin as compare to other sub basin is responsible higher surface runoff as a result of low infiltration and less permeability of rocks, while the values of stream frequency obtained from the Tittur Basin is 2.95 streams per sq. km. The Tittur Basin has a drainage density of 2.40 km per sq. km. Pimpri sub basin has lowest drainage density of 1.94 km per sq. km, indicating higher rate of infiltration, greater subsurface flow, high moisture retentive capacity and relatively low relief. Dungri, Valjhari and Gadad sub basin

are having drainage density of 2.70, 2.33 and 2.80 km per sq. km indicates that these sub basin are dominated by erosion, comparable relief, low infiltration and higher surface runoff with decreased overland flow.

The value of constant channel maintenance of the Tittur Basin comes to 0.41 sq. km per km. it means that 0.41 sq km surface of the basin is required to maintain a stream length of 1 km. This can be attributed to higher surface runoff and low infiltration rate of the basin.

The mean area ratio of the basins is 4.19 this rule holds well in Tittur basins of the region. Law of Basin Area almost good in the case of Tittur drainage basin as the coefficient of correlation is 0.78 and percentage of variance explained is 53.66 %.But the fitted function show considerable underestimation in the case of basin area of 1st, 2nd and 7th order stream and an overestimation in case of 3rd, 4th, 5th and 6th stream order basin area.

The relief of 248.10 meter within a distance of 58.25 km clearly indicates higher amount of potential energy available for water to flow in downstream reaches with high velocity, low infiltration and flashy discharge at the basin outlet, low infiltration and flashy discharge at the basin outlet. Basins have ruggedness number of 22.26. It indicates gentle and short slopes. It also shows a subdued relief with moderately rugged to old stage of terrain development.

The values of Dissection index vary between '0' (complete absence of vertical dissection/erosion and hence dominance of flat surface) and '1' (in exceptional cases, vertical cliffs, it may be at vertical escarpment of hill slope or at seashore).Maximum dissection index is calculated as 0.27 in the southern and south east part of the watershed.

The slope map of the Tittur Basin reveals that maximum area of the basin i.e. 773.36 sq.km ,its cover 79.92 % to total lies under Level slope category of 0° to 1° . The pediment slope area i.e. above 1° to 7° covers 10.96% area. The Level and Pediment slope has a greater significance to enhance infiltration. The remaining 9.32 % areas which under lie's Moderate slope to escarpment are mostly runoff zone area; this area has not favorable for infiltration because in this area there is mostly first and second order stream with higher gradient. While the exponential function fitted to mean channel slope and stream order the Tittur drainage basin, reveals a perfect relationship as is evident from high coefficient of -0.83.

The longitudinal profile of the Tittur River exhibits overall concavity to the sky with gradually decreasing channel gradient downstream. This indicates the longer transfer of surface and groundwater along the channel in downstream direction. The profiles of the valley floor appear to be flat with graded valleys in their lower reaches. Thus, all the profiles of Tittur Basin indicate that upper and lower reaches of the basin are having moderate to steep sided valley walls, while the valley floors are quite flat. The valley cross profiles of the Tittur Basin reveals symmetrical valley form in upper reaches, indicates surface water takes characteristically less time for hydrological concentration of flow from both valley side slopes as compare to the asymmetric valley forms in downstream reaches of the basin.

The Hypsometric integral has been accepted as an important morphometric indicator of the stage of basin development. The Hypsometric integral of Tittur basin is 19 % indicating old stage of landscape development.

Hydrological analyses of the Tittur drainage basin reveals that it receives input in the form of rainfall and excess input flows through streams and main river channel and further flows out of the basin in the form of surface runoff. Average areal rainfall the basis of isohyetal method is 707.76 mm and on the basis of TRMM Satellite data is 831.2 mm. The orographic effect of the Ajanta Satmala hill range in the southern part is responsible for enhancing the spatial variation in monsoon rainfall. with the help of TRMM Satellite data demarcate five rainfall zone, viz Very Low Rainfall Zone occupy 162.85 sq km, Low Rainfall Zone occupy 239.33 sq km, Moderate Rainfall Zone covers 240.79 sq km, High Rainfall Zone covers 178.19 sq km and Very High Rainfall Zone occupy 148.94 sq km.

The runoff estimated by SCS CN method. Total available annual surface runoff in the Tittur Basin after evaporation, evapotranspiration, Soil moisture retention, Initial abstraction and infiltration loss comes around 6.85×10^8 cubic meters. The Average Annual runoff of Tittur basin if distributed over its area is 675.9 mm. which accounts for 65.30 % of the rainfall become runoff. The remaining 34.70 % of rainfall is lost by evaporation and percolation underground. Results obtained for four sub basin reveals that Valjhari sub basin generates 704.8 mm of surface runoff as compare to 664.1 mm of Gadad basin, 623.9 mm of Dungri and 627.8 mm of Pimpri basin Amongst hydrological abstractions, the infiltration losses are accounting for net recharge to groundwater in Tittur Basin.

Average daily pan evaporation for the entire Tittur Basin comes around 5.0 mm per day. Summer months are characterized by higher evaporation while monsoon month's shows drastic reduction in

evaporation and winter months (Nov, Dec, Jan) register a significant drop in evaporation.

Evapotranspiration estimate using Penman-Monteith Equation, it reveals that April and May months experience higher evapotranspiration losses because of high temperatures, dry air, and vegetation require more water for transpiration and negligible rainfall, drastic reduction of evapotranspiration during winter season (November to February). In the Tittur basin highest Potential evapotranspiration is in May it 195.9 mm and lowest Potential evapotranspiration is in August due to excess of soil moisture.

The determined values of the initial abstraction are close to the suggested the highest initial abstraction is 21 mm in the March month due to not sufficient rainfall for runoff in the Tittur basin. In the month June to October initial abstraction values are same due to Rainy season and wet soil. In the month of November to May total rainfall account to initial abstraction. While highest Soil moisture retention estimate in March that is 105 mm.

Total available annual infiltration in the Tittur Basin after evaporation, evapotranspiration, Soil moisture retention, Initial abstraction and surface runoff loss comes around 229.30 mm.

The time of concentration for the Tittur Basin after fulfilling the initial losses comes to 616.70 minutes (10 Hour 27 minutes). Larger travel time with respect to elevation as well as distance reveals that water takes larger path from its point of source to travel up to basin outlet in the case of southern divide location points as compare to northern divide location points though they are located farthest distance from basin outlet.

This indicates that rain occurring over this area has greater chance for infiltration by natural process.

The Tittur basin displays a more complex flow regime that is related to several factors. The discharge is exceptionally high during the monsoon i.e. July, August and September. This is the rainiest part of the year. June is also a month of heavy rains, but in this month evaporation is higher than the rest of the monsoon months. May and June, both record high temperature. Wind speed is also very high in the month of June. High velocity winds accelerate the rate of evaporation; consequently, the runoff is low in June, despite good rains. In the month of October, transpiration is more from plants besides a decrease in rainfall as a result of recession of the monsoons.

The water balance study shows that the water need (1066.1 mm) is higher than the water supply by precipitation (1035 mm), though an amount of 461.7 mm of water is recorded as rain-fall excess, on account of concentration of rainfall from June to October compared to the lower values of water need during these months. Water deficiency (SMD) obtained from the water balance studies indicates the amount of water (442 mm) needed for supplemental irrigations in agricultural operations, adjustment of crop calendar (so that harvest will precede drought) and crop rotation to improve the soil structure and increase the soil moisture storage capacity. Crop yields can increase if the moisture deficiency could be avoided. Water surplus is 286.2 and deficit is 442 mm, since annual water deficit is more than water surplus, Tittur basin is under drought.

Groundwater hydrological investigations in the Tittur Basin indicate presence of three different aquifers. Alluvial aquifers composed of coarse-grained silt and gravelly sand of alluvial and colluvial origin found along the river bank and foot hills respectively yields 20 to 50 cubic meters of water per day depending upon the recharge from the surrounding and adjacent materials permeability and porosity. The open wells located in alluvial aquifers discharges 20 m³ to 35m³ water per hour depending upon the capacity of well and drawdown of 1 to 2 m. Wells that are located close to or within the stream channel usually support high discharge. The groundwater from this aquifer is being extensively exploited and utilized for irrigation and domestic use.

Basaltic aquifers also called as weathered basaltic aquifers with dense, open vertical joint, and pattern forms good aquifer in the study area. Wells located in this aquifer zone yields 10 to 20 cubic meters of water per day. In basaltic aquifers, red bole at shallow depth acts as aquitard. Yield, drawdown and recuperation of wells in basaltic aquifer show wide range of variation on account of variations in fracture, porosity and permeability of rock. The basin as a whole shows three to four lithological units such as soil, weathered basalt, hard and jointed basalt, massive basalt, thickness of which depends upon the physiographic location. Wells situated along and near the river channel, foothill zone shows all (comprising mostly clay, silt sand), clayey and gravelly sand, weathered and jointed basalt with massive basalt at the base.

The characteristics of fracture zone aquifers make them an excellent source of groundwater in arid and semiarid environments. Fracture zone aquifers are located by seeking major faults. The evaluation of the groundwater potential of Tittur basin is to study the structures

displayed in satellite images to map the faults, fractures, and lineaments. Tittur basin located near foot hill zone of Ajanta Satmala Ranges, which is formed because of a major Fault activity within in Tapi basin. Several Fracture and lineament situated in the southern side of the Tittur basin. Wells located in fracture zone aquifers yields 10 to 25 cubic meters of water per day.

The well inventory reveals that average depth of open wells around 12 m (± 2 m) and the diameter of these wells is 6 m (± 1 m). The wells that are located in alluvial aquifers have larger diameter as compare to the wells in basaltic aquifer to store large volume of water for the extraction.

Analysis of groundwater table data reveals that Pimpri sub basin has greater groundwater potential because of natural recharge by all means of various natural sources such as precipitation, runoff. The wells from this basin on an average do not show much of water level fluctuation from May 2009 to November 2010. On the contrary, Gadad basin show greater water level variation as well as decreasing trend, indicating that this basin has very low potential of groundwater recharge. Valjhari basin wells shows increasing trend of groundwater level. In all four sub basins, hydraulic gradient is towards topographic lows. Direction of groundwater in the Tittur Basin is from topographic high to valley floor and ultimately towards the main river channel.

The average recuperation level of the Tittur basin comes to 0.70 m per hour the well that are located in alluvium aquifer have greater recuperation compare to the well in basaltic aquifers. Representative time-drawdown- recuperation curve for the open wells reveals that rate of recuperation (0.56 m/hour) is very slow against the drawdown (0.94 m/hour) of Chalisgaon and Lohatar wells. This can be attributed to the

location of the wells in alluvial aquifers hold the water in porous spaces of soil for longer duration. Greater recuperation rate of Bodhra and Neri wells as compare to Chalisgaon and Lohatar wells can be attributed to the higher degree weathering and fracturing of basalt rock beneath the surface is responsible for higher permeability for the higher recharge.

The groundwater contour map reveals that the Spacing of water table contours in the lower part of the basin becomes compact whereas sparse in the south west part of the basin. This unusual phenomenon of closely spaced contours is the indication of increase in hydraulic gradient. As a result, the subsurface flow of groundwater has greater speed as compare to the middle reaches of the basin which ultimately reduces groundwater recharge.

The analysis of groundwater water samples collected from open wells reveals that pH, electric conductance, hardness, chloride and sulphate, nitrate , quantity total dissolved solids are within the permissible limits indicates that salts like carbonates, bicarbonates, phosphates along with hydroxyl ion are in a free state which is not so hazardous to drinking purpose. Majority of the samples analyzed fall in the permissible range with the exception of doubtful to unsuitable groundwater occurring in the alluvial tracts of lower reaches of the Tittur Basin. The analyzed data also reveals that the upper reaches of all four sub basins can be categorized in moderate to good quality of water.

GIS and Remote Sensing analysis have proved a vital tool in delineating different groundwater potential zones based on integration of various thematic layers. By integration of all the maps (Hydrological soil Group, Runoff Zone, Geomorphology, Geology, Slope, Land use/ Land Cover, Lineament Density and Drainage Density), groundwater potential

zones were delineated and classified as: very high potential, high potential, moderate potential, low potential and very low potential. Hydrogeomorphologically, the investigated area is occupied by Structural Hills, Lineaments, Escarpment, Dykes, Pediment, Pedepain, Alluvial Plain, Monadnock, Dissected plateau, Tor, Ridge, Gully and Rill, Denudational Hill, Braided river, Floodplain, Fluvial terraces, Valley fills, Paleo-channel, Plunge pool, Stream pool and Talus. Lineaments, pedepain, alluvial plain and valley fills units has moderate to good and good groundwater potentiality respectively. Whereas pediment unit in the study area is having poor to moderate groundwater potentiality due to variation weathering thickness, joints and fractures in weathered basalt rock. 47.53 % of the total basin area is occupied by flat surfaces. These flat surfaces are observed in pedepain and valley fill units having high density of dug wells. The lineaments are acting as pathways of groundwater movement. As a result, the groundwater level is increasing considerably during monsoon period.

In the study area, 291 lineaments have been mapped through visual interpretation of satellite imagery and most are cross checked during the field investigation. They are having varying dimension and the smallest of them is 0.99 Km long and the longest of them is 22.64 km. In the present study, lineaments were classified based on their length into three categories as Major (>15km); Medium (5-15km) and Minor (<5km). There are three predominant sets of lineaments, one set trending SW – NE and second set trending SE - NW and last set trending south - North. Total cross lineaments have been 94. The high density lineament occupied as patches throughout the study area, the other lineament density zone are well distributed throughout the study area whereas the high and medium lineament intersection zones are distributed as patches

in the study area. The rose diagram of the detected lineaments show three prominent trends in the directions of the S-N, SW-NE and SE - NW axes, which are also the principal directions of the regional structures in basement complexes. The rose diagram indicates that the most dominant lineament direction is SE - NW.

Deforestation in the study area has intensified soil erosion, removal of thin soil cover along the hill slope of Saigavan, Vadgaon, Bahadarpur and Haraswadi villages. Area occupied by the structural hills in the study area is devoid of vegetation and forest cover along the Northern slopes. Rill erosion on hill slope and gully erosion along the Pediment and pedepain units has intensified and accelerated the process of capillary rise and thereafter evaporation of sub surface soil moisture from the steep banks of the gullies causing depletion groundwater table along these gullies.

The continuous growth of non-agricultural, commercial and industrial activities in the Tittur valley plain in recent years has created large size impervious surfaces. The permeable soils have become waterproofed resulting depletion of local water table through lack of infiltration and increased runoff lower order streams.

Problem of high water table during monsoon months is observed in valley flat where the hydraulic gradient and surface slope is very low. Middle reaches of the study area more prone high water table phenomenon causing swelling and lithification of black cotton soil ultimately causing water logging situation in low lying valley flats.

Sinuuous channel of the Tittur River in middle reaches indicates that this reach contributes the water to adjacent alluvial aquifers only during the peak flows. During the absence of stream flow, the base flow

contribution also gets minimized due to low recharge during peak flows. Tittur River basin is prone to erosion and sediment generation in its upper reaches only during monsoon season. Increase in wash load and reduction in stream power is responsible for deposition of sediment within channel in the middle stream reach making the channel shallower and prone to the avulsion and flooding.

Vertical cutting of rock strata in various quarries along the hill slopes have exposed the weathered basaltic aquifers underneath. Numerous springs have been emerged due to vertical cutting of rock. It has influenced indirectly on to the subsurface supply of water to downstream reaches.

Hard and compact foundation of Central Railway and national highway no. 211 has significantly modified the surface and subsurface flow regimes of the Tittur valley. Central Railway line and National highway are acting as an artificial surface dyke to these flows causing the low recharge of wells located to the south of Central Railway line, east of highway and downstream to the flowing reach.

structural alterations and process alterations in the natural hydrological behavior of the basin has created many hydrogeomorphic problems such as fragmentation of riverine morphology, sediment accumulation behind percolation tanks, degradation of groundwater quality, discontinuance of tributary flow, increased sedimentation from surrounding channels to the master stream etc.

The spatio- temporal Land surface temperature change detection in response to climatic change can be analyzed through hydrological regime in hydro-geomorphic physical entity like river basin, which could be affected by climatic variations in recent decades and may be resulted

from the global warming. The hydrological regime covers the changing condition of water and sediment discharge positions in river channel as well as basin area. The prominent channel change is aggradations. Aggradations lead to the decreases of channel capacity causing high floods even in low to moderate rainfall. The basin also face the problems of depletion of water level in channel as well as water table and salinization of basin soil due to accelerated rate of evaporation with increase of the temperature This sort of change can be detected, monitored and predicted using GIS with renewed satellite information from remote sensing data.

7.2 Suggestion

Rainwater harvesting is a traditional technology of collection, storage or ground recharge of water in semiarid, seasonal and arid climatic region on the earth surface. The fundamental structure of this technology involves three integrated systems .viz Catchments system or receiver, collecting system or storage devices and distribution or uses or recharging for exploitation (Bhamare, 2010). The catchments system or devices are of two types one is natural like watersheds on the different scales from micro watershed of few hectares to major river basin on continental scale and cultural like rural or urban house rooftop to the catchments area of multipurpose mega dams. Both the catchments systems require different technologies. The collecting system of rainwater from house roof require simple devices like down flow pipes ,storing measures, tanks, containers, pits, over and underground tanks, reservoirs etc. The stored water can directly used to maintain greenery within the compound of houses, toilet flush or irrigation and recharging the ground water on large scale. It may

be used for drinking and domestic purposes after treatments. The natural catchments require quite different technology. As far is concerned to the planning of water resources the first step is the terrain analysis. Recently remote sensing and GIS is the best suitable and most advanced technology for the terrain analysis. The rainwater harvesting using open surface area needs the demarcation of the catchments area by means well-defined natural water divides or water parting in which a drainage network is well established under the influence of surface configuration. Mostly, relief and slope guide drainage network. The received rainfall in watershed generates overland flow, through flow, runoff and stream flow in an integrated network system. Every watershed has a one single outlet through which water passes out of the catchments systems. This outflow of water requires planning in the watershed. The terrain analysis is the proper parameter for the water resource planning. Recently in developed countries, remote sensing and GIS technology is used for this purpose. The following suggestion attempts the Remote Sensing and GIS technology for rainwater harvesting and water resource planning in Tittur basin or the land surface catchments rainwater harvesting.

Rainfall distribution needs to highlight before terrain analysis. The rainfall distribution map is prepared based on remote sensing data as shown in fig.2.5. The rainfall of the Tittur basin ranges between 600 and 800mm. Over 60% areas of basin receives above 700 mm rainfall. This area includes eastern hill slope and plain area.

Table 7.1 Rainwater harvesting potential

Rainfall mm→	600	650	700	750	800
Roof Top Area sq.m ↓	Rainwater Harvested in Cubic Meter.				
100	48	52	56	60	64
200	96	104	112	120	128
300	144	156	168	180	192
400	192	208	224	240	256
500	240	260	280	300	320

The Tittur basin has good potential for rainwater harvesting and development of ground water. The roof water potential for the basin is given in the Table 7.1.

7.2.1 Terrain Classification and Rainwater harvesting

By using, remote sensing data and GIS technology Tittur basin terrain is classified into seven categories as shown in map no1. Viz. Plain, Pediment, Moderate slope, Moderately Steep slope, Steep Slope, Escarpments and Crest slope. These seven terrain types may be converted into four hydro-geomorphic zones for the rainwater harvesting and planning of the watershed (Fig.7.1). They are as follows-

1. Water divide zone or no erosion or critical zone (Water devoid Zone),
2. over land flow- runoff zone,
3. Percolation - Storage zone and
4. Recharge zone

Fig. 7.1 Hydro-Geomorphic Zones for the Rainwater harvesting

1) Water Divide Zone or Critical Belt of No Erosion (WDZ or CBNE)

This is the peripheral elevated narrow zone of watershed. It is covered by bare rock, almost devoid of ground water, soil, natural vegetation settlement. However, it may receive more rainfall due to altitudinal influence. The rainwater loss is the maximum in this region by means evaporation, generation overland flow and runoff. This is the most water scarcity zone needs the rainwater harvesting. This is the bare rock land surface catchments system. This zone requires digging the pits and small ponds or inside caves to store rainwater and check the loss of water by overland flow and runoff. The stored water is comparatively less contaminated and easily distributed by drainpipes where it requires down slope under the influence of gravity without any power requirement. This technique not only conserves water but also generate power or energy. This is an ancient technology. It was used in forests. The water will also used to maintain greenery of forest on hillcrest as well as on slopes. In the Tittur basin this region may devoid of settlement. Therefore, roof water catchments are not important absent. If there is, an urban expansion over such WDZ or CBNE then roof water harvesting system will be effective.

2. Overland flow or Runoff zones (OFZ or RZ)

This is the more extensive area of watershed with moderate relief and comparatively steep slopes. It is the most effective overland flow and runoff zone and severely suffered from intense erosion, and loss of water and vegetation through runoff. This zone plays a key role in generation floods to trunk streams and main rivers. Tremendous soil and water is lost in the floods. The slope wash processes are also active in this region, which enhance the sheet erosion. The land surface system is the basic

rainwater catchments system requires for this region. It involves the arresting of runoff by digging trenches and erecting bunds or small earthen dams across the slope on the terrace. The runoff will be delayed and collected in trenches the delayed runoff enhances the infiltration in to the ground to develop underground water for its exploitation in dry season. The ground water is natural filtered water and safer than surface for domestic and even for drinking purposes. The rainwater harvested from this region is also used for terrace cultivation, to maintain the greenery of the forest. It can be easily drained through pipes or open artificial channels. The collected water stored into big tanks or reservoirs where it can be treated for its further use like drinking, domestic, irrigation and industrial purposes. The rainwater from the agricultural field can also be harvested by digging field tanks of size 30m x 20m x10 m sizes and covered with polythin paper for protection from infiltration in porous structures. This stored water amounts 6000M³. This water is sufficient to irrigate one hectare of land by sprinkle irrigation. The pond may be used for fish culture. All the water harvested in this land catchments system will certainly checks soil erosion and floods, protects the forest and agricultural land. It is certainly a low cost technology of land catchments system of rainwater harvesting.

3. The Percolation and Storage Zone Catchments (PSZC)

This is the pediment zone of the watershed. They are rocky and with exposed outcrops at some places. The slope on the pediments is 1 to 7 degree and relief is moderate to low. The operation of geomorphic processes sheet flood erosion, lateral planation by stream and back weathering, forms them. The pediments may exhibits considerable degree

of dissection in semiarid or monsoon regions. The pediments on crystalline rocks like basalts formations are impervious in nature. They have thin layer of soil or sediments. The thickness of sediments increases in down slope direction. The impervious nature of pediments especially on upslope provides ideal sites for storage or reservoirs of harvested rainwater. The percolation dams may be constructed on lower pediments.

4. Recharge Zone Catchments (RZC)

The recharge zone starts from streamline zone and covers with integrated drainage network system. Below the pediments, the area extends up to the outlet of the watershed or mouth. This is an extensive flat rolling plain with extremely faint relief and slope less than one degree. It covered by comparatively thick layer of alluvium. The alluvial sediments are extremely porous in nature. The upper soil layer is clay rich with high porosity. Essentially, there are high rates of water loss due to infiltration into the ground. Infiltration continues until the saturation of the ground. Sometimes pseudo-saturation creates water logging problems. The excess water enters into the stream channels and it is lost through stream flow. The stream flows may be arrested by constructing numerous masonry or concrete anicuts across the channel at every successive segments of different magnitude. The stored water in anicuts is used for irrigation and other uses like drinking domestic and industrial purposes.

7.3 Suggested Methods of Rain Water Harvesting

Once the hydro-geomorphic zones of the watershed have determined it is easy to adopt the proper method in each zone. Each zone is separately divided into cultural and natural catchments. The roof top catchments rainwater harvesting method is useful for cultural areas like houses. There are several methods for roof top water harvestings as follows;

7.3.1. Roof Top Rain Water Harvesting

This method is suitable for recharge zone of watershed. This is a fertile tract and supports dense population settlements. The houses are more therefore large volume of water may be collected.

A) Through Recharge Pits

This method is suitable for large roof catchments less than 200 sq m. area and shallow aquifers. The collected rainwater from the rooftop by drainpipes is collected into the pit of size 2M x 3M x 4M filled with boulders at the bottom gravel in mid and coarse sand at the top. A mesh should be provided at the roof to prevent the leaves or any solid waste material from entering into the pit. The water from the filter pit recharge to shallow aquifer wells.

B) Through Recharge Trench

This method is suitable for large roof catchments with 200-500 sq m. area and shallow aquifers. The trench consist of 0.5-1 M Breadth 1-2M Depth and 10-20M L filled with the boulders at bottom gravel in mid and coarse sand above for filter of water. PVC pipes drain the water from roof to trench. The collected water recharges shallow aquifer well.

Fig. 7.2 Recharge pit for the Rainwater harvesting

Fig. 7.3 Recharge Trench for the Rainwater harvesting

C) Trough Recharge Trench for deep aquifer

The trench of considerable length more than 30 m may be used for larger roof catchments. The same method is used but the trench is connected to the tube wells in deep aquifers.

7.3.2. Watershed Ground Catchments rainwater harvesting systems in Overland flow and Runoff Zone

The watershed unit is a ground catchments system. It covers a large area than roof catchments and collects a huge quantity of rainwater. The following techniques may be adopted for rainwater harvesting

A) Rainwater Harvesting Through Rill or Gully Plug

The rills and gullies are active during rainfalls on a hill slope. They are essentially parallel on upslope and converge into a master rill or gully by the process of micro grading (Rill capturing) on lower slope. The gully or rill plugs are built using local stones, clay, bushes across the master rill. The water collects into tiny catchments. The gully plugs check runoff, conserve soil and moisture on a hill slope. The water harvested in a gully plug recharges debris, and maintains greenery on a hill slope.

B) Rainwater Harvesting Through Contour Bunds

The contour bunding is the most effective technique of soil conservation to conserve moisture in soil at least up to the crop harvesting season. The earthen bunds are constructed across the lower slope. A series of bunds keeps space to resist the erosive velocity of runoff and overland flows. The harvested water is used fully for irrigation to paddy fields on terraces.

7.3.3 The Rainwater Harvesting In Stream Line Zone

The zero value on hydro-geomorphic map indicates streamline zone. The streamline zone starts from the first order channel to the outlet of final order of watershed. The final order of Tittur basin is seventh. Following techniques are used for rainwater harvesting in channel cross sections of various micro watershed in Tittur basin.

A) Small Check Dam (SCD) or Gabion structure

It is one the effective method of rainwater harvesting through gabion structures or the small check dams across the first order stream channel by means of putting local boulder in steel wire mesh. The waste hard cement bags are also used instead of boulders. The height of the dams is maintained equal to the depth channel cross section in order to submerge only channel area. The excess water overflows this structure. This structure becomes impervious after concentration of silt into interstices of boulders and established vegetation. The water retained in this CSD for sufficient time after rains to recharge ground water. This water can also lift for irrigation nearby field during delaying rainfall period to protect the standing crops.

B) Percolation Tank Structure (PT S)

The percolation tank should be constructed on second or third order streams. The fractured or weathered rock is ideal for the construction of dam across stream for percolation. The ground water is augmented and downstream well will be benefited by this dam. The percolation dams are usually earthen with masonry spillway structures. This dam is most effective for well irrigation downstream. The water can also be used for rural water supply and for cottage industries.

C) Masonry Check Dams (MCD) on small streams of third or fourth order

The ideal site for MCD is deep channel with weathered basalt or permeable formation. The height of the dam is up to two meter and excess water spill over the dam. Series of dams may be constructed in the stream channel to harness maximum runoff. The planks also be erected on spillways to harness maximum water.

D) Under Ground Dam (UGD) or Sub-surface Dams or dykes (SSD)

The underground dam is a subsurface barrier across the stream. This dam retards the base flow and stores water bellow the ground. The stored water is naturally filtered and used for town water supply after treatments. The wells are also recharged in surrounding areas.

E) Series of Barrages of Final Order Stream or River Channels

Series of barrages may be constructed in down stream direction of main channel of the final order river or streams. These are the concrete dams across the channel. The seasonal river becomes perennial after construction of dams. The huge quantity of water is stored and used for all purposes like domestic, irrigation industries and drinking purposes after treatment to the nearby urban as well as urban areas.

Surface water has limitations to meet the demand of drinking, domestic, industrial and irrigations in small watershed of low rainfall regions like Tittur basin, due to the long duration aridity. The rainwater harvesting is the best solution to made availability of water in dry periods for drinking, domestic, irrigation and industrial use of water. The watershed is best confined geographical unit in which rainwater harvested into cultural as roof water catchments and watershed as surface

catchments. The data generated from landsat ETM+ imageries and analyzed with GIS technology. Terrain of watershed is classified into various terrain types. They are converted into various hydro-geomorphic zones. The appropriate technique of rainwater harvesting is adopted for each hydro-geomorphic zone. Tittur basin has good potentials for rainwater harvesting.

REFERENCES

- Abrahams, A. D. (1984). Channel networks: a geomorphological perspective. *Water Resource Res.* Vol.20, pp.161–168.
- Abbott, M. B., J. C. Bathurst, J. A. Cunge, P. E. O’Connell, and J. L. Rasmussen. (1986). An introduction to the European Hydrology System SHE, 2, Structure of a physically-based, distributed modeling system. *Journal Hydrology*, vol.87 (1-2), pp.61-77.
- Acharya T and Chatterjee A (2010). Fracture-correlated lineaments and groundwater prospect; Abstract, Proc. National Seminar on Sedimentation, Tectonics and Hydrocarbon Potential in Himalayan Foreland Basin, University of Jammu, Jammu, pp. 44–45
- Adejuwon, J.O., Jeje, L.K. and Ogunkoya, O.O. (1984), Hydrological Response Patterns of some Third Order Streams on the Basement Complex of Southwestern Nigeria, *Hydrological Science Journal*, Vol.28(3), pp.377-391.
- Agarwal, C. S. (1998) “Study of drainage pattern through aerial data in Naugarh area of Varanasi district, U.P.” *Jour. Indian Soc. Remote Sensing*. Vol.26, pp. 169-175.
- Agarwal, C.S and Garg, P.K. (2000), *Textbook on Remote Sensing In Natural Resources Monitoring and Management*. Wheeler Publishing. Pp. 213.
- Agone V.M. and Bhamare S.M. (2012). Change Detection of vegetation cover using Remote Sensing and GIS, *Journal of Research and Development*, Vol.2 (Issue 4). April. pp. 4-12.

Allen, R.G.; Pereira, L.S.; Raes, D. & Smith, M. (1998). Crop evapotranspiration – Guidelines for computing crop water requirements. FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper, No. 56, FAO, Rome.

Allen, R.G.; Clemmens, A.J.; Burt, C.M.; Solomon, K. & O'Halloran, T. (2005). Prediction accuracy for projectwide evapotranspiration using crop coefficients and reference evapotranspiration. *Journal of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering*, Vol. 131, Issue 1, pp.24-36.

Anand, R. R. & Paine, M. (2007). Regolith geology of the Yilgarn Craton, Western Australia: Implications for exploration. *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences: An International Geoscience Journal of the Geological Society of Australia*, Vol.49, Issue 1, pp. 3-162. DOI:10.1046/j.1440-0952.2002.00912.x

Arlegui, L. E., Soriano, M. A. (1998). Characterizing lineaments from satellite images and field studies in the central Ebro basin (NE Spain), *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol.19 (16), pp.3169-3185.

Arnaud, P., Bouvier, C., Cisner, L., and Dominguez, R. (2002). Influence of rainfall spatial variability on flood prediction, *J. Hydrol.*, Vol.260, pp.216–230.

Arnold, J. G., J. R. Williams, A. D. Nicks, and N. B. Sammons (1990). *SWRRB - A Basin-Scale Simulation Model for Soil and Water Resources Management*. College Station, Texas: Texas A&M Press.

Arnold, J. G., J. R. Williams, and D. R. Maidment. (1996). Continuous-time water and sediment-routing model for large basins. *J. Hydraulic Eng.* Vol.121 (2), pp. 171-183.

Arnold, J. G., R. Srinivasan, R. S. Muttiah, and J. R. Williams. (1998). Large-area hydrologic modeling and assessment: Part I. Model development. *J. American Water Resources Assoc.* Vol.34 (1), pp.73 -89.

Attoh, K.; Brown, L. D. (2008). The Neoproterozoic Trans-Saharan/Trans-Brasiliano shear zones: Suggested Tibetan Analogs. American Geophysical Union.

Ayandike, R.N.G. and Phil Eze, R.C. (1989), Runoff Response to Basin Parameters in South-Western Nigeria, *Geogr. Ann.*, Vol. 71A (1& 2), pp.75-84.

Babar, M d (2005). *Hydrogeomorphology: Fundamentals, Applications, Techniques.* New India Publishing Agency. New Delhi.

Babar, Md. and Kaplay, R. D. (1998). Geomorphometric analysis of River Puma basin in Parbhani district (Maharashtra) India, *Indian Journal of Geomorphology*, Vol.3. No.1(Jan-June).pp. 29-39.

Bajpai, V. N., and Mahanta, C. (2003). Hydrogeomorphic classification of the terrain in relation to the aquifer disposition: A case study of Gurgaon-Sohna region, Haryana, *Journal of Geol. Society of India*, Vol. 62. pp. 318-334.

Baker, V.R., 1982. *The Channels of Mars.* University of Texas Press, Austin.

Baker, V.R., 1985. Models of fluvial activity on Mars. In: Woldenberg, M. (Ed.), *Models in Geomorphology.* Allen & Unwin, Winchester, MA, pp. 287–312.

Baker, V.R., 1990. Spring sapping and valley network development. In: Higgins, C.G., Coates D.R. (Eds.), *Groundwater Geomorphology: the*

Role of Subsurface Water in Earth-Surface Processes and Landform. Geol. Soc. Am. Bull. Vol.252, pp.235–265 (Special Paper).

Bala AN, Ike EC (2001). The aquifer of the crystalline basement rocks in Gusau area, North-western Nigeria. J. Min. Geol. Vol.37 (2), pp.177-184.

Bassey, N.E., Ezeigbo, H.I. and Kwache, J.B. (1999). A hydrogeological study of Duhu area (Sheet 135) NE Nigeria on the basis of aeromagnetic data. Water Resources-Journal of NAH, vol.10, pp. 26-30.

Bates and Jackson (1980). Glossary of Geology: American Geological Institute.

Bathurst, J. C. (1986). Sensitivity analysis of the Système Hydrologique Européen for an upland catchment. Journal of Hydrology, vol.87 (1-2), pp. 103-123.

Beck, M. B. (1991). Forecasting environmental change. Journal of Forecasting 10(1-2): 3-19. doi: 10.1002/for.3980100103.

Bell, V. A. and Moore, R. J. (2000) The sensitivity of catchment runoff models to rainfall data at different spatial scales, Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci., Vol. 4, pp.653–667. <http://www.hydrol-earth-syst-sci.net/4/653/2000/>

Bergström, S. (1995). The HBV model. In Computer Models of Watershed Hydrology, V. P. Singh, ed. Water Resource Publication, Highlands Ranch, Colorado.

Beven Keith (2004). Robert E. Horton's perceptual model of infiltration processes, Hydrological Processes, Wiley Inter sciences DOI 10:1002/hyp 5740.

Beven, K. J. (1983). Surface water hydrology-runoff generation and basin structure. Reviews of Geophysics, vol.21 (3), pp.721-730.

Beven, K. J., A. Calver, and E. M. Morris. (1987). The Institute of Hydrology distributed model. Technical Report 89, Institute of Hydrology, Wallingford, United Kingdom.

Beven, K. J. (1989). Changing ideas in hydrology: The case of physically-based models. *Journal of Hydrology*, vol.105 (1-2), pp.157–172.

Bhamare S.M. (1978). Geomorphic Analysis of Panzara Basin. Unpublished Ph.D.Thesis. Pune University.

Bhamare S.M. (1983). Morphometric Analysis of Panzara River and its important Tributaries, *Trans.Inst.Indian Geographer*, Vol. 5 Number 2 P.P. 183- 188.

Bhamare S.M. (1985).Morpho-Hydrological Analysis of Panzra Basin. *The National Geographical journal of India*, Vol. 31 pp. 23 – 27.

Bhamare S.M. (1990). Calcretes and Ground – Water Potentiality in the Panzara Basin. *Indian Geomorphology- Volume of Selected papers Of International Conference of I.G.I on Environmental Geomorphology* P.P. 115-122

Bhamare S.M. (1996).Chemical characteristics of ground water in Burai Basin. *National Geographer, Allahabad (U.P) India*, Vol. – 31 No 182. Page 51-56

Bhamare S.M. (2011).Rain Water Harvesting & Water Resource Planning in Watershed: A GIS Application.a paper published *Proceeding Volume of 15th International Rainwater Catchments System Conference at Taipei Taiwan 28 March –4, April 2011.*

Bhamare S.M. and Agone V.M. (2011).Change Detection of Surface Temperature and its Consequence Using Multi-Temporal Remote

Sensing Data and GIS Application to Tapi Basin of India. Global Conference on Global Warming 2011, Lisbon, Portugal. ISBN: 978-989-95091-3-9

<http://www.cge.uevora.pt/GCGW/html/sessions/session19.html>

Bhamare S.M. and Agone V.M. (2011). Identification of groundwater potential zone of Tapi Basin in central India: A Remote sensing and GIS Approach. UNESCO & HELP international symposium 2011, Panama.

http://www.cazalac.org/documentos/simposio_help_2011/

Bhuyan SJ, Mankin KR, Koelliker JK (2003). Watershed scale AMC selection for hydrologic modeling. Trans ASAE, Vol. 46, pp.237–244.

Binley, A. M., and K. J. Beven. (1989). A physically based model of heterogeneous hillslopes. Effective hydraulic conductivities. Water Resources Research, vol.25 (6), pp.1227-1233.

Birkeland, Peter W. (1999). Soils and Geomorphology. Oxford University Press, New York.

Bishop, M.P., Shroder, J.F., Bonk, R. and Olsenholler, J. 2002. Geomorphic change in high mountains: a western Himalayan perspective. Global & Planet. change, Vol.32, pp.311-329.

Bisson R, A. and El-Baz F (1990). Mega watershed exploration model. Proceeding of the 23 rd Inter. Sym. On Remote sensing on Envir. ERIM. Ann Arbor , MI , Vol. 1, pp. 247-273.

Blanchet P H (1957). Development of fracture analysis as an exploration method; Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol. Bull. vol.40, pp.1748–1759.

Blum, M., and T.E. Tonqvist, (2000). Fluvial responses to climate and sea-level change, a review and look forward. *Sedimentology*, vol. 47 suppl. 1, pp. 2-48.

Boughton, W. C. (1984). A simple model for estimating the water yield of ungauged catchments. *Civil Engineering Transactions*, vol.26 (2), pp.83–88.

Boman, B.J., and E.W. Stover. (2002). Outline for Managing Irrigation of Florida Citrus with High Salinity Water AE217. Gainesville, University of Florida Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences, <http://edis.ifas.ufl.edu/pdf/files/ae217>

Booth, D. B. and C. R. Jackson. (1997). Urbanization of Aquatic Systems: Degradation Thresholds, Stormwater Detection, and the Limits of Mitigation. *Journal of the American Water Resources Association*, vol.33 (5), pp.1077-1090.

Boyer R and McQueen J (1964). Comparison of mapped rock fractures and airphoto linear features; *Photogram. Eng. Remote Sens.* vol.30, pp.630–635.

Brassington, R. (1999). *Field Hydrology*. John Wiley and Sons. New York. 2nd Ed. Pp. 248.

Brown, A. D. and Bradley, C. (1995). *Geomorphology and Groundwater: Convergence and diversification*. In: *Geomorphology and Groundwater* edited by Brown, A. D. John Wiley & Sons Ltd, New York. pp. 1-20.

Brown, N (1994). Integrating structural geology with remote sensing in hydrogeological resource evaluation and exploration; *Proc. Tenth*

Thematic Conference in Geologic Remote Sensing, San Antonio, TX, vol.1, pp.144–154.

Buchanan, T.J. and Somers, W.P. (1969). Discharge Measurements at Gaging Stations: U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations, Book 3, Chapter A8, pp.1.

C.Michael Hogan. (2010). *Abiotic factor*. Encyclopedia of Earth. eds Emily Monosson and C. Cleveland. National Council for Science and the Environment. Washington DC.

Cabrol, N. A., and E. A. Grin (2001), Composition of the drainage network on early Mars, *Geomorphology*, Vol.37(3), pp.269–289.

Calef, Wesley (1950). Slope studies of northern Illinois: Illinois Academy of Science, Transactions, vol. 43, and pp.110-115.

Calef, Wesley, and Newcomb, Robert (1953). An average slope map of Illinois: *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, vol. 43, no.4, pp. 304-316

Caponera, F. (1989). Remote Sensing Applications to Water Resources: Remote Sensing Image Interpretation for Ground Water Surveying. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, pp.234.

Caran C S, Woodruff C M Jr and Thompson E J (1982). Lineament analysis and inference of geologic structures –examples from the Balcones/Ouachita trend of Texas; University of Texas at Austin, Bureau of Economic Geology, Geological Circular, vol.82 (1), pp.59–69.

Carter, R. W. (1961). Magnitude and frequency of floods in suburban areas. US Geological Survey Prof. Paper. Vol. 424-B, pp. 9-11.

Craddock, R. A., and A. D. Howard (2002). The case for rainfall on a warm, wet early Mars, *J. Geophys. Res.*, Vol.107 (E11), pp.5111, doi: 10.1029/2001JE001505

Craddock, R. A., R. P. Irwin III, and A. D. Howard (2003), Characteristics of Martian valley networks and the implications for past climates, *Lunar Planet. Sci.*, XXXIV, Abstract 1888

Carr, M.H., Clow, G.D. (1981). Martian channels and valleys: their characteristics, distribution, and age. *Icarus*, Vol.48, pp.91–117.

Carr, M.H.(1999). The Martian drainage system and the origin of networks and fretted channels. *J. Geophys. Res.* Vol.100, pp.7479–7507.

Carr, M. H., and J. W. Head (2003), Basal melting of snow on early Mars: A possible origin of some valley networks, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, Vol.30 (24), pp.2245, doi: 10.1029/2003GL018575.

Casas, A. M., Cortes, Angel L., Maestro, A., Soriano, M.A., Riaguas, A., Bernal, J., 2000, A program for lineament length and density analysis, *Computers and Geosciences*, Vol. 26, No. 9/10, pp.1011-1022.

Census, 2001: District Provisional Abstract, Census of India. Government of India.

Chakraborty, S. and Paul, P.K. (2004). Identification of potential groundwater zones in the Baghmundi block of Purulia district, West Bengal using remote sensing and GIS, *Journal of Geol.Society of India*, Vol. 64. July. pp. 69-75.

Charman, PEV & Murphy, BW (1998). 5th edn, *Soils, their properties and management*, Oxford University Press, Melbourne.

Charlton, Ro (2008). Fundamentals of fluvial geomorphology. London: Rutledge. pp.234.

Chatterjee S and Rudra D K (1992). KT events in India: impact, rifting, volcanism and dinosaur extinction; Memoir of the Queensland Museum, Vol. 39 pp. 489-532

Cheeny R.F (1983). Statistical methods in Geology, George Allen Unwind Ltd., London, pp.169.

Chenet, anne-lise, courtillot, Vincent, fluteau, frederic, besse, jean, subbarao, k.v., khadri, syed, bajpai, sunil, and jay, Anne (2005). Magnetostratigraphy of the upper formations of the Deccan traps: an attempt to constrain the timing of the eruptive sequence. Geological Society of America, www.geosociety.org.

Chesworth Ward (2008).Encyclopedia of Soil Science, eds, Uniw. of Guelph Canada, Publ. Springer, ISBN 978-1-4020-3994-2

Chi, K. H., & Lee, B. J. (1994). Extracting potential groundwater area using remotely sensed data and GIS techniques. Proceeding, regional seminar on integrated applications of remote sensing and GIS for land and water resources management *ESCAP*, Bangkok, pp.64–69

Chiew, F. and T. McMahon. (1994). Application of the daily rainfall runoff model MODHYDROLOG to 28 Australian catchments. Journal of Hydrology, vol.153 (1-4), pp.383-416.

Chorley, R. J. (1957). Climate and morphometry, Journal of Geology. 65. pp. 628-668.

Chorley, R. J. (1969). Water Earth and Man, Methuen, London, pp.1-4.

Chorley, R.J. (1978). The Hill slope Hydrologic Cycle, In Hill slope Hydrology. Edited by M.J. Kirby. Wiley, New York, NY, pp. 1-42.

Christopherson, R. W. (2001). Elemental Geosystems. 3rd ed. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice-Hall.

Clarke, J. I. (1970). Morphometry from maps. In: Essays in Geomorphology Dury, G.H. Heinemann, London, pp. 235-274.

Cooke, R. U. and Doornkamp, J. C. (1974). Geomorphology and environmental management: An Introduction. Oxford University Press. Ely House, London.

Crawford, N.H. and R.K. Linsley, (1966). Digital Simulation in Hydrology: Stanford Watershed Model IV. Technical Report No. 39, Department of Civil Engineering, Stanford University, pp. 210.

Daniel Rogge (1999). Deforestation and Landslides in Southwestern Washington. University of Wisconsin-Eau Claire.

Davie T.J.A. (2002). Fundamentals of Hydrology. Routledge , London, pp.169.

De'gnan J R and Clark S F Jr (2002). Fracture-correlated lineaments at Great Bay, Southeastern New Hampshire; U.S. Geological Survey Open-File Report, pp.02-13.

DE Wiest, R. J. M. (1965). Geohydrology. John Wiley and Sons, New York. pp.1-13.

Deshpande, G. C. (1998). Geology of Maharashtra. Geol. Society of India Publication, Bangalore.

Deshpande, M. G. (2004). Groundwater exploration and management. Saket Prakashan. Aurangabad. Pp.1-4.

Devi, P. D.S., Srinivasulu, S., and Raju, K.K. (2001). Hydrogeomorphological and groundwater prospects of the Pageru river basin by using remote sensing data, *Environmental Geology*, vol. 40. pp. 1088-1094.

Dhakate R, Singh V S, Negi B C, Chandra S and Rao V A (2007). Geomorphological and geophysical approach for locating favorable groundwater zones in granitic terrain, Andhra Pradesh, India; *J. Environ. Manag.*, doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2007.07.014

Dietrich, W.E., and Dunne, T., 1978, Sediment budget for a small catchment in mountainous terrain: *Zeitschrift fur Geomorphologie Supplementband*, vol. 29, pp.191-206.

Dikshit, K. R. (1986). Maharashtra in maps. Maharashtra State Board for Literature and Culture. Bombay.

Dixey F (1960). The geology and geomorphology of Madagascar, and a comparison with Eastern Africa. *Quarterly Journal of the Geological Society of London*, vol. 116, pp 255- 268.

Doorenbos, J., and Pruitt, W. O. (1977). "Crop water requirements." *Irrigation and Drainage Paper No. 24(revised)*, FAO, Rome.

Doornkamp, J. C. and King, C. A. M.(1971). Numerical analysis in geomorphology: An Introduction. St. Martins Press, New York. pp.

3-20.

- Douglas, I. (1983). *The Urban Environment*. Baltimore: Edward Arnold.
- Dowling, T.I., Richardson, D.P., O'Sullivan, A., Sumrnerell, G.K. and Walker, J. (1998). Application of the hypsometric integral and other terrain based metrics as indicators of the Catchment health: A preliminary analysis. CSIRO Land and Water, Technical Report 20/98. Canberra.
- Drahovzal, J.A., Neathery, T.L. and Wielchowsky, C.A. (1973). Significance of selected lineaments in Alabama. In *third Earth Resources Technology Satellite-1 Symposium*. Goddard Space Flight Centre, Greenbelt.
- Drury, S.A. (1993). *Image Interpretation in Geology* (2nd Edition). London: Chapman & Hall. ISBN 0-412-48880-9.
- Dukes, M.D., M.L. Shedd, and S.L. Davis. (2009). *Smart irrigation Controllers: Probramming Guidelines for Evapotranspiration-Based Irrigation Controllers AE445*. Gainesville, University of Florida Institute of Food and Agricultural Acienes, <http://edis.ifas.ufl.edu/pdffiles/ae445>
- Dury, G.H (1952), "Methods of Cartographical Analysis in Geomorphological Research", *Silver Jubilee Volume*, Indian Geographical Society, Madras, pp 136-139.
- Easterbrook, D.J. (1993), *Surface Processes and Landforms*, Macmillian Publishing Co., New York, 325pp.
- Easterbrook, D. J. (1999). *Surface processes and landforms*. (Second Ed). Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey.
- Ebisemiju, F.S. (1979), A Reduced Rank Model of Drainage Basin Morphology: *Geografiska Annaler*, Vol.16A (1-2), pp.103-112.

Edet, A.E., Teme, C.S., Okereke, C.S. and Esu, E.O. (1994). Lineament analysis for groundwater ex-ploration in Precambrian Oban Massif and Obudu Plateau, SE Nigeria. *Journal of Mining and Geology*, vol.30 (1), pp.87-95.

Edet, A.E. and Okereke, C.S. (1997). Assessment of hydrogeological conditions in basement aquifers of the Precambrian Oban Massif, southeastern Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Geophysics*, vol.36, pp.195-204.

Edet, A.E., Okereke, C.S., Teme, S.C. and Esu, E.O. (1998). Application of remote sensing data groundwater exploration: A case study of the Cross River State, Southeastern Nigeria. *Hydrogeology J.* vol.6, pp.394-404.

Engman, E.T. and Gurney, R.J (1991). *Remote sensing in Hydrology* (London: Chapman and Hall).

ESRI (2001), *ArcGIS*. Environmental Systems Research Institute, Redlands, California, USA.

Eyles, R.J. (1965). Slope studies on the Wellington Peninsula: New Zealand Geographer, vol.21, no.2, pp. 133-144.

F. Becker, Z.L.Li (1990). Towards a local split window method over land surface. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, Vol.3, pp. 369-393,

Fairbridge, R. W., (1968). *Encyclopedia of Geomorphology*. Reinhold Book Company, New York.

FAO Land and Water Division retrieved 14 September 2010.

Fernandes, A.J. and Rudolph, D.L. (2001). The influence of Cenozoic tectonics on the groundwater production capacity of fractured zones: a

case study in Sao Paulo, Brazil. *Hydrogeology Journal*, vol.9, pp.151–167.

Fetter, C. W. (2000). *Applied Hydrogeology*, 2nd Indian Edition, CBS Publishers and Distributors. New Delhi.

Freer, J., K. Beven, and B. Ambrose. (1996). Bayesian estimation of uncertainty in runoff prediction and the value of data: an application of the GLUE approach. *Water Resources Research*, vol.32 (7), pp.2161–2173.

Freeze, R. A. (1972). Role of subsurface flow in generating surface runoff 2. upstream source areas. *Water Resources Research*, vol.8 (5), pp. 1272-1283.

Fullen, M.A. & A.H. Reed. (1987). Rill Erosion on Arable Loamy Sands in the West Midlands of England. Bryan, R.B. (ed). *Rill Erosion: Processes and Significance*. Catena Supplement 8. W. Germany:Catena Verlag.pp.85-96.

G.Shankar Narayana, N.Lakshmaiah & P.V.Prakashgoud (1996). Hydrogeomorphological study based on remote sensing of Mulug Taluk, Warangal District, Andhra Pradesh, India *Hydrological Sciences-Journal-des Sciences Hydrologiques*, Vol.41(2), pp.137 - 152

Gangopadhyaya, M., Uryvaev, V.A., Oman, M.H., Nordenson, T.J., Harbeck, GE., (1970). *Measurement and estimation of evaporation and evapotranspiration*. WMO Technical No. 83, Geneva, Switzerland.

Garg, D. M. (1977). *Principles of Hydrology*. Water Information Centre, Hutington, New York. USA.

Garg, S.K. 1983. Geology- the Science of the earth. Khanna Publishers, New Delhi.

Gardiner, V. (1975), Drainage Basin Morphometry, British Geomorphological Resource Group Technical Bulletin 14.

Gaile G L and Burt J A (1980). Directional Statistics, Concept and techniques in modern geography, No.25.Geo Abstracts, Univ.East Anglia, Nkorwish, pp.39.

GARY M., McAFEER. & WOLFC. L. (1972). Glossary of Geology. American Geological Institute, Washington, pp.857.

Garza, L D L and Slade, R M (1986). Relations between areas of high transmissivity and lineaments – the Edwards aquifer, Barton springs segment, Travis and Hays counties; In: The Balcones Escarpment, Geology, Hydrology, Ecology and Social Development in Central Texas (eds.) Abbott P L, Woodruff CM Jr, The University of Texas Libraries, The University of Texas at Austin, pp. 131–144.

Gelnett, R.H. and Gardner, J.V. 1979. Use of radar for groundwater exploration in Nigeria, West Afri-ca. Proc. 14th Int. Symp. Remote Sensing of Environment, Ann Arbor, Michigan, pp.11.

Ghose, R. (1993). Remote sensing for analysis of groundwater availability in an area with long unplanned mining history; J. Indian Soc. Remote Sensing, vol.21 (3), pp.119–126

Gilbert, G.K. (1877). Report on the Geology of the Henry Mountains. U.S. Geographical and Geological Survey of the Rocky Mts. Region. U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington, DC.

Goodchild, M.F (1993). The State of GIS for environmental problem solving. In *Environmental Modeling with GIS*, M.F. Goodchild, B.O. Parks and L.T. Steyaert (Eds), (New York: Oxford University Press), pp. 8–15.

Goldspiel, J., and S. Squyres (2000), Groundwater sapping and valley formation on Mars, *Icarus*, Vol. 148(1), pp.176–192.

Gopinath, G. and Seralathan, P. (2004). Identification of groundwater prospective zones using IRS-ID LISS and pump test methods, *Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 32, No.4. pp. 329-342.

Goudie, A. S., 2004, *Encyclopedia of Geomorphology*, vol. 1. Routledge, New York. ISBN 0-415-32737-7.

GSI, (1976) *Geology of Pune District*, Geol. Survey of India, New Delhi.

Gurnell, A.M. and Gregory, K.J. (1995). Interactions between semi-natural vegetation and hydrogeomorphological processes. *Geomorphology*. Vol. 13.pp. 49-69.

Gumbel E. J Greenwood J. A and Durand D (1953). The circular normal distribution: Tables and theory. *J. Amer. Soc.*, vol.18, pp.131-152.

Gupta, A. (1980). Correlation of Landsat and airborne magnetic anomaly data of a part of the Bihar mica belt; *Proc. Symp. Remote Sensing in subsurface exploration*, held on 25 Oct., Bangalore, India, pp. 23–30.

Gurnell Am, Gregory Kj (1995). Interactions between Seminatural Vegetation and Hydrogeomorphological Processes. *Geomorphology* Vol. 13, (1-4) 49-69.

Gulick, V., and V. R. Baker (1989). Fluvial valleys and Martian paleoclimates, *Nature*, Vol. 341(6242), pp.514–516.

Gulick, V. C. (2001), Origin of the valley networks on Mars: A hydrological perspective, *Geomorphology*, Vol.37 (3), pp.241–269.

Grant, J. A. (2000), Valley formation in Margaritifer Sinus, Mars, by precipitation recharged groundwater sapping, *Geology*, Vol.28 (3), pp. 223–226.

Grayson, R. B., I. D. Moore, and T. A. McMahon. (1992). Physically based hydrologic modeling 2. Is the concept realistic? *Water Resources Research*, vol.28 (10), pp. 2659-2666.

Greenbaum, D. (1985). Review of remote sensing applications to groundwater exploration in basement and regolith, *Brit. Geol. Surv. Rep. OD vol.85 (8)*, pp.36.

Gregory, K.J. and Walling, D.E. (1973), *Drainage Basin Form and Process: A Geomorphological Approach*, Edward Arnold, London, 456pp.

Harrison, C.G., Miskell, K.J., Brass, G.W., Saltzman, E.S. and Sloan, J.L. (1983). Continental hypsography. *Tectonics*, Vol.2, pp.357-377.

Haan, C.T., B.J. Barfield, J.C. Hayes. (1994). *Design Hydrology and Sedimentology for Small Catchments*. Academic Press, New York. pp.588.

Hadithi, M.A., Shukla, D.C. and Israil, M (2003). Evaluation of groundwater resources potential in Ratmau-Pathri Rao watershed Haridwar district, Uttaranchal, India using geo-electrical, remote sensing and GIS techniques. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on*

Water and Environment (WE-2003), Bhopal, India, Ground Water Pollution, pp.123–125.

Hansen, J.E., and S. Lebedeff, (1987). Global trends of measured surface air temperature. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 92, 13345-13372, doi: 10.1029/JD092iD11p13345.

Hardcastle, K.C. (1995) Photolineament Factor: A new computer – aided method for remotely sensing the degree to which bedrock is fractured. *Photogrammetric Engg. Remote Sensing*.vol.61, pp.739–747.

Hart, M. G. (1986). *Geomorphology Pure and Applied*. George Allen and Unwin (publishers) Ltd. London, UK. pp. 129-162.

Haberle, R. M. (1998), Early Mars climate models,*J. Geophys. Res*, Vol. 103(E12), pp.467–28.

Henderson G (1960). Airphoto lineaments in Mpanda area, Western Province, Tanganyika, Africa; *Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol. Bull.* Vol.44, pp.53–71.

Hewlett, J.D. and Hibbert, A.R. (1967), Factor Affecting the Response of Small Watersheds to Precipitation in Humid Areas, In: Sopper, W.E. and Lull. H.W. (Eds.), *Forest Hydrology*, Pergamon, pp.275-290.

Higgins, C. G. (1982), Drainage systems developed by sapping on Earth and Mars, *Geology*, Vol. 10(3), pp.147–152.

Hobbs, W.H. (1904). Lineaments of the Atlantic border region, *Geological Society of America Bulletin* 15, pp.483–506.

Hobbs, W.H. (1912). *Earth Features and Their Meaning: An Introduction to Geology for the Student and General Reader*, Macmillan, New York, NY pp.347.

Hodgson, R A (1961). Regional study of jointing in Comb Ridge-Navajo Mountain area, Arizona and Utah; Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol. Bull.vol.45, pp.1–38

Hong, S. Y., Noh Y., and Dudhia, J. (2006). A new vertical diffusion package with an explicit treatment of entrainment processes, Mon. Weather Rev., Vol.134, pp.2318–2341.

Horton, R. E. (1932). Drainage basin characteristics, Trans. Amer. Geophysical Union. Vol. 14, pp.350-361.

Horton, R. E. (1945). Erosional Development of Streams and their drainage basins; hydrophysical approach to quantitative geomorphology. Bulletin of Geological Society of America, Vol. 56, pp.275-370.

Hough M.N. and Jones, R.J.A. (1997). The United Kingdom Meteorological Office rainfall and evaporation calculation system: MORECS version 2.0 — an overview. Hydrol. Earth Sys. Sci.,vol.1, pp.227–239.

Howard K. W. F. , M. Hughes, D. L. Charlesworth, G. Ngobi (1992).Hydrogeologic Evaluation Of Fracture Permeability In Crystalline Basement Aquifers Of Uganda. Applied Hydrogeology, Volume 1, Issue 1, pp 55-65.

Howard, A. D., J. M. Moore, and R. P. Irwin III (2005). An intense terminal epoch of widespread fluvial activity on early Mars: 1. Valley network incision and associated deposits, J. Geophys. Res., Vol.110, pp.12S14, doi: 10.1029/2005JE002459.

Hubbert, M. K. (1956). Darcy's law and the field equations of the flow of underground fluids. *Trans. Am. Inst. Min. Metal! Pet. Eng.* vol. 207, Pp.222-239.

Hung LQ, Batelaan O, Smedt F (2005). Lineament extraction and analysis, comparison of LANDSAT ETM and ASTER imagery. Case study: Suoimuoi tropical karst catchment, Vietnam. In *Proceedings of SPIE*, Vol. 5983.

Huffman, G.J., Adler, R.F., Bolvin, D.T. Gu, G., Nelkin, E.J., Bowman, K.P., Hong, Y., Stocker, E.F., Wolff, D.B. (2007). The TRMM Multisatellite Precipitation Analysis (TMPA): Quasi-Global, Multiyear, Combined-Sensor Precipitation Estimates at Fine Scales. *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, Vol.8, pp.38-55.

Hurtrez, J. E., Lucazean, F., Lave J. and Avouac, J. P. (1999b). Investigation of the relationship between basin morphology, tectonic uplift and denudation from the study of an active fold belt in Siwalik Hills (Central Nepal). *J. Geophys. Res.*, Vol.104, pp.779-796.

Hynek, B. M., and R. J. Phillips (2003), New data reveal mature, integrated drainage systems on Mars indicative of past precipitation, *Geology*, Vol.31(9), pp.757–760

Ifabiyi, I.P. (2004), A Reduced Rank Model of Drainage Basin Response to Runoff in Upper Kaduna Catchment of Northern Nigeria. *Geostudies Forum*, Vol.2 (1), pp.109-117.

IPCC (Intergovernmental pannel on climate change) Special Report on Land Use, Land-Use Change And Forestry, 2.2.1.1 Land Use. <http://www.ipcc.ch>

Israil, M., Al-Hadithi, M. and Singhal, D.C (2006). Application of resistivity survey and geographical information system (GIS) analysis for hydrogeological zoning of a piedmont area, Himalayan foothill region, India. *Hydrogeology Journal*, vol.14, pp.753–759.

Jaiswal, R.K., Mukherjee, S., Krishnamurthy, J. and Saxena, R (2003). Role of remote sensing and GIS techniques for generation of groundwater prospect zones towards rural development: An approach. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol.24, pp.993–1008.

Jain, V. and Sinha, R. (2003) Evaluation of Geomorphic Control on Flood Hazard through Geomorphic Instantaneous Unit Hydrograph. *Current Science*, Vol.85 (11), pp.26-32.

Jain, M. K., Mishra, S. K., and Singh, V. P. (2006). Evaluation of AMC-Dependent SCS-CN-Based Models Using Watershed Characteristics, *Water Res. Manag.*, Vol.20, pp.531–552.

Jarvis, R.S. (1976). Classification of nested tributary basins in analysis of drainage basin shape, *Water Resources Research*, Vol. 19. pp.1151-1164.

Jarvis R. S. (1976). Stream Orientation Structures in Drainage Networks. *The Journal of Geology*, Vol. 84, No. 5 pp. 563-582.

Jefferson Anne (2010) .What do you mean by “hydrogeomorphic processes”? (Some thoughts following my GSA session on the topic). <http://all-geo.org>

Jensen M.E. (ed.) (1973). *Consumptive use of water and irrigation water requirements*. American Society of Civil Engineers, New York.

Jensen J.R. (1986). *Introductory digital image processing*, Third Edition Prentice Halls, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, pp.544

Jensen, M.E., R.D. Burman, and R.G. Allen. 1990. Evapotranspiration and Irrigation Water Requirements. ASCE Manuals and Reports on Engineering Practice No. 70, Am. Soc. Civil Engr., New York, NY. Pp.332.

Jha, M.K. and Peiffer, S (2006). Applications of Remote Sensing and GIS Technologies in Groundwater Hydrology: Past, Present and Future (Bayreuth, Germany: Bay CEER).

Jha, M.K., Chowdhury, A., Chowdary, V.M. and Peiffer, S (2007). Groundwater management and development by integrated remote sensing and geographic information systems: Prospects and constraints. Water Resources Management, vol.21, pp.427–467.

Johnston, P. R., and D. H. Pilgrim. (1976). Parameter optimization for watershed models. Water Resources Research, vol.12 (3), pp.477-486.

Jones, F. E. (1991). Evaporation of Water: with Emphasis on Applications and Measurements. Chelsea, Michigan: Lewis Publishers, Inc.

Jones, J.A.A. (1999), Global Hydrology: Processes, Resources and Environmental Management, Longman, 399pp.

Juhari MA and Ibrahim (1997). Geological Applications of Landsat Thematic Mapper Imagery: Mapping and Analysis of Lineaments in NW Peninsula Malaysia. ACRS. Available online at: www.gisdevelopment.net

Kale, V. S. and Deodhar, L. A. (1999). Downstream adjustments in allochthonous rivers: Western Deccan Trap Upland region, India. In:

Varieties of Fluvial Form. Edited by A.J. Miller and A. Gupta. John Wiley and Sons Ltd. New York. pp. 295-315.

Kale, V. S. and Gupta, A. (2001). Introduction to Geomorphology, Orient Longman, Hyderabad.

Kale, V. S. (1980). Slope Morphology of Shivganga Basin, Unpublished M. Phil. Dissertation, University of Poona, p.65.

Kazemi R, Porhemmat J and Kheirkhah M (2009). Investigation of lineaments related to groundwater occurrence in a karstic area: A case study in Lar catchment, Iran; Res. J. Environ. Sci. vol.3 (3), pp.367–375.

Kendrew W. G. (1953). The climates of the continents. Oxford (Clarendon Press). 4th Edition, Pp. 607

Khan, M. A. and Moharana, P. C. (2002). Use of remote sensing and GIS in the delineation and characterization of groundwater prospect zones, Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing, Vol. 30, No.3. pp. 131-141.

King, L. C. (1950), The study of the worlds plain lands. A new approach in geomorphology, Quarterly journal of Geological society of London 106, pp 101-103.

Kirpich, P. Z. (1940). Time of concentration of small agricultural watersheds. Civil Engg. (New York). 10 (6): 32.

Knighton, A.D. (1999). Downstream variation in stream power. Geomorphology. 29, pp.293-306.

Koch, M. and Mather, P.M. (1997). Lineament mapping for groundwater resource assessment: a comparison of digital Synthetic Aperture Radar

(SAR) imagery and stereoscopic Large Format Camera (LFC) photographs in the Red Sea Hills, Sudan. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol.27, pp. 4471–4493.

Kokkonen, T. S., and A. J. Jakeman. (2001). A comparison of metric and conceptual approaches in rainfall-runoff modeling and its implications. *Water Resources Research*. Vol.37 (9), pp.2345–2352.

Krishnamurthy, J., Venkatesa, K.N., Jayaraman, V., and Manivel, M. (1996). An approach to demarcate groundwater potential zones through remote sensing and a GIS, *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 17(10).pp. 1867-1884.

Krishnan M S (1982). *Geology of India and Burma*, 6th edition, (Delhi: CBS Publishers and Distributors).

Krishnamurthy, J., Srinivas, G., Jayaram, V. and Chandrasekhar, M.G. (1996), Influence of rock types and structures in the development of drainage networks in typical hardrock terrain, *ITC Journal* vol.3–4, pp 252-259.

Krishnamurthy, J., & Srinivas, G. (1995). Role of geological and geomorphological Factors in ground water exploration: A study using IRS LISS data. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol.16 (14), pp.2595–2618.

Krishnamurthy, J. V., Kumar, N., Jayaraman, V., & Manivel, M. (1996). An approach to demarcate ground water potential zones through remote sensing and a geographical information system. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol.7 (12), 1867–1884.

- Krishnamurthy, J., Mani, A., Jayraman, V., & Manivel, M. (2000). Groundwater resources development in hard rock terrain-An approach using remote sensing and GIS techniques, *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, vol. 2(3/4).
- Kshetrimayum, K. S., & Bajpai, V. N. (2012). Assessment of groundwater quality for irrigation use and evolution of hydrochemical facies in the Markanda river basin. *Journal of the Geological Society of India*, vol.79 (2), pp.189–198.
- Kulkarni, H. (1991). Hydrogeological significance of drainage analysis in the Deccan Basaltic Terrain of Maharashtra, *IAH Journal of Hydrology*, vol. XIV, No.3.pp. 173-184.
- Kumar, A., and Tomar, S. (1998). Groundwater Assessment Through Hydrogeomorphological and Geophysical Survey- A case study in Godavari sub-watershed, Giridh, Bihar, Photonirvachak, *Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 26, No.4. pp. 177-183.
- Laity, J. E., and M. C. Malin (1985), Sapping processes and the development of theater-headed valley networks in the Colorado Plateau, *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.*, Vol.96, pp.203–217.
- Langbein, W. B. (1947). Topographic characteristics of drainage basins, U.S. Geological Survey, Water supply Paper 968-C, pp.125-157.
- Larson, I (1972). Ground water in granite rocks and tectonic models. *Nordic Hydrology*, vol.3, pp.111-129.
- Larsson, I. (1968). Groundwater in Precambrian rocks in Sweden. In: *Groundwater problems, Wenner Green Center Int. Symp. Series*, vol.11, pp.23-41.

Larsson, L. (1977). Groundwater in hard rocks, International Seminar "Groundwater in Hard Rocks", Stockholm - Cagliari.

Larsson, I (1984). Groundwater in hard Rock. Project 8.6 of the Inter. Hydrology Prog. UNESCO.

Lattman, L H and Segovia, A V (1961). Analysis of fracture trace pattern of Adak and Kagalaska Islands, Alaska; Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol. Bull. vol.45, pp.249–251.

Lattman L H and Matzke R H (1961). Geological significance of fracture traces;Photogram. Eng. Vol.27, pp.435–438.

Lattman, L.H., Parizek, R.R. (1964). Relationship between fracture traces and the occurrence of ground water in carbonate rocks, Journal of Hydrology, vol.2, pp.73–91.

Leeper, GW & Uren, NC (1993). 5th edn, Soil science, an introduction, Melbourne University Press, Melbourne.

Leet, L.D., S. Judson, and M.E. Kauffman, (1982). Physical Geology, 6th Edition. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall. ISBN 0-13-669762-3

Leopold, L. B. and Maddock, T. (1953).The hydraulic geometry of stream channels and some physiographic implications. USGS professional paper Vol. 252, pp.1-57.

Leopold, L.B., Wolman, M.G., and Miller, J.P. (1964). Fluvial Processes in Geomorphology. W.H. Freeman, San Francisco, California

Leopold L.B. and Miller J.P. (1956).Ephemeral streams – hydraulic factor and there relation to the drainage net. U.S.G.S. Prof. Paper 282 A

Leopold, Luna B. (1968). Hydrology for Urban Planning — A Guidebook on the Hydrologic Effects of Urban Land Use, USGS Circular 554, Washington, D.C.

Lillesand T.M. and Kiefer R.W. (2000). Remote Sensing and Image Interpretation, Fifth Edition, John Wiley and Sons (Asia) Pte. Ltd, Singapore, 820.

Lipfert G, Tolman A and Loisel M (2001). Modeling recharge zones in fractured bedrock for Maine's Source Water Assessment Program; Fractured Rock, Toronto, Ontario, Canada.

Loch, R.J. & E.C. Thomas. (1987). Resistance to Rill Erosion: Observations on the Efficiency of Rill Erosion on a Tilled Clay Soil Under Simulated Rain and Run-On Water. Bryan, R.B. (ed). Rill Erosion: Processes and Significance. Catena Supplement 8. W. Germany:Catena Verlag. Pp.71-83.

Lohman, S. W. and Robinove, C. J. (1964). Photographic description and appraisal of water resources. International Archives of Photogrammetry, XIV, Lisbon, 19(3), p. 40.

Lokesha, N., Gopalkrishna, G.S., Gowda, H. and Gupta, A.K. (2005). Delineation of groundwater potential zones in a hard rock terrain of Mysore district, Karnataka using IRS data and GIS techniques, Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing, Vol. 33, No.3. pp. 405-412.

Mabee, S.B., Hardcastle, K.C., Wise, D.U. (1945). A method of collecting and analyzing lineaments for regional scale fractured-bedrock aquifer studies. Ground Water, vol.32 (6), pp.884–894.

Mackenzie L. Davis and Masten Susan J., Principles of Environmental Engineering and Science. ISBN 0-07-235053-9.

Madigan Thomas (2007). The Geology of the MNRRA Corridor, National Park Service, p. 26.

Magar, P. P., Nagarale, V. R., Bhamre, S.M. and Mishra, N.C. (2007). Hydrogeomorphic analysis of Shivganga drainage basin for groundwater exploration- A GIS Approach. Bull. Geo. Phy. Sciences. Vo. 1 (1st Issue). Pp. 1-5.

Magar, P. P (2007), Hydro- geomorphic Analysis of Shivganga Drainage Basin, Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis. NMU, Jalgaon.

Magowe, M., and Carr, J.R. (1999). Relationship between lineaments and ground water occurrence in western Botswana”, Ground Water, vol.37 (2), pp. 282–286.

Mah A, Taylor G R, Lennox P and Balia L (1995) Lineament analysis of Landsat Thematic Mapper Images, Northern Territory, Australia;Photogram. Eng. Remote Sens.vol.61, pp. 761–773.

Malin, M. C., and M. H. Carr (1999), Groundwater formation of Martian valleys, Nature, Vol. 397(6720), pp.589–591.

Malin, M. C., and K. S. Edgett (2000), Evidence for recent groundwater seepage and surface runoff on Mars, Science, Vol. 288, pp.2330–2335.

Manimaran D. (2012). Groundwater geochemistry study using GIS in and around Vallanadu Hills, Tamilnadu, India, Res. J. recent sci, vol.1(6), pp.32–37.

Mardia K. V (1972). Statistics and directional data, Academic Press Ltd, London, p.357.

Mars Channel Working Group (1983), Channels and valleys on Mars, Geol. Soc. Am. Bull., Vol.94, pp.1035–1054.

Matthew, C. (2004). Using OTIS to model solute transport in streams and rivers: U.S. Geological Survey Fact Sheet FS, vol.4, pp.138-199.

Matzke R H (1961). Fracture trace and joint patterns of Western Centre County, Pennsylvania; MS thesis, The Pennsylvania State University.

McCuen RH (2002) Approach to confidence interval estimation for curve numbers. J Hydrol Eng, vol.7 (1), pp.43–48.

Doi: 10.1061/(ASCE) 1084-0699(2002)7:1(43)

Mead, D. (1950). Hydrology, The Fundamental Basis of Hydraulic Engineering, 1st Ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, p. 626.

Meinzer, O. (1942). Hydrology. Dover Publications, New York. P.4.

Meyer, W.B. (1995). Past and Present Land-use and Land-cover in the U.S.A. Consequences 1.

Miller,V.C.(1953). A quantitative geomorphic study of drainage basin characteristics in the Clinch Mountain area, Virginia and Tennessee. Project NR 389 - 042, Tech. Rept. 3, Columbia University , Department of Geology, ONR, Geography Branch, New York.

Miller, O.M., and Summerson, C.H. (1960). Slope-zone maps: Geographical Review, vol.50, no.2, pp.194- 202

Misgna, G., Tsou, M. ve Zhan, X. (2004). Integrated GIS-Ann AGNPS modeling system for watershed assessment. *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering*.

Mishra, S. K. and Singh, V. P. (2003). *Soil Conservation Service Curve Number (SCS-CN) Methodology*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, The Netherlands, ISBN 1-4020-1132-6.

Mishra, S. K., Jain, M. K., and Singh, V. P. (2004). Evaluation of the SCS-CN-based model incorporating antecedent moisture, *J. Water Resour. Management*, vol.18, pp.567–589.

Mishra, S. K., Jain, M. K., Pandey, R. P., and Singh, V. P. (2005). Catchment area-based evaluation of the AMC-dependent SCS-CN-inspired rainfall-runoff models, *J. Hydrol. Process*, Vol.19 (14), pp.2701–2718.

Mithal, R. S., Gohain, K., and Joshi, B. C. (1982). Geomorphic analysis of a part of Ramganga basin Himalaya, In: *Landform and Process*, by Verma, V.K. and Saklani, P. S.(ed). Today and Tomorrow Publications, New Delhi, pp. 1-27.

MOCT (Ministry of Construction and Transportation) and KOWACO (Korea Water Resources Corporation) (1998). *The Handbook of Drawing and Management of Hydrogeological Map*. MOCT, Korea, pp.456.

Mogaji K. A., Aboyeji O. S., and Omosuyi G.O. (2011). Mapping Of Lineaments for Groundwater Targeting In Basement Complex Area of Ondo State Using Remotely Sensed Data. *International Journal of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering* Vol. 3(7), pp. 150–160.

Moore, J.D. and Hinkle, F. (1977). High-yield wells and springs along lineaments interpreted from LANDSAT imagery in Madisen County Alabama, USA. In:Jolson, J.S and Doyle, F.L. eds, Karst Hydrogeology, pp.447-486.

Morency R. (1994). A conceptual groundwater model for north east Sinai Peninsula, Egypt with application to Satellite Groundwater exploration. Ph.D. dissertation, Boston University.

Morgan, K.T., E.A. Hanlon, and T.A. Obreza. (2009). A Web-Based Model to Improve Water Use Efficiency and Reduce Nutrient Leaching for Florida Citrus SS499. Gainesville, University of Florida Institute of Food and Agricultural Acienes, <http://edis.ifas.ufl.edu/pdffiles/ss499>

Morisawa, M.E. (1957), Measurement of Drainage Basin Outline Form. Journal of Geol., Vol.66, pp. 86-88.

Morisawa, M.E. (1959), Relation of Morphometric Properties to Runoff in the Little Mill Creek, Ohio Drainage Basin, (Columbia University, Dept. of Geol.) Technical Report, 17, office of Naval Research, Project NR pp.389-042

Morisawa, M.E. (1962), Quantitative Geomorphology of Some Watersheds in the Appalachian Plateau, Geol. Soc. Amer. Bull 73, pp.1025-1046.

Morisawa, M. (1985). Rivers (Form and Process). Longman, London.

Muley, R. B., Kulkarni, P. S.and Babar, Md. (1988). An Integrated approach of geomorphological and hydrological studies forwatershed development: A case study, Journal of Applied Hydrology, Vol. XV, No.1. Pp.31-36.

Muller, J. E. (1968). An introduction to hydraulic and topographic sinuosity index. *Ann.Assoc. Amer. Geogr.* Vol.58. No.2. pp.371-385.

Murthy K.S.R. and Venkateswara Rao, V. (1999), Mapping of hydrogeomorphological features in varaha River basin using IRS Data. *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, vol.27 (2), pp.155-166.

Murthy, K. S.R., Amminedu, E. and Rao, V. V. (2003). Integration of thematic maps through GIS for identification of groundwater potential zones, *Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 31, No.3. pp. 198-210.

Musgrave, G.W. (1955). How Much Water Enters the Soils, U.S.D.A. Yearbook, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Washington, DC, pp. 151-159.

Mutreja, K. N. (1990). *Applied Hydrology*. Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi.

Myung-Seo Koo, Song-You Hong and Jhoon Kim (2009). An Evaluation of the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) Multi-Satellite Precipitation Analysis (TMPA) Data over South Korea. *Asia-Pacific Journal Of Atmospheric Sciences*, Vol.45, issue 3, pp. 265-282.

Nag, S. K. (2005). Application of Lineament Density and Hydrogeomorphology to delineate groundwater potential zones of Baghmundi block in Purulia district, Bengal, *Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 33, No.4. pp. 522-529.

Nagarale, V. R., Magar, P. P. and Harpale, D. (2007). Geomorphology and groundwater potential. *Research Link*. 35. Vol. V (10). January Special. Pp.51-54.

Nath, S. K., Patra, H. P. and Shahid, S. (2000). Geophysical prospecting of groundwater. Oxford and IBH Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi. pp. 167-188.

National Institute of Hydrology Report. (1990). A Report on geomorphology of Kolar sub-basin for hydrological studies. National Institute of Hydrology. Roorkee. Pp. 1-68.

National Institute of Hydrology Report. (1992). Hydrogeomorphological study of Tawi catchment, J & K, National Institute of Hydrology, Western Himalayan Regional Centre, Jammu Cantt. CS-124.

National Resources Conservation Service (NRCS). 2001. Section-4 Hydrology, in National Engineering Handbook, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Washington, D.C.

Neitsch, S.L. (2001). Soil and Water Assessment Tool user's manual version 2000. Available at <http://www.brc.tamus.edu/swat/doc.html>.

Nelson, R. (2004). The Water Cycle. Minneapolis: Lerner. ISBN 0-8225-4596-9.

Novotny, V. and G. Chesters. (1981). Handbook of Urban Nonpoint Pollution: Sources and Management. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold Company.

Nwa, E.U. (1979), Hydrologic and Physiographic Characteristics of Small, Forested Humid Tropical Watersheds, Nigerian Geographical Journal, Vol.22(1), pp.45-51.

O'Connell, P. E. and Todini, E. (1996). Modelling of rainfall, flow and mass transport in hydrological systems: an overview, J. Hydrol., Vol.175, pp.3-16.

Odeyemi, I.B., Anifowose, Y.B. and Asiwaju-Bello, Y.A. (1999). Multi-technique graphical analyses of fractures from remote sensing images of Basement regions of Nigeria. *Journal of Mining and Geology*, vol.33 (1), pp.9-21.

Odeyemi, I.B., Malomo, S. And Okufarasin, Y.A. (1985). Remote sensing of rock fractures and ground-water development success in parts of southwestern Nigeria. *Natural Resources Forum, United Nations, New York*, vol.9 (4), pp.311-315.

Obi Reddy GP, Chandra Mouli K, Srivastav SK, Srinivas CV and Maji AK (2000). Evaluation of groundwater potential zones using remote sensing data — A case study of Gaimukh watershed, Bhanadra District, Maharashtra. *J Indian Soc Remote Sens.* Vol.28 (1), pp.19–32

Obi Reddy, G. E., Maji, A. K. and Gajbhiye, K. S. (2002). GIS for morphometric analysis of drainage basins. *GIS India*, Vol. 4(11), pp. 9-14.

Obled, C., Wending, J., and Beven, K. (1994) The sensitivity of hydrological models to spatial rainfall patterns: an evaluation using observed data, *J. Hydrol.*, Vol.159, pp.305–333.

Oke, TR (1987). 2nd edn, *Boundary layer climates*, Methuen & Co. in association with Methuen, Inc. New York.

Okoko, E.E. and Olujinmi, J.A.B. (2003), *The Role of Geomorphic Features in Urban Flooding: The case of Ala River in Akure, Nigeria*, *Int. Journal of Environmental Issues*, Vol.1(1), pp.192-201.

O'leary D W, Freidman J D and Pohn H A (1976). Lineament, linear, lineation: Some proposed new definitions for old terms; Geol. Soc. Am. Bull. Vol.87, pp.1463 –1469.

Omvir Singh and A. Sarangi (2008). Hypsometric analysis of the lesser Himalayan watersheds using geographical information system. Indian J Soil Cons. Vol. 36(3). pp.148-154.

Owoade, A. And Moffat, W.S. (1989) Groundwater Prospects in Southwestern Nigeria. 15th WEDC Conference Water Engineering and Development in Africa, Kano, Nigeria. Pp.112-116

Patil, D. N., Sawant, S. B. and Dey, B. (1986). Changes in natural vegetation pattern of some river basins of western Maharashtra, India: A study based on remote sensing techniques. Int. Semi. On Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing for developing Countries, New Delhi, Vol. 1. T.4, pp. 5.1-5.13.

Pareta, K (2004), "Hydro-Geomorphology of Sagar District (M.P.): A Study through Remote Sensing Technique", Proceeding in XIX M. P. Young Scientist Congress, Madhya Pradesh Council of Science & Technology (MAPCOST), Bhopal.

Parizek , R. R. (1976) On the nature and significance of fracture traces and lineaments in carbonates and other terrains; Karst Hydrology and Water Resources, Proceedings of the US–Yugoslavian Symposium, Dubrovnik, Yugoslavia, pp.47–100.

Patton, P. C. (1988). Drainage basin morphometry and floods, In: Flood Geomorphology. V.R. Baker, R.C.Kochel and P.C. patton (Eds). John Wiley and Sons, New York, pp. 51-64.

Patton, P. C., and V. R. Baker. (1976). Morphometry and floods in small drainage basins subject to diverse hydrogeomorphic controls. *Water Resources Research*, Vol12, pp.941–52.

Penman, H. L. 1956. Evaporation :an introductory survey. *Netherl. J. Agric. Sci.*4:9-29, Discussions: 97-97; 151-153.

Petts, G. and Foster, I. (1985). *Rivers and Landscape*. Edward Arnold (Publishers) Ltd., London. UK.

Peterson, R (1980). Lineament analysis for oil and gas exploration and production in Wyoming; *Abstr. Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol. Bull.* Vol.64, pp.764.

Phukan I., Ravindran K.V. and Banerjee D.M. (1999). Delineation of Groundwater Prospect Zones using Remote Sensing and Geographic Information System in the West Garo Hills District, Meghalaya, “Geoinformatics: Beyond 2000”, an International Conference on Geoinformatics for Natural Resource Assessment, Monitoring and Management, Jointly Organized by Indian Institute of Remote Sensing (National Remote Sensing Agency) Dehradun, India and ITC (International Institute for Aerospace Survey and Earth Sciences) The Netherlands, pp.203-211.

Pike, R.J. (2000). *Geomorphometry — diversity in quantitative surface analysis*. *Progress in Physical Geography*, Vol. 24 (1), pp. 1–20

Pike, R.J.(2002). A bibliography of terrain modeling (geomorphometry), the quantitative representation of topography — supplement 4.0. Open-File Report 02-465. U.S. Geological Survey, Denver, pp. 116
<http://geopubs.wr.usgs.gov>.

Pieri, D.C. (1976). Martian channels: distribution of small channels on the Martian surface. *Icarus*, Vol.27, pp.25–50.

Pieri, D.C. (1980). Martian valleys: morphology, distribution, age and origin. *Science* Vol. 210, pp.895–897.

Pitty, A.F. (1968). Some comments on the scope of slope analysis based on frequency distributions: *Zeitschrift fur Geomorphologie*, vol.12, no.3, pp. 350- 355.

Planchon, O., E. Fritsch & C. Valentin. (1987). Rill Development in a Wet Savannah Environment. Bryan, R.B. (ed). *Rill Erosion: Processes and Significance*. Catena Supplement 8. W. Germany:Catena Verlag. pp.55-70.

Ponce, V. M. and Hawkins, R. H. (1996) Runoff curve number: has it reached maturity? , *J. Hydrol. Eng. ASCE*, Vol.1, pp.11–18.

Pradeep KS, Kumar S and Singh RP (2000). Neotectonic study of Ganga and Yamunatar faults, NW Himalaya using remote sensing and GIS. *Int. J. Rem. Sens.*, vol. 21, pp.499-518.

Prakash,S Ravi and Mishra, D. (1993). Identification of groundwater prospective zones by using Remote Sensing and geoelectrical methods in and around Saidnagar area. Dakor block, Jalaun district, U.P; *J. Indian Soc. Remote Sensing*, vol.21 (4). Pp.217–227.

Qureshy M. N and Hinze W. J (1989). Workshop Overview. Proc. Joint Indo -US Workshop on Regional geophysical lineaments-their tectonic and economic significances, Mem. Geol. Soc. Ind., Bangalore, No.12, pp.3-10.

Raghunath, H. M. (1996). Groundwater, New Age International Publications, 2'd Ed. p. 563.

Rahiman T I H and Pettinga J R (2008). Analysis of lineaments and their relationship to Neogene fracturing, SE Viti Levu, Fiji; Geol. Soc. Am. Bull. vol.120 (11–12), pp.1544–1555.

Raju, K., Das, G. J. and Anji Reddy, M. (2003). Drainage morphometry to evaluate the geomorphic stage of Kotgir watershed, A.P. India. In (Ed) Proceedings of Int. Conf. on Hydrology and Watershed Management, BS Publications, New Delhi, Vol-II, pp.437-446.

Raju, N. J., Reddy, T. V. K., Kotaiah, B., and Nayudu, P.T. (1995).Hydrogeomorphology of the upper Gunjanaeru river basin, Cuddapah district, Andhra Pradesh, using remote sensing techniques. Journal of Applied Hydrology, Vol. III, No.1 to 4, 1995, pp.99-104.

Ramesh Y (1990). Geomorphic Studies in Upper Gostani River Basin with Special References to Borra (Karst) Caves Visakapatnam District, A.p., India. Ph.D. Thesis, Andhra University, India, pp.131.

Ramasastri KS, Seth SM. (1985). Rainfall – runoff relationships, Rep. RN-20, National Institute of Hydrology, Roorkee, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Rawat, J. S. (1982). A quantitative morphometric analysis of the stratigraphical formation in the lower Ramganga catchment, Dist, Pauri and Almora. Journal of Himalayan Geology, Vol. 9 (I1).pp.701-715.

Rao, B.V. and Briz-Kishore, B.H (1991). A methodology for locating potential aquifers in a typical semi-arid region in India using resistivity and hydrogeologic parameters. Geoexploration, vol.27, pp.55–64.

Rao, U.R (1992). Remote Sensing for national development. *Curr. Scien.*, vol. 61 (3&4), pp.121.

Rao, K. V., Bhattacharya, A. K. and Mishra, K. (1996). Runoff estimation by curve number method- case studies, *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 40, pp. 1-7.

Rao, N.S (2003), groundwater prospecting and management in agro-based rural environment of crystalline terrain of India. *Environmental Geology*, 43, pp 419–431.

Rao, Y.S. and Jugran, D.K (2003). Delineation of groundwater potential zones and zones of groundwater quality suitable for domestic purposes using remote sensing and GIS. *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol.48, pp.821–833.

Rao, N., Latha, S., Kumar, A., and. Krishna, H. (2010), Morphometric Analysis of Gostani river basin in Andhra Pradesh state, India using spatial information technology, *International Journal of Geomatics and Geosciences*, Vol.1(2), pp 179-187.

Rao, L. A. K., Ansari, Z. R, and Yusuf, A (2011). Morphometric Analysis of Drainage Basin Using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques: A Case Study of Etmadpur Tehsil, Agra District,U.P., *International Journal of Research in Chemistry and Environment*, Vol. 1 (2). Pp.36-45.

Rauws, G. (1987). The Initiation of Rills on Plane Beds of Non-Cohesive Sediments. *Catena Supplement 8*. W. Germany:Catena Verlag. Pp.107-118.

Ravindran A. Antony, Ramanujam N. and Somasundaram P. (2012). Wenner Array Resistivity And Sp Logging For Ground Water

Exploration In Sawerpuram Teri Deposits, Thoothukudi District, Tamil Nadu, India. ARPN Journal of Earth Sciences, VOL. 1, NO. 1, pp.1 -5.

Ravi Shankar, M.N. and Mohan, G (2006). Assessment of the groundwater potential and quality in Bhatsa and Kalu river basins of Thane district, western Deccan Volcanic Province of India. Environmental Geology, vol.49, pp.990–998.

Roohani, M. S. and Gupta, R. P. (1988). Quantitative Hydrogeomorphic investigations in the Chenab Catchment, Himalayas. IAH Journal of Hydrology, Vol. XI, No. 4, Oct-Dec. pp.25-44.

Rosenblatt, P. and Pinet P.C. 1994. Comparative hypsometric analysis of Earth and Venus. Geophys. Res. Lett., Vol.21, pp.465-468.

Ruhe. (1971). Stream regime and man's manipulation. In: Environmental Geomorphology. Edited by Coates, D. R. Publishers in Geomorphology State University of New York, Binghamton. pp. 9-23.

Raisz, E.J., and Henry, Joyce (1937). An average slope map of New England: Geographical Review, vol. 27, no. 3, p. 467-472.

Raju, N. J., Reddy, T. V. K., Kotaiah, B., and Nayudu, P.T. (1995).Hydrogeomorphology of the upper Gunjanaeru river basin, Cuddapah district, Andhra Pradesh, using remote sensing techniques. Journal of Applied Hydrology, Vol. III, No.1 to 4, 1995, pp.99-104.

Y. S., Krishnareddy, T. V., and Nayudu, P. T. (1997). Hydrogeomorphological studies by remote sensing application in Niva river basin, Chittoor dist., Andhra Pradesh, Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing, Vol. 25, No.3. Pp.187-194.

- Rasemann, S., Schmidt, J., Schrott, L. and Dikau, R. (2004). Geomorphometry in mountain terrain. In: M.P. Bishop and J.F. Shroder, ed. GIS & Mountain Geomorphology. Springer, Berlin, pp.101–145.
- Rawat, J. S. (1982). A quantitative morphometric analysis of the stratigraphical formation in the lower Ramganga catchment, Dist, Pauri and Almora. *Journal of Himalayan Geology*, Vol. 9 (II).pp.701-715.
- Roohani, M. S. and Gupta, R. P. (1988). Quantitative Hydrogeomorphic investigations in the Chenab Catchment, Himalayas. *IAH Journal of Hydrology*, Vol. XI, No. 4, Oct-Dec. pp.25-44.
- Robinson, A.H. (1946). A method for producing shaded relief from aerial slope data: *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, vol. 36, no. 4, p. 248-252. [Reprinted 1948, in *Surveying and Mapping*, vol.8, no, 3, pp. 157-160]
- Rosgen, D. L. (1994). A Classification of Natural Rivers, *Catena*, Vol. 22, pp. 169-199.
- Ruhe. (1971). Stream regime and man's manipulation. In: *Environmental Geomorphology*. Edited by Coates, D. R. Publishers in Geomorphology State University of New York, Binghamton. pp. 9-23.
- Rich John, (1916). A graphical method of determining the average inclination of a land surface from a contour map: *Transactions of the Illinois Academy of Sciences*, v. 9, pp.195-199.
- Ritter, D.F., Kochel, R.C. and Miller, J.R. (2002). *Process Geomorphology*. McGraw Hill, Boston.

S.C. Cande & D.R. Stegman (2011). Indian and African plate motions driven by the push force of the Réunion plume head; *Nature*; Volume 475; pp. 47–52; doi:10.1038/nature10174

Sali S. A. (1973). Direct evidence of Late Pleistocene tectonic movement in the central Tapi basin in Maharashtra. *Bombay: Tata Institute of Fundamental Research*, pp 96 -105

Sander, P., Minor, T.B. and Chesley, M. (1997). Groundwater exploration based on lineament analysis. *Groundwater*, pp.35.

Sankar K, Jegatheesan M. S and Balasubramanian A (1993). Hydrogeological Studies in the Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu., Regional Seminar on Groundwater development problems in Southern Kerala Proc. Volume., pp.12-18.

Sankar K, Jegatheesan M .S and Balasubramanian A (1996). Geoelectrical Resistivity Studies in the Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, *J. of Applied Hydrology Vol.IX, Nos 1&2*, pp.83-90.

Sankar, K. (2002). Evaluation of groundwater potential zones using remote sensing data in upper Vaigai River basin, Tamil Nadu, India, *Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing, Vol. 30. No.3*.pp. 119-129.

Sapiano, M.R.P. and Arkin, P.A. (2009). An intercomparison and validation of high-resolution satellite precipitation estimates with 3-hourly gauge data. *Journal of Hydrometeorology, Vol.10*, pp. 149–166.

Saraf, A. K. and Choudhary, P. R. (1998). Integrated remote sensing and GIS for groundwater exploration and identification of artificial recharge

sites. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 19, No. 10. pp. 1825-1841.

Sarangi, A and Bhattacharya, A. K. (2000). Use of geomorphological parameters for sediment yield prediction from watersheds. *J. Soil & Water Cons. India*, Vol. 44, pp.99-106.

Sarbhukan, M. M. (2001). *Water resources planning: for sustainable development in Maharashtra*. Publisher A. M. Sarbhukan, Pune. Pp.37-52.

Scheidegger, A.E. (1973). Hydrogeomorphology. *Journal of Hydrology*, 20 (2). pp.193-215.

Schumm, S.A. (1954), *The Relation of Drainage Basin Relief to Sediment Loss*. *Internat. Assoc. Sci. Hyd. Pub.*, Vol.36, pp.216-219.

Schumm, S.A. (1956), *The Evolution of Drainage Systems and Slopes in Badlands at Perth Amboy, New Jersey*, *Geol. Soc. Amer. Bull.*, Vol.67, pp.597-646.

Schumm, S.A. (1963), *A Tentative Classification of River Channels*. U.S. Geol. Survey Circular, 477 (10pp)

Schumm, S. A. (1964). *Air photos and water resources*. *Transactions Toulouse, UNESCO*: pp. 70-80

SCS. 1972. *Hydrology*. Section 4 in *National Engineering Handbook*. Washington, D.C.: USDA Soil Conservation Service.

Sen Gautam (2001). *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Earth Planet. Sci.)*, 110, No. 4, pp. 409-431.

Sen, Z. (1995). Applied hydrogeology for scientists and engineering. Lewis Publishers, New York. Pp.161-299.

Sener, E., Davraz, A. and Ozcelik, M (2005). An integration of GIS and remote sensing in groundwater investigations: A case study in Burdur, Turkey. Hydrogeology Journal, vol.13, pp.826–834.

Selby, M.J. (1985). Earth's Changing Surface: an Introduction to Geomorphology. Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Sethupathi A.S, Lakshmi Narasimhan C, Vasanthamohan.V. (2012). Evaluation of hydrogeomorphological landforms and lineaments using GIS and Remote Sensing techniques in Bargur – Mathur subwatersheds, Ponnaiyar River basin, India. International journal of geomatics and geosciences, Vol.3, No 1. Pp.178-190.

Shah, S. M. S., O'Connell, P. E., and Hosking, J. R. M. (1991). Modelling the effects of spatial variability in rainfall on catchment response. 2. experiments with distributed and lumped models, J. Hydrol., Vol.175, pp.89–111,

Shahid, S., Nath, S.K. and Ray, J (2000). Groundwater potential modeling in softrock using a GIS. International Journal of Remote Sensing, vol.21, pp.1919–1924.

Shahid, S. and Nath, S.K (2002). GIS integration of Remote sensing and electrical sounding data for hydrogeological exploration. Journal of Spatial Hydrology, vol.2, pp.1–10.

Sharma, S. K. (2003). Assessment of demand and potential of water Resources in the Tons Basin (M.P.), A Water Scarcity Region. In Singh,

D. N. et al. (ed.) Water Crisis and Sustainable Management. XXV JIG conference Volume, Tara Book Agency, Varanasi, pp.179-193.

Sharp, R.P., Malin, M.C.(1975). Channels on Mars. Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.Vol.86, pp. 593–609.

Shaw, E. M. (1988). Hydrology in Practice. Van Nostrend. Reinhold Int. Co. Ltd. Londoan. pp. 263-293.

Sheth, Hetu C. (2006). The Deccan Beyond the Plume Hypothesis. www.MantlePlumes.org,

Sherman, L. K. (1949). The unit hydrograph method. In Physics of the Earth, O. E. Menizer, ed. Dover Publications, Inc., New York, New York, pp.514–525.

Shukla Acharjee (2012). Hydro-Geomorphological Study of the Bhogdoi River Basin, Assam: A Remote Sensing and GIS Approach. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.

Shukla, S. ans Verma, V.K. (1973). Geomorphostatistical investigations in a part of Doon Valley, Garhwal Himalayas, Journal of Himalayan Geology. Vol. 8 (II).

Sidle, W.C., Lee, P.Y. (1995). Estimating local ground water flow conditions in a granitoid: preliminary assessments in the Waldoboro pluton complex, Maine. Ground Water, vol.33 (2), pp.291-302.

Sidle Roy C. and Onda Yuichi (2004). Hydrogeomorphology: overview of an emerging science. Hydrological Processes, Vol. 18 (Issue 4), pp. 597–602. DOI: 10.1002/hyp.1360

Sikdar, P.K., Chakraborty, S., Adhya, E. and Paul, P.K., (2004). Land use/land cover changes and groundwater potential zoning in and around

Raniganj coal mining area, Bardhaman District, West Bengal: A GIS and remote sensing approach. *Journal of Spatial Hydrology*, vol.4, pp.1–24.

Simonne, E.H., M.D. Dukes, and L. Zotarelli. (2010). Principles and Practices of Irrigation Management for Vegetables, p. 17-26, In: S. M. Olson and E. Simonne. eds. *Vegetable Production Handbook for Florida 2010-2011*. IFAS, Gainesville, FL.

Singh, S., and Dubey, A. (1994). Geo-environmental planning of watersheds in India, Allahabad, India: Chugh Publications, 28 (A), pp.69.

Singh, Savindra. (2004). *Geomorphology*. Prayag Pustak Bhawan. Allahabad. pp.353-384.

Singh, V. P. (1994). *Elementary Hydrology*. Prentice-Hall of India Private Limited, New Delhi. pp.80-117.

Singh, V. P. (1992). *Elementary Hydrology*, Prentice-Hall, Engle-wood Cliffs, N. J., pp.973.

Siyal, A.G., F.C. Oad, M.A. Samo, Z. Hassan and N.L. Oad, (2002). Effect of compactions on infiltration characteristics of soil. *Asian J. Plant Sci.*, vol.1, pp. 3-4.

Singhal, B.B.S. and Gupta, R.P. (1999). *Applied hydrogeology of fractured rocks*, Kluwer academic publishers, The Netherlands, pp.400.

Smajstrla, A.G., B.J. Boman, D.Z. Haman, F.T. Izuno, D.J. Pitts and F.S. Zaxueta. (1997). *Basic Irrigation Scheduling in Florida AE111*. Development Division, United Nations Food and Agriculture Service, Rome, Italy.

Smith, Guy-Harold (1938). The morphometry of landscape an analysis of slope (abs., paper read at 36th Annual Meeting, Ann Arbor, 1937): *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, vol. 28, no.1, pp. 63-64.

Smith, J.D., (2006). Beaver, willow shrubs and floods, *in* Johnson, E.A. and Miyanishi, K., eds., *Plant Disturbance Ecology: The Process and the Response*, Elsevier Academic Press, pp.603-672.

Sokolov, A.A. (1969), Interrelationship between Geomorphological Characteristics of a drainage basins and the streams. *Soviet Hydrology Selected Papers*1, pp.16-22.

Soil Conservation Service (SCS) (1956). Hydrology, *National Engineering Handbook, Supplement A, Sect. 4, Chapt. 10*, Soil Conservation Service, USDA, Washington, D.C.

Soil Conservation Service (SCS) (1972). *National Engineering Handbook, Sect. 4, Hydrology, Chapt. 10, Estimation of direct runoff from storm rainfall* by Victor Mockus.

Solomon S and Ghebreab W (2006). Lineament characterization and their tectonic significance using Landsat TM data and field studies in the central highlands of Eritrea. *J. Afr. Earth Sci.*, vol. 46, pp. 371-378.

Solomon, S. and Quiel, F (2006). Groundwater study using remote sensing and geographic information system (GIS) in the central highlands of Eritrea. *Hydrogeology Journal*, vol.14, pp.729–741.

Spark, B. W. (1960). *Geomorphology*. Longmans, Green London.

Strahler, A.N. (1952). Hypsometric (Area-Altitude) analysis of erosional topography. *Bulletin of Geological Society of America*, Vol. 63. pp.1117-1142.

Sparks, B.W. (1960), *Landform in arid and semi-arid climates; Geomorphology* 2nd edition, (Longman Group Ltd.), pp. 335-341.

Spear, R. C., T. M. Grieb, and N. Shang. (1994). Parameter uncertainty and interaction in complex environmental models. *Water Resources Research*, vol.30 (11), pp.3159–3169.

Sreedevi, P.D., Srinivasulu, S. and Raju, K.K (2001). Hydrogeomorphological and groundwater prospects of the Pageru river basin by using remote sensing data. *Environmental Geology*, vol.40, pp.1919–1924.

Sreedevi, P.D., Subrahmanyam, K. and Ahmed, S (2005). Integrated approach for delineating potential zones to explore for groundwater in the Pageru River basin, Kuddapah District, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Hydrogeology Journal*, vol.13, pp.534–545.

Srinivasa RY, Jugran KD (2003). Delineation of groundwater potential zones and zones of groundwater quality suitable for domestic purposes using remote sensing and GIS. *Hydro. Sci. J.*, vol.48, pp.821–833.

Srivastava, P. K., & Bhattacharya, A. K. (2000). Delineation of groundwater potential zones in a hard rock terrain of Bargarh district, Orissa- using IRS data. *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, vol.28 (2&3), pp.129–140.

Srivastava, P. and Bhattacharya, A (2006). Groundwater assessment through an integrated approach using remote sensing, GIS and resistivity

techniques: A case study from a hard rock terrain. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol.27, pp.4599–4620.

Stafford, D.B. (Ed.), (1991). *Civil engineering applications of Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems* (New York: ASCE).

Stepinski, T. F., and M. L. Collier (2004), Extraction of Martian valley networks from digital topography, *J. Geophys. Res.*, Vol. 109, pp.11005, doi:10.1029/2004JE002269.

Strahler, A.N (1952). Hypsometric Analysis of Erosional Topography, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of America*, Vol.63, pp 17-42.

Strahler A.N. (1953). Revisions of Horons 'Quantitative Factors in Erosional Terrain, *Trans.Am.Geophys.U*, Vol.34, p.345.

Strahler, A.N (1956), Quantitative Slope Analysis, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of America*, Vol.67, pp 571-596.

Strahler, A.N. (1957). Quantitative analysis of watershed geometry, *Transactions American Geophysical Union*. Vol.38, pp. 913-920.

Strahler, A.N (1964). Quantitative Geomorphology of Drainage Basin and Channel Network, *Handbook of Applied Hydrology*, pp 39-76.

Strahler, Alan and Strahler Arthur. (1996). *Introducing physical geography*. John Wiley and Sons, New York.

Strahler, Alan and Strahler Arthur. (2000). *Introducing physical geography*. John Wiley and Sons, New York.

Stumm, W. (1986). Water and integrated ecosystem. *Ambio*, Vol.15, pp.201–207.

Subba Rao, N. (1992). Factors affecting optimum development of groundwaters in crystalline terrain of the Eastern Ghats, Visakhapatnam area, Andhra Pradesh, India. *J. Geol. Soc. India*, vol.40 (5), pp.462–467.

Subba Rao, N., Chakradhar, G.K.J. and Srinivas V, (2001), Identification of Groundwater Potential Zones using Remote Sensing techniques In and Around Guntur town, Andhra Pradesh, India, *Journal of the Indian Society of remote Sensing*, vol.29 (12), pp 69-78.

Sugawara, M. I., I. Watanabe, E. Ozaki, and Y, Katsuyame. (1983). Reference manual for the TANK model. National Resources Center for Disaster Prevention, Tokyo, Japan.

Suresh, R. (2005). *Watershed Hydrology*. Standard Publishers, New Delhi. pp. 44-105.

Suzan ML, Toprak V (1998). Filtering of satellite images in geological lineament analyses: An application to a fault zone in Central Turkey. *Int. J. Rem. Sens.*, vol.19, pp.1101-1114.

Swank, W., and Douglass, J. (1974). *Science*. Vol.185 (4154), pp.857-859

Syed AA and Saied P (2004). Geological applications of Landsat Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM) data and Geographic Information System (GIS): Mapping and structural interpretation in south-west Iran, Zagros Structural Belt. *Int. J. Rem. Sens.*, vol.25, pp.4715-4727

The Shuttle Radar Topography Mission, *Rev. Geophys.*, 45, RG2004, doi: 10.1029/2005RG000183

Thomas E. Reilly (2004). A Brief History of Contributions to Ground Water Hydrology by the U.S. Geological Survey. *Ground Water Magazine*, vol.42, number 4, pp.625-631.

Thorat, S. K. (1992). Chemical weathering of basalt and formation of soils in the Gunjawani River Basin, Western Maharashtra, India. Unpublished Ph. D. Thesis. University of Poona. Pp. 7-20.

Thornbury, W.D. (1990). *Principle of Geomorphology*. Wiley Eastern Limited, New Delhi, pp 594.

Thornthwaite, C. W. (1948). An approach toward a rational classification of climate. *Geographical Review*, vol.38 (1), pp.55–94. doi:10.2307/210739

Timbal, B, Power, S, Colman, R, Viviani J & Lirola, S (2002). 'Does soil moisture influence climate variability and predicability over Australia', *Journal of Climate*, Volume 15, pp.1230 – 1238.

Tobler, W. R. (1976). Analytical cartography. *The American Cartographer* Vol.3, pp. 21-31.

Tobler, W. R. (2000). The development of analytical cartography – a personal note. *Cartography and Geographic Information Science* Vol.27, pp. 189-194.

Todd, D.K. (1980). *Ground-water hydrology (Second Edition)*: John Wiley and Sons, New York, pp.535.

Todd, D. K. (2003). *Groundwater Hydrology*. John Wiley and Sons Ltd, New York, 2nd Ed, 530 p.

Todd, D.K., and Mays, L.W. (2005). *Ground-water hydrology (Third Edition)*: John Wiley and Sons, New York, pp.636.

Tomar, M. (1999). Quality Assessment of Water and Waste Water. Lewis Publishers, London. pp. 36-64.

Torri, D., M. Sfalanga & G. Chisci. (1987). Threshold Conditions for Incipient Rilling. Bryan, R.B. (ed). Rill Erosion: Processes and Significance. Catena Supplement 8. W. Germany:Catena Verlag. pp.97-105.

Travaglia, C. (1989). Remote Sensing Applications to Water Resources: Ground water Search by Remote Sensing Case Histories: Yemen and the Philippines. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, pp.356.

Tripathy. J.k., Panigrahy. R.C. and Vinod Kumar. K. (1996). Geological and geomorphological Studies of a part of Ganjam District, Orissa by Remote Sensing Techniques, Journal of the Indian Society of remote Sensing, vol.24 (3), pp.169-177.

Tsou, M., Zhan, X. (2004). Estimation of runoff and sediment yield in the Redrock Creek Watershed using AnnAGNPS and GIS. Journal of Environmental Sciences, Vol.16 (5), pp. 865-867.

USDA (1986) Urban hydrology for small watersheds. Technical release, no 55 (TR-55). Soil Conservation Service, Washington, DC.

USDA-SCS. (1985). National Engineering Handbook, Section 4 - Hydrology. Washington, D.C.: USDA-SCS.

USDA (1993) Soil survey manual. Handbook 18. Soil Conservation Service, Washington, DC.

Venkatachalan, P., Murthy, C.V.S.S.B.R., Chowdhary, S., and Sharma, L.N. (1991). Groundwater potential zone mapping using a GIS approach. *Asia-Pacific Remote Sensing Journal*, 4(1), pp.75-78.

Verstappen, H. Th. (1983). *Applied Geomorphology-Geomorphological Surveys for Environmental Development*. Elsevier Publishing, Amsterdam. pp. 57-85.

Viessman, W., Lewis, G. L. and Knapp, J. W. (1980). *Introduction to Hydrology*. Happer and Row Publishers. Singapore.

Vittala, S. S., Govindaiah, S. and Gowda, H.H. (2005). Evaluation of groundwater potential zones in the sub-watersheds of north Pennar River basin around Pavagada, Karnataka, India using remote sensing and GIS techniques, *Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 33, No.4. pp. 483-493.

Wang, Jinfei, Member, IEEE, Howarth and Philip J. (1990). Use of the Hough Transform in Automated Lineament Detection, *IEEE Transactions on Geosciences and Remote Sensing*, Vol. 28, No. 4, pp.561-566.

Wentworth, C.K. (1930). A simplified method of determining the average slope of land surfaces, *American Journal of Science. Series. 5*, Vol.20, pp.184-94.

Weissel, J.K., Pratson, L.F. and Malinverno, A (1994). The length-scaling properties of topography. *J. Geophys. Res.*, Vol.99, pp.13997-14012.

Wilcox, B. P., W. J. Rawls, D. L Brakensiek, and J.R. Wight. (1990). Predicting runoff from rangeland catchments: A comparison of two models. *Water Resources Research*, vol. 26 (10), pp. 2401-2410.

Woodruff, K.D., Talley, J.H. and Miller, J.C. (1974). Selection of sites for high yielding wells in the Del-aware, Piedmont area. In: Abstract with programs, Northeastern Section Geological Society of America, Baltimore, Maryland.

World Health Organization (1992). Revision of WHO Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality: Report of Final Task Group Meeting, Geneva, Switzerland, pp.21-25.

Zambre, M. K. (1982). Hydrogeology of the Shivganga Basin, district Ptme, Maharashtra, Unpublished Ph. D. Thesis, University of Poona, p. 10.

Zaporozec, A. (1979). Water: availability, demand and use. *GeoJournal*, 3(5),pp.417-508.

Verstappen, H. Th. (1983). Applied Geomorphology-Geomorphological Surveys for Environmental Development. Elsevier Publishing, Amsterdam. pp. 57-85.

Van Bavel, C.H.M. (1966). Potentiale evaporation. The combination concept and its experimental verification. *Wat. Resour. Res.* Vol.2 (3), pp.455-467.

Viessman, W., Lewis, G. L. and Knapp, J. W. (1980). Introduction to Hydrology. flapper and Row Publishers. Singapore.

Vittala, S. S., Govindaiah, S. and Gowda, H.H. (2005). Evaluation of groundwater potential zones in the sub-watersheds of north Pennar River basin around Pavagada, Karnataka, India using remote sensing and GIS techniques, *Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 33, No.4. pp. 483-493.

Wentworth, C.K. (1930). A simplified method of determining the average slope of land surfaces, *American Journal of Science*. Series 5, Vol.20, pp.184-94.

Wheeler, D.A. (1979). The overall shape of longitudinal profiles of streams. In: Pitty, A.F. (Ed.), *Geographical Approaches to Fluvial Processes*. GeoAbstracts, Norwich, pp. 241–260.

Whitten & Brooks, (1972). *The Penguin Dictionary of Geology*.

Williams, J. R. (1995). The EPIC model In *Computer Models of Watershed Hydrology*, pp.909-1000. V. P.Singh, ed. Highlands Ranch, Colo.: Water Resources Publications.

Williams, R. M. E., and R. J. Phillips (2001), Morphometric measurements of Martian valley networks from Mars Orbiter Laser Altimeter (MOLA) data, *J. Geophys. Res.*, Vol.106, pp.737–23.

World Health Organization (1992). *Revision of WHO Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality: Report of Final Task Group Meeting*, Geneva, Switzerland, pp.21-25.

Y. S., Krishnareddy, T. V., and Nayudu, P. T. (1997). Hydrogeomorphological studies by remote sensing application in Niva river basin, Chittoor dist., Andhra Pradesh, *Photonirvachak, Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, Vol. 25, No.3. pp.187-194.

Yassaghi A (2006). Integration of Landsat imagery interpretation and geomagnetic data on verification of deep-seated transverse fault lineaments in SE Zagrosa, Iran. *Int. J. Rem. Sens.*, vol.27, pp.4529-4544.

Young, R. A., C. A. Onstad, D. D. Bosch, and W. P. Anderson. (1987). *AGNPS, Agricultural nonpoint-source pollution model: A watershed*

analytical tool. Conservation Research Report No.35. Washington, D.C.: USDA.

Younesi Alamouti, M. and M. Navabzadeh, (2007). Investigation of plowing depth effect on some soil physical properties. Pak. J. Biol. Sci., vol.10, pp.4510-4514.

Zambre, M. K. (1982). Hydrogeology of the Shivganga Basin, district Pune, Maharashtra, Unpublished Ph. D. Thesis, University of Poona, p.10.

Zhan, Xiaoyong, Huang, Min-Lang (2004). ArcCN-Runoff: an Arc GIS tool for generating curve number and runoff maps. Environmental Modelling & Software, vol.19, issue 10, pp.875 – 879.

Zaporozec, A. (1979). Water: availability, demand and use. GeoJournal, 3(5).pp.417-508.

Zaporozec, A., (1979). One hundred years of Wisconsin public water supplies: Transactions of the Wisconsin Academy of Sciences, Arts and Letters, vol. 67, pp. 149-153.

Zolfaghari A.A., S. Mirzaee and M. Gorji (2012). Comparison of Different Models for Estimating Cumulative Infiltration. International Journal of Soil Science, vol.7, pp.108-115.

Plate 1. Escarpment near Patna Devi

Plate 2. Dhaval Tirtha waterfall near Patna Devi

Plate 3. Plunge pool at Kedar Kunda Waterfall near Patna Devi

Plate 4. Fluvial Terrace at Dungri River near Chalisgaon

Plate 5. Pothole at Dungri River near Pital Khora Caves, Chalisgaon

Plate 6. Pothole at Dungri River near Pital Khora Caves

Plate 7. Steep Slope and Dense vegetation in source area

Plate 8. Escarpment, Steep Slope and Dense vegetation in source area

Plate 9. Well developed Forest Soil Profile (Shallow Black Soil) near Saigavan

Plate 10. Structural Hills (Background), pediment and Pedepain (Foreground)

Plate 11. Colluviums Deposit near Patna Village

Plate 12. Alluvium deposit along Dungri River near Patna village

Plate 13. Balancing Stone at the top of Dyke (Bodhra)

Plate 14. Mass movement (Bodhra)

Plate 15. Expose basalt at the Top of Dyke (Bodhra)

Plate 16. Basalt with vertical joints at the Top of Dyke (Bodhra)

Plate 17. Red Bole inter trap bed near Autrom Ghat area, Chalisgaon

Plate 18. Red Bole and Green Bole near Autrom Ghat area, Chalisgaon

Plate 19. Near surface water table (October) Neri open well

Plate 20. Near surface water table (October) Chalisgaon open well

Plate 21. Low water table (May) Lohatar open well

Plate 22. Escarpment and Talus near Patna Devi Temple

Plate 23, Landsat TM 5 Satellite Image (Band 123) Date: 09-10-2009

Plate 24, Landsat TM 5 Satellite Image (Band 234) Date: 09-10-2009

Plate 25, ASTER Satellite Image (Band 3b, 2, 1) Date: 26-05-2010